

**22nd Conference on
Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries**

COMPIT'23

Drübeck, 23-25 May 2023

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Edited by Volker Bertram

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Dedicated to Prof. Horst Nowacki for his 90th birthday

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Optimisation of an Electric Catamaran in the Early Design Stage

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Abstract

The paper presents a design study for a crew transfer vessel undertaken in the early design stage. The vessel is designed as a catamaran with electric propulsion to meet port requirements. Striving for small battery weight, the key design mission was to reduce resistance as far as possible to improve performance and range of the vessel. For this purpose, a parametric modeling and hydrodynamic optimization campaign was conducted. A parametric model for the hull was set up in CAESES. Resistance predictions. Power requirements were calculated using CFD with FINE/Marine using a simplified propulsor model. The optimization was accelerated using surrogate models for a coarse optimization search, before employing high-fidelity models for the final search. Potential for further improvement in design details is discussed.

1. Introduction – Design task

The maritime industry steadily gains momentum in introducing new ways of providing boats and ships with clean(er) energy. For more than a century the main source of energy for shipping came first in form of coal, then in form of fuel oils, and more recently increasingly in the form of LNG (Liquefied Natural Gas). The IMO (International Maritime Organisation) targets for decarbonization of shipping will lead to fundamental changes in ship fuels and energy converters in the next three decades. The transformation process has already started.

For usual deep-sea shipping, i.e. long-distance, high-deadweight shipping, the most likely scenarios are based on diesel engines and fuel cells, using alternative fuels with low carbon footprint, such as biofuels, methanol, LNG, and ammonia, *Bertram (2021)*. For short sea shipping, more and more projects consider purely electric propulsion, using fuel cell or battery technology, *Hoedemaker (2022)*. Ferries for relatively short distances have turned out to be good candidates for early adaptation of such e-propulsion. They allow full charging of batteries during the nights when in port and intermediate recharging of batteries when (un)loading, *Jokinen et al. (2021)*.

Fig.1: Port of Singapore

The project presented in this paper focuses on the hydrodynamics of a small crew transfer vessel for the port of Singapore, Fig.1. Singapore Port is a major international crew change hub for ships and its port authority is seeking to electrify all harbour craft. The particular focus of this project was on effi-

cient outer port limits (OPL) crew transfer. The new design had to be fully electrical, and its performance was to exceed those of existing conventional craft in service, in terms of speed and range, with in combination with high battery weight poses a considerable design challenge.

Normally, such a small ferry project would not undergo a thorough hydrodynamic optimization campaign. However, the high price and weight of batteries justified the extra design effort in this project, as it did in several other for applications of simulation-driven design (SDD) to electrically powered small craft in our experience, *Albert et al. (2020, 2021)*.

Gloss Design and Icarus Marine as small craft design specialists assumed the leading role as designers, while FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS and NUMECA Ingenieurbüro contributed their expertise of geometric modeling and numerical flow simulation, respectively. Fig.2 shows the general arrangement of the base design.

Fig.2: General arrangement of base design

The base design is a catamaran, Fig.3. The chosen canoe stern design, Fig.4, features generally very low resistance compared to conventional hulls, with low appendage drag as there are no exposed shafts or brackets.

Fig.3: Artist vision of design

Fig.4: Canoe stern design

2. Partially parametric modelling

Parametric modeling for the design and optimization of ship hulls, propellers, appendages, etc. is by now widely accepted and applied in both academia and industry. To balance intelligently a meaningful range of shape variations and a small enough set of free variables to control them, different approaches of parametric modeling have been developed; see *Harries (2020)* for an overview.

In SDD these Computer Aided Design approaches (CAD) are typically subdivided into fully parametric and partially parametric modeling. While fully parametric modeling (FPM) is more powerful with regard to the scope and the precision of achievable modifications, partially parametric modeling (PPM) is easier and faster to set up and handle. For this project, a PPM model was set up in the CAESES framework of FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS, <https://www.caeses.com>. CAESES is a flexible CAD modeler for fast and robust design studies. Integrated capabilities for process automation and shape optimization make it an all-in-one design system for simulation engineers.

2.1. BRep morphing

In a first approach, a PPM model based on radial basis functions (RBFs) was used. RBFs offer a very intuitive set-up of defining modifications on a base design and can be considered a morphing approach in its broader sense. (Note that quite frequently the term morphing is used for most partially parametric modeling approaches.) In CAESES two RBF techniques are available: A discrete approach for interactively changing point data (trimeshes) and a continuous approach for changing mathematically closed geometries represented by B-splines (BReps), *Harries and Abt (2021)*. For the catamaran optimization presented here, the continuous BReps approach was chosen since it allows the design team a fine-tuned modification of various regions that are likely to influence the hydrodynamic performance positively. For details of the RBF approach in CAESES, see *Albert et al. (2021)*.

Fig.5: Push stern in as parametric variation example

Variations in the stern were particularly effective in adjusting transom immersion, trim, anti-ventilation, propeller inflow, and pressure recovery, all affecting the resistance respectively the power requirements. The tunnel height was an important parameter to ensure enough room for the propeller

at lower transom heights. Pushing the stern in, Fig.5, was surprisingly effective, but cannot be overdone because the propeller shaft still needs to fit. Asymmetry was also found to be very important due to a very bad combination of speed and demi-hull spacing in the base design. Maximum asymmetry allowed to get reduce the unfavorable wave interference significantly, but it was tricky to still fit the batteries, Fig.6.

Fig.6: Asymmetry as parametric variation example

2.2. Free Form Deformation

The second technique that was used is Free Form Deformation. Here, based on an existing baseline design, the modification of the shape (and not the shape itself) is defined parametrically. Transformations of the control points of the B-spline volume are easy to set up and control, but give very good results (both in terms of surface quality and resistance reduction). The “taper aftbody” shown in Fig.7 was responsible for more than 40% of the total resistance reduction in the optimization. In the “taper forebody” modification, it was again important to allow enough space for the batteries at large asymmetries and gentle waterline entry, Fig.8.

Fig.7: Taper aftbody modification in Free Form Deformation

Fig.8: Taper forebody modification in Free Form Deformation

2.3. Lackenby transformation

The last transformation applied to the model before sending it to the CFD analysis was a Lackenby transformation, shifting sections in longitudinal direction, <https://www.caeses.com/blog/2016/ship-hull-optimization-generalized-lackenby/>. In a way, Lackenby transformations are the “holy grail” of transformations for the naval architect.

Whatever we have done to the model so far, with this single transformation we can simultaneously set 100% accurate displacement and LCB (either fixed, or within user-defined limits) and simultaneously (even independently) shift the mid frame (our free design variable in this step). As a result, we will only generate feasible designs (from a hydrostatics' point of view) with maximum shape variations.

A few more words on the hydrostatics - Batteries make up a large portion of the deadweight of a battery-electric vessel. They are also quite large and need to be fitted into the narrow demi-hulls, preferably very low for stability reasons. In search of the optimum shape, we must shift the batteries longitudinally within the permissible limits. This changes the LCG (longitudinal center of gravity), but the Lackenby transformations can ensure a corresponding LCB. We can shift the batteries to generate a few more mm of clearance in critical areas. We found that even with just a few mm of clearance for the batteries, we were able to achieve large variations in shape, Fig.9, which in turn facilitated significant improvements in hydrodynamics.

Fig.9: Variations in battery positions to shift LCG and LCB

3. CFD evaluation for base design

NUMECA's FINE™/Marine package was used for the viscous CFD calculations, utilizing a volume-of-fluid (VOF) method for free surface capturing, *Queutey and Visonneau (2007)*. The numerical representation and accuracy of the time-dependent free surface is strongly affected by the spatial discretization in the grid, especially perpendicular to the air-water-interface. FINE™/Marine features an adaptive grid refinement (AGR) technique, which can create or remove mesh cells during solver runtime, triggered by various physical phenomena. The current location of the free surface acts as the sensor and the mesh is refined until a user-specified threshold in terms of the cell size is achieved. This procedure is called in certain intervals and ensures an ideal grid at all locations and at all time steps. Such an approach does not require any pre-refined mesh zones where the user would need to anticipate important phenomena in the flow field beforehand, e.g. wave patterns and regions of breaking waves. During an optimization with variable geometry and for two different displacements, which on their own strongly affect the location of the free surface. An AGR thus reduces the necessary CPU time for each variant investigated.

The typical starting point for any optimization campaign is a detailed analysis of the baseline, the setup of a smooth workflow and the investigation of possible numerical sensitivities like boundary conditions and grid resolution. The aim of the project was a reduction of total resistance for the wetted hull, including the lower parts of the freeboard. The superstructure was not taken into account. This is a valid approach since, especially for low operating speeds, air drag is rather small and even in rough weather the variation of the hull should have only negligible effect on the flow about the superstructure. The cat was supposed to run straight ahead in calm seas, solving for sinkage and trim for the two displacement conditions using an integrated body-motion solver, *Leroyer and Visonneau (2005)*.

The flow was simulated at full-scale for only one speed, 12 kn, and one displacement condition, 19.5 t (fully loaded). Such a simulation can be handled fully automatically using the C-Wizard in FINE™/Marine, which provides meshing templates for various densities as well as the full solver set-

up. However, for more flexibility, we used our own set-up in Python. In conjunction with the stable yet flexible STL file export from CAESES® the Python set-up ensures a smooth workflow. For the set-up of a suitable flow domain and the exchange of data between CAESES® and FINE™/Marine via STL files, see *Albert et al. (2016)* for details. Importantly, within CAESES the topology of the flow domain along with the colors and name tags assigned to various parts of the domain (e.g. inner hull, outer hull, spray rail, deck, transom etc.) stay unaltered during any variation. Hence, when exporting them in a multi-body STL file, FINE/Marine can readily handle any new variant without manual interaction.

The propeller was modelled by an actuator disk, enhanced with an open-water characteristics of the design propeller, Fig.10. Such a model gives similarly good results for global resistance and propulsion cases as using meshed propellers, but at a fraction of the computational costs.

Fig.10: Open-water characteristics of propeller

The CFD mesh was generated using HEXPRESS, exploiting port-starboard symmetry. Based on our experience, we decided that a mesh with 610000 cells and a $y^+ \approx 80$ would suffice to capture all important flow patterns for reliable resistance values. This can be considered a “competitive” numerical set-up that should allow many design variations in a short timeframe (3.5 h on two cores), fairly balancing computational effort and accuracy.

4. Optimisation campaign

4.1. Overview

The next step was the assembly of the optimization chain as illustrated in Fig.7(a). The optimization tool employed was NUMECA FINE™/Design3D, which controls all the sub-processes like geometry variation and export, meshing, solver runs and data collection in the post-processor. A Python API ensures a flexible and easy to use access to the various tools and exchange of data. The optimization loop itself is based on a surrogate model. The approach is shown in Fig.7(b). It starts with the generation of a database from a sampling of the design space via a Design-of-Experiment (DoE). It aims at a maximum scattering of the samples within the bounds of the free variables with as few designs as possible. Here, 13 free variables were used and 10 designs created in a Sobol sequence. The displacement is kept constant, and $LCB = LCG$ for all designs. No hard points were violated.

From this discrete set of data points, bringing together geometry and performance, a surrogate model is built which offers a continuous description that is cheap and fast to evaluate. An evolutionary algorithm then calls this surrogate model thousands of times to generate new candidates in the design loop. The algorithm mimics evolutionary processes with selection of strong traits in a design with respect to the performance and to the constraints over several generations.

Fig.11 : Optimization chain and loop

Weak samples tend to become extinguished while methods like mutation help to keep a large diversity from one population to the next. In the end such an optimizer yields a high probability of finding optimum solutions, even globally, especially in comparison to local strategies such as a gradient method. Since the actual search is performed on the surrogate model the number of variants can be very high without using any tangible computer resources. When a new and promising candidate is identified it is evaluated by means of (substantially more expensive) CFD simulations, using the optimization chain. The results are subsequently appended to enrich the database and to provide an even better surrogate model. The process is then re-started until convergence.

4.2. Design-of-Experiment (DoE)

Prior to starting the DoE to create the actual database, a few checks for plausibility of parameter ranges and stability of the meshing and workflow templates were made. Naturally, the bounds of the free variables constitute a crucial input to any optimization: It is desirable to have sufficient geometric variability, while as few variants as possible should be unusable. The latter can appear quite easily if the chosen parametrization is not well-suited for the design task or if extreme parameter combinations lead to designs that any engineer would readily reject. Moreover, any failure in the optimization chain should be handled correctly by the optimizer. Machine issues or plain technical issues like licensing must be identified so that the optimizer does not neglect any region in the design space which could be of interest. In addition, physical phenomena like excessive drag or strong unsteadiness in resistance values should also be monitored. For this purpose, the time series for total resistance for each variant was evaluated for the last 30% of simulation time, delivering both a mean value as objective and a standard deviation for quality checks.

Results of the DoE, i.e., the database run, are displayed in Fig.12, giving the mean total resistance values and the shaft power values. The baseline is shown in the center, indicated via a large blue cross, while the points give the performance of the 39 DoE samples. The overall scattering of the resistance is quite large, and there is only little clustering of the designs, which indicate a nice sampling even with the relatively few samples. As can be seen, there are variants that perform far worse but also quite a bit better than the baseline design. The database sampling gets already a good improvement, but the subsequent optimizing achieved almost 10% in shaft power.

A surrogate-based optimization relies heavily on the quality of the prediction. If a surrogate model does not predict new and unknown variants with a certain accuracy or fails to capture trends correctly, there is no chance for any optimizer to find good solutions, at least within a reasonable timeframe.

Fig.12: Shaft power over total resistance for 12 kn and 19.5 t displacement

One way to quantify the accuracy is the “leave-one-out analysis”, which calculates the correlation and, hence, the surrogate quality of a given set of data without the need for an additional set of evaluation samples. Such an analysis is depicted in Fig.13. The correlation in this case is relatively poor compared to other projects in our experience, very likely due to the limited number of samples in limited time and some issues encountered in the CAESES process control.

Fig.13: Correlation between surrogate model prediction and CFD values

Still, the achieved “optimum” represents a significant progress in the design, albeit for one operating point (design point). The next phase was to reveal how much room for improvement there was left to exploit and whether an improved design good be achieved for a range of operating points.

4. Next design iteration

Figs.14-16 show CFD results from the first optimization campaign with the relatively coarse CFD mesh. Flow details indicating further improvement potential include:

- Bow spray still hits the tunnel in the optimized version, Fig.14.
- Ventilation at the stern still occurs in the optimized version, Fig.15.

Fig.14: Bow spray hits tunnel in both Base and Opt design (12 kn, 19.5 t)

Fig.15: Ventilation in both Base and Opt design (12 kn, 19.5 t)

One lesson learnt in this project was that designer experience can also be misleading in some cases. The flat bottom above the propeller was intended to prevent ventilation, according to literature, but the simulation proved that wrong in this case, Fig.15.

The experienced small-craft designers in our team, Stefano Carugno and Günther Migeotte, now tried to improve the design based on their experience, but unaware of parameter sensitivity. Key modifications were:

- Implement an inner spray rail, Fig.16
- Move tunnel upwards, Fig.16
- Move tunnel backwards
- Slightly modify the stern (the sensitive part!), Fig.17

Fig.16: Designer modifications at bow

Fig.17: Designer modifications at stern

Base design (“base”), design optimized for 12 kn (“opt”) and human designer modified design (“insp”) were then assessed with high-fidelity CFD simulations, 2.3 million cells and $y^+ \approx 50$. This time, a matrix of operational conditions was assessed, with 4 speeds (8, 10, 12, and 14 kn) and 2 loading conditions (17.5 t and 19.5 t). Meshing was done in FIDELITY, using the family tree option, Fig.18. The “family tree” allows very similar grids for a family of similar designs, accelerating meshing and making results well comparable.

Fig.18: Meshing in FIDELITY

Figs.19 to 22 show mesh details in CFVIEW after simulation, i.e. with the AGR free-surface modifications on the original FIDELITY mesh. Separation zones were also meshed in FIDELITY (although that could have been left to AGR as well). The local clustering in Fig.22 is also from the AGR algorithm, as we have spray there.

Fig.23 shows the results for 17.5 t displacement. Results for 19.5 t were similar in general characteristics and conclusions. Compared to the base design, the “opt” design showed improvements over the speed range, except for 10 kn (start of the hump in the resistance curve at Froude number $F_n = 0.43$). There is a higher uncertainty about the data at this speed due to a very strong unsteadiness in the flow observed in the simulations. The “insp” design lost some of the improvements of the “opt” design.

Fig.19: Mesh at bow, blue box: AGR

Fig.20: Mesh at stern, blue box: separation zone

Fig.21: Cut view actuator disc including inflow and outflow

Fig.22: Tunnel edge, blue box: separation zone

Fig.23: Resistance at 17.5 kn

Fig.24: Push stern in details for “opt” and “insp” contributing significantly to resistance difference

Small design changes have a big impact in this case. The importance of the push stern in parameter was revealed already in the DoE phase, and confirmed in this concrete comparison. This episode is a reminder of the importance of data mining, and that design parameter elucidation is a powerful tool that should not be ignored.

5. Conclusions

- A design for an electrically powered catamaran vessel was improved in a very early design stage, resulting in -10% power consumption.
- The partially parametric modelling was very time efficient for design variations, once it had been created.

- Such a design study has only modest hardware requirements: CFD simulations and optimization on 80 samples were run over a weekend on a 32-cores machine.
- The DoE phase offered important insights into critical parts of the hull which affect overall power consumption above proportion.

The project brought four companies together, two from a traditional naval architecture culture, two from a CFD simulation culture. We experienced some “frictional” losses in communication between the two cultures. Lessons learnt on the human factor side were:

- Naval architects: Do not touch an optimized design.
- CFD engineers: Tell the naval architects what you know (in a language they can understand)

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CAVE Matrix Reloaded

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Abstract

This paper presents an updated perspective on modern ship design looking at four key tasks collected under the acronym CAVE: creating design alternatives, analyzing them, visualizing options, and results, and deriving enlightenment (or knowledge) from design exploration. The paper gives some historical perspective before reviewing some modern software developments in ship design, drawing frequently, but not exclusively, on the experience of the author.

1. Introduction

The ship design process is traditionally described as a design spiral following the initial model of *Evans (1959)*. This model has been "refined" by proposing spiraling cones, *Andrews (1981)*, or interconnected spirals, *Mistree et al. (1990)*, but in essence it was the spiral in disguise, Fig.1. This model for ship design has been rejected frequently, e.g. *Ebrahimi et al. (2018)*, *Florea et al. (2022)*, as the sequence of analyses and decisions is not as sequential as the spiral models suggest. Ship design seems to be instead a rather chaotic process of combining various analyses with 'intelligent' or 'creative' generation of solutions, sometimes in parallel, which are then analyzed, evaluated, possibly rejected or modified. The sequence of these elements in the design process changes even for absolutely the same design task from designer to designer. There is no absolute criterion for what the best design process sequence is.

Fig.1: Ship design has been frequently described as a design spiral process

While different designers may well apply the same tools (or at least tools of comparable performance power), some manage to get better results. I see this in rough analogy to nature. The DNA is composed of the same four basic elements, whether it is the DNA of a bacterium or the DNA of a Nobel Prize laureate. Apparently, the proper combination of the same four simple elements can make a big difference. Rather than speculating whether computers in the (distant) future may outperform humans in the design process, I focus on the "basic elements" of ship design and highlight advances in computer technology supporting the ship design process. The ship design process remains human-centric and human-driven, but the computer accelerates processes and improves the "classical toolkit" of the designer.

Repeatedly performed tasks of the designer may be grouped into the following four key CAVE tasks:

1. Creation (creative, intelligent, or systematic creation of alternatives or design candidates)
2. Analysis (evaluation, simulation, computation, using 'Digital Twins')
3. Visualization (representation, communication)
4. Enlightenment (knowledge, identification, learning, building meta-models)

2. CAVE reloaded

The following revisits the CAVE matrix, *Bertram (2017)*, discussing the four elements, in the light of the developments of the six years that have passed since then.

2.1. Creation

The generation of candidate solutions is a rather creative task, especially in concept design. While “Artificial Intelligence” is by now widely accepted as an additional useful tool also for naval architects, *Bertram (2020)*, nobody contemplates (seriously) “Artificial Creativity”. And yet the computer may help us to generate design candidates, namely in the context of concept exploration and/or optimization, where human designers set up parametric models for a design family, Fig.1 *Harries (2020)*, and the computer explores the resulting possible designs systematically (but not exhaustively), *Bertram (2003)*, *Bertram and Campana (2020)*.

Fig.1: Parametric model, source: Friendship Systems

The key approaches are:

- Design of experiments (DoE) (previously known as concept exploration model) has been proposed as an alternative to ‘automatic’ optimization: A large set of candidate solutions is generated by varying design variables. Each of these solutions is evaluated in key performance indicators and stored. DoE thus generate a “map” of the unknown design space. Using suitable graphical displays, the designer gets a feeling for how certain variables influence the performance of the design. The approach was deemed impractical for ship design in the 1990s due the then excessive computational requirements, *Erikstad (1996)*. However, parallel computation has changed this, and concept exploration has been used in several commercial projects, e.g. *Bertram and Hochkirch (2015)* for a navy frigate.
- Optimization looks at thousands or even tens of thousands of designs and uses an optimization algorithm to find the best design. For many modern optimization problems, genetic algorithms (GAs) or related evolutionary optimization algorithm are the preferred choice. On single processors, GAs are significantly less efficient than older gradient-based search algorithms. However, they are easily parallelized and robust in finding global optima, i.e. they do not get stuck at local optima. Optimization is in theory a mathematically well-posed problem. However, objective and all constraints must be expressed as mathematical functions. This is not easy in practice.

- Multi-objective optimization is strictly speaking nonsense. Mathematically you can only optimize for one objective, respectively an optimum is only defined for one objective function. In layman terms, finding the fastest (objective: speed) and cheapest (objective: price) car will result in the question: Make up your mind, what do you want? Multi-objective optimization in practice is short for a combination of DoE and optimization. The concept exploration helps in making up one’s mind (“requirements elucidation” in the words of David Andrews of UCL). Then objectives may be reformulated as constraints or combined in one artificial objective function using weights for the individual objectives. The “best compromise” objective function can then be determined formally by the optimization algorithm of choice.

Integrated design optimization frameworks, such as CAESES, www.caeses.com, allow designers to focus on the design task and are in standard use in industrial ship design projects, achieving typically gains of 4-6% in energy efficiency (for yearly fuel consumption for main propulsion), Fig.2.

Fig.2: Typical hull optimization result, base design (bottom) and optimized design (top)

Remember that computers are essentially dumb, but diligent and fast. The human designer needs to supply the design “intelligence” in setting up parametric geometry models, objectives, and constraints to let the computer explore, diligently and efficiently, the available potential for improvement. Examples of supplying human design insight to formal optimization to obtain better results are:

- Allowing asymmetric shapes in the aftbody of ships to obtain 2-3% additional percent point on energy efficiency, *Hochkirch and Krebber (2017)*
- Considering variations in operational conditions (speed, draft) and ambient conditions, resulting in disappearing bulbous bows for full hull forms, *Bertram and Campana (2020)*, *Løvstad and Bertram (2022)*.
- Optimizing ship hulls for wind-powered or wind-assisted ships, adding simple models for the effect of the wind-harnessing systems, *Thies and Renzsch (2022)*

2.2. Analysis

Designs need to be evaluated or assessed according to various characteristics, such as resistance, strength, seakeeping, vibration, or even aesthetics. We extensively use computer models for this

purpose. When physics are modelled, we used to call the models ‘simulation models’, but more recently the buzzword ‘Digital Twin’ has become more en vogue. In most cases, it is just applying a new label to the old, familiar technology, *Bertram (2021)*.

Wikipedia defines a ‘Digital Twin’ as “a real-time digital replica of a physical device”. Siemens elaborates on this to give “a smart (dynamic), virtual representation (model) of the physical product, production process, or product’s utilization. It has the required accuracy and fidelity to predict actual, physical performance”, Fig.3. In simple terms, the vision was some IT model with the look and feel of the real deal. Not only would it look like its physical twin (this would be mere Computer-Generated Imagery or Virtual Reality), but it would behave like its physical twin, and evolve in time like it. The Digital Twin of a ship would lose strength in time as it rusts, slow down as the hull gets fouled, etc.

Fig.3: Digital Twin vision

Fig.4: Typical hydrodynamic simulation model, source: CNR

We now use the term ‘Digital Twin’ often less ambitiously for any engineering or simulation model, even if we don’t update the model to follow the as-is real-world physical twin. Digital model (for simulation) would be much more appropriate as a term, *Cabos and Rostock (2018)*.

Digital Twins can be built up completely on First Principles, i.e. basic, universally applicable physical laws, such as conservation of energy, mass, or momentum (white-box models). Digital Twins can also be built on system identification, i.e. fitting a model to empirical or statistical data (black-box models). These days, this frequently resorts to machine-learning techniques. In reality, most models are ‘grey’ boxes, combining physical insight with empirical model tuning against measurements.

Stability analyses were among the first applications of computers in naval architecture. Today, the naval architect can perform stability analyses in intact and damaged conditions quasi at the push of a button. Two other classic applications of simulations for ships are CFD (computational fluid dynamics) and FEA (finite-element analyses). Both have been used for several decades to support ship design, but today’s CFD and FEA applications are far more sophisticated than 20 years ago, *Bertram and Peric (2013,2021)*, Fig.4. Cloud computing, flexible licensing schemes and software connections have led to a democratization of CFD, where small-and-medium design offices and shipyards may have direct access to the technology, *Hildebrandt and Reyer (2015)*, *Gentzsch et al. (2016)*.

Fig.5: Digital Twin application to aerodynamics, fire, and ice breaking flows

The last decade has seen a rapid profusion of a plethora of ‘Digital Twins’ applications for ships. Flow simulations have been extended to “wind, fire, and ice”, Fig.5, modelling aerodynamic flows around ship superstructures and for ventilated rooms, fires, and numerical ice-breaking.

Discrete Event Simulation (DES) combines discrete events of a multitude of objects that are associated with specified characteristics or parameters. DES Digital Twins are increasingly used in production planning on advanced shipyards, *Steinhauer (2011)*, but can be used for a wide scope of applications from design to operation. Despite a relative simplicity of the fundamental theory, simulation for complex systems offers considerable benefits in qualitative insight (e.g. identifying bottlenecks) and quantitative information (e.g. times to perform an assembly or to unload a ship), Fig.6. Combined with simple expert systems (‘agents’), DES may be used for traffic flow simulations, e.g. to assess evacuation times of ferries.

Fig.6: DES simulation for shipyard (left) and port (right) operation, Siemens, *Steinhauer (2011)*

Fig.7: Energy flow simulation set up from object library to insight, *Kakalis et al. (2014)*

Similar object-oriented Digital Twins can be set up for energy flow simulations, where the model considers energy providers (= main engine, generator sets, sails, etc.) and energy consumers (propeller, pumps, heat exchangers, ventilators, cargo handling gear, etc.) in a network, Fig.7, *Kakalis et al. (2014)*, *Georgopoulou et al. (2021)*. Ambient conditions and operational profile are input dynamically (i.e. changing over time) and the simulation reveals energy flows and utilization rates (with bottlenecks and idleness). The detailed insight can be used to improve designs or operations.

2.3. Visualization

Wooden ships of the 16th century used already the ship definition based on cross sections erected on the longitudinal keel. The hull planks were aligned along thin wooden splines over the cross sections, Fig.8. These splines can be regarded as the forefathers of the splines used later on drawing tables to create ship lines on paper, Fig.9, and the mathematical splines used in CAD programs. *Harries (1998)*, *Bole (2012)*, and *Biran (2018)* give good overviews of the state of the art in ship hull design CAD systems.

Fig.8: Cross sections and splines, ca.1700

Fig.9: Ducks and wooden spline, TU Berlin, ca. 1995

While we retained essentially the same representation of ships over centuries, the way we design ship hulls has moved from a curve-driven process to three-dimensional models even in the conceptual stage. Parametric modelling is a powerful concept in this respect, supporting rapid exploration of design spaces interactively in CAD or automatically in optimization, Fig.10, *Harries (2020)*.

Fig.10: Variation of propeller with parametric form description, Source: CAESES

A more recent development is using 3D laser scans. These may be integrated into CAD systems using automatic surface fitting to recreate complex surfaces, *Bole (2014)*. But more recently, *Blom and Stonestreet (2022)* showed applications of direct integration of high-res photorealistic 3D laser scan data into commercial CAD software models, Fig.11. Such capability is important and required for many retrofit applications where original information is no longer available. It may also show the way to geometric Digital Twins that are updated continuously to the as-built status, not just during production but through the lifetime of ships which may see many retrofits to comply with evolving regulations and technology.

Fig.11: : Laser data integrated with 3D model in E3D Design, *Blom and Stonestreet (2022)*

The progress in CAD systems towards 3D product data models, Fig.12, envisioned already by *Aarnio (2000)* in the first COMPIT conference, allows today not only performing a large variety of analyses and simulations, but also advanced representation in photo-realistic displays or in Virtual Reality, Fig.13. While better visualization options are a bonus, the main benefit of 3D design lies in data management and creation of Digital Twins.

Fig.12: Development of ship CAD systems towards three-dimensional product models, *Aarnio (2000)*

Fig.13: Photorealistic representation of offshore supply vessels in waves, *Harries et al. (2012)*

Beier (2000) described in the first COMPIT conference how the grand vision of “fully immersive” Virtual Reality (VR) got reduced to something much more modest and tangible, namely a 3D computer model with walk-around capabilities: “The term Virtual Reality initially referred to [...] immersive systems. With time, the meaning of VR broadened and, as of today, VR is also being used for semi-immersive systems, [...] even non-immersive systems, like monitor-based viewing of three-dimensional objects.” The down-to-earth VR is useful for many applications in our industry, mainly in understanding and selling designs, Goh (2022), to training, Bertram and Plowman (2018), and marketing, Figs.14 and 15. Many papers in more than two decades of COMPIT bear witness to that.

Fig.14: VR in design, source: Siemens

Fig.15: VR in training, Bertram et al. (2020)

2.4. Enlightenment

Knowledge remains at the heart of design. Knowledge comes largely from education and work experience. However, machine learning may support human knowledge in ship design. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) allow very general functional fitting to data sets. ANNs can be applied if the functional relation between data is unknown or too complex to be explicitly specified. However, as with most Artificial Intelligence techniques, ANNs benefit from adding human knowledge. If human knowledge can e.g. eliminate irrelevant parameters or supply already a good approximation e.g. from theoretical analysis, the ANN will perform that much better in approximating the residual quantities.

ANNs and related response surface techniques can be used to derive empirical design formulas which allow fast estimates in very early design stages. In my experience, this approach has worked well for a variety of narrow-domain applications, including power predictions for tugs, Bertram and Bentin (2023), Fig.16, planing and semi-planing monohulls and catamarans, Bertram and Mesbahi (2004), and SWATHs.

Fig.16: ANN predicted and actual tug power, Bertram and Bentin (2023)

Fig.17: Propeller flow details predicted by CFD and ANN, Boogaard et al. (2022)

While earlier applications were limited to mere integral values such as power or resistance, more recent applications predict also distributions of quantities of interest, such as pressures or velocities well, provided there is enough training data and the application domain is narrow. Parametric designs and simulations can be combined to create “numerical series” for a given ship type, a term chosen in analogy to classical ship design series such as the Series 60 of the 1960s. The resulting database can then be used to fit a neural net or other response surface. Once this has been done, designers can quickly extract data from the numerical model series to substantiate their design during the bidding and tendering process (which normally takes place under considerable time pressure). For example, empirical propeller thrust and torque coefficients were used to train neural nets by *Mesbahi and Atlar (2000)*. Two decades later, *Boogaard et al. (2022)* showed very good agreement of detailed CFD simulations and ANN-predicted flow fields for propellers, Fig.17.

Numerical statistics is immensely powerful and, given enough and the right data, it can yield very powerful insight and enhance many applications in our field in the hands of intelligent engineers. But we should see A.I. as a sober engineering tool and not expect true intelligence as in Einstein’s out-of-the-box thinking from it, *Bertram (2018)*.

Knowledge-based systems (KBS) a.k.a. expert systems have been successfully applied to a wide variety of marine applications, *Bertram (2000)*. However, applications to ship design are rare and mostly disappointing. This is not really surprising. Expert systems are best suited to support tasks that are relatively simple and do not involve common sense or a “wide picture”. Ship design is a largely unstructured and creative task, where even human experts have difficulties describing how they proceed in their design work. However, partial support can be given and aid the designer in practice as demonstrated by the Dutch navy in applying QUAESTOR, a design expert system with focus on ship hydrodynamics, Fig.18, *Es and Hees (2003)*.

Fig.18: QUAESTOR expert system, source: MARIN

Fig.19: Web-based transatlantic cooperation between CAESSES and HydroComp combining best-of-breed software, *Harries et al. (2015)*

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Incentives to Holistic Methodology and Computer Aided Tool Support in Naval Vessels Design

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Abstract

This paper presents the past and present challenges of naval ship design, based on a literature review and industry specific empirical surveys. Validated evidence on support options via methodology and computer applications are presented, as well as proposals for further support and their impact on the way ships can be developed in the future. Therefore, this paper gives incentives for a holistic and coherent development of ship design methodology and tool support in research and practical implementation. The research focuses on the development system during the phases of concept design and preliminary design.

1. Introduction

The increasing complexity of sociotechnical systems requires new holistic approaches to system development, *Acatech (2022)*. In a holistic approach, both the operational environment of the system to be developed and the operational environment of the development system must be taken into account, as they influence each other, *Dove and Schindel (2019)*. The design of ships has numerous industry-specific characteristics that concern both the system to be developed and the development system. The process underlining the development system of ship design is generally divided into four phases: conceptual design, preliminary design, contractual design, and detailed design, *Gillmer (1975)*, *Watson (1998)*, *Papanikolaou (2014)*. This paper focuses on the challenges and support approaches within the development system during the conceptual design and preliminary design phases as well as within the system to be developed.

With regard to the development system, uncertainty and complexity are inherent challenges of ship design and constitute a "Wicked Problem", *Andrews (2017)*. This means that the problem is not understood until a solution is formulated, *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. Therefore, ship design methodology evolved specific processes and techniques to counter this "wicked problem". The spiral model according to *Evans (1959)* has been the most widely used model of ship development since the 1950s. Nowadays, computer aided design (CAD) and specific tools for computer aided ship design (CASD) support the design process and enable designers to create new concepts in a shorter time as well as to explore larger numbers of configurations, *Gaspar (2019)*. Even though the data-driven ship design enables sophisticated design practices, *Gaspar (2019)*, there is a need to develop further methodological support for the design of complex ships, as the spiral model provides only an unreliable representation for complex ship designs, *Pawling et al. (2017)*.

Systems Engineering (SE) methods support the development of "the right design" for complex vessels, but need to be combined with the spiral model in order to develop "the design right" with respect to the system ship, *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. The classic document-based SE approach has limitations, as it is difficult to keep information up-to-date and consistent across multiple documents, *Friedenthal et al. (2014)*, and the effort and error-proneness of making changes is high, *Madni and Purohit (2019)*. Therefore Model-Based System Engineering (MBSE) approaches improve the ability to manage system complexity, *INCOSE (2015)*. To use MBSE successfully, the three pillars: language, method, and tool must be considered, *Delligatti (2013)*, which results in an additional need for method application and computer applications in ship design.

Furthermore, new methodological approaches are required to address uncertainties in the development phases, *Agis (2019)*, since uncertainty about the operational environment of the system to be developed arises. This is especially true for naval vessels, as volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity

(VUCA acronym) characterize the environment of military operations, *Whiteman (1998)*, and multi-mission capabilities are demanded, *Andrews (2017)*. To tackle these challenges there is a need for methodological consideration and computer applied support.

As shown, the evolution of challenges in ship design is accompanied by the need for methodological support as well as tool support via computer applications. However, the relations between specific challenges, methodological support and computer applications are not always obvious. In order to enable a holistic and coherent development of ship design methodology and tool support regarding research and practical implementation in the future, this paper intends to answer the following questions:

1. What are past and present challenges of ship design with regard to the development system and the system to be developed?
2. Which validated support approaches via methodology and computer applications exist for the specific challenges?
3. Which insights and contradictions become apparent in the analysis of challenges and support approaches and which challenges remain unanswered?

To answer these questions, a literature review, as well as empirical surveys in naval vessels design were made. The results are presented in this paper.

2. Past and present challenges in naval vessels design

This paper presents the most important challenges in naval vessel design from 1945 onwards, since there was a major turning point in the technical and tactical naval development of warships, *Friedmann (1979)*. Most challenges from 1945 on are results of the changing characteristics in operating ranges of naval vessels, *Andrews (2017)*, and the way warships are designed, *Atkinson et al. (2020)*. To gain a better understanding of these challenges, some characteristics of the development system (including stakeholders, processes and tools) and the system to be developed (including operational environments and the warships itself) are presented.

Primarily, there is a need to understand that every warship is a compromise between the desires of the naval staff and the economic limits set by the government buying it. Moreover, the dominant factors in warship costs changed over the past decades from steel, to armament, sensors and command and control systems, *Friedmann (1979)*. Secondly, one needs to understand that there is a difference between wartime builds before 1945 and peacetime builds after 1945. Peacetime builds are characterised by design stagnation due to limited research budgets and cost efficiency efforts in design and manufacturing, *Atkinson et al. (2020)*, as well as the endeavour to multi-mission capability in order to provide a wide range of capabilities with a small fleet, *Atkinson et al. (2011)*. Based on this understanding some trends and resulting challenges in naval vessel design over the past decades become apparent.

One major challenge is the rising complexity and uncertainty in requirement elicitation. In times of single purpose naval vessels, a set of naval staff requirements like specified range to fight enemies, moving through seas of known character, maintaining endurance with specified speed through specified distance, was available and the basis for naval vessel design, *Friedmann (1979)*. Nowadays, naval vessels are multirole self-sufficient entities with a high degree of system complexity, *Andrews (2017)*. This results in an exponential growth of internal and external requirements and the need for methodological and computer aided support in requirements elicitation and management. Furthermore, the additional uncertainty in requirements provides a further support need, *Agis (2019)*.

As result of cost reduction efforts in ship design, there were decades without new conceptualisation of the design problem, but of pure optimisation of design spaces within existing reference concepts, *Atkinson et al. (2020)*. Therefore, the development of ships is largely based on lessons learned from existing ships and successful designs, *Papanikolaou (2014)*. Concerning the development system, amorphous procedures in concept and preliminary design used to be big problems, *Friedmann (1979)*.

To solve this problem, methodological support was developed, as shown in paragraph 3. One challenge arising from this is the fact that methodology in ship design is set up to start with reference products and optimizing designs, but not for exploiting new conceptual designs, which will be a core demand of future war ship designs according to, *Atkinson et al. (2020)*.

Subsequently, the approach to fit more and more functionality into existing design spaces led to an increasing number of subsystems and density, *Andrews (2017)*, as well as system complexity, *Atkinson et al. (2020)*. The rising complexity in systems to be developed in turn leads to the challenge of a higher complexity in the development system. Due to the necessity to integrate more several subsystems, additional staff roles in naval ship design were needed and the naval architect may not be the overall ship's architect anymore, *Andrews (2017)*. To integrate new roles and tasks in the development systems seems to be a challenge.

The support of computer applications fitted to the current design methodology within the development system will be shown in paragraph 3. Although computer applications deliver major support to ship design, there are several challenges arising from it, as shown by *Gaspar (2019)*. Computer Aided Ship Design (CASD) Software includes ship designer required special functionality for simulation and analysis. More advanced product data management (PDM) and mechanical CAD Software, as for example Siemens NX, does not. As a result, in practice there are two models in two places plus an Excel spreadsheet with calculations from trials and previous designs. Major challenges in computer applications in ship design are: missing uniform interface formats for data exchange, lack of tool integration, licensing and profit orientation of tools and high training costs and times for personal. Furthermore, the usage of generalised software for mechatronic product development does not always allow the usage of terms from ship design, which may result in information loss. Additionally new risks appear, as the risks of declining productivity levels through fully 3D practices, the risk of being locked to a system, the risk of ineffective problem solving via new methods and as lack of integration in classification society tools, *Gaspar (2019)*.

3. Support approaches via methodology and computer applications

A wide range of theoretical and practical approaches to overcome the presented challenges by methodology and computer applications support could be found in a literature review. To limit the number of approaches presented in this paper, only validated approaches from the literature or from empirical surveys conducted by the authors were considered for presentation. Nevertheless, the following sections provide only an overview of support approaches for the main challenges in ship design. The support approaches presented are not conclusive due to the large number of sources found.

3.1. Need to handle increasing complexity and uncertainty in requirements

The need for methodological support to overcome the rising complexity and uncertainty in requirements arose over the past decades. Until the 1970s, methods focused on extracting known requirements from naval staff, *Friedman (1979)*, and helping the naval staff from their point of view to elicit requirements with analytical procedures, as mission analysis, threat analysis and environment analysis, *Gillmer (1975)*. Due to the rising complexity of naval vessels and their requirements, methods of Systems Engineering (SE) with their requirements engineering and requirements management approaches gave methodologic support, *Thomas (1981)*. *Andrews (1986)* stated the further methodological need to distinguish between need analysis and the formulation of functional requirements, in order not to pre-empt the choice of solutions. He further introduced an interactive computer aided design (CAD) approach to explore further requirements by computer application support. *Watson (1998)* states the support via differentiation between essential and desirable requirements and their clarification by strategic studies and consideration of alternative future scenarios. The methodological support of requirement engineering in ship design was meanwhile questioned, as its emphasis of abstraction is counter intuitive and operational users were forced to identify future tasks without picturing potential physical solutions, *Andrews (2003)*.

Hence, more attention was paid to the concept of requirements elucidation through parallel development of problem definition, solution design and the introduction of a requirements dialogue between designer and stakeholders by exploration of different conceptual designs, *Andrews (2003)*. With the increasing support of computer applications in early phases of ship design, parallel concept and requirements exploration (C&RE) methods have been focused on, *Brown and Thomas (1998)*, *Hootman (2003)*. In particular, computer-aided simulation and analysis through computer-aided ship design (CASD) tools provide important support, *Hootman (2003)*. The method of requirements elucidation by concept exploration and concept studies is still valid, *Andrews (2018)*. Further improvements of requirements elucidation by C&RE are available, as communication of the design can be more immersive and intuitive by combining 3D models with virtual reality (VR) technology, as proven by *Linskens and van der Tas (2019)* using the UNITY VR environment.

Recent approaches, such as the Whole-of-System Analytical Framework (WSAF) in Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) by *Morris (2018)* revive Requirements Engineering approaches by introduction of computer application support via System Modelling Language (SysML). Mission modelling and analysis as introduced by *Power (2021)* is also supported by SysML computer applications. The variety of computer application tools for SysML is large and comprises CAMEO, ENTERPRISE ARCHITECT, PAPYRUS, RHAPSODY and TTOOL, to name just a few, *De Saqui-Sannes et al. (2022)*. According to *De Saqui-Sannes et al. (2022)*, the IBM Rhapsody Tool with its DOORS integration is the only computer application support that provides the full capabilities of requirements expression, requirements database management and requirements traceability.

The NAVAIS modular design process by *Rouhan et al. (2022)* represents a combination of MBSE approaches and requirements elucidation supported by continuous computer applications in 3D EXPERIENCE program by Dassault Systèmes. The methodological support of MBSE that includes Requirements (R), Functional (F), Logical (L), and Physical (P) framework (R-F-L-P) complies with the managing of one single digital model. Therefore, requirements traceability is enabled in design process as well as the reuse of requirements in future projects, *Rouhan et al. (2022)*.

Fig.1: Methodology and computer application support to overcome challenges in requirements

3.2. Need to replace amorphous procedures in concept design and preliminary design

The design spiral by *Evans (1959)* provides basic methodological support to challenge amorphous procedures in concept design and preliminary design. The spiral model has been the most widely used model of ship development since the 1950s, *Papanikolaou (2014)*. In this framework, the requirements are considered as input variables of the spiral, *Evans (1959)*, *Watson (1998)*, *Papanikolaou (2014)*, and the ship development activities are run to the concept design in the first iteration. This is followed by two to three more iterations of all activities to generate the preliminary design, *Papanikolaou (2014)*.

By iterative going through the sequences of the development spiral, an increasing level of detail of the design is generated and the iterative and interactive nature of ship development is mapped. Over time, the spiral model has evolved and been adapted to the requirements of naval ship development by *Watson (1998)* and others. According to *Watson (1998)*, the activities within the design spiral for warship design are: Configuration of weapons, space, variable weights, fixed weights, displacement, dimensions and hull form, propulsion, selection of machinery, equipment, general arrangement, superstructure, trim and stability, seakeeping, vulnerability, signature, and costing. The traditional spiral model of ship development is considered useful for properly developing ships as a technical solution using an appropriate and orthodox methodology, *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. It remains suitable for low-complexity development projects, *Manfredi and Tirone (2018)*, but provides only an unreliable representation of the development process for complex ship designs, *Pawling et al. (2017)*. Another major weakness of the traditional methodology is that stakeholder requirements are considered a fixed input at the beginning of the spiral in all variants of the spiral model, *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. More detailed process descriptions following the activities of spiral model as flowcharts were offered, for example by *Gillmer (1975)*, *Friedmann (1979)* and *Andrews et al. (2018)*.

The view of naval ships as complex systems and the use of Systems Engineering (SE) techniques to formalize the development phases are well recognized, *Andrews (1998)*. Hence, the SE Vee Diagram was also introduced to formalise and guide the procedures in ship design. SE is used significantly in ship development to manage complexity and ensure requirements are met, *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. Since the Spiral Model cannot assure that requirements are met, and Systems Engineering cannot assure that the ship design is right, *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)* introduces a hybrid between SE and Spiral Model for “Getting the right design” and “design in the right way”. Unfortunately, he does not introduce computer appicated support.

Fig.2: Methodological support to overcome amorphous procedures in concept and preliminary design

3.3. Need to handle increasing numbers of subsystems and system complexity

SE was not just introduced to ship design to overcome amorphous procedures, but also to handle increasing systems complexity. *Stark (1963)* recognized the need to examine and find methods to handle increasing numbers of interfaces and interrelationships as result of increasing functions of a single ship. The strong awareness for SE methodologies and techniques in naval ship design, as well as the establishment in practical usage were stated by *Andrews (1998)* and *Calvano et al. (2000)*. There are many papers on addressing complexity in ship design by systems engineering approaches, as stated by *Gaspar (2012)*. The necessary introduction of Systems Engineer role to the warship design process to handle the complexity of the system is also stated by *Andrews (2017)*.

More recent approaches focus on Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) in naval ship design. In MBSE, the system model becomes the primary artifact of the SE process. MBSE improves the ability to manage system complexity by allowing system models to be viewed from multiple perspectives and analyzing impacts of changes, *INCOSE (2015)*. To use MBSE successfully, the three pillars: language, method, and tool must be considered, *Delligatti (2013)*. The necessity of additional MBSE tools in computer application landscape for ship design can be stated by the expressions of *Delligatti (2013)*.

With respect to MBSE in warship design, most papers found used SysML as modelling language, *Manfredi and Tirone (2018)*, *Morris et al. (2018)*, or UML, *Tepper (2010)*. As MBSE methods for warship design, there are examples of transferring common MBSE methods to ship design as Object-Oriented Systems Engineering Methodology (OOSEM), or the Requirements-Function-Logic-Physic (RFLP) approach, *Morris (2019)*, *Rouhan et al. (2022)*. Further, there are specific methods validated for requirements, as Whole-of-System Analytical Framework (WSAF) by *Morris et al. (2018)*, and architectures, as Department of Defense Architecture Framework (DoDAF), by *Kerns et al. (2011)*, and the Nato Architecture Framework (NAF) by *Manfredi and Tirone (2018)*. Several tools were used in validated MBSE approaches, as Vitech CORE, *Kerns et al. (2011)*, Sparx ENTERPRISE ARCHITECT *Morris (2019)*, IBM RATIONAL RHAPSODY, *Brusa et al. (2018)*, and Dassault 3D EXPERIENCE, *Rouhan et al. (2022)*. These key findings on three pillars of MBSE in warship design are summarized in Fig.3.

Fig.3: Three pillars of MBSE in warship design

Although all three pillars of MBSE in warship design are approved, there are still major limitations, as shown by the following examples. *Manfredi and Tirone (2018)* validated the applicability of MBSE for complex naval vessels on example of Italian Fremm frigates, by using SysML as language and using the NAF for architectural views and to allocate physical architecture. However, they did not determine necessary tasks of concept and preliminary ship design within their framework, as e.g. hydrostatic and hydrodynamic simulations. Similar limitations are shown by introduction of MBSE to ship design by *Rouhan et al. (2022)*, by using the common RFLP method in SysML with 3D EXPERIENCE tool of Dassault Systèmes. The computer application support of the 3D EXPERIENCE tool for handling system complexity is proven by interconnecting requirements, functional structures and CAD models, *Rouhan et al. (2022)*. However, the method lacks the tasks of the spiral model methodology which are necessary to “design ships in the right way” as stated by *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. Therefore, a fit method for MBSE in ship design, as proposed by *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)* for SE in ship design, could not be found yet.

Specific support for handling the complexity of interacting parts in accordance with ship design methodology is provided by *Abels et al. (2022)* with the modular simulation approach and computer application support via ship design platform E4 (hullform, CFD, maneuvering etc.), MATLAB SIMULINK and VR visualization by UNITY. However, this approach lacks traceability within the development system and overall system complexity handling support.

3.4. Need for efficient design process via computer applications

The need for a faster and efficient design of naval vessels according to the spiral model methodology is strongly supported by computer applications. The potentials of usage of computer aided design (CAD) techniques for ship synthesis were highlighted by *Andrews (1986)* and further developed from 2D CAD tools to 3D CAD tools as standard nowadays, *Gaspar (2019)*. The reuse and optimization of successful designs, as well as scaling of similar concept solutions and parametric design are common practices supported by computer applications, *Rouhan et al. (2022)*.

Gaspar (2019) also highlighted the value of specialized Computer Aided Ship Design (CASD) tools for efficiency of the ship design process. Simulation and analysis are important tasks within the processes and activities according to the ship design spiral model (see paragraph 3.2), especially within tasks of lines and bodyplan, propulsion, hydrostatic and hydrodynamic analyses, structure analyses, stability and damage stability, *Papanikolaou (2014, Gaspar (2019))*. So specific analytical tools, like NAPA, MAXSURF, CAESES and others, accelerated the design process as well as CAD tools for construction, outfitting and documentation as NAPA CADMATIC, FORAN, and early structure analysis by DNVGL SESAM. Further advanced simulations tools like PYTHON, MATLAB, SHIP X and STAR CCM offer additional functionalities, *Gaspar (2019)*.

The usage of CASD tools also became more efficient over the past decades. Single simulation tools, that needed to be filled by hand with e.g. hull coordinates advanced to ASCII text input and automatically extracting key data from geometry to calculate propulsion and stability with integrated tools like MAXSURF. The European R&D project HOLISHIP (HOLIstic optimisation of SHIP design and operation for life cycle) also made an approach to integrate and utilize software tools for the design, analysis and optimization of maritime assets, primarily of ships, within CAESES, *Harries and Abt (2018)*. The CAESES tool unites major functionalities needed to design in the right way, according to the spiral model of ship design, but does not include functionality for MBSE. According to *Graignic (2013)*, MBSE enables the coupling of CAx islands in model-based simulation, as well as the completeness of the solution in terms of methodical development. Although PLM tools promise an integration of all specific tools and models within the lifecycle, the reality in ship design still relies on separate models. The integration in PLM tools with open standardized interfaces is a major future opportunity, *Gaspar (2019)*. Until then, the further integration of capabilities in proprietary systems like 3D EXPERIENCE by Dassault Systèmes, that combine certain CAD, CASD and MBSE tools offer additional potentials, as shown by *Rouhan et al. (2022)*.

4. Insights of the findings, contradictions and unanswered challenges

From the consideration of the challenges in chapter 2, and the support approaches via methodology and computer applications in chapter 3, some insights, unanswered challenges and contradictions become apparent. The most important insight is, that to tackle the comprehensive challenges nowadays both are needed: traditional ship design methodology as well as Model-Based Systems Engineering approaches. As the successful and efficient realization of traditional ship design methodology and MBSE nowadays relies on computer application support, a coherent toolchain of CAD, CASD and MBSE tools in concept and preliminary design stages are needed. As requirements need to be clarified by C&RE, VR applications should be considered to make the design more immersive and intuitive.

The analysis of the support approaches in chapter 3 shows that mostly single challenges are addressed by very specific solutions and that the methodological support of traditional ship design and Model-Based Systems Engineering are, in most cases, considered separately. Well-known MBSE approaches in ship design, such as *Manfredi and Tirone (2018)*, show the steps of applying MBSE in SysML, but not the methodology behind it and how it interacts with the classical spiral model ship design tasks. Other approaches like the NAVAIS modular design process by *Rouhan et al. (2022)*, consider the three classic MBSE pillars with SysML language, 3DEXPERIENCE as tool and R-F-L-P method, but do not consider the tasks and methods of ship design. The NAVAIS modular design process is also limited by not considering specialized CASD Tools on the computer application support. The only attempt at real

methodological integration is done by *Bottero and Gualeni (2022)*. Their approach in turn neglects the Model-Based Systems Engineering methodology and the computer application support required to combine the spiral model and SE in practical usage. None of the papers found, presented a coherent development that integrates MBSE methodology with traditional ship design methodology as well as the required computer application support for both. This is a contradiction to the findings of challenges and required support to overcome these challenges. Hence, an integrated approach in methodological and computer application level is demanded to solve the current challenges with available support measures.

The yet to be developed integrated MBSE Ship Design Methodology needs to be able to elucidate requirements by concept and requirements exploration (C&RE) as well as to perform mission analysis by Model-Based Requirements Engineering. In addition, it needs to unite one of the available MBSE methodologies with the tasks and procedure of warship spiral model, such as *Watson's (1998)*. The yet to be developed integrated MBSE Ship Design Methodology will need to be a computer application supported by integrated CAD, CASD and MBSE tools and optional VR applications. Therefore, a need for integration of separate tools in PLM or the development of an integrated proprietary tool with these capabilities can be stated. An unanswered question is, if the current available methodologies, or the yet to be developed integrated MBSE Ship Design method are able to solve the core demand of *Atkinson et al. (2020)* to depart from existing reference systems, abstract and open up new conceptual design spaces in naval vessels design.

Fig.4: Need for holistic support via methodology and computer applications in war ship design

5. Conclusions

The findings of this paper underline, that today’s challenges in naval vessel design are faced by both, methodological and computer application support. Available support approaches either focus on traditional methods and CASD tools in ship design, or on application of MBSE methods and MBSE tools in ship design. As solving today’s challenges requires both, there is a compelling need to integrate available methods and tools in a holistic way and extend them to tackle future tasks. On methodological level, there is a need for combination of traditional ship design spiral with SE Vee model and MBSE methods as the R-F-L-P approach. The realization will require fully integrated CAD, CASD and MBSE tools and optional VR in computer applications. Therefore, this paper gives incentives for a holistic and coherent development of ship design methodology and computer aided tool support in naval vessels design.

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Development of a Small Autonomous Surface Vehicle for Academic Competitions, Research and Teaching

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Abstract

This paper presents the process of building a small Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV) used in the Autodrone 2022 competition and in research and teaching activities at the University of South-Eastern Norway (USN). The Autodrone contest consists of four tasks where the ASVs must observe, navigate, and make decisions autonomously. USN's SeaDrone is an ongoing project. New features and equipment are continuously integrated. This paper presents the implementation of hardware and improvement of software as well as the tests done in 2022. The aim to improve and thoroughly test the software for completing the different competition tasks has resulted in an ASV that convincingly completes the given tasks. Major software improvements were a neural network to detect buoys and boats and the addition of a Human Machine Interface. Regarding the hardware, a new GPS unit with RTK capabilities made the navigation more precise. At the end, our ASV won first place in the Autodrone 2022 competition.

1. Introduction

The term autonomous have many different definitions. For this project the definition of autonomous will be “responding, reacting, or developing independently” and “undertaken or carried on without outside control”, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/autonomous>. I.e., when the ASV (Autonomous Surface Vehicle) is in autonomous mode, it will control itself and make its own decisions on where to sail. The concept of using more autonomous technology is a growing factor, as with time the technology is teaching itself and more data is generated. This can result in machines doing the repetitive, boring, or dangerous jobs and tasks for humans.

An ASV is a small vessel designed to navigate autonomously. That involves a system that can navigate, maneuver, and obey navigation regulations all by itself. To achieve this, the USN's Autonomous SeaDrone (ASD) is equipped with advanced sensors connected through advanced algorithms that provide a smart system for completing its objectives. The ASD has batteries for electric propulsion and steering, which is interesting for future electric propulsion systems and green technology. The ASD offers the possibility to perform research on a smaller vessel then later scale up to a full-scale ship. An autonomous ship could reduce crew size, and subsequently accommodation and utilities for people onboard. Space and weight savings could be used for cargo. Autonomous technology could also reduce the possibilities for human error. One of the most challenging factors is weather, with varying current, wind, and wave conditions. This affects the ASD's maneuvering and makes it harder to steer away from obstacles to avoid collisions.

The ASD uses the Robot Operating System (ROS), *Quingley (2009)*, a set of software libraries and tools widely used to build robot applications. ROS includes own commands used to implement ROS functions. ROS uses topics and messages to connect control systems, sensors, and actuators. Any equipment that has a software interface can be included in an ROS service. ROS today is used as standard in teaching robotics. It is used on a global basis in small student projects and big multi-institution collaborations. ROS is designed to be integrated with all other types of software; so it will be a part of the solution instead of giving more problems. ROS is supported and tested on Linux, Windows, macOS, and various embedded platforms. It allows seamless development of robot autonomy with both python and C++. As ROS also is open source, the community gets access to high-quality and fully featured robotics SDK.

Object detection processes images or video to detect and recognize an object as it locates it in a frame. To build up the algorithm, the software exploits machine learning or deep learning. Training the software creates a model. The objective is to make this model as fast and accurate as the human eye and brain, if not faster, <https://se.mathworks.com/discovery/object-detection.html>. The object detection technique used in this project was the SSD, *Liu et al. (2016)*. It relies on predetermined regions of pixels. The model builds a grid of anchor points that lays over the input image. Within each box in the grid is a shape that is compared with the input image. Then the model can do a prediction on how similar the shapes are. Within all these shape comparisons, many predictions are made. In post-processing the best is selected and presented.

GNSS positioning is based on how long it takes for a signal to go from a satellite to a unit on the ground. With multiple satellites it is possible to calculate the position of the unit on the ground, *Utiugova (2021)*. The calculated position is usually accurate within 2-4 m. However, with RTK (real-time kinetics) allows determining position on a centimeter level. RTK needs two GNSS receivers. One receiver is a base station placed at a known position. The base station calculates the error in position and sends corrections messages to the rover. It is not necessary that the base station is directly in line of sight of the rover. It can be in the vicinity of the rover with the use of NTRIP, *Lenz (2004)*. The rover and the base station must be within the view of 5 same satellites to correctly compute the corrections. The base station and rover can both be connected to internet and send/receive correction messages with NTRIP.

Node-RED is a programming tool for wiring together hardware devices, APIs, and online services, <https://nodered.org>. It has also community-made custom nodes for special use cases. There are special nodes for integrations with ROS. Running a MQTT bridge from the ASD and connecting with a special ROS node in Node-RED facilitates extracting information about the rover.

Autodrone (www.autodrone.no) is an annual championship for universities and other people interested in ASVs. The championship was arranged for the first-time in 2021 in Horten/Norway. The goal of USN's team in 2022 was to develop an ASV by equipping an existing one with better hardware and software, to improve the detection of buoys with different colors and other boats for collision avoidance and to use RTK GNSS for better position estimation. In addition, a Human Machine Interface (HMI) was implemented to visualize what the ASV is observing and doing. The main goal of the project was to have a fully ASV competing in Autodrone 2022 that could complete all the subtasks, including the following added features:

- Speed mission: use object detection to detect buoys of different color, then make waypoints and navigate through and around the right buoys;
- Obstacle channel: use object detection to detect buoys of different color, then make waypoints to navigate safely through the path;
- Collision avoidance: use both the lidar sensor and the object detection to detect obstacles, then navigate through a trafficked area and avoid collision; and
- Docking: use object detection to detect buoys, then make a waypoint, navigate to the point and hold the ASD steady on that point.

The next section gives more details about each mission in the championship.

This project is continuous work from the previous USN entry to the Autodrone 2021, *Tufte and Falleth Olsen (2021)*. As some of the equipment changed, some of the software had to change as well. After testing more on water and with new equipment, some of the code for the missions in the competition was updated or changed entirely.

2. Autodrone 2022 contest

The Autodrone 2022 is a contest for small ASVs where different universities compete. The competition is open for participants outside academia, too. USN hosted the Autodrone 2022 for the second year. For

the competition, there are a set of rules, regulations, and requirements for ASVs. All these must be fulfilled to participate. The requirements are listed in the Autodrone rules document. Each competitor had to compete in four challenges, Fig.1:

Task 1 – Speed Mission: The ASV will be timed from when it passes through the start gate. Then the ASV must navigate around a yellow buoy before returning to the start gate again. Completing the course within 10 minutes awards 10 points, and additional points will be awarded the 3 fastest teams.

Task 2 – Obstacle Channel: The ASV must maneuver through a course of buoys while also avoiding obstacles in its way. The AS must always stay within the defined pathway and avoid contact with other objects. Each collision will result in a 10 points penalty. The mission will be timed, and for every minute there will be subtracted 5 points from the starting number of points. For each successful gate passing the team will be awarded 5 additional points

Task 3 – Collision Avoidance: The ASV must pass through a trafficked area while maneuvering through according to navigational collision avoidance regulations. After completing the maneuver, the ASV must track back to its original path passing through the gate buoys. Each successful gate awards 10 points, and a collision gives a 30 points penalty. Managing to correctly obey the navigation regulations awards 30 points.

Task 4 – Docking: The ASV must be able to dock to a designated area marked with a green and red buoy. A successful docking implies that the ASD can localize the docking area, maneuver into docking position, and stay docked for at least 30 s in the defined area. After a completed docking the ASV must leave the dock. Points will be awarded for reaching the dock, docking correctly and 2 points for every second it stays docked. This must be completed within 10 minutes.

Fig.1: Autodrone 2022 mission layout, *Autodrone (2022)*

3. Methodology

Throughout the project, there were three stages of building. First, the previous system was run through to study how the entire system was connected, and test if the different components would work. The second phase was implementing the new equipment and making the necessary changes. Last phase includes testing of the different systems and components and the complete process.

3.1. Rebuild – First phase

The focus was on understanding the previous systems, how it all comes together and communicates with the different ROS nodes through ROS messages. This phase was spent studying code, literature, documents and wiring the previous used equipment to check status and wiring diagrams.

3.2. Implementation – Second phase

The improvements were implemented. New equipment with better data, measurements, and range was installed, new and better software developed. One of the new implementations was changing from color

recognition to object detection to detect buoys and other boats. A new GPS with better accuracy was installed to support more precise navigation of the ASD. A new router with a new Wi-Fi-antenna was installed for better range of wireless communication. An industrial version of the previously used camera was installed, which is more robust and has a polarizing filter for better video quality when outdoors. Different mounts for some of the hardware were designed and 3D-printed. The different mounts made it possible to fasten the equipment to the hull of the ASD and add protection to the hardware.

3.3. Testing and tuning – Last phase

All the hardware and software were tested, and that the communication between them worked. First, they were tested in the lab when the equipment got installed, later on land as installed on the hull, then in water to see how it worked in its operating environment.

4. Development

From the previous version of the SeaDrone, *Tufte and Falleth Olsen (2021)*, the hull is new but has the same design as before. Reused equipment includes a RPLidar, emergency switch, T200 thrusters, Jetson Xavier NX, Raspberry Pi 3b+, Emlid Navio 2, Radio controller with receiver, JX servo and 12V batteries. When keeping the same servos and thrusters, the Raspberry Pi code for these could be reused with no changes.

4.1. Edited functions

The previous programming was used as a good foundation where assorted changes were implemented. The functionality of how waypoints are stored and placed was already implemented, but now the waypoints in the different missions were slightly adjusted. The navigation script which navigates to different waypoints was edited to better handle the different tasks. With new equipment installed, all code related to these had to be updated. As more testing was done on each mission, faults were addressed to find more suitable solutions.

4.2. New implementations

Some of the old equipment was replaced with newer or sturdier versions for better performance of the ASD. The new equipment included a Zed 2i camera, Teltonika router with a Poynting Omni antenna, a GPS with IMU from Xsens for better accuracy. The Xsens unit had to be configured with the correct settings. Calibration for the magnetic fields surrounding the unit was done with the ASD in its working environment. To indicate which mode the boat is in a light with red, yellow, and green light was installed controlled via a relay card. The previous buoy recognition was replaced with object detection to increase range and stability of detections. The object detection also allowed detecting other boats and is used in addition to the lidar to avoid collisions. A new HMI was created that allows the operator to observe the thruster input, servo angle, a live video from the ASD with live detections with additional range, and a live map that plots ASD position with waypoints and buoys. Some of the new equipment and new solutions demanded specially designed and 3D-printed mounts.

4.3. Hardware

To enable the ASD able to navigate and receive inputs from the surroundings, it is necessary to have hardware such as sensors, actuators, and microcontrollers. Table I lists the equipment used, with some information about each equipment and their task in the ASD.

Table I: Equipment list

Quantity	Type	Model	Comments
1	Microcontroller	Raspberry Pi 3b +	ROS master and communication with Arduino
1	HAT for microcontroller	Emlid Navio 2 HAT	Mounted on top of Raspberry Pi and responsible for PWM signals to the actuators
1	Radio controller	FRSKY Taranis X9D Plus	Steer the SeaDrone when in manual mode and switch to auto mode.
1	Microcontroller	Nvidia Jetson Xavier NX	Collects and processes all sensor data.
1	Router	Teltonika RUTX12	Includes different antennas and used to connect the different devices
1	Wi-Fi-antenna	Poynting Omni-496	Connected to the router to extend the wireless communication range
1	Stereo camera	Stereolabs Zed 2i	Used to capture the images for the object detection.
1	RPLidar	Slamtec RPLidar S1	Used to map the environment in the collision avoidance and docking.
1	GPS/IMU	Xsens MTi-680G	Including antenna. Gives the position and orientation of the SeaDrone.
2	Thruster	BlueRobotics T200	Gives speed to the SeaDrone
2	ESC	BlueRobotics Basic ESC	Controls the speed of the thrusters
2	Servo	JX BLS-12V7146	Controls the heading of the ASD
	Light	Luban Led signal tower stack	Indicates the state of the ASD.
2	Batteries	Skanbatt LiFePO4 12V 20AH	Powers the SeaDrone
1	Microcontroller	Arduino Nano	Communicates with the Raspberry Pi and controls the relay card.
1	Relay card	Velleman VMA436	8 channels. Connects the Arduino Nano to the light and actuators.

4.3.1. Installation

To install and power up all this hardware, it was necessary to make some installation drawings. Fig.2 shows how the main power circuit is installed. The two batteries are connected in parallel and further divided in two individual circuits that supply a servo, thruster, and microcontroller each. One circuit is also supplying the router, and the other is supplying the light.

Fig.2: Power circuit

Fig.3 (left) shows how the control circuit for the Raspberry Pi is connected. The Pi is connected to the router through ethernet and that powers the Arduino Nano through USB. The Nano is connected to the relay card and the PWM signals from the Navio 2 go through the relays. Fig.3 (right) shows how the control circuit for the Nvidia Jetson is connected. The Jetson is connected to the router through ethernet and that powers the camera, lidar and GPS through USB. Fig.4 shows the final version of the SeaDrone with all the equipment.

Fig.3: Control circuit raspberry Pi (left) and Nvidia Jetson (right)

Fig.4: SeaDrone with all equipment installed

4.3.2. Watertight boxes

Navio 2, ESC, router and relay card are all mounted in three watertight boxes, Fig.5. These boxes also make the design tidier inside the ASD. The lid of every box is labelled with what is inside to facilitate searching for specific components in case of changes or troubleshooting. All the equipment inside the boxes is attached with Velcro for easy removal or arrangement.

Fig.5: Outside and inside the watertight boxes. Raspberry Pi box, Nvidia jetson box and Router box

4.4. Software

To make the ASD perform, software is needed to let all the hardware communicate together and code to tell how the ASD shall act in given situations. This is described in this chapter.

4.4.1. ROS

ROS allows controlling the servos and thrusters from both the Taranis x9d controller and from coded algorithms created with Python. In auto mode, the stereo camera, lidar and GPS are all included to position and maneuver the ASD in the water. To connect everything, ROS can manage the two control systems, Jetson, and Raspberry Pi to communicate and take inputs to give the correct outputs. Python is used for almost all the coding within this project, along with imported ROS libraries. Each Python script is integrated with ROS; so messages are sent to different other scripts.

4.4.2. Object detection

Object detection with neural networks was one of the biggest upgrades to the ASD in this project. The use of neural networks makes detection fast and accurate. To detect buoys, a code was developed to implement the TensorFlow model as described in the following sections. The code takes the image published to a rostopic by the Zed 2i camera and converts it to an input tensor. This image is then fed through the loaded model. The model returns an array of detections with bounding-boxes, scores as well as detection classes. A copy of the image from the Zed 2i is then manipulated with bounding boxes, detected color and distance to the object. Libraries in TensorFlow io to visualize detections existed. However, TensorFlow io could not be implemented on the Jetson Xavier NX. Therefore, code was implemented to visualize the detections. The detected color is extracted by taking five points in the middle of the detection and then taking the average RGB values and converting to HSV, Fig. 6. The HSV value is then converted to text. The necessary data about the buoys are published to separate rostopics depending on the color of the buoy. This includes distance in (x, y, z) and relative angle to the buoy.

Fig.6: Buoy detection flow (SharkD)

The same model is used for the detection for boats, with input from the Zed 2i and through the model. When creating the model, it was built with TensorFlow, but with the diverse types of boats and ships it can encounter on the water, the number of pictures necessary increased. Using Open Images, it was possible to download pictures already annotated, and with Roboflow, <https://roboflow.com>, these annotation files could be converted to .xml files fitting the TensorFlow format.

4.4.3. HMI

To view data about the ASD's different sensors and actuators, an HMI in Node-RED was created. A special node which subscribes to the different ROS topics was used to extract relevant sensor and actuator data. From this node, several JavaScript function nodes were used to sort the relevant data from the topic to display in the HMI, Fig.7. The data is sorted in distinct categories so that the user can easily get an understanding of what the ASD is doing and observing.

Fig. 7 Node-RED HMI

Also, a map was implemented to display different waypoints and observations of buoys with GPS coordinates. It is then easy for the observer to see where, in relation to the ASD, the different observations and waypoint are placed. An example of this is shown in the bottom left corner of Fig.7. The detection camera feed is also displayed at 5 Hz in bottom right corner of the HMI. The camera feed is throttled by using “topic tools”.

The Node-RED application is run on a laptop due to CPU limitations on the Xavier. The laptop is connected to the ASD’s Wi-Fi and gets data from a ROS package called `rosbridge_suite`. It is also possible to connect through a phone (see instructions on the Node-RED-contrib-remote webpage). The phone connection does not depend on Wi-Fi. Therefore, in the future, it will be possible to run the Node-RED application onboard the ASD and get the HMI on the phone over a 4G connection.

4.4.4. RTK GNSS

An RTK GPS on a rover needs to access correction data from a base station. This can either be solved with a radio setup or NTRIP, *Lenz (2004)*. NTRIP, or Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol, works by sending correction data from a base station over internet to a rover. This is essential to achieve a high level of accuracy. To implement this solution onto the ASD, an already made ROS package called `ntrip_ros` was installed to the system. This package acts as a NTRIP client, where information about the NTRIP caster/server is filled into a launch file. The caster/server information is taken from a website which lists different casters, www.rtk2go.com.

The Xsens MTI-680G is configured to subscribe to this rostopic and sends the correction data to the onboard processor. In return the Xsens MTI-680G publishes to a rostopic called `/status`. This is a 16-bit status “word” that indicates the status of Xsens. This “word” is displayed in the HMI, but is converted and displayed as “FIX”, “FLOAT” or “NO FIX/FLOAT”. FIX indicates that the Xsens unit can calculate its position with high accuracy. Float means that its able to calculate its position, but not as accurate. The “NO FIX/FLOAT” means that only the raw GPS signals are used to estimate position. To indicate whether the correction messages are accessible to the Xsens unit, the sequence number is displayed in the HMI. The sequence number is part of the message header published and works as a counter.

4.4.5. Competition modes

To make the ASD complete each mission in the Autodrone competition, it must interpret and act differently to the different circumstances:

- Speed mission** – Here, the ASD is placed in front of one red and one green buoy with a yellow buoy 20-30 m further ahead. The ASD shall then navigate through the first buoys, around the yellow buoy and then back through the green and red buoy again. When the ASD is placed in front of the first gate and detects the buoys, the program will make the first waypoint in the middle between the two buoys. Then it will make six more waypoints straight ahead, each 5 m apart. The reason for making so many waypoints is to try to keep the heading of the ASD as steady as possible and keeping it from drifting away. This approach is illustrated in Fig.8 (left). When the ASD detects the yellow buoy, the ASD will stop its forward motion and the program will delete the remaining waypoints and make six new surrounding the yellow buoy: The first 3 m to the right of the buoy, the second 3 m behind the buoy, the third 3 m to the left of the buoy, the fourth 3 m in front of the buoy, the fifth 5 m in front of the red and green buoy, and the sixth in the middle of the buoys, so that the ASD navigates back through the gate. This will make the ASD navigate fast and safely through the path.

Fig.8: Speed mission (left), Collision avoidance (center), and Docking (right) waypoint placement

- Collision avoidance** - Here, the ASD shall navigate between red and green buoys and avoid colliding with other boats on the track. The ASD is programmed to make three waypoints in the direction of the heading at the start (WP0, WP1, WP2 in Fig.8 (center)). When entering the first two gates, the camera will detect the boats. Depending on position and direction of the oncoming boat in relation to the ASD, the ASD will either wait or continue to the next waypoint. If the lidar detects an object directly in front, the ASD will stop and wait for the obstruction to disappear. The alternative solution is to navigate behind the oncoming traffic. The waypoint(s) associated with this solution is marked with “AWP” in Fig.8 (center).
- Docking** - Here, the ASD starts with a red buoy, a green buoy, and a pier 10 m straight ahead. The ASD shall navigate between the buoys, dock at the pier, and hold the position for 30 s. Fig.8 (right) shows the navigation planning. The ASD will in the beginning move forward towards two waypoints straight ahead. When the ASD detects both the red and the green buoy, the thrusters will go in reverse for 2 s to stop the ASD. WP2 will then be calculated. WP2 is the docking point, and the ASD will move very slowly towards that point. When the waypoint is reached the thrusters will turn 90° to push the back of the ASD toward the dock. When the lidar is registering that the dock is close to the side, the thrusters will slow down keeping a low force towards the dock and the outer thruster will be aligned with the ASD and used with a

simple P-controller to hold the position in X direction steady. The P controller takes the distance to the green buoy from the lidar and regulates to a setpoint. When the docking is finished, both thrusters will push the ASD back out with an angle for 7 s and will then navigate back to the starting position.

- **Obstacle channel** - Here, the ASD shall navigate through a path of red and green buoys, with yellow buoys placed as obstacles in random places on the path. To make the ASD navigate safely through a path like this, several different scenarios must be considered. Fig.9 shows how the waypoint will be set between the buoys, when there is more room to pass through. The ASD will calculate the space between each of the buoys and set a waypoint where the spacing is the biggest. If only the yellow buoy is detected, Fig.9(b), the ASD will go around the buoy and continue to the backside of the buoy where it should be able to detect the next set of buoys. If the buoy is located on the right side, the ASD goes around the left side and opposite for the other side. If the ASD detects a normal gate without any obstacle, it will set a waypoint in the middle, Fig.9(b), and drive right through. If only one green or red is detected, the waypoint will be set to one of the sides, Fig.9(c). If it is a red buoy then the ASD knows that it must pass on the right side as through the whole obstacle course it mostly keeps red buoys on its left side, and the opposite applies for the green buoys. If no buoys are detected, the lidar will search for the closest object and turn the boat to that angle and head that direction.

Fig.9: Obstacle channel solution setup

4.4.6. PID Navigation

To improve the navigation of the ASD, a PID controller was added to the navigation system, namely the simple-pid, *Lundberg (2011)*. The PID controller regulates the heading of the ASD where the input is the current heading, and the setpoint the desired angle. The output of the PID controller is converted to servo-angle, to make the ASD reach its waypoints.

5. Results

Hardware and software were tested to find potential weaknesses and optimum solutions. Tests were performed on three different stages: in the lab, on the university's parking lot, and in water.

5.1. Lab testing

The first tests were performed in the lab, to check the wiring and overall functionality. Since there was no GPS signal in the lab, testing the entire system or any programs dependent of the GPS was reserved for outdoor testing.

Fig.10: Lab testing of the buoy detection and boat detection

For the buoy detection test in the lab, we just tested that the detection worked and did not test the detection range. The reason for this is that the lighting conditions are different indoors, so results most likely would be different.

5.2. Onshore testing

The systems were tested also outside, on the university's parking lot, where the rest of the code that needed a GPS signal could also be tested.

For buoy detection, a camera was fixed to one location, and every 1 m was marked in front of the camera, Fig.11 (left). The test assessed how far the model can detect buoys and how stable the detection is. While moving further back 1 m at a time, the percentage is observed and noted in a table used later to calculate a score for the model. The model with the best score and best observations was used later for boat detection. Models 100 000, 120 000, 140 000, and 180 000 got the highest scores, Fig. 11 (right). Model 120 000 had the highest stability score of the four.

Fig.11: Results for the buoy detection test

For the heading test, a big rectangle was drawn on the parking lot, Fig.12 (left). The ASD was then pushed on a trolley, following the line of the rectangle, and plotting the heading data to see if the heading was stable on the straight lines, that the ASD turned 90° in every corner, and that the heading was the same at the start and stop location, Fig.12 (right). The heading on the Xsens is much more stable than on the Navio 2. The Navio 2 has a lot of oscillations and the Xsens none. The Xsens ended up at the same heading after completing the whole rectangle.

Fig.12: Heading test - heading on the y-axis (north referenced) and time on the x-axis

For the GPD accuracy test, the ASD was placed at a point and stood on exactly same position during the whole test. The coordinates were plotted every 10 s for 5 min, with and without correction messages. Fig.13 (left) shows the results. One square equals ~0.5 cm in x-axis and 1 cm in y-axis, i.e., the GPS has a deviation of ~1.5 cm in longitude and 3 cm in latitude. The graph shows only six points, because

a lot of the points were on the same coordinates. On Fig.13 (center), each square equals ~ 5 cm in x-axis and 10 cm in y-axis, i.e., the GPS has a deviation of ~ 6 cm in longitude, and ~ 31 cm in latitude. On Fig.13 (right), each square equals ~ 5 cm in x-axis and 10 cm in y-axis. It shows how much more accurate the GPS is when it gets correction messages.

Fig.13: Plotted result of holding position test with FIXED signal (left) and with no correction messages (center). Comparison of the results (right). Latitude on the y-axis, longitude on the x-axis.

For the follow path test, the USN logo was drawn with big letters on the parking lot. The ASD was then pushed, following the lines of the drawing, Fig.14. All the three rounds of each test are plotted in the same graph. On both graphs, each square equals ~ 2 m in x-axis and 1 m in y-axis. The produced USN logo is recognizable, and it is difficult to separate the colors from each round, i.e. just small deviations.

Fig.14: Results of follow path; latitude on the y-axis, longitude on the x-axis.

To test the accuracy of the placement of the waypoints, a test was performed where the ASD was placed on a given place on the university's parking lot. When the ASD was placed on these coordinates the heading was noted, so it was possible to calculate where the waypoint theoretically should be placed. The ASD was then programmed to place a waypoint 10 m straight ahead. The coordinates of the placed waypoint were then plotted. To calculate and show the difference, every coordinate was plotted in a table at the end. Table II shows the results from the waypoint test. The calculated waypoint is calculated using an online version of Vincenty's formula. The plotted waypoint is noted from what was shown on the HMI, and - as shown - it is very accurate.

Table II: Results from the waypoint test

	Start point	Calculated waypoint	Plotted waypoint	Deviation
Longitude	10.4401928°	10.4403164°	10.4403161°	0,0000003° ≈ 1.5 cm
Latitude	59.3691632°	59.3692274°	59.3692271°	0,0000003° ≈ 3 cm

5.2.1. Mission tests

- **Speed mission:** By following the commands shown on the HMI, the ASD was at the end pushed through the path with satisfactory results. It had good clearance to the yellow buoy and found the way back through the red and green buoy.
- **Obstacle channel:** Although there were only three buoys available, the testing of this mission onshore was successful. Following the thruster and servo output displayed on the HMI, the ASD was pushed in the correct direction. The waypoints placed made the ASD navigate through all the different scenarios it encountered.
- **Collision avoidance:** Not tested due to the lack of boats on land.

- **Docking:** By following the commands shown on the HMI, the ASD was pushed in between the buoys and stood there for a given time before it reversed out and returned home. Since there is no outdoor inference (wind and waves), when the ASD is placed on a trolley, results could be very different when performing offshore.

5.3. Offshore testing before the competition

The results from the offshore tests are the most important results, as the last step from testing to actual use. The ASD was taken outside and placed in water and tested with the conditions expected during operation. The results from these tests are the most relevant for choosing the right model for object detection, timing, and behavior in the water for the ASD during the competition. The boat detection test assesses the model's ability to detect other boats at different angles and at two different ranges. The long range is when the whole boat fits inside the camera frame. The short range is when only parts of the boat fits inside the frame. The three different angles are straight across, incoming across and passing by and away across the frame. For the test, a video is recorded of a boat crossing in all the diverse ways. Then the video is fed to the model and analysed to document how well the model performs. Each model is given a score based on the results, Fig.15, and the scores are compared to find the most optimal one. The 100 000 and 120 000 models give the two best values with the 100 000 model scoring five points more.

Fig.15: Graph presenting the total score from the boat detection test

5.3.2 Mission tests

- **Speed mission:** After testing it several times in water with small adjustments, the ASD was able to run perfectly through the path. Even in strong wind, the ASD was able to navigate through the path with good clearance to the yellow buoy.
- **Obstacle channel:** Not tested
- **Collision avoidance:** Not tested
- **Docking:** The docking mission seemed to be the most difficult mission for the ASD. Since the gap between the buoys was 2 m and the ASD is 1.8 m long, it only has a clearance of 20 cm between the buoys. The technique used for the docking makes the mission not as difficult. At first it was tried to parallel park the ASD as a car would do, but the timing and precision was too difficult.

7. Conclusion

The ASD was rebuilt from scratch with some new hardware, with most equipment mounted with newly designed mounts. 3D-printed mounts make the design of the ASD much tidier, which facilitated adjusting and moving equipment to fit the needs for this project.

The software was improved using object detection rather than algorithms to detect round shapes and color. The object detection software is fast and accurate but takes up a lot of CPU and GPU. The range of the object detection could be improved using a different object detection model, but should be good

enough for this application. Implementation of an HMI made troubleshooting and deploying improvements or changes easier.

The ASD is fully autonomous and can navigate through different paths by making waypoints from what it detects in the water. The lidar data also helps with making decisions and navigation.

The main project goal was to have a fully Autonomous SeaDrone (ASD) able to complete the different tasks on the Autodrone 2022 competition. Implementation of new hardware and software took a lot of time, but we were rewarded by winning the competition.

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Applying ANNs to Derive Empirical Design Formulas for Harbor Tugs

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Abstract

This paper describes how a database of harbor tugs was used to derive simple design formulas for conceptual design. The approach used artificial neural nets to predict power and displacement based on speed and bollard pull, using length as additional parameter that may be estimated using conventional design formulas for tugs. The agreement of predictions with an independent validation data set is very good.

1. Introduction

Tugs are work boats which differ in many aspects from normal cargo ships, Fig.1, *Allan (2003)*. The main design specification concerns manoeuvrability and ability to assist escort vessels in manoeuvring. Design experience and empirical design formulas for conventional cargo ships or fast pleasure craft are not applicable to tugs. This was the motivation for us to develop corresponding semi-empirical formulas for harbour tug design, *Bentin and Bertram (2000)*, *Bertram and Bentin (2001)*.

Fig.1: Typical harbor tug

Conventional regression analysis has been extensively used in naval architecture in system identification to provide required factors and coefficients. Based on databases of existing designs, coefficients are then interpolated or even extrapolated to calculate coefficients for a new application, e.g. for simple design methods as in *Watson (1998)*, *Schneekluth and Bertram (1998)*, *Bertram (2012)*. This procedure requires specification of not the main input parameters, but also the type of functional relation between input and output parameters. Most often in the past, simple linear relations (or even worse just constants) have been chosen. Designers plotted data and by visual inspection sometimes chose also simple polynomial relations. Higher-order polynomials have the unfortunate tendency to introduce unphysical oscillations.

This approach is cumbersome and unsuitable for many nonlinear relations. Unsatisfactory approximations in conventional regression analyses stem mainly from the inappropriate choice of inherent function used in statistics. In the language of Germans and mathematicians, we fail from the 'ansatz'. Wouldn't it be nice to have some mathematical way of mimicking the curve we would instinctively draw through such data sets, ignoring implausible outliers and following the trends our eye sees, something flexible yet smooth and free of inappropriate oscillations? For the naval architect, this is old hat. We have approximated arbitrary point sets for centuries, Fig.2), using first flexible thin beams (splines), Fig.3, and later using aptly named spline curves, which do not oscillate and form smooth curves and surfaces, see e.g. *Veelo (2004)*.

The machine learning community prefers other functions, such as sigmoid functions, Fig.4. Combining many of these, we have similar basic qualities of flexible approximation and avoiding oscillations.

Fig.3: Rembrandt painting of shipbuilder using smooth curves to describe ship lines

Fig.4: Traditional splines for ship design, source: TU Berlin

Fig.4: Sigmoid function (typically $\beta = 1$ in our applications)

2. Artificial Neural Nets for functional approximation

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) offer a more versatile and user-friendly approach to system identification, *Mesbahi (2003)*, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artificial_neural_network. ANNs can generally represent the mapping of multi-dimensional input/output data sets, i.e. an arbitrary number of input variables x_i and output variable y_i . An ANN structure consists of several layers; each layer consists of several nodes. In the example in Fig.5, we have the input layer, the output layer, and one hidden layer.

Fig.5: General structure of an Artificial Neural Network

The ANN is “trained” on data sets. This training process results in mathematical relationship output variables y_i and input variables x_i , e.g. of the form (for a single-input, single-output ANN):

$$y = c_0 + c_1 \cdot \text{sig} [b_0 + b_1 \cdot \text{sig}(a_{10} + a_{11} \cdot x_1 + a_{12} \cdot x_2 + \dots) + b_2 \cdot \text{sig}(a_{20} + a_{21} \cdot x_1 + a_{22} \cdot x_2 + \dots) + \dots]$$

Here, sig denotes the sigmoid function. After sufficient training, adjusted values for the coefficients a , b , and c are derived and the non-linear relationship is determined. Now the ANN can very rapidly determine values y_i for given values x_i . For numerical reasons, it is advisable to normalize input and output values between 0 and 1:

$$\text{Normalised value} = (\text{Real value} - \text{Min. Value}) / (\text{Max. value} - \text{Min. value})$$

“Deep Learning”, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deep_learning, is a more recent buzz word used when neural nets with two or more hidden layers are used. Having an additional layer means that the transfer function (e.g. the sigmoid function) is calling in itself a transfer function. This adds more flexibility in approximating functions, but requires also more data for training to be successful.

ANNs are a powerful tool in numerical statistics for many applications, and particularly in our context for empirical formulas used in conceptual ship design or formal optimization applications, when fast and moderately accurate estimates are needed. They are not a magic bullet; they cannot perform miracles. ANNs reach their limitations in several cases, *Bertram (2022)*, *Colle and Morobé (2022)*:

- random or quasi-random processes
- scarce data sets
- extrapolation far beyond the data set used in the system identification

3. Application to harbor tugs

The starting point of each ANN analysis is a database. In our case, the database was developed using tug designs of Kölln/Jacoby consulting engineers in Hamburg, enriched by additional data supplied by Hitzler shipyard, Schottel, and Voith Hydro. 58 tugs of different size, age, and propulsion systems retrieved from paper files to feed the database.

For the ANN analyses, between 70% and 80% of the datasets were used for training the ANN; the rest was set aside for validation. The accuracy of the ANN predictions was presented by calculating the correlation between the real and predicted outputs.

Key input parameters are design speed V in [kn], bollard pull t in [t] and length L_{pp} in [m]. The non-metric units of knots and tons (for forces) are used, as these are the customary units in the tug design community.

Key output parameters are mass displacement Δ in [t] and engine power P in [kW]. If L_{pp} is not known in early design (as it depends in turn typically on installed power), it may be estimated based on required bollard pull t and propulsion type:

- Schottel: $L_{pp} = (60.513 \cdot t - 40.278)^{0.1560} / 0.1269$
- Voith-Schneider: $L_{pp} = (72.103 \cdot t - 8.0)^{0.2244} / 0.1996$
- Conventional: $L_{pp} = 7.272 \cdot t^{0.4063}$

To make the results accessible for the wider community, we extracted the internal representation from the ANN software to derive the following explicit and programmable formulas, *Bertram and Mesbahi (2000)*:

$$\Delta = 26 + 886 \cdot \text{sig}[-4.36 \cdot \text{sig}(-0.1093 \cdot t - 0.6485 \cdot V + 14.1646) - 3.08 \cdot \text{sig}(-0.0579 \cdot t - 0.6912 \cdot V + 7.402) + 3.6]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P = & 1060 + 3354 \cdot \text{sig}(1.23 - 6.44 \cdot \text{sig}(0.08652 \cdot L_{pp} - 0.3171 \cdot t - 3.84 \cdot V + 60.4709) \\
& + 2.97 \cdot \text{sig}(0.8539 \cdot L_{pp} + 0.2307 \cdot t - 0.484 \cdot V - 23.07) \\
& - 5.98 \cdot \text{sig}(0.2596 \cdot L_{pp} + 0.0856 \cdot t + 0.51 \cdot V - 17.577) \\
& + 2.61 \cdot \text{sig}(0.2857 \cdot L_{pp} + 0.7132 \cdot t + 0.476 \cdot V - 25.7645))
\end{aligned}$$

After training the neural network on the data subset for training, predicted results were compared with real values from the data subset for validation. Agreement was good, e.g. for the power prediction, Fig.6, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9945.

Fig.6: Comparison of ANN predicted and installed power in validation data set

4. Conclusion

Artificial neural nets are a powerful tool to derive empirical design formulas. They require a sufficiently large data set; this can be a challenge in some applications in ship design, namely for unconventional ship types. Training process and application are straight-forward in comparison.

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Tell me

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Abstract

Maritime software development for ship design is at a crossroads. The developments in past decades were predominantly aimed at automating human labour. Even when new methods have been developed for a task — such as mathematical representations of the ship's hull, as a replacement of the hand-drawn lines plan — they were designed on the basis of closed algorithms and determined outcomes. These developments will never really come to an end, for there will always be a need for new integrations, features, options, interfaces etc. However, the core set of algorithms used for such applications are matured, by now. On the other hand, a new direction has evolved, employing machine learning, big data, and large arrays of sensors. It is generally expected that this will bring a new outlook for ship design, as demonstrated by the sheer number of papers on this subject. Under the slogan “practice what you preach”, at SARC we have also set some careful steps in the direction of design automation over the past years, and concluded that their reception by the daily user is not warm. These examples, and a qualitative analysis are elaborated in this paper.

1. Introduction

PIAS, www.sarc.nl/pias/, is a computer program for the naval architectural design and computations and verifications of ships. It was conceived in the early 1980s and has in the decades of development matured to a reliable and versatile tool. Market acceptance of PIAS in its early period was smooth, which comes as no surprise, because what we essentially had done was automating the dull and tedious labour of manual-driven computations of e.g. stability, damage stability, grain stability, launching and tank soundings. Those computations used to be done either manually, or with some computer support, albeit not very integrated, and predominantly with tabular input and output. I remember a particular shipyard which besides the design office had a ‘calculation office’, where the production of a damage stability manual (including maximum allowable VCG in damaged condition and extensive tables and graphs) for a chemical tanker under BCH Code took some 1000 man hours. With PIAS that was reduced by a factor 10 (in those days; now it will be another order of magnitude lower), so that was an easy sell! Because what our program did was essentially the same as what they used to do, although much faster.

So, what we essentially did was automating the manual labour, and that has essentially been completed. Obviously, the work is never finished; there will always remain demand for new functions, features and enhancements, illustrated by the record of SARC's ticketing system over the past decade. That includes some 3000 issued items, from which some 2500 are closed which leaves 500 still open. This will require a continuous maintenance and development effort, but fundamentally the work has been done.

Although, apart from this kind of maintenance work, four domains of development remain:

1. Software collaboration, integration and interfacing.
2. The balance between computational accuracy and computation time.
3. Enhanced representations or algorithms, aimed at improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the program. As expressed by, e.g., minimizing the user's screen time, reducing data replication, improving redundancy or providing a more intuitive view on the ship model or the program.
4. The fruits of novel technologies, such as fast optimization, machine learning and AI.

Where the first two areas are regularly emphasized by the users, the latter two mostly originate from SARC.

Not so much the technical merits, but more the market engagement of these subjects forms the further content of this paper. We apologise in advance for the somewhat gloomy sound this paper occasionally may have. In the end it will not be so bad, the last chapter dives a little deeper into this aspect.

2. An anthology of innovative PIAS functionality

For an overview of current PIAS functionality, reference is made to www.sarc.nl/pias/modules/. Many modules operate in a conventional fashion, such as those for intact stability, stability criteria, Anchor Handling Tug Supply vessel chain forces and tank sounding tables. Some applications are based on more innovative technologies. This will be detailed in the next subchapters, while the subsequent chapter will address their market receptions.

2.1. Fairway

As motivated in *Koelman et al. (2001)* and *Koelman and Veelo (2013)*, the conventional mathematical (NURBS) method for ship hull surface representation is quite user-unfriendly. An alternative method has been developed, and implemented in a PIAS module called Fairway, from which advantages are listed in *Koelman (2003)*.

2.2. LEANURBS

Although the NURBS method has its drawbacks, it is still a standard in many downstream computer programs. For that reason, we have developed a mathematical process which bends and shakes Fairway's geometrical model towards the limitations of NURBS, and delivers a watertight (hence, without gaps; closed) NURBS model with a modest number of NURBS surfaces. This can be exported in IGES format. This method and its benefits has been described in *Koelman and Veelo (2018)* and is fully implemented in Fairway, please see this [white paper](#), and Fig.1 for an example.

Fig.1: LEANURBS demo: left the Fairway model, right the resulting NURBS surface, through IGES file imported in Rhino

2.3. Interconnectedness between compartments and bulkheads & decks

Lee et al. (2009) provide the analysis “All compartment modeling systems have their own compartment modeling methods. However, these methods are based on the bottom-up approach for compartment modeling. That is, a compartment model of the ship is being generated by modeling all compartments one by one. Thus, these methods require much time and efforts because the ship consists of compartments of several tens to several hundreds.” To solve this problem they propose a space subdivision method, incorporated in a non-manifold kernel. That will indeed address the issue, although the non-manifold technology will bring a seriously increasing complexity. To solve the same issue, for PIAS an easier, BSP-based, method was chosen, and presented in *De Koningh et al. (2011)*. Despite its simplicity, this method offers advantages as a) consistency between compartments and bulkheads and decks, b) creation of multiple compartments with a single “split compartments by a plane” command, and c) modify many compartments simultaneously with the single “change bulkhead||deck location” command.

2.4. A collaborative CAD system based upon CADMATIC and PIAS

As a specialized ship design program suite, PIAS is always complemented with other software, such as for structural modelling and production. For those purposes, quite a few users of PIAS are using CADMATIC, so an interface between the two seems obvious. As ‘interface’, most people imagine some kind of common file format, however that has the disadvantage that to a very deep level representations of all components have to be the same, or have to be convertible from one to the other. So, for this purpose an alternative communication method has been developed, which allows each system to give a direct command (or ask a direct question) over the network connection to the other. If, for example, a user sitting behind PIAS is changing a bulkhead position, at the same time PIAS gives the corresponding command to CADMATIC, which processes that in its own data structures. In this fashion CADMATIC and PIAS act more or less as two faces of the same system, without exchanging files. The essentials of this system are elaborated in *Koelman et al (2015)*, Fig.2 presents an example.

Fig.2: CADMATIC at the right, PIAS at the left, working as one system.

2.5. Numerical integration for probabilistic damage stability

In SOLAS' probabilistic damage stability rules the probability of damage is derived from the combination of aft, forward, inner and upper boundaries from each compartment, and from their compositions (in case of multi-compartment damages). This principle comes with some flaws, as first described in *Koelman (1995)*. To counter these problems, in general, instead of real compartments, a simplified subdivision into fictitious ‘zones’ is used. This will indeed hide some of the problems, albeit at the costs of less accuracy, hence resulting in a lower Attained Subdivision Index. Fortunately, alternative calculation schemes exist which don't suffer from this problem.

These methods are not based on crisp compartment boundaries, but on all possible combinations of damage boundaries instead. Such have been proposed under the names ‘Monte Carlo method’, see *Krüger (2023)* for a recent paper, and ‘numerical integration method’, *Koelman (2005)*. The latter has been implemented in PIAS, as an alternative to compartment-based and zonal-based methods.

2.6. Multithreading

PIAS' module for probabilistic damage stability was released in 1991. In the very first version the damage cases had to be defined manually, just as in the existing module for deterministic damage stability. With the first commercial application it appeared that the number of damage cases for the probabilistic method is an order of magnitude higher than for the deterministic one, so defining the cases took us a day, or two. This experience led to the development of a damage case generator, which made life much easier, because it generates damage cases on the basis of user-configurable maximum damage dimensions and number of involved compartments. It will be obvious that by changing these parameters the user will influence the number of resulting damage cases.

In those early days, the number of cases had a practical limit, determined by the time required for the computation. In practice — on an Intel 80386 processor with 80387 mathematical co-processor — some 200–300 damage cases typically took some 24 hours, which was deemed to be doable. Fast forward now: today people are still prepared to wait some 24 hours for their calculation, which is now the time required to generate and compute a few thousand damage cases. The reason why such a high number of damages is being used is not always clear to us — it will probably be based on the notion that each additional damage case may deliver a contribution to the Attained Subdivision Index — but that is up to the judgement of the program user.

Anyway, this mechanism illustrates the huge user demand for processor speed. Fortunately, modern processors are equipped with ever more cores, so gradually PIAS' working load is distributed over multiple cores. That started some 15 years ago with two simultaneous threads (to be run on a dual core processor) and increased to twenty simultaneous threads today. Sadly, the optimal strategy of spreading a process over multiple cores depends on the number of cores, so each increase in order of magnitude (from two to eight to twenty cores) requires re-analysis and reprogramming.

2.7. Constraint management as a design aid

The noble craft of the ship designer consists partly of design and creativity, but it also involves a lot of repetitive calculation work. During the design action the latter is often shaped as 'trial and error', for instance filling the aft peak with ballast, in order to verify whether the propellor immersion meets its minimum requirement. Although these kinds of actions are not per se time consuming, they occur rather often, so some streamlining of this process will assist the designer.

For this purpose, as an experiment, PIAS has been extended with the so-called 'constraint management' tool, aimed at some design requirements with regard to the subdivision of a ship (i.e. the division into compartments). In particular, the requirements on distances between bulkheads (or decks), on deck areas or on compartment volumes. Where 'requirement' means a minimum and/or maximum value.

In this respect, such requirements can be considered to be 'constraints', because they constrain the position of bulkheads and/or decks. After the requirements have been filled in, PIAS has a 'solve' button which repositions all bulkheads and decks to meet all requirements. What the program actually does is repetitive trial and error, just as a human would do, albeit without human time being wasted. If the requirements appear to be mutually conflicting, then the interactive 'constraint balancer' tool can be used to balance the relative importance of the requirements. More information can be found in *De Koningh et al. (2011)* and in [this white paper](#).

Technically, this whole system is not related to Machine Learning, because underneath is a conventional optimization algorithm. On the other hand, it is a demonstration of the direction CAD software is taking, where the human expresses its goals, while the computer provides a design solution which meets the goals. This constraint management system was in this experiment limited to properties of decks, bulkheads and compartments, with the idea that once used in practice it could be extended to include other features, such as constraints on trim, draft and stability.

2.8. Interface with DNV Poseidon

DNV Poseidon software is widely used for the strength assessment of hull structures. Its input contains ship data, many of which are already available from PIAS, such as hull shape, positions of bulkheads and decks, tank top loadings, compartment volumes, positions and particulars of girders, and bending moments & shear forces. Manually defining these parameters into Poseidon takes quite some hours, time which is saved by using the PIAS → Poseidon interface that has been developed around 2016, see Fig.3 for an example.

Fig.3: Poseidon construction models coming straight out of PIAS

2.9. Container cargo optimization

Loosely inspired by *Kemp et al. (2003)*, to the PIAS-derived onboard loading and stability software, [LOCOPIAS](#), an experimental container loading planning module was added, featuring a genetic algorithm-based optimization algorithm. Because of a reason motivated in the next subchapter, this pilot has never been converted into a product.

2.10. Ballast optimization in LOCOPIAS

For deployment on a submarine, LOCOPIAS has been extended with a feature of ballast optimization. Based upon the requirement of a specific trim and draft (and once the submarine is submerged, weight instead of draft) it determines the distribution of ballast water over all ballast tanks in an optimal fashion, i.e. which requires the least transfer of ballast water, compared with the situation just before. Recently, this feature has been enhanced with trim optimization, so now it consists of two steps; a) determine draft and trim for which resistance is minimal, and b) (re-)allocate ballast water over all ballast tanks to achieve that draft and trim, with the minimum amount of fluid transferred.

3. The market reception of these innovations

Please allow me to take a quick advance on what is to come; these innovations did not receive a warm welcome; their sales ratio compared with conventional PIAS modules will be some 5-15%. The focus of this paper is on the question why? Why must we conclude that the average user cannot be convinced of the added value of these innovations? A first impulse would be to ask the involved persons for their motive. However, some reasons prevent that:

- In practice it is not a person who decides, it is an organization. And different persons, on different decision levels, may have different views, so an unequivocal answer for an entire organization will be hard to obtain.
- People might be expected to give a reason for something they did. Reasoning about not acting will be harder.

Nevertheless, at the next SARC user day, in May 2023, this question will be asked to the audience, and we will keep you informed on the replies. In the meantime, from informal discussions, we still have deduced some possible arguments:

- A. The offer is not convincing from a commercial point of view. In other words, the benefit compared to the cost is low.
- B. The offered functionality is not sufficiently complete.
- C. The proposed functionality is not according to de facto standards.
- D. The proposed functionality is not according to legal standards.

Although Table I does not prove it, it still illustrates that these arguments play a role. The columns of this table contain:

- The subject of the software functionality, as listed in Chapter 2.
- The development domain(s), as listed in the introduction (1=integration & interfacing, 2=accuracy/computation time, 3=enhanced algorithms, 4=novel technologies).
- Market reception level, 1=cold, 10=warm.
- The estimated argument for lukewarm receptions, from the a-d list just above.
- An occasional note, as listed beneath the table.

Table I: Analysis of reception of beyond-standard software modules

	Subject	Domain	Reception	Argument	Note
1	Fairway	3	5	C	
2	LEANURBS	1	3	C	a
3	BSP for compartments and bulkheads & decks	3+1	4	A	
4	CADMATIC interface	1+3	2	A+B	
5	Probabilistic damage numerical integration	2+4	3	A+D	
6	Multithreading	2	7	A	d
7	Constraint management	4	2	A+B	
8	Poseidon interface	1	2	A+C	b
9	Container optimization	4	1	A	c
10	Ballast advice	4	4	A+B	

Notes:

- Although the underlying algorithms deliver a watertight set of NURBS patches automatically and in reasonable time, the division of the hull surface into four-sided patches (which is an inevitable requirement for using NURBS) is still manual labour. Admittedly, although the GUI has efficient tools for this task, so for an average vessel it takes an hour.
- Poseidon was a development of former Germanischer Lloyd, and some people suspect(ed) that its continuity would not be guaranteed after the merger with DNV. Might be so — or not, we don't know — but with this argument, people have refrained from using a handy tool, with a rather low price/yield ratio, while they could have enjoyed from 2016 to the present. And Poseidon still continues.
- After completion of this pilot, we demonstrated it to a shipowner, for whom the manual compilation of a container stowage plan reportedly took several hours. Knowing that by our optimization module this task was reduced to some 15 minutes, we expected a certain enthusiasm. On the contrary, they thought 15 minutes was far too long and demanded it to be done in 5 minutes. With that, the pilot development came to an end.
- Sometimes multithreading is seen as a license to add damage cases in a non-linear pace. One soon loses that battle, as computation time is only inversely proportional to the number of threads, while [Amdahl's law](#) may play a delaying role.

4. Discussion

From Table I we learn that there is a mixture of domains of and arguments for the lukewarm reception. Which is a pity because it leaves us no focal point as counterargument. However, the first question is whether we should wish to argue at all. After all, perhaps the market is happy now? That could make sense; in the introduction we looked back to the eighties, with production increases by a factor ten, and today we have to make do with a factor of 1.5, 2 or 3. So that is the first question, are we satisfied with lesser productivity gains in further development of Computer Aided Ship Design, compared to what was once realized? Or do we stop developing it altogether? People who answer the second question in the affirmative can stop reading here. We would like to confront the others, including ourselves, with the following considerations:

- In literature on standards and innovation, the general trend is to conclude that norms and

standards stimulate innovations, see e.g. *Riillo (2009)* and *Viardot et al.(2016)* (although the latter also concludes “A common adage in the management community is that innovation is about creativity while standardization is about uniformity and that standardization constrain entrepreneurs in seeking opportunities”). Disregarding this consensus, in our field of applications some standards have an inhibiting effect, such as the de facto NURBS standard for curved surfaces, and the CDF (Cumulative Distribution Function) nature of SOLAS’ rules for probabilistic damage stability. While we realize that such standards are often embedded in legislation or software, that should not imply that we are stuck with them until the end of time. Alternative arrangements are often feasible.

- It is up to SARC to quantitatively explain the costs/benefits of innovative software as well. We are going to do that, e.g., the next SARC user day by holding a live duel between the conventional method and PIAS’ BSP-based method for modeling compartments.
- A ship designer is neither a mathematician, nor a software developer. Nevertheless, some knowledge of the background of mathematical models and algorithms can be of assistance when judging the present and future merits of software. Teaching that will be a long-term process, but to get a start, I have initiated a course ([Advanced Engineering Tools for ShipX](#)) offered to maritime undergraduate students and professionals in the maritime sector.
- In the case of software with a pilot nature, SARC will make effort to emphasize that the included functionality is only a preview, and not the final set. That should be doable, after all in 1984 we succeeded in convincing a shipyard to acquire PIAS’ ship hull form generation program, which existed at the time of a pilot capable for ships of 60 m in length and 12 m in breadth. The yard could very well imagine that if we were able to produce such a program, the step towards a freely chosen length and width would be very small.
- Users are asked to accept that the days of productivity gains of hundreds of percent are over, this follows from the law of the diminishing returns. But the risks of buying newer software are also much lower. After all, in the early 1980s, one bought a software package with a price of an average car from a one-man startup, of which it was questionable how long that would exist. And now one buys the innovative add-on modules for the price of an electric bicycle from an established firm with a diverse staff.

5. Conclusion

Awaiting the effect of the actions as proposed in the previous chapter, at SARC we will proceed with the development of novel software tools, because, until shown otherwise, it is still our belief that this will serve the maritime sector. An excerpt of the list from today shows:

- Explicit support for the geometry of pipes and ducts, including their connections, either mutual, to compartments or other spaces, or to the outside weather. For quite some decades PIAS has its so-called ‘compartment connections’ facility, and although that works well, it was designed for an occasional connection, and not for massive application as classification societies require ever more, for damage stability assessment. Because this new system is based on the real shape and topology its modus operandi and requirement on input data is very intuitive, Fig.4 shows the GUI. This system supports both stages-of-flooding as well as time domain damage stability computations.
- A pilot implementation on an application of Artificial Intelligence on (the optimization of) Probabilistic Damage Stability.
- Further integration between CADMATIC and PIAS, as part of the EU Horizon SEUS project, <https://www.sarc.nl/the-smart-european-shipbuilding-project-seus/>.

Besides, effort will also be spent on conventional enhancements; processing many of the 500 open tickets, which may be larger or smaller. Although most are not fundamental, they are still important for users, and will enhance productivity further.

Fig.4: PIAS' piping definitions GUI

6. Postscript

In the foregoing, we may have given the impression that our business is moribund. This is certainly not the case, as evidenced by the many enthusiastic young naval architects working at SARC, as well as the stylish new office, Fig.5, we recently moved into; an investment for years to come. We are not complaining, sales of conventional software are thriving. We just wonder what the mechanisms are, so that we can make the best use of the scarce resources.

Fig.5: SARC's new office

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The Use of ChatGPT and Similar AI in Marine Engineering: Limitations and Opportunities

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Abstract

ChatGPT and other artificial intelligence (AI) tools have the potential to significantly impact marine engineering, offering better information access, e.g., time savings in literature reviews or assistance with language barriers. However, they come with potentially inaccurate or incomplete representation of marine-related concepts, facilitating plagiarism or cheating, dependency on technology, perpetuation of bias, and privacy concerns. We examine here some pros and cons of such AI tools in the context of marine engineering, drawing on results of our own testing of ChatGPT and other software on selected application cases. As an anti-climax conclusion, we did not find ChatGPT as useful as promised.

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence or “AI” is a term often used, yet little understood. The technology is both overestimated and underused. The blind faith in AI is reminiscent of the 1970s’ misconception of computers and software: the computer says so and therefore it must be true.

There is no coherent definition of what “Artificial Intelligence” is, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artificial_intelligence. In its broadest sense, AI is concerned with the investigation and simulation of human intelligence with the ambition to replicate the processes in machines. A not exhaustive list of sub-branches of AI encompasses:

- machine learning
- knowledge-based systems
- machine vision
- natural language processing / gesture processing
- robotics
- ...

Machine learning is the most prominent AI application, and frequently “using AI” means “using machine learning” these days. For better context and understanding, it is useful to recall that “machine learning” was denoted as “numerical statistics” in the past. It builds models and produces results based on empirical knowledge, and if underlying data bases are sparse or biased, or if the software attempts extrapolation beyond the scope of the data base, errors occur.

Bertram (2018) reviewed AI applications in the maritime context, with focus on the first three items in above list, concluding that AI techniques can be put to good use for maritime applications, but cautioning against just using new tools without understanding their fundamental working principles and resulting limitations. In similar vein, *Colle and Morobé (2022)* warn against an ignorant use of machine learning, in the context of ship performance monitoring.

We will focus here on the fourth item of above list, namely natural language processing, and discuss in passing also more symbolic processing, e.g., for images, as employed in naval architectural teaching and scientific communication. We use the term “marine engineering” here to encompass the various maritime disciplines from design to operation of ships.

2. ChatGPT for maritime applications

2.1. Precursing ChatGPT

ChatGPT is only the latest in natural language processing computer programs that may fool human users into believing that they converse with a human being, with knowledge, intelligence, and even compassion.

For Volker Bertram, there is a déjà vu feeling in “chatting” with a computer, dating back to 1978 when first encountering ELIZA, Fig.1, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ELIZA>. ELIZA was a computer program, combing pattern matching and rules to simulate conversations. Initially, ELIZA seemed very clever, but the illusion of chatting with a human was short-lived, as responses were repetitive and formulaic. An early case of AI hype and disillusion.

```
Welcome to
          EEEEE LL    IIII  ZZZZZZ  AAAAA
          EE    LL    II    ZZ    AA  AA
          EEEEE LL    II    ZZZ   AAAAAA
          EE    LL    II    ZZ    AA  AA
          EEEEE LLLLLL IIII ZZZZZZ  AA  AA

Eliza is a mock Rogerian psychotherapist.
The original program was described by Joseph Weizenbaum in 1966.
This implementation by Norbert Landsteiner 2005.

ELIZA: Is something troubling you ?
YOU:   Men are all alike.
ELIZA: What is the connection, do you suppose ?
YOU:   They're always bugging us about something or other.
ELIZA: Can you think of a specific example ?
YOU:   Well, my boyfriend made me come here.
ELIZA: Is it important to you that your boyfriend made you come here ?
YOU:   He says I'm depressed much of the time.
ELIZA: I am sorry to hear that you are depressed.
YOU:   It's true. I am unhappy.
ELIZA: Can you explain what made you unhappy ?
YOU:
```

Fig.1: ELIZA conversation, mimicking compassion and intelligence

2.2. Introduction to ChatGPT

ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer), <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ChatGPT>, is an AI-based chatbot, that has caused furore since its launch in November 2022, and concern, particularly in academic and educational circles. We tested only ChatGPT, and not its more recent competitor Bard, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LaMDA#Bard>, but suspect that limitations are similar for Bard, as basic approaches are similar.

But maybe it is best to let ChatGPT introduce itself (based on a ChatGPT session in February 2023):

Question: “What is ChatGPT?”

Answer: “ChatGPT is a conversational AI language model developed by OpenAI. It's based on the transformer architecture and was trained on a large corpus of text data to generate human-like responses to a given prompt. ChatGPT can be used for various natural language processing tasks such as text completion, question answering, and conversation generation. The goal of ChatGPT is to enable developers to build conversational AI systems that can understand and respond to user inputs in a more human-like way.”

ChatGPT is not Google, and it is based on AI, i.e., on experience, trained on vast amounts of text files taken from the internet, but not using real-time access to internet sites. ChatGPT was ignorant about itself one month after the launch. But chat with follow-up questions and ChatGPT will generally improve its response:

Question: “Who are you?”

Answer: “I am an AI language model developed by OpenAI. I was trained on a large corpus of text data and designed to respond to user inputs in a conversational manner. My primary purpose is to assist users in generating human-like text based on the prompts given to me, and to answer questions to the best of my abilities.”

Apart from the (human-like) repetition, the answer is a good explanation of what ChatGPT is and can do. It also hints at its limitations. ChatGPT is intended to create texts, where it draws on its training, but cannot specifically search ad hoc outside its inherent knowledge base.

ChatGPT’s ability to create human-like texts has raised concerns within the educational community. Within seconds, ChatGPT can create some text to a given assignment, and with several follow-up questions, the text can be modified and made unique, passing state-of-the-art plagiarism tests. This is of particular concern for “soft sciences”, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hard_and_soft_science, where texts play a big role in examinations (“write an essay of 2000 words on the concept of ...”) and academic achievement is based on producing texts. Incidentally, these are also academic curricula where plagiarism and ghost-writing have been traditional issues of strong concern. In engineering, the concerns are not (yet) as pressing, as mathematical derivations and simulation software coding and application are seen as the predominant intellectual achievements.

The use of software as such in academic tasks is widely accepted and even expected:

- Literature research via search machines
- Checking grammar and spelling in writing texts
- Referencing via databases
- Translating texts from one language to another (typically between native language and English)
- Layout with desktop publishing software (with imbedded intelligence on making suggestions for suitable layout)
- Statistical analyses and charts generated by spreadsheet tools

ChatGPT is the new kid on the block – and we have yet to decide whether it is just another tool to support research and publishing, or whether it is disrupting our examination and grading traditions, possibly even threatening jobs. To get some decision support, we decided to put ChatGPT to the test with some application cases coming from marine engineering.

2.3. Application tests

2.3.1. Exploring heave motion for a barge

We approached the subject of heave motion for a barge as we might have done with a student in an oral exam on ship seakeeping, asking successively more detailed questions:

- Stability of a boat: $GM = KB + BM - KG$
- What is added mass, in hydrodynamics?
- What is the heave movement of a ship?
- How [would you] code heave for a rectangular barge of $L = 100$, $B = 20$, $D = 10$, in water?

The detailed responses of ChatGPT are given in Appendix 1. The responses to the questions consisted of several lines, using suitable jargon. If you were not an expert in ship stability or seakeeping, you

probably would have a favourable impression. But an expert in the field would pick out several shortcomings, such as mistaking BM as the beam of the vessel and setting wrongly added mass proportional to accelerations in fluids, ignoring that added mass depends on frequency in ship motions, that it is predominantly determined in potential-flow calculations and not experiments, etc.

ChatGPT gives libraries to download and a short source code. At first glance, one may be impressed again. But ChatGPT assigns without justification that added mass in the case is 50% of real mass, but added mass cannot simply be assigned independent of motion frequency. And ChatGPT's suggested code makes a force due to added mass proportional to speed, but damping forces would be proportional to speed; added mass forces would be related to acceleration.

The “student ChatGPT” tries to blind us with science, hoping we will give credit for using some related, semi-true sentences. Probably the student would pass the exam, say with a C, as we would give the student the benefit of doubt. As an advisor, ChatGPT would be very dangerous, as we would not look through the façade of jargon and code, and just take the advice and move on.

2.3.2. Writing a Book / Compendium in Data-Driven Principles applied to Ship Design

As ChatGPT can be trained into slowly getting into a topic, we decide to feed the chat with text from a previous COMPIT paper, *Gaspar (2018)*, and asked the tool to ‘help me write a book about Data-Driven Principles Applied to Ship Design’. The initial answer was a list of suggestions on how to get started in writing a book, akin to a motivation post that one would find if searching in Google for how to write a book in 5 steps.

A list of chapters was then provided and for each topic that ChatGPT suggested for the chat, we asked it to help us write the introduction. One example is given below (more detail in Appendix 2):

In the introduction to your book, you'll want to provide an overview of the topic of data-driven principles applied to ship design. (...) Here is an example outline for the introduction of your book:

- I. Definition of data-driven design
- II. Benefits of data-driven design in shipbuilding
- III. Overview of the shipbuilding industry and challenges
- IV. Outline of the book's structure and main topics
- (...)

The tools seem to be very efficient in itemizing and synthetizing information, but quite poor in actual writing, almost as if trying to avoid the task. Apart from wrongly equating ship design and shipbuilding, ChatGPT's suggestions were valid and worth considering. Similar efficiency in organizing was found in all other questions, especially when in a wider and popular topic as data-driven approach, where clearly the tool had more knowledge than for marine engineering.

As a positive surprise, ChatGPT suggested some topics that we had not considered, especially when asked for more information, i.e., when asking ChatGPT to “Explain”. In the example above, ChatGPT seems to combine popular data-driven concepts and merge them to ship design ones, such as “the role of hull data”. ChatGPT seems to understand that role of data is a larger topic, with specific instances from the ship design domain, such as hull, and suggesting the role of hull data as a part of our book.

We performed similar exercises for other marine topics, such as structuring chapters on general arrangement or seakeeping, for a hypothetical book. After filtering for mistakes and redundancies, we had useful text structures, as for the data-driven approach above.

ChatGPT was efficient in re-writing or summarizing existing texts. In our tests, is successfully removed some redundancies and shortened some sentences when asked (e.g., “rewrite this chapter in only 300

words”). On the other hand, when asked to create new, original text, ChatGPT produced repetitive and longwinded text. One of ChatGPT’s largest drawbacks is the amount of redundant and useless information given. It is a chatty chat-bot, not a concise chat-bot!

2.3.3. General arrangement plan (GAP) for a frigate

While ChatGPT deals with text, another AI application from the same company, Dall-E 2, claims to be capable of also returning images, not just alphanumeric information (prose texts, poetry, programming code, formulas, etc.). Fig.2 shows the response to the request “Can you make a general arrangement drawing of a frigate ship”.

The interpretation is subject to attitude and expectation to AI. Were Dall-E 2 our child, say 8 years old, we would probably be proud and point out correct details such as superstructures, gun turrets, and helideck. As it is not our child, we notice wrong ratio of length-to-draft, no sonar dome or bulbous bow, no propeller, no internal compartmentation, and wrong arrangement of some of the equipment. The image would probably not even pass as a first concept sketch, leave alone a general arrangement plan. The test was challenging, and AI failed.

Fig.2: Dall-E 2 response to the request of a general arrangement plan for a frigate

3. Other AI-based software

3.1. AI-based software for presentations and training

Developing presentations (such as for a conference) and trainings based on presentations or e-learning frameworks takes generally a lot more time than outsiders suspect, *Bertram and Plowman (2019)*. And time is money, especially in industry, where hourly rates for skilled staff are typically 150-250 €/h. Against this backdrop, DNV management stumbled across an advertisement: “Get AI-based learning content in minutes - Content can make or break your learning programs. Let Shape’s AI do the heavy lifting.”, <https://www.docebo.com/products/shape/>.

As many of DNV's training topics are highly specialized, and Google would reach quickly limits in finding relevant text or images, we decided on a rather simple test case beyond the narrow domain of ship technology, namely DNV's "Train the Trainer" course aimed at giving an initial training for ship technology experts with no previous pedagogical experience. We had course material based on PowerPoint, but we were curious what AI would make of it. Maybe we would see ideas, our human development experts had not thought of.

The start was easy. After trial registration, the upload of the original file was fast, and within a minute, as promised, we had the suggested online content for a training. But the result was largely useless, sometimes amusingly so, as the AI software just picked up keywords and assigned images that matched the keywords, but out of context: In introducing the trainers for the course, which hold post-graduate degrees in pedagogy, an image for a fitness trainer was selected, Fig.3 (left). Or for training workshops, an industrial workshop with a worker welding was chosen as visual aid, Fig.3 (centre). Text was chopped into fragments and reassembled, adding apparently random text snippets to form new sentences, which often are nonsensical, Fig.1 (right). For example, "Bernhard Löbermann has a master [degree] in teaching. He has developed trainings in maritime applications for specific purposes." was converted into "Bernhil Loesbermann has a Masters in Teaching for Specific Purposes". (Typos were introduced by the software.)

Fig.3: Images are selected based on keywords without context resulting in "nonsense"

In essence, it was lack of context knowledge that led to irrelevant text and images. For the specific application we tested, the AI-based software created useless material. This should not be surprising. For the rather creative task of designing presentations and trainings, there is less structure and fewer rules, making it difficult for statistics-based or rule-based AI to produce working products.

Other AI-based tools are also promising a lecture within minutes, based on a PowerPoint file, e.g., <https://www.synthesia.io/learning-and-development> and <https://aws.amazon.com/polly/>. The reality is not useless, but soberingly limited in capability. You need to design the lecture as such, including the speaker notes of what you would say in a self-recorded lecture or video conference. You can also pick an avatar (almost photorealistic person) and a voice (from various nations). The tool then converts this into a speaking avatar that delivers your narrative. This can be useful in some cases:

- Your English is not very good, or you have a speech impediment.
- You want to develop several lectures and maintain/update them over years, but your real-world lecturer may leave your organization and not be available anymore.

The glorified text-to-speech function is more sophisticated than what was on the market 5 years ago, but still has the inherent drawbacks of automated text-to-speech. It sounds a bit artificial, and you need to put in much extra work to get speech pauses and stressing of words the way you want. For most of us, recording ourselves and giving thus also visual credit to the expert behind the lecture will remain the preferred option.

3.2. Language processing/translations

AI may help in scientific writing, especially for non-native speakers. For automatic translation, DeepL (www.deepl.com) has produced good results in our experience for general texts, and reasonable results for technical translations, where specific marine, engineering, or mathematical terms were not correctly

translated. This is similar to using human translators who may have a good command of a language for common vocabulary, but lack the specific vocabulary of a narrow technical domain. Even if resulting texts needed some final editing, the automatic translation was saving significant time and eliminated grammatical and spelling mistakes. The highly technical terms were the easy parts for non-native speakers with an engineering background.

DeepL is limited to translations from/to 26 languages, including British and American English. ChatGPT may be used for another “special” type of translation, namely that from stilted writing into easy language, from cumbersome jargon to plain English. This is useful for native speakers as well, as their wider range of vocabulary and idiomatic expressions may introduce inadvertently linguistic hurdles for a non-native audience. Again, often some human post-processing is needed, e.g., in judging with context information what jargon is useful and what harmful for the intended audience.

AI-based translations are experience-based on what texts are found in web and what may be corrected by human translators. Too small data bases generally will lead to poor performance in AI approaches, also in the context of translation.

4. Conclusions

The popularity of ChatGPT has increased immensely during the time of writing this paper, and much appeared online about the usability of Chat GPT. Therefore, we expect that you have already read some third-party assessments of ChatGPT. Our assessment, in a classical anti-climax, is that this is yet more smoke than fire for specialized areas like marine engineering. ChatGPT did not write usable text and did not create usable lists of references. It did not save us time in writing a conference paper. It can be useful to explore new ideas, organize or summarize texts, but the texts produced needed so much reworking, as to destroy any time savings as compared to writing yourself.

If the tool was a BSc student in an exam, it would probably get a B or C grade, as it is clearly able to organize some pertaining knowledge and discusses a little about everything. The devil is in the detail. When asked about the mathematical modelling or to go deeper, errors appear, and incorrect statements make the lack of knowledge apparent. As a MSc student, where many courses are report-based, we do not see the tool as any more dangerous than Google, as the quality of the writing is shallow and repetitive. If you want to cheat the system, it probably is more efficient to just copy and paste from source in the web and rephrase.

ChatGPT may be useful (although not always reliable) mentor. The way that the tool organizes ideas, corrects phrases, and includes logical additions to writing text may add value, not only in education, but writing overall. But beware, unlike peer-reviewed Wikipedia, ChatGPT tells convincing lies, where truth and nonsense may be dangerously mixed. The tool can be “corrected”, akin to prompting a student that gave a wrong answer, but in practical terms this is inefficient, and you need to understand enough of the matter to spot the errors.

The image processing sidekick Dall-E 2 fared similarly poorly in finding/creating useful images for our specialized applications. Docebo’s Shape fared even worse for creating presentation material.

However, testing the tools for this work was entertaining. ChatGPT and Dall-E 2, like once Eliza, were fascinating time thieves. You can spend hours with them, without getting tangible results that can be used in a paper or presentation in marine engineering.

Asking some peers for input, impressions varied depending on how specialized the topic was. A professor teaching introduction to mechatronics at NTNU was worried, as the tool could pass his exams effortless, including preparing the Arduino code that he requests from his students. Similarly worried was the colleague teaching basics of Python and data-handling. A colleague from hydrodynamics, on the other hand, shared our impression that ChatGPT did not “understand” (or better express) more specific concepts.

To clarify this, we asked the tool about:

Question: Why do you understand some concepts well, such as data handling, but are poor in specific concepts, such as ship design and stability?

Answer: One of the reasons that OpenAI's understanding of specific concepts may vary is due to the size of the sample used to train the AI. OpenAI's models are trained on a massive amount of text data from the internet, and the quality and relevance of the information included in the training data can have a big impact on the model's ability to understand and generate text about a specific topic. In the case of ship design, it's possible that there was less relevant and high-quality text data included in the training data compared to other topics, such as data handling. As a result, the model may have a weaker understanding of ship design compared to data handling. It's also worth noting that the OpenAI models have a very large capacity, meaning they can learn a wide variety of information, but the accuracy of their outputs can still be influenced by the quality and relevance of the training data they were exposed to.

It seems that ChatGPT is currently deliberately downgraded to commercialize a more powerful tool, ChatGPT Plus. Google's Bard as a competitor is of course also advertised as being more powerful, better, etc., etc.

As a popular topic, clearly in the peak of the hype cycle, we still need to wait to see if the promises match reality. Exploration aside, after over a month of periodic use for writing this paper, we do not see ourselves using ChatGPT regularly, as for most of our applications, the required postprocessing exceeds the time-savings. *Chomsky et al. (2023)* reach an even harsher conclusion, pointing out the lack of cognition. “[ChatGPT’s] deepest flaw is the absence of the most critical capacity of any intelligence: to say not only what is the case, what was the case and what will be the case - that’s description and prediction - but also what is not the case and what could and could not be the case (...) The crux of machine learning is description and prediction; it does not posit any causal mechanisms or physical laws. Of course, any human-style explanation is not necessarily correct; we are fallible. But this is part of what it means to think: To be right, it must be possible to be wrong.”

In this sense, Google indexed database style of (mostly) human generated content still wins, as getting information to create your own texts and presentations is faster than correcting ChatGPT’s suggestions. Maybe, in the future, there will be customized bots trained on our domain or even the complete IP (intellectual property) of a company like DNV, to create useful, rather standard texts within that domain or company. But such speculation brings us to another déjà vu of the 1970s: The next release will fix all bugs and be able to do everything that you require...

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Appendix 1: ChatGPT response on heave motion of barge

1. Stability of a boat: $GM = KB + BM - KG$

The equation states that the metacentric height of a boat (GM) is equal to the distance between the center of buoyancy and the center of gravity (KB), plus the beam of the boat (BM), minus the distance between the keel and the center of gravity (KG). This equation helps calculate the stability of a boat, and a higher metacentric height generally indicates a more stable boat.

2. What is added mass, in hydrodynamics?

In hydrodynamics, added mass is the inertia a body gains when it is submerged in a fluid. It is a property of the fluid that causes an increase in the effective mass of a submerged object, which can affect the motion and stability of the object. The added mass coefficient is a dimensionless number that describes the added mass relative to the mass of the object itself. It is typically determined experimentally, and can vary depending on the shape and size of the object and the properties of the fluid.

3. What is the heave movement of a ship?

In ship hydrodynamics, the heave movement of a ship refers to the vertical motion of the ship's hull, moving up and down in the water. This motion can be caused by a variety of factors, including waves, wind, and the ship's own propulsion system. Heave motion can have a significant impact on the comfort and safety of passengers and crew, as well as on the ship's stability and performance. To reduce the effects of heave motion, ships are often designed with features such as bilge keels, which help to dampen the motion, and active or passive heave compensation systems, which can help to smooth out the motion.

4. How to code heave for a rectangular barge of $L = 100$, $B = 20$, $D = 10$, in water?

Coding the heave motion of a rectangular barge in water would involve a few steps. Here is an example of one approach you could take using the Python programming language:

Import the necessary libraries, such as NumPy for mathematical calculations and SciPy for solving differential equations:

```
import numpy as np
from scipy.integrate import odeint
```

Define the dimensions of the barge (L , B , D) and any other relevant properties, such as the mass of the barge, the density of the water, and the added mass coefficient:

Copy code

```
L = 100
B = 20
D = 10
mass = 1000
density = 1000
added_mass_coefficient = 0.5
```

Define a function that describes the heave motion of the barge. This function should take in the current state of the barge (position and velocity) and return the derivative of the state (acceleration). The equation of motion for the heave motion can be modeled as $ma = -mg + F_h$ where m is the mass of the barge, a is the acceleration, g is the acceleration due to gravity, and F_h is the hydrodynamic force acting on the barge.

```
def heave_motion(state, t):
```

```

x, v = state
Fh = added_mass_coefficient * density * L * B * D * v
a = (-mass*9.81 + Fh) / mass
return [v, a]

```

Use the `odeint` function from the SciPy library to integrate the differential equation and solve for the position and velocity of the barge over time:

```

t = np.linspace(0, 10, 100)
initial_state = [0, 0]
state = odeint(heave_motion, initial_state, t)

```

The state variable contains the position and velocity of the barge over time. The first column will be the position and the second one the velocity. You can visualize the results with a plot or print them out to check the results.

Please note this is a simple example and the hydrodynamic forces acting on the barge can be more complex depending on the velocity, the frequency of the waves, the draft of the barge, etc. Therefore, the real-world application would be more complex than this example.

Appendix 2: ChatGPT response on writing a book

Question: Help me write a book about Data-Driven Principles applied to Ship Design.

Answer: Certainly! I'd be happy to help you write a book about data-driven principles applied to ship design. Here are some steps you can follow to get started:

Define your target audience: Who do you want to read your book? What level of knowledge do they have about ship design and data-driven principles? Understanding your audience will help you tailor your content and language to their needs and interests.

Outline the main topics you want to cover: What are the key principles of data-driven ship design that you want to discuss? What examples and case studies do you want to include to illustrate these principles?

Research and gather information: To write an accurate and informative book, you'll need to do thorough research on the topic of data-driven ship design. This may involve reading academic papers and articles, consulting with experts in the field, and gathering data and examples from real-world projects.

Write and revise: Once you have a solid understanding of the topic and an outline of your book, it's time to start writing. Remember to take breaks and get feedback from others as you go. Revising and editing your work will help you polish and improve the final product.

Publish and promote: Once your book is complete, you'll need to decide how you want to publish it. There are many options for self-publishing, including e-book platforms and print-on-demand services. You can also consider submitting your book to traditional publishers. Once your book is available, don't forget to promote it to your target audience and beyond!

I hope these steps are helpful as you work on your book. Let me know if you have any other questions.

[remains of detailed answers per chapter omitted for conciseness]

Corrosion Cracking Segmentation in Ship-Vessels using Few-Shot Techniques

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Abstract

Ship damage due to corrosion or cracking is a big threat in the marine industry. This research aims to segment cracks in ships using a small amount of data. To achieve this, two segmentation models are compared in terms of their generalization capabilities on a small dataset. The results indicate that Few-Shot segmentation techniques (F1-score: 60.9) can outperform traditional segmentation algorithms (F1-score: 56.9) in the context of small data when carefully trained and fine-tuned to the target dataset. This potentially mitigates the need for creating large datasets with dense image annotations which are expensive to obtain or not widely available.

1. Introduction

Experts estimated that damages on ships due to corrosion can cost up to 80 billion dollars a year, lowers the lifespan of a ship and reduce structural safety of the ship, <http://impact.nace.org/economic-impact.aspx>. Additional research has shown that 90% of ship failures are due to corrosion, *Melchers (1999)*. As such, an early detection of cracks is in the benefit of safety, while timely action may also prevent the repair cost get out of control. This topic is therefore in wide interest of stakeholders such as ship owners, ship repair yards and classification societies. Particular types of damage are cracks that can be formed due to metal fatigue, stress corrosion cracking (SCC) or fractures, *Crooker et al. (1975)*. Metal fatigue cracks are cracks that form under the action of cyclic stresses. SCC happens due to sustained tensile stress in combination with harsh environmental conditions, mostly salty seawater. Both metal fatigue and SCC are a big threat to the reliability and life-cycle costs of ships. Fractures related to cracks in elastic materials can arise spontaneously and without warning. Many researchers have proposed to detect the presence of cracks by analysing images, e.g. at a previous COMPIT, *Xie et al. (2016)*. In this paper that will also be the starting point, in particular using Computer Vision with Segmentation.

Several attempts have been made to detect or segment regions on materials that are impacted by corrosion. In bridge defect inspection, several works focused on per-pixel segmentation of corroded regions, *Bembenek et al. (2022)* and *Liao and Lee (2016)*. In the domain of ship-defect segmentation, research has been conducted that focuses on segmenting a combination of corroded regions and cracks, *Bonnin-Pascual and Ortiz (2010,2018)*.

The contributions of this work are twofold. First, the goal is to segment solely cracks compared to general corroded regions as seen in other literature. Second, the research is conducted in the context of small data. Collecting many images of stress cracks is a cumbersome task as most damages are eventually repaired. As such, only a limited number of images accompanied by per-pixel segmentation maps are publicly available. Unfortunately, segmentation models often require many images to generalize well to unseen images.

In this work, a state-of-the-art Few-Shot Segmentation (FSS) model is tested and contrasted against the state-of-the-art baseline model, DeepLabV3+, *Chen et al. (2017a)*. It is demonstrated that FSS models can be an enticing option when only a few densely annotated samples are available. However, obtaining good results for FSS models is not straightforward and requires a careful design process.

2. Background

This section first describes the process of Semantic Segmentation, Transfer Learning and Few-Shot Learning. Finally, the notion of Few-Shot Learning is explained in the context of segmentation.

2.1. Semantic Segmentation

Semantic segmentation, hereafter referred to as segmentation, is an essential component in the domain of Computer Vision in which each pixel of an image is assigned to a pre-defined class. Many applications currently exist that rely on segmentation approaches to segment objects. Examples are brain tumor segmentation and material segmentation in urban scenes, *Myronenko and Hazamizadeh (2020)* and *Ros et al. (2016)*. Nowadays, Convolutional Neural Networks are used primarily to achieve this, *Long et al. (2015)*, *Chen et al. (2017b)* and *Ronneberger et al. (2015)*. To train a segmentation model, segmentation masks are required which specify these per-pixel annotations. The goal is to train a model that minimizes the discrepancy between its semantic output predictions and the ground-truth per-pixel annotations. It should be noted that constructing these dense annotations is a laborious task and, consequently, collecting numerous annotations for semantic segmentation purposes becomes expensive, difficult or infeasible. Simultaneously it is well-known that semantic segmentation models are data-hungry and require many dense annotations for robust training, *Milan et al. (2018)* and *Garcia-Garcia et al. (2017)*. To alleviate the need for abundant pixel-level segmentation maps, Few-Shot Semantic Segmentation approaches (Section 2.3 and 2.4) have been developed. Additionally, techniques such as transfer learning (Section 2.2) can also be applied when dealing with small data. In this work, a combination of transfer learning and few-shot learning is applied to train sample-efficient segmentation models.

2.2. Transfer Learning

Deep Learning models tend to overfit easily when data are scarcely available. In such situations, constraining the capacity of the model is paramount to reducing the likelihood of overfitting. An often-applied technique in transfer learning tackles the problem of small data in two steps. First, a model is pre-trained on a source dataset for which many images are available. In that way the model can leverage feature representations obtained from a source dataset. Finally, the target dataset is used to fine-tune the model. The effectiveness of pre-training is dependent on the similarity between the source and the target dataset, *Torrey and Shavlik (2010)*. In this work, models are used which are pre-trained on a segmentation task. This way, relatively generic features are extracted for segmentation purposes. Afterwards, the models are fine-tuned using a Few-Shot Learning approaches.

2.3. Few-Shot Learning

Although humans are able to identify novel objects from a small number of examples, Machine Learning methods typically require significantly more examples to achieve comparable performance. In some cases, it is difficult to collect enough data to train a model using traditional supervised learning techniques.

To close this gap, Few-Shot Learning (FSL) can be applied to build sample-efficient models which enable the use of pre-trained models to generalize to unseen classes of images given only a few examples.

The FSL paradigm differs from traditional supervised learning in which images together with their annotations are presented. Instead, FSL, requires two sets of classes C_{seen} and C_{unseen} . The model is trained on class samples from C_{seen} and evaluated on class samples from C_{unseen} . The goal is to train a model and extract features from class samples in C_{seen} . If the data in C_{seen} allows for learning generic filters, it could be used to train a model to obtain meaningful feature representations of the samples in C_{unseen} . The extent to which the feature representations of the class samples in C_{unseen} are meaningful boils down to the correspondence between the class samples in C_{seen} and C_{unseen} .

It is widely known that traditional Supervised Learning approaches cannot generalize to unseen classes without adjusting the architecture of the model. FSL models can directly generalize to unseen classes without making adaptations to the model. To explain this, it is important to first discuss the notion of a support and query set.

Support Set S : A support set S holds a number of annotated images per class. Typically consisting of K images from N classes including their annotations. Formally, this is referred to as N -Way K -Shot.

Query Set Q : A query set Q is composed of images without annotations. Each of these images are classified on the basis of the support images and their annotations.

FSL models are able to generalize to samples from unseen classes C_{unseen} by projecting query and support images in some embedding space after which classification can be performed by utilizing distances between the query embedding vectors and the support embedding vectors. These support and query sets could contain images from novel classes.

Note that traditional supervised learning tasks iterate multiple times over the entire dataset. Such an iteration is frequently called an epoch. Instead, FSL relies on episodic training which uses a single query and support set per episode. Each episode requires a new N -Way K -Shot support set from which prototypes are extracted. Generating a new support set at each episode is important for the generalization performance of the model. After training, the FSL model can be used to perform predictions on query instances from a test set.

Popular approaches include Matching Networks and Prototypical Networks, *Vinyals et al. (2016)*, *Snell et al. (2017)*. In Matching Networks, inputs are embedded into a latent space after which a nearest neighbor lookup is performed to classify the inputs. Prototypical Networks learn for each class an embedding vector (prototype) in a trainable embedding space. The distance from these instances to each of the embedding vectors is computed according to some metric. The instances are then assigned to the class corresponding to the closest embedding vector.

2.3. Few-Shot Semantic Segmentation

In Section 2.3, the concept of FSL is explained in the context of classification. Segmentation can be seen as a generalization of classification by performing classification on a per pixel basis. As a result, an area of research has evolved that is concerned with segmenting images when only a few samples are available. In general, these techniques operate by performing segmentation through pixel-level matching within an embedding space. Few-Shot segmentation (FSS) models require the use of support samples to generate dense output masks on query instances. A popular FSS approach is PANet, *Wang et al. (2019)*, which can be seen as an extension of Prototypical Networks for dense prediction tasks. PANet embeds both support and query images in an embedding space and simultaneously learns prototypes for each semantic class. The embedding features that match the closest prototype are selected for segmentation. Many derivative FSS models are built on top of PANet including Self-Support FSS which is described in Section 3.2.

3. Model Architectures

In this section, the specific state-of-the-art models are described. This includes DeepLabV3+ and Self-Support Few-Shot Segmentation.

3.1. DeepLabV3+

DeepLabV3+ is a state-of-the-art semantic segmentation model with many useful properties, *Chen et al. (2017a)*. It requires the use of backbone model to extract features from an input. In the encoding phase, multi-scale feature maps are extracted by an Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP) module to effectively increase the receptive field of the model without introducing more parameters or

reducing the size of the images. A specialized decoder is used to refine the segmentation results along the borders of the object. The feature maps are aggregated to form dense segmentation masks. An overview of this architecture is depicted in Fig.1.

Fig.1: DeepLabV3+ architecture

3.2. Self-Support Few-Shot Segmentation

The Self-Support Few-Shot Segmentation (SS-FSS), *Fan et al. (2022)*, network is an extension of PANet, *Wang et al. (2019)*. PANet suffers from the dependence on the support prototype for query segmentation. This leads to poor performance whenever the intra-class appearance fluctuates slightly. To alleviate this problem, SS-FSS analyses the feature cosine similarity of cross-object and intra-object pixels. This follows the *Gestalt* principle, suggesting that pixels from the same object are more similar than pixels from different objects. As a result, SS-FSS leverages self-support prototypes which attempts to match the query features. A high-level overview of this architecture is depicted in Fig.2.

Fig.2: The Self-Support Few-Shot architecture. Identical to PANet, support prototypes are generated from the support image which are matched with the features extracted from the query image. This yields a segmentation mask for the background and foreground class. Afterwards, prototypes are generated for the query images by leveraging a Self-Support Foreground Prototype (SSFP) and Adaptive Self-Support Background Prototype (ASBP) module. Finally, both the self-support prototypes and support prototypes are matched against the query features to yield the output mask.

4. Dataset

The dataset used in this research is a subset from the Structural Defects (SD) dataset, *Bonnin-Pascual and Ortiz (2018)*. It contains images of vessel structures damages including corrosion, cracks and break-down of coating. In this research, the main goal is to segment cracks. To achieve this, a new dataset is formed by taking a subset of the SD dataset in which exclusively cracks are visible. The resulting dataset consists of 36 images.

3.1. Dataset Splits

The dataset is split into a training, validation and testing set holding respectively 24, 6 and 6 images. An impression of these images is provided in Fig.3. Due to the limited number of images in the train and validation test, the images in each of the splits need to be carefully picked. The process of picking these images is performed in three steps: a pre-trained ResNet50 model extracts feature vectors from the second to last layer for each image. T-SNE is applied to the feature vectors reducing the high-dimensional feature vectors to two dimensions. Then the images are separated into three splits by means of stratified sampling. This strategy ensures that that different types of images are distributed evenly in all splits.

Fig.3: 2D T-SNE plot of dataset. Samples are divided over the train, validation and test split in a stratified way to ensure that the sets are diverse.

5. Experimental Setup

In this section, the experimental setup is described. First, model-specific details including the use of a backbone, transfer learning and fine-tuning are discussed, then training and testing details.

5.1. Backbone Model

Both DeepLabV3+ and Self-Support Few-Shot segmentation (SS-FSS) require the use of a backbone model for feature extraction. Identical to *Fan et al. (2022)*, a pre-trained ResNet-50 model is used that has been trained on an ImageNet1k classification task. This ensures that both models have a similar capacity, allowing for a fair comparison.

5.2. Pre-Trained Segmentation Weights

As described in Section 5.1, both models make use of a ResNet-50 backbone model with pre-trained classification weights. In the case of SS-FSS it is possible to directly use the backbone model to perform segmentation with. However further pre-training the backbone model on a segmentation task could yield better performance when faced with another segmentation task. To achieve this, the pre-trained ResNet-50 model is further fine-tuned on a downstream Pascal VOC segmentation task. For DeepLabV3+, the ResNet backbone is further fine-tuned using a standard supervised learning routine. SS-FSS is trained in an episodic way as described in Section 2.3. This ensures that filters are obtained which are specialized for segmentation purposes.

5.3. Fine-Tuning on Target Dataset

After fine-tuning the pre-trained classification weights for both models on the Pascal VOC segmentation task, it is possible to fine-tune both models on the SD dataset. For DeepLabV3+ this entails replacing the penultimate layer to support two classes: background and crack. In the case of SS-FSS no architectural changes are required in order to support the new output classes as few-shot models traditionally are designed to directly generalize to unseen classes by constructing support sets. In this work the routine as described in *Hu et al. (2022)* is followed which demonstrated that fine-tuning has a positive effect on the generalization performance of few-shot models. To fine-tune SS-FSS, the training and validation split of the dataset are used for episodic training. Each episode samples a set of query images I_q and a set of support images I_s separately for each split where $I_s \cap I_q = \emptyset$. The training details are given in Section 5.4.

5.4. Training Details

All models are trained end-to-end with the Adam optimizer. Early stopping is applied by incorporating a learning rate scheduler which anneals the learning rate by a factor of 10 with a patience of 2. When a learning rate of 1e-8 is reached, the training process terminates. All images are resized to 256x256 or 512x512 using bilinear interpolation. For both models a batch size of 6 is chosen. The shared training configurations for DeepLabV3+ and SS-FSS are given in Table I. The specific training details for the SS-FSS models are depicted in Table II. Finally, data augmentations are optionally applied during training which are described in Table III.

5.5. Testing Details

To assess the generalization capabilities of the models, the testing set is used to assess the performance of the different models. During testing the images are resized to 256x256 or 512x512 using bilinear interpolation. No augmentations are performed. The process for DeepLabV3+ is straightforward in which a forward pass over the set of test images yields the segmentation masks. In case of SS-FSS, a support set is constructed by randomly picking images from the training split. Naturally, the query images are picked from the testing split. To assess the performance of the models, the models are evaluated on recall, precision and F1-score for the defect class.

Table I: Shared training settings for Self-Support Few-Shot Segmentation and DeepLabV3+

Setting	Value
Image Size	{256x256, 512x512}
Backbone Model	ResNet50
Learning Rate	0.0001
Optimizer	Adam
LR Scheduler	ReduceLROnPlateau (patience 2)
Augmentations	{ Yes, No }

Table II: Training setting for Self-Support Few-Shot Segmentation

Setting	Value
N-Query	6
K-Shot	{1, 5}
N-Way	1
# of Episodes	100

Table III: Applied segmentation during training

Augmentation	Value
ColorJitter	probability=0.5
	brightness=0
	contrast=0.5
	saturation=0.2
	hue=0.01
Grayscale	probability=0.5
HorizontalFlip	probability=0.5
Rotate	probability=1
	limit=30

6. Results

In this section, quantitative and qualitative results are given for the DeepLabV3+ and SS-FSS models. In Table V the results are given for the DeepLabV3+ models. The best performing configuration is highlighted in bold. In Table IV the results are given for the 5-shot SS-FSS models. All SS-FSS configurations using 5-shot outperformed the corresponding 1-shot counterpart (see Table VI in the Appendix). Fig.4 shows a selection of test images. An analysis of the results is found in Section 7.

Table IV: The results of Self-Support Few Shot segmentation in a 5-shot context

Model	Augmented	5-Shot		
		Recall	Precision	F1-Score
SS-FSS (256x256)	YES	46.7 ± 3.05	48.1 ± 1.75	47.4 ± 2.14
SS-FSS (512x512)	YES	58.2 ± 1.60	63.9 ± 2.13	60.9 ± 0.53
SS-FSS (256x256)	NO	35.6 ± 2.05	45.9 ± 1.14	40.0 ± 1.05
SS-FSS (512x512)	NO	47.1 ± 0.84	56.4 ± 1.75	51.3 ± 0.31

Table V: The results of DeepLabV3+

Model	Augmented	Recall	Precision	F1-Score
DeepLabV3+ (512x512)	YES	51.2 ± 9.73	47.2 ± 5.43	48.3 ± 2.39
DeepLabV3+ (512x512)	YES	51.2 ± 3.02	59.3 ± 2.70	56.9 ± 6.55
DeepLabV3+ (512x512)	NO	38.5 ± 3.85	78.0 ± 4.18	51.4 ± 2.70
DeepLabV3+ (512x512)	NO	33.3 ± 4.70	72.6 ± 5.95	45.4 ± 4.23

Fig.4: Qualitative results corresponding to the best quantitative results of Tables IV and V. The first and second column are respectively the input images together with the ground-truth masks. The third and fourth column depict the predictions of DeepLabV3+ 256x256 and 512x512 images. Column five and six depict the results of 5-shot SS-FSS on 256x256 and 512x512 images.

7. Discussion

In this work, the SS-FSS model is contrasted against DeepLabV3+. To make a fair comparison, both models use of the same ResNet-50 backbone which is pre-trained on the PASCAL-VOC dataset. In Section 6, the quantitative and qualitative results are given.

7.1. Best Performing Model

The best F1-scores are obtained with 5-shot SS-FSS models on the larger 512x512 images when data augmentation is applied as can be derived from Tables IV and V. These SS-FSS models achieve an average F1-score of 60.9% with an average recall and precision that are respectively 58.2% and 63.9%. Without data augmentation, a considerably lower F1-score is achieved: 40.0%. It also appears that applying SS-FSS on higher resolution images has a positive effect on the overall F1-score. The qualitative results in Fig.4 show that although some regions are undersegmented or oversegmented, the model is successful in finding the region with the crack.

7.2. Influence Image Size

Interestingly, DeepLabV3+ outperforms SS-FSS in all experiments with images of size 256x256. An explanation might be that the low-level features are leveraged to the decoder block. This yields considerably sharper segmentation masks, in contrast to SS-FSS which generally yields coarser masks. These coarse masks could have a negative impact on the precision when the crack is over-segmented or lead to recall issues if the crack is under-segmented. However, from the qualitative results, Fig.4, it can be observed that SS-FSS is better at detecting if there is a crack, regardless of how well it is segmented.

7.2. Influence of Data Augmentation

For all models, except the DeepLabV3+ model on 512x512 images, data augmentation has a positive influence on the F1-score of the models. This suggests that the SS-FSS models benefit from data augmentation techniques to improve its generalization performance. Further research needs to be conducted to gather more empirical evidence if data augmentation truly has a positive impact on the performance of these Few-Shot models.

8. Conclusion and Future Work

This work provides a comparison of two state-of-the-art segmentation models: DeepLabV3+ and Self-Support Few-Shot segmentation (SS-FSS) on a small dataset containing crack defects in ships. The highest F1-scores were obtained with a SS-FSS model in a 5-shot setting that considers data augmentations to generate more diverse images from the small crack dataset. When testing the SS-FSS models, it appeared that all 1-shot models are outperformed by their 5-shot counterpart. This suggests that multiple support images are helpful to extract useful features needed to perform segmentation.

These results indicate that Few-Shot segmentation models in combination with fine-tuning can be an enticing option when limited images are available over traditional supervised segmentation approaches.

Although we obtained promising results, there are several opportunities for future research, both on further developing the application of FSS and on the use in practice.

8.1. Optimizing the application of Few-Shot Techniques for the detection of cracks

First, a research opportunity would be to study the effectiveness of pre-trained segmentation weights as this is not evaluated in this paper. Although some research suggests that pre-training on a large segmentation dataset such as Pascal VOC positively influences the performance after fine-tuning on a small dataset, additional experiments need to be conducted to confirm this.

Second, a research opportunity would be to study whether FSS models outperform traditional supervised segmentation models on a wide variety of different segmentation tasks. This research is a first effort to better understand the Few-Shot strategies and how they compare to deep traditional segmentation techniques.

Third, research needs to be conducted to investigate how to robustly evaluate the performance of such models when only a handful of images are available. Although each set of experiments is performed five times to account for initialization, the models tend to have a high variance due to the small number of images that are available for training.

Finally, research should be conducted to investigate the importance of a representative support set. From the experiments it seems that providing a support set during testing time improves the robustness of the predictions (reducing the standard deviation in all experiments for SS-FSS

compared to DeepLabV3+). Research can be conducted to find strategies to obtain a representative support which works well for arbitrary query images.

8.2. Further exploring the application of Computer Vision based crack detection in practice

In the introduction it is postulated that for multiple types of stakeholders in the maritime domain this crack detection based on Computer Vision technology may be of interest. If we widen that scope somewhat, it could also be of interest for other steel objects of similar sizes, such as bridges and other constructions in the open air. Expanding further, rust detection could also be an option. So, with the results presented in this paper as a basis, we intend to gauge with organizations that may have an interest whether these results appeal to them in such a way that we can start looking further into practical questions, such as:

- What are the minimum conditions for taking usable pictures?
- What will be the required training or instruction level of the photographer?
- What are the minimum required (or minimum usable) recall and precision scores, for the various applications?
- What will be the (estimated) required number of training pictures to achieve these scores?
- Will statistics, regression or other data processing or machine learning techniques be of assistance in bringing the requirements of the last two items down? E.g. by predicting the spread of cracks over the steel ship construction on basis of a number of samples, or on basis of vision-based detection with scores lower than 100%.

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Appendix

Table VI: The results of Self-Support Few Shot segmentation in a 1-shot context.

Model	Augmented	1-Shot		
		Recall	Precision	F1-Score
SS-FSS (256x256)	YES	45.0 ± 5.64	46.9 ± 1.21	45.8 ± 3.28
SS-FSS (512x512)	YES	49.2 ± 2.49	57.9 ± 2.65	53.2 ± 2.37
SS-FSS (256x256)	NO	25.1 ± 1.79	50.3 ± 1.44	33.5 ± 1.59
SS-FSS (512x512)	NO	42.8 ± 1.01	63.5 ± 1.84	51.1 ± 0.62

Improving Vessel Safety with a Digital Twin for Ice Accretion

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Abstract

This paper presents a methodology to predict ice accretion caused by wave-generated and wind-generated sea-spray on a vessel. A droplet trajectory model is combined with a spray impact simulator to determine the quantity and location of seawater droplets hitting the vessel. The mass flux of ice formation is determined by solving a set of partial differential equations describing the conservation of mass, heat, and salt in the boundary layer of brine near the ice surface. Icing on the vessel is computed using a meshed representation of the vessel geometry in three-dimensional space. The methodology is validated on a documented fishing vessel capsized due to excessive icing.

1. Introduction

The effects of marine icing on vessels at sea can be catastrophic, *Shellard (1974)*, *Huuhtanen (2018)*. Vessel icing can impact shipping, defence operations, fisheries, offshore exploration and production and the support and services of vessels and offshore platforms. Specific hazards described by *Ryerson (2009)* include a reduction in stability, damage to vessel structures, slipping hazards on decks, ladders, handrails, and damage to equipment including winches, cranes, and antennas as well as rescue equipment, hatches, and firefighting equipment. In the worst case, rapidly accumulating ice can cause a rise in the vessel centre of gravity and, depending on the location of the icing, a heel which can cause a reduction in the righting arm and possible vessel capsized. As polar regions continue to become more navigable, the icing phenomenon, and its impact, is expected to increase.

One particularly tragic case occurred on the U.S. flagged fishing vessel ‘Scandies Rose’. Sadly, the vessel capsized in extreme spray-icing conditions on December 31, 2019, with the loss of five of seven fishermen onboard. However, ‘Scandies Rose’ is unique because the survivors could attest to the weather conditions on the day of the incident; the environmental factors contributing to the icing shown in Table I have been corroborated by both the may-day call and on-scene reports from the rescue helicopter. ‘Scandies Rose’ is also distinctive because its deck load, 198 net-type fishing pots, ice differently than solid plates and cylinders because they are porous. This can present added challenges when predicting the rate of ice accretion. While fishing vessel icing accidents and near-accidents such as this are often treated as singular events, they are becoming more and more commonplace (see F/V ‘Destination’ and F/V ‘Sandra Five’) and demand further investigation.

Table I: On-scene weather, *USCG (2021)*

Weather Element	Value
Wind Velocity	18 – 25 m/s (35 – 50 kn)
Wind Direction (Relative to the Vessel)	045°
Significant Wave Height	6 – 10 m
Wave Period	9 – 10 s
Water Temperature	3° C
Air Temperature	-12° C

Furthermore, fishing vessel traffic in the Arctic and near-Arctic waters is increasing at a rapid pace. Measurement of the volume of shipping, taken between 2013 and 2019, show a substantial increase in traffic, when counting both the number of individual ships (up 25%) and the total nautical distance sailed during the six-year period (up 75%), *Protection of the Arctic and Marine Environment (2020)*.

Fishing vessels dominate both groups, representing more than 40% of all ships in the Arctic area, and, of the total distance sailed, fishing vessels account for 45%.

Early research on marine icing focused on forecasting techniques which alerted the mariner to potentially dangerous conditions at sea. Most common were methodologies that used statistical data to develop relationships between weather conditions, e.g., air temperature and wind, to predict the severity of icing, *Overland (1990)*. In fact, many simple algorithms are still in practice today. For example, the maximum assumed icing loads on fishing vessels in both the International Code on Intact Stability 6.3 and US 46 CFR 28.550 is 30 kg/m² of ice on horizontal surfaces and 15 kg/m² of ice on vertical surfaces. There are limitations to approaches such as these. First, both regulatory schemes assume a uniform ice loading and do not consider the effects of listing due to off-centre weight additions. This assumption is short-sighted as vessels rarely have wind and seas directly off the vessels bow. Second, in the case of fishing vessels, these rulesets assume that icing is applied over the top and sides of the fishing pots, commonly referred to as the “shoebox method.” However, fishing pots are porous (being constructed of steel tubing with netting), which causes ice to build up on the exterior and interior of the pot. The result of this approach is that potential vessel icing can be vastly underestimated, *National Transportation Safety Board, (2021)*. More recently, physical models of the ice accretion process have been developed. Using a boundary layer approximation, the icing problem may be reduced to three partial differential equations consisting of a mass, heat, and salt conservation of brine on the ice-brine interface, *Hansen (2012)* and *Horjen (2013)*. With specific environmental conditions and knowledge about the vessel geometry, the quantity and location of ice on the vessel is predicted.

2. Problem formulation

The solution to the icing problem is shown in Fig.1. First, the trajectory of water droplets is predicted using first principles. Velocity flow fields are generated using computational fluid dynamics (CFD). Next, the spray flux, i.e., the location and amount of water striking the vessel, is determined. Finally, the quantity of ice generated from the spray flux is calculated by solving differential equations describing the conservation of mass, heat, and salt of brine at the ice surface. Once the quantity and location of ice is determined, a stability analysis on the vessel can be performed to determine safe and unsafe operating conditions. An overview of each section of the model is described next.

Fig.1: Ice accretion model and problem formulation

1. **Droplet Trajectory Model.** This approach combines Newton’s Second Law for spray droplet trajectories with streamline velocity to predict mass accumulation of precipitation on the vessel. Inputs to the droplet trajectory model include wind velocity, injection angle, droplet size, and droplet velocity. Streamline velocities are generated using computational fluid dynamics with fishing pots modelled as porous surfaces using the Darcy-Forchheimer Law.
2. **Spray Flux.** The liquid water content (LWC) of wind-generated and wave-generated sea-spray are calculated to determine the total mass of water striking the vessel. The spray flux is determined by simulation, where the weight of water per cubic meter of air for each type of spray event is determined.

3. Ice Accretion Model. The mass flux of ice formation is determined by solving a set of partial differential equations describing the conservation of mass, heat, and salt in the boundary layer of brine near the ice surface.
4. Stability Model. After calculating the amount and location of ice for a set time simulation, righting arm curves with ice loads were developed for a documented capsized event.

An abbreviated overview of the droplet trajectory model and spray flux calculations is described in this paper, but the primary focus is the ice accretion model and stability analysis of the F/V ‘Scandies Rose’.

2. Sea-spray mass flux

2.1 Sources of icing

There are two primary sources of offshore icing: atmospheric icing and sea-spray icing. The freezing of freshwater is called atmospheric icing and includes the precipitation of rain, snow, hail, and drizzle resulting from the deposition of water vapor directly as ice crystals, *Ryerson (2011)*. Atmospheric icing is less of a danger to vessels and offshore structures and is less frequent than sea-spray icing, *Shellard (1974)*.

Sea-spray icing is generated from either wave-generated spray or wind-generated spray. Wave-generated sea spray is caused by the collision of waves with the vessel. Wave-generated sea spray is generally the source of large but brief periodic water flux that originates near the bow of the vessel, *Hansen (2012)*. Wind-generated sea spray is caused by lifting droplets from wave crests on the ocean surface. The wind-spray is a small but constant water flux present in the air when the wind speed is greater than 9 m/s. In this paper, the contribution of atmospheric icing is discounted.

2.2 Calculation of water flux

To determine the rate of ice accretion, the mass flux of sea-spray events incident on the vessel must be computed. The mass flux is a function of the environmental conditions, droplet radii, droplet trajectories, vessel speed and vessel geometry. Computational fluid dynamics is used to calculate the droplet trajectories around the complete geometry of the vessel and generate velocity fields used in the both the wind-generated and wave-generated sea-spray equations of motions, *DeNucci and Brahan (2022)*.

It is impractical to simulate all droplets within even a cubic meter of air during one second, let alone all droplets that travel through a plane 20 m x 10 m during an hour. Therefore, a method proposed by *Kulyakhtin and Tsarau (2014)* is used where one droplet is released into the air flow, but that one droplet represents a “parcel” of mass representing all the droplets that are of a given range of sizes passing through an area for a certain period.

2.3 Wind-generated sea spray flux

Wind-generated sea spray flux was solved using a set of experimental relationships to calculate droplet concentrations near the ocean surface for a range of wind velocities (0 – 28.8 m/s), *Jones and Andreas (2012)* and *Brahan et al. (2023)*. This approach relates droplet size to that droplet’s overall contribution to the LWC for implementation where one droplet may now represent a parcel of mass.

2.4 Wave-generated sea spray flux

To determine wave-generated sea spray flux, a relationship between droplet size and mass was developed, *Brahan et al. (2023)*. The correlation between droplet size and mass flux was determined using empirical wave and spray data collected during a Bering Sea patrol aboard the U.S. Coast Guard Cutter (CGC) ‘Midgett’ in the month of February, *Ryerson (1995)*. These results were integrated to determine

to determine the percent weight contribution of the overall spray cloud by a certain size of droplet. *Lozowski et al. (2000)* and *Zakrzewski (1986)* provide methods to determine the overall mass of water which originates from the waves in a single spray event.

2.5 Total incoming water flux to the fishing pot stack

After determining both the mass fluxes and droplet sizes of water generated from wave-vessel interaction and the mass flux in air given the on-scene weather conditions, the total mass flux impinging the fishing pot stack could be calculated. This was accomplished by releasing each droplet, which represented a mass parcel, into the wind at an initiation location and simulating using the droplet trajectory model, *DeNucci and Brahan (2022)*. The trajectory of the droplets was tracked to determine whether the droplet hit the fishing pot stack, which was represented by a plane located on the starboard beam. Using the pot porosity, γ , of 0.905, it was simulated that $(1 - \gamma)$ or 9.5% of the mass of the parcel was deposited on the starboard boundary of the fishing pots.

This approach yields the mass flux of the water striking the fishing pot stack from both the water droplets present in the atmosphere and those generated from the vessel-wave interaction. While the mass flux from the wind spray can be assumed to be steady state, the mass flux generated from the vessel-wave interaction is not steady state.

To capture the high mass flux when the vessel encounters a wave *and* the period of relatively low mass flux from only the wind-generated spray which follows, the total mass flux is modelled as a step function. When considering the heat capacity associated with incoming mass, there is likewise a period of high incoming heat capacity followed by a period of minimal heat capacity warming the ice and brine.

The duration of the spray event is, *Zakrzewski (1987)*:

$$\tau_s = \frac{C v_{sw} h_s}{U_{10}^2} \quad (1)$$

where C is an experimental constant which depends on both the dimensions and configuration of the vessel hull. *Zakrzewski (1987)* suggests $C=20.62$ for a fishing vessel which experiences a wave-generated spray every second wave collision. h_s is the significant wave height, v_{sw} is the vessel's speed relative to the wave, and U_{10} is the wind velocity 10 m above the free surface.

Aksyutin (1979) describes the wave encounter interval, P_w , as:

$$P_w = \frac{1.56 \tau_w^2}{v_{sw}} \quad (2)$$

where τ_w is the wave period.

The total mass flux, \dot{M}_t , striking the vessel is described by:

$$R_w = \dot{M}_t = \Pi(t) \dot{M}_{wave} + \dot{M}_{wind} \quad (3)$$

where $\Pi(t)$ represents a step function with a wave duration (Eq.(1)) and the wave encounter interval (Eq.(2)). Since every other wave causes a sea-spray event, *Zakrzewski (1987)*, the spray period begins after $2P_w$ periods. Fig.2. shows an example of this flux for one node on the fishing pot stacks.

Using the environmental conditions described in Table I, one hour of modelled sea-spray events resulted in 27 MT of water striking the meshed surface of the fishing pots on the 'Scandies Rose'.

Fig.2: Mass flux versus time for a period of five waves

3. Icing equations

The thermodynamic icing calculations are based on differential equations, *Horjen (1990)*. Normally, sea-spray icing occurs in a *wet icing* mode, where the icing surface is covered by a film of liquid brine. In this instance, the heat flux away from the surface exposed to water spray is insufficient to freeze or entrap the impinging water. In the special case where the heat flux is sufficient, i.e., typically when air temperatures are less than 10°C, the icing calculations are vastly simplified. This is referred to as a ‘dry icing’ mode.

3.1 Heat flux

Ice accretion prediction requires a thermodynamic heat balance. When water droplets strike a vessel, they freeze due to various heat fluxes. The heat fluxes are convective heat flux (Q_c), evaporative heat flux (Q_e), radiant heat flux (Q_r), and heat capacity of impinging water droplets (Q_d). The heat flux due to viscous aerodynamic heating (Q_v), conduction (Q_a), and kinetic energy of incoming droplets (Q_k) are usually neglected because they are small.

Although numerous authors describe the heat flux equations, *Horjen (1990)*, *Lozowski (2000)*, *Hansen (2012)*, *Dehghani et al. (2017)*, this model uses a parameterized form in which heat flux equations are presented as functions of T_s , where T_s is the equilibrium freezing temperature of the surface brine.

The convective heat flux is the sensible heat flux between the freezing surface and the surrounding air:

$$Q_c = h_c(T_s - T_a) \quad (7)$$

where h_c is the heat transfer coefficient, T_s the temperature of the water at the air-water interface, and T_a the air temperature. The heat transfer coefficient is given by:

$$h_c = \frac{Nuk_a}{L} \quad (8)$$

where k_a is the thermal conductivity of air and L is the characteristic length of the component, which for cylindrical components is the diameter. Nu is the Nusselt number which *Lozowski et al. (2000)* define for cylindrical components as:

$$Nu = 3.0Re^{0.50} \quad (9)$$

Q_e is the evaporative heat loss to the surrounding air flow is given by *Bergman et al. (2011)*:

$$Q_e = h_c \left(\frac{Pr}{Sc}\right)^{0.63} \left(\frac{\varepsilon \ell_f}{P c_a}\right) (e_s(T_s) - RH \cdot e_a(T_a)) \quad (10)$$

where h_c is the heat transfer coefficient, Pr is the Prandtl number, Sc is the Schmidt number, ε is the ratio of molecular weights of water vapor and dry air, P is the atmospheric pressure, ℓ_v is the latent heat of vaporization for water at the surface temperature, c_a is the specific heat capacity of dry air at constant pressure, RH is the relative humidity of the air, and $e_s(T)$ is the saturated water pressure. The saturated water pressure has been linearized by *Myers (2001)*:

$$e_s(t) \approx E_o + e_o T \quad (11)$$

where $e_o = 27.03$ Pa/K and $E_o = -6803$ Pa.

Q_r , the radiative heat flux is given by:

$$Q_r = \sigma(\varepsilon_s T_s^4 - \varepsilon_a T_a^4) \quad (12)$$

where σ is the Stefan Boltzmann constant, and ε_s and ε_a are the emissivity's of the air flow and icing surface, both considered to be 1. Using these values, Eq.(12) simplifies to:

$$Q_r = 4.4(T_s - T_a) \quad (13)$$

Q_d , the heat capacity of impinging water droplets, is given by *Zarling (1980)* as:

$$Q_d = M_{wt} c_w (T_s - T_d) \quad (14)$$

where c_w is the specific heat capacity of water, T_d the droplet temperature of the wave spray prior to impingement, and M_{wt} the mass flux of water. The value of T_d can be calculated on the individual droplet scale by the heat equation, *Kato (2012)*, but the assumption that the incoming droplet temperature is the average between the temperature of the air and water proposed by *Stallabrass (1980)* is used. The total heat out of the system, Q , is the combination of Eqs. (7), (10), (13) and (14).

3.2 Wet icing

Conservation of mass, heat and salt give the approximate differential equations of the brine film:

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} + \nabla_t(v_b X) = R_w - I \quad (15)$$

$$c_b X \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + v_b \nabla_t\right) T_b = Q + (1 - \sigma) l_f I \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{X}{S_b} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + v_b \nabla_t\right) S_b = I(1 - \sigma) - R_w \left(1 - \frac{S_w}{S_b}\right) \quad (17)$$

In Eqs.(15) – (17), X is the local brine amount per unit area (kg/m^2), T_b the brine temperature and S_b the brine salinity (in parts per thousand). R_w is the impinging sea spray flux ($\text{kg/m}^2\text{s}$) and I ($\text{kg/m}^2\text{s}$) is the rate of accretion of both the ice and the brine trapped in the ice. The parameter v_b is the brine velocity and ∇_t is the differential operator in the tangential direction, i.e., along the direction in which the brine will move. c_b is the specific heat capacity of the brine, σ is the fraction of entrapped brine in the

accretion, l_f is the latent heat of freezing and S_w is the salinity of seawater. Mass flux due to evaporation is neglected, *Myers and Charpin (2004)*.

3.3 Ice accretion rate

Using relationships between brine salinity and brine temperature provided by *Assur (1958)*, *Horjen and Vefnsmo (1987)*, Eqs. (16) and (17) are combined, resulting in:

$$I(1 - \sigma) - R_w \left(1 - \frac{S_w}{S_b}\right) = -F(S_b) \left(\frac{Q}{l_f} + I(1 - \sigma)\right) \quad (18)$$

where

$$F(S_b) = K_o \frac{(1 - 10^{-3} S_b)^2}{S_b},$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_o &\approx 1.46 \cdot 10^3, & S_b < 125 \\ K_o &\approx 8.16 \cdot 10^2, & 125 \leq S_b < 230 \end{aligned}$$

Solving for I , results in the following ice accretion rate:

$$I = \frac{\left(1 - \frac{S_w}{S_b}\right) R_w - \frac{F(S_b) Q}{l_f}}{(1 - \sigma)(1 + F(S_b))} \quad (19)$$

By introducing a variable $Y \equiv X S_b$ and the assumption that brine will only travel in the negative z direction, non-linear hyperbolic differential icing equations are derived from Eqs. (15) and (17):

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (v_b X) = R_w - I \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (v_b Y) = R_w S_w - \sigma I \frac{Y}{X} \quad (21)$$

For purely horizontal and vertical geometries, *Horjen (1990)* provides for brine velocity:

$$v_b = -0.264 \frac{g}{\rho_b \mu_b} X^2 \quad (22)$$

3.4 Mesh geometry and nodal analysis

While Eq.(22) is valid for a purely vertical or horizontal surface, the geometry presented on a fishing pot is different than a vertical plate, where water droplets generally flow downward. The mesh webbing on a fishing pot force water to move at a 45° angle to the deck, and thus water is not free to flow in a purely vertical manner.

Fig.3: Diagonally linked fishing pot stack nodes where brine may run off at 45° to deck.

Instead of nodes being linked in a vertical manner, the nodes, shown in Fig.3, are linked at 45° bias in the fishing pot meshing. Assuming the brine flows only along the mesh of the fishing pot at a 45° angle, and it does not drip, Eq.(22) is modified to:

$$v_b = -0.264 \cos(45^\circ) \frac{g}{\rho_b \mu_b} X^2 \quad (23)$$

To simplify calculations, all the brine flows toward the aft node, in the -x direction, rather than having half of the brine flow in the +x and half in the -x directions. Also, since nodes are not linked in the z direction, but at a 45° angle, Eqs. (21) and (22) are also modified. A new variable, φ , represents this new direction.

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi}(v_b X) = R_w - I \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi}(v_b Y) = R_w S_w - \sigma I \frac{Y}{X} \quad (25)$$

3.5 Dry icing

If the sea spray flux is relatively low, and the weather is sufficiently cold, it is possible for all the incoming spray to freeze on impact, *Hansen (2012)*. As described in *Horjen (1990)*, this occurs when:

$$R_w \leq \frac{Q}{l_f(1-\sigma)} \quad (26)$$

where R_w is the spray flux during a spray event and σ is the interfacial coefficient, assumed to be 0.34. Simply stated, Eq.(26) describes a condition where the heat transport away from the brine is greater than or equal to the latent heat produced if all the impinging spray freezes.

It was first assumed that dry icing was not present on the fishing stack. However, there are periods of heavy sea spray followed by periods of extremely little spray, if any at all. This presents the situation where dry icing may exist for a period in between sea spray events followed by a period of wet icing. Additionally, water spray is non-uniform on the fishing pot stack, meaning certain areas receive higher fluxes of impinging spray than others, i.e. dry and wet icing may exist on the fishing pot stack simultaneously for different locations on the stack. To factor the presence of the brine, Eq.(26) is modified:

$$R_w + X \leq \frac{Q}{l_f(1-\sigma)} \quad (27)$$

4. Numerical solution of icing equations

4.1 Initial conditions

The model assumes an infinitesimally thin brine film layer is present on the surfaces at the beginning of icing. The first wave generated spray hits the surface at $t=0$. At $t=0$,

$$X = 0, \quad Y = 0, \quad v_b = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad t = 0$$

Accordingly, we cannot use the result,

$$S_b = \frac{Y}{X}$$

to determine the brine film salinity (which is needed to calculate the icing intensity) at the initial time step. Applying initial conditions to Eqs. (16) and (17) the icing intensity becomes:

$$I = -\frac{Q(S_b)}{l_f(1-\sigma)} \quad (28)$$

$$I = \frac{R_w \left(1 - \frac{S_w}{S_b}\right)}{(1-\sigma)} \quad (29)$$

When ice and brine coexist, the brine salinity is a function of brine temperature only, so it becomes critical to properly approximate the initial brine temperature. In fact, there are several empirical expressions which predict brine salinity from brine temperature, *Assure (1958)* and *Cox and Weeks (1983)*.

4.2. Method of lines

Eqs. (20) and (21) are solved using the method of lines. In this approach, the solution is based on discretizing the equations in the direction unique to fishing pots and solving the problem as a series of ordinary differential equations, where the solution of one point is used as input for the point directly below. Mathematically, this is represented by combining Eqs. (20) and (21) with Eq.(23):

$$\frac{\partial X_i}{\partial t} = R_w^i(t) - I \left(\frac{Y_i}{X_i}, t\right) + \frac{c}{\Delta\varphi} (X_{i+1}(t)^3 - X_i^3) \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial Y_i}{\partial t} = S_w R_w^i(t) - \sigma \frac{Y_i}{X_i} I \left(\frac{Y_i}{X_i}, t\right) + \frac{c}{\Delta\varphi} (X_{i+1}(t)^2 Y_{i+1}(t) - X_i^2 Y_i) \quad (31)$$

X_i and Y_i are the amounts of salt and brine at point z_i , and $R_w^i(t)$ the time dependent spray flux to φ_i .

5. Simulation results

5.1 Ice accretion results

Incorporating the CFD trajectory results and incoming mass fluxes to the fishing pot stack, ice accretion on the ‘Scandies Rose’ is simulated. The simulation evaluates the icing on the extreme edge (starboard beam), where forensic evidence and witness statements indicates ice build-up. The fishing pot stack was divided into 0.2 m x 0.2 m cells, and a 45° angle nodal analysis, Fig.3, was performed, with incoming spray to each node representing that of a step function in Fig.2. Table I shows the modelled weather conditions.

The icing simulation was conducted for an hour, with the time step in the simulation set as 0.005 s. Over an hour, 16.89 MT of ice accumulated on the fishing pot stack on the starboard beam of the vessel from the 27 MT incident on the vessel. Fig.4 displays the total mass of ice accumulation as a function of area for the given grid location.

Fig.4: Ice mass per unit area (kg/m^2) for a one-hour simulation. The greatest icing concentrations are 590 kg/m^2 .

The simulation indicates significant ice accretion in the vicinity of the forward quarter of the fishing pot stack. The highest concentrations are over 590 kg/m². Crew testimony after the incident indicates little icing was seen on the fishing pot stack from the pilothouse. Also, the crew was unable to even access the starboard side of the fishing pot stack. These results corroborate testimony as the results show that the region with the heaviest icing is an area where the crew would not have been able to see nor access ice build-up, only a minute portion of the wind spray would even strike the top of the fishing pot stack, resulting in minor dry icing or a “glaze” of build-up as described in testimony, *National Transportation Safety Board (2021)*.

While the simulation incorporates CFD for modelling the airflow and droplet trajectory, it is only a snapshot of the time immediately before freezing begins to occur. However, it can be inferred that as the regions of higher concentration begin to ice, the resulting airflow will change and the resulting droplet trajectories, porosities, and water fluxes will change. This change affects the trajectories of the smallest droplets more than the larger ones. The larger droplets are less susceptible to environmental effects of the wind. However, it is likely the rate of icing will increase due to the increased coefficient of convection caused by the increased air velocities surrounding the icing regions. While the larger droplets are largely unaffected by the decrease in porosity, all water droplets will have a higher tendency to hit the fishing pot stack with a decreased porosity.

While the limitations discussed above exist in the icing model, it can be assumed that increased rate of icing due to the increased magnitude of the heat fluxes will force more water to freeze in the vicinity of the heaviest icing concentrations. Despite the simulation’s limitations, there is still high confidence in the results.

The results from the simulation are alarming. The amount and location of ice, 16.89 MT on the starboard beam of the vessel, approach the maximum assumed icing quantities on fishing vessels in both 46 CFR 28.550 and IS Code 6.3. For ‘Scandies Rose’, this would amount to 19.84 MT of ice, making the quantity of ice from this simulation, only on the outer edge of the fishing pots in only one hour, close to the regulatory requirements for uniform loading. From the simulations presented in this paper, these maximum quantities and assumptions should be reviewed.

6. Stability analysis of F/V ‘Scandies Rose’

An accurate stability analysis of the ‘Scandies Rose’, Fig.5, is crucial to understanding the capsizing mechanism of the vessel. Combining the icing data from the simulation results with automatic identification system (AIS) data and survivor testimony, four different stability scenarios were analysed.

Fig.5: F/V ‘Scandies Rose’

The estimated initial displacement and vertical centre of gravity of the vessel are 1072 MT and 4.01 m respectively with the centroid of the fishing pot icing located at 6.67 m aft of the bow, 7.14 m from the keel, and on the starboard deck edge, 15.18 m from the centreline of the vessel. In scenarios with ice, 16.89 MT of ice is added at this centroid. A 40-knot wind force applied 45 degrees off the vessel’s starboard bow models vessel operating conditions prior to the capsizing. During the stability analysis, the wind is shifted as the vessel turns to starboard in accordance with events of December 31, 2019. The stability scenarios are described in Table II.

Table II: ‘Scandies Rose’ stability scenarios

Condition	Ice (MT)	Wind (kn)	Trim (degrees)	List (degrees)	Draft (m)	Disp (MT)
Departure (no ice, no wind)	0	0	1.17 fwd	0	4.01	1072
Icing w/ 45° wind off STBD bow	16.89	40 stbd	0.99 fwd	3.75 stbd	4.06	1089
Icing w/o wind (no restoring moment from wind)	16.89	0	1.00 fwd	5.24 stbd	4.06	1089
Ice w/ wind as capsizing (upsetting) moment	16.89	40 port	1.88 fwd	178 stbd	-2.46	1089

6.1 Initial vessel condition (no Ice, no wind)

The initial vessel condition with no icing or wind results in a draft of 4.01 m and a displacement of 1072 MT. The vessel has no heel but a slight forward trim. This condition does not present any stability issues because it is representative of full load departure conditions without topside icing or wind. ‘Scandies Rose’ has a large righting arm and excess righting energy in this condition resulting in a very stable vessel.

6.2 Ice accretion after one hour (40 knot wind 45° off starboard bow)

16.89 MT of ice was applied at the centroid of fishing pot icing (6.67 m, 7.14 m, 15.18m) resulting in an increased draft of 4.06 m and increased displacement of 1089 MT. The slight increase in draft is due to the added weight from the ice. Since the ice is off-centre, the vessel develops a 3.75° starboard heel, but this may have not been significant enough to raise alarm with the crew, especially in heavy seas. Fig.6 shows that the vessel has an extremely low righting arm, suggesting the vessel is on the verge of instability. In fact, the vessel is deceptively unstable, with the wind off the starboard bow improving the heel and providing the mariners with a false sense of safety and stability.

Fig.6: ‘Scandies Rose’ righting arm curve with a 40 kn wind 45° off the starboard bow

6.3 Ice accretion after one hour (diminishing wind)

The effects of the wind on the stability of the vessel are observed as the ‘Scandies Rose’ turns to starboard and the wind shifts across the bow. This condition is modelled by a head-on wind which results in an increased starboard heel of 5.24°, demonstrating that the wind originally off the starboard bow created a restoring force that reduced the list of the vessel. Note that this condition was modelled as the

vessel turned through the wind, and at this point, the wind had no effect on the heel. The increased heel also caused the deck edge to submerge. The righting arm was reduced further, and negative between 16° and 30°. The righting arm curve experiences a zero crossing at ~5°, confirming it will sit at about a 5° heel. Fig. 7 also shows limited righting energy in this condition, and it is possible that a strong wave or other effect could induce a loll at approximately 30°. Depending on the location of the first non-watertight opening, or downflooding point, this condition would likely induce a catastrophic failure of the vessel's watertight integrity and could cause rapid capsizing from additional water ingress.

Fig.7: ‘Scandies Rose’ righting arm curve with head on wind

6.4 Ice accretion after one hour (40 knot wind 45° off port bow)

The final condition analysed was icing with the wind acting on the port bow, mimicking a turn to the north. In this scenario, the wind would act as a capsizing (upsetting) moment. With the heeling arm due to the wind on the port side and the weight of the ice on the starboard side, the vessel is unstable even in the hydrostatic condition. Fig. 8 shows the resulting righting arm of the capsized vessel. This analysis does not consider the downflooding point, where a loss of watertight integrity would cause rapid water ingress into multiple locations of the vessel.

Fig.8: ‘Scandies Rose’ with wind acting as a capsizing (upsetting) moment

7. Conclusions

The magnitude of ice on the ‘Scandies Rose’ using the methodology presented in this paper aligns with the icing quantities using other prediction techniques and survivor testimony. The icing location presented also corroborates survivor testimony, as Fig.4 shows little icing on the top of the fishing pot stack – the only visible location of the icing region from the bridge. However, this paper only analysed icing for one hour. If the simulation was run for the entire time the vessel was subjected to extreme sea icing conditions, it is likely that the predicted ice would exceed those other methods. In addition, this methodology considers non-uniform icing, a critical feature missing from other methodologies.

While the simulation is limited in scope to the outer edge of the fishing pots, it begins to show the location of the ice accretion. While the predicted vertical centre of gravity of ice is lower than the location prescribed by the regulations, the simulation showed that ice accretes off-centre, in a non-uniform fashion, with a vertical centre of gravity off the deck. Results indicate that the transverse centre of gravity of the ice impacted stability more than the vertical centre of gravity.

The icing estimations only represent one hour of ice accretion on the outer edge of the fishing pot stack, not the whole pot stack nor the whole vessel. The results are surprisingly close to the pertinent regulatory requirements for the ‘Scandies Rose’. The underlying assumptions of the regulations were not a scope of this paper; for example, it is not known how long the regulations allow for a vessel to be subjected to spray icing conditions before the master shall take evasive action to seek shelter or manually remove ice from the vessel.

The results in this paper only showcase the results after one hour with quasi-static computational fluid dynamic wind velocity data. Future work includes adding a feedback loop that would capture changes in the flow velocities as the fishing pot porosities change with icing. To do this, multiple fishing pot surfaces would be modelled, not just the outer edge of the pot stack. Both effects will likely cause ice to accrete at a faster rate than predicted in this paper.

Finally, the methodology presented in this paper should be applied to other vessels which transit in high latitudes. Of particular interest would be the fishing vessel *Destination*, a casualty which likely sank because of topside icing, *National Transportation Safety Board (2021)*. In addition, the U.S. Coast Guard is building new cutters which will operate in high latitudes such as the Polar Security Cutters. Other bow designs could be analysed as well, designing flare or bow rake to decrease the mass flux from wave impacts.

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Enhancing the 3D Approval Process using Functional Zones in Ship Design

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Abstract

Digitalising the class verification and approval process offers great benefits to designers, yards, and classification societies. By using the 3D model, the quality of the design and the review process can be significantly improved. 3D zones combining both functional and spatial requirements are used to identify and resolve regulatory requirements early in the design process. We demonstrate how this concept can be applied to describe the International Convention on Load Lines requirements for weathertight integrity as part of the loadline approval by the classification society. An end-to-end 3D experience reduces the risk of errors and inconsistencies, improves data quality and safety, and limits lead times and costs.

1. Introduction

1.2 From a sequential to an integrated ship design process

Traditionally, 3D CAD systems have been used in the later design stages of the project, mainly in detail design. Nowadays, major ship designers and yards have realised the importance of using a 3D solution for the basic (class) design, allowing for the review of previous decisions and facilitating the re-work tasks, *Pérez-Martínez and Pérez Fernández, (2021)*. The consequence of the objective of reducing costs and delivery time but maintaining and even improving quality has produced changes in all aspects of shipbuilding: construction process, project management process and design process. As a result, the ship design process has moved towards an integrated design process illustrated in Fig.1 where the 3D models have become the core of the design synthesis.

Fig.1: Integrated ship design process chart. Reproduced from *Pérez-Martínez et al. (2021)*

1.3 Use of 3D Models in the design process

It is a relatively novel approach to use the 3D model throughout the entire shipbuilding process, *Seppälä (2021)*. It is a commonly used and accepted way of designing highly complex ships. The use of 2D drawings has become increasingly outdated, and the order of creation has turned to the extraction of 2D drawings from 3D models, and not 3D modelling according to 2D documentation. This was not the case some 15 years ago when 2D drawings were the basis of ship design, approval, and production. In recent years, there have been significant shifts that were enabled by new computing technology and comprehensive access to 3D manipulation. It has provided numerous possibilities to avoid 2D documents. Examples of these include direct interfaces with CNC machines, welding robots and cobots, new options to submit 3D models for class approvals, and more. *Seppälä* identifies three major use cases for 3D models in the ship design process at the yard:

1. Boost for communication (project overview, handover, visualisation replacement of drawings)
2. Integration of information flows (Integration with ERP, PLM/PDM, planning systems and different stakeholders)
3. A platform for digital twins (consolidating ship management information with 3D dashboard)

Seppälä further concludes that the reality at shipyards is still far from the ideal situation with a myriad of specialized systems, interfaces, and data storage methods used in different departments. A step that would provide unification is the expansion of the use of the 3D model and increased interoperability between systems, thereby ensuring support for the specific needs of each discipline and shipbuilding process stage.

The Open Class 3D Exchange (OCX) standard, *Astrup et al. (2022)*, *Bitomsky et al. (2021)* is an example of a new development which aims to replace the traditional 2D drawings providing a more efficient way of exchanging 3D data between different software applications used in the shipbuilding industry. This initiative addresses use cases 1 and 2 in the examples listed by *Seppälä*. Although the OCX standard is still relatively new it has grown into a larger initiative supported by more than 30 stakeholders in the Maritime industry, <https://3docx.org/members>, already with real use cases, *Deltamarin (2022)* and *Damen (2023)*.

The standard has the potential to significantly improve collaboration and data exchange in the shipbuilding industry *Bitomsky et al. (2021)*, making it easier to design and build ships more efficiently and with higher quality. It is designed to be flexible, vendor-neutral, and adaptable to different workflows, making it easier for shipyards, suppliers, and other stakeholders to collaborate on shipbuilding projects. The digital exchange of rich 3D data models supports the integrated design process with many parallel activities illustrated in Fig.1. This enables all stakeholders to have access to at any time updated design information from a single source of truth.

Shipyards and classification societies should therefore modify the traditional design documentation and review process and enable a direct 3D digital classification process to improve the exchange of information between the different stakeholders and ultimately accelerate the classification process. To date, plan approvals for new-build projects have been based on conventional 2D drawings. An obvious next step is to extract the information needed for design approvals directly from the CAD 3D models and perform the entire review process digitally instead of manually. The authors will in the following sections demonstrate how the model-based approval can be applied to the loadline design and verification.

2. The International Convention on Load Lines (ICLL)

The International Convention on Load Lines (ICLL) *IMO (1968)* is a set of regulations that governs the minimum freeboard for ships, based on the ship's size and operating conditions. As part of the loadline approval process by the classification society, the ship's weathertight integrity must be

assessed to ensure that it meets the requirements of the ICLL.

It has long been recognized that limitations on the draught to which a ship may be loaded make a significant contribution to her safety. Seafaring nations have for thousands of years set limitations to how much cargo a merchant vessel could load – often marked on the side of the vessel in the form of a line, cross or circle. The modern institute of load line originates from Samuel Plimsoll’s pioneering work in the 1870ties on improving the malpractice of overloading vessels in the British merchant fleet. The first International Convention on Load Lines, adopted in 1930, was based on the principle of reserve buoyancy, although it was recognized then that the freeboard should also ensure adequate stability and avoid excessive stress on the ship's hull as a result of overloading. This international convention applies to almost all ships in international trade.

The regulations consider the potential hazards present in different geographical zones and different seasons. The technical annexe contains several additional safety measures concerning doors, freeing ports, hatchways, and other items. The main purpose of these measures is to ensure the weathertight integrity of ships' hulls below the freeboard deck.

The core principle of the load line convention is that:

- 1. The volume, including hull and superstructures that contributes to the survivability of the vessel, and how this volume is distributed, will determine how deep the vessel may be loaded
- 2. To prevent the ingress of seawater to these volumes in all sea and weather conditions.

This will ensure that the vessel:

- 1. Has the ability to lift itself out of the waves and not be broken down or torn apart by the sea,
- 2. Has the ability to get rid of green sea accumulating on deck and not to be pushed down by the weight of the water.
- 3. Can operate safely (sufficient navigating power) in rough weather conditions.

To apply the concept of using 3D ship modelling to improve the quality and speed up the design process for weathertight integrity, designers can create 3D zones that combine both functional and spatial requirements, such as the location of hatches, doors, and other openings (see Fig.2 for typical examples of opening and closing appliances), with the necessary regulatory requirements for weathertight integrity.

Fig.2: Typical opening and closing appliances

Designers can work closely with the classification society during the loadline approval process to ensure that the ship's weathertight integrity meets the requirements of the ICLL. By using a shared

virtual environment, designers can receive feedback and input from the classification society in real-time, reducing the time and effort required for the review process.

In the following, we will investigate how 3D approval can be used to check the requirements for opening and closing appliances that protect the buoyant (weathertight) volume of the vessel, such as doors, hatches, air pipes and ventilators.

3. The current design process

3.1 Designer's challenges

Moving from typical 2D drawings in Basic design, to a 3D model-centric design and engineering process, also in the early phases enables the designers to work more closely across multiple disciplines and design the vessel with all its features in one common environment/model.

It also allows the designers in the early phase to convey the design intentions /class requirements in the Basic Design model, making it easier for the engineers to follow those intentions in the later detail phase.

Depending on the agreed scope with the yard, the designer may just define a generic type of fittings and their approximate location in the vessel in Basic Design; or place each component with detailed attributes and exact coordinates in Detail/Production design.

In an early phase, it may be critical for the designers to clarify in which areas of the vessel certain types of fittings are allowed/not allowed. This may be more relevant for prototypes, or vessels where the definition of the zones/areas is not clear based on definitions in ICLL or class/flag rules. Defining 3D spaces or 2D boundaries in the 3D model that can be verified by the classification society in an early phase, would help the designers to follow those requirements when detailing the model and laying out the components.

Although many of the relevant components/fittings such as doors, windows, hatches, ventilators etc are placed in the model, they may not be available for the classification society today. Also, the components may contain data/attributes that are seen as relevant by the designer/yard but may not contain all the relevant data approval of the load line requirements by the classification society. The document requirement list from the classification societies and national authorities are partly built around 2D drawing or documents/lists. There are also the traditional expectations from the customers, yards and shipowners, that certain data are available in a certain format.

Currently, the designers are collecting data from multiple sources for approval of the location and types of all openings. Fig.3 shows an example of a loadline drawing or arrangement plan. Here 2D plan drawings (marked with rectangles A on the figure) are used to show the location of an opening/closing appliance. The data showing the individual appliance attributes are collected into tables (marked with rectangles B in the figure). Tables I-III show typical appliance attributes required by the classification society. It is a big task for the designer to keep the data on the arrangement/Freeboard Plan in sync with the continuously evolving design.

Table I: Typical data required for the verification of doors

ID	Material	Sill height	Height	Width	No of cleats	Window	Deadlight
D1	Steel	600	1700	800	8	Portlight	Y
D2	Aluminium	380	1700	800	6	Window	N
D3	GRP	380	1700	800	6	NA	N

Table II: Typical data required for the verification of hatches

ID	Length	Width	Coaming height	Closing type	Material	Ref. drawing/standard
H1	800	800	450	Cleats	GRP	NS2048
H2	1000	2500	0	Bolted	Steel	815-005

Table III: Typical data required for the verification of ventilators

ID	Type	Mounting	Coaming height	Size	Closing appliance	Coaming thickness	Brackets
V1	Gooseneck	Deck	760	200	Lid	8.8	Y
V2	Natural	Bulkhead	900	100x200	Hatch	10	N
V3	Gooseneck	Bulkhead	2300	168	Lid	8.8	N
V4	Mushroom	Deck	900	200	Screwdown	10	N

Fig.3: Example of a drawing prepared for the classification society

Keeping all data in one source, the 3D model and database, and creating a standardized way of collecting and sharing the required data would greatly increase the quality of the data, reduce the manhours for both designers, yards and classification societies and reduce approval time. It could also reduce the time need to inspect/verify the locations and types of the actual fitting physically on the vessel.

3.2 The classification society's challenges

The objective of ship classification is to verify the structural strength and integrity of essential parts of the ship's hull and its appendages, and the reliability and function of the propulsion and steering systems, power generation and those other features and auxiliary systems which have been built into the ship to maintain essential services on board – basically that the vessel is safe to operate.

Classification Societies aim to achieve this objective through the development and application of their own Rules and by verifying compliance with international and/or national statutory regulations on behalf of flag Administrations. Compliance towards the requirements of the International Convention on Load Lines is one of these international regulations that class societies verify.

To verify compliance towards the requirements of the International Convention of Load Lines, the classification societies receive multiple drawings and data with details of opening and closing appliances and appendages that need to be checked. Items that need to be checked are numerous, often several hundred on larger vessels. Attributes that are checked typically include coaming heights, thickness, type of material, type of closing, and direction of opening to mention a few, Tables I-III. Requirements are often linked to where the items are placed on the vessel, in general, more stringent requirements are applied in the forward part of the vessel and closer to the waterline. To check multiple attributes on numerous items is a simple but time-consuming and repetitive task, time that could be put to good use on more challenging classification tasks.

4. Zonal ship design

4.1 Functional zones

A zone is a spatial region of a ship. In a general sense, the boundaries of the zone can be arbitrary, but to maximize survivability, the zones of multiple distributed systems, as well as damage control zones, should be aligned. For shipboard distributed systems, this typically means the zone boundaries are the exterior skin of the ship and selected transverse watertight bulkheads. The zone boundaries may rise above the watertight bulkheads into the superstructure, or the superstructure may be composed of one or more zones independent of the zones within the hull.

A functional zone is a spatial region of the ship with a specific purpose. Functional zones are frequently used in ship design to identify regions with specific requirements. We see great potential for the use of functional zones in 3D CAD design to e.g. ensure that regulatory requirements are met and that the design intent is accurately captured. By assigning functional zones to specific regions of the ship in the 3D CAD model, designers and engineers can more easily identify and address potential safety hazards, fire risks, and other design challenges. Functional zones can be used in 3D CAD design to describe design intent and ensure regulatory compliance:

- easily identify potential safety risks and design appropriate safety measures to mitigate those risks.
- Fire protection: Functional zones can be used to identify fire zones and other areas that require fire protection measures, such as fire-resistant materials or fire suppression systems. This can help ensure that the ship meets regulatory requirements for fire safety.
- Watertight compartments: Functional zones can be used to identify watertight compartments and ensure that the ship meets regulatory requirements for watertight integrity.
- Escape routes: By assigning functional zones to escape routes, designers can ensure that there are appropriate means of egress for passengers and crew in case of emergency.
- Maintenance: Functional zones can also be used to identify areas of the ship that require regular maintenance, such as machinery rooms or electrical systems.

Incorporating functional zones into the 3D CAD model can also help streamline the design process by making it easier to communicate design intent between different stakeholders, including designers, engineers, and regulatory authorities. Additionally, it can help ensure that the design meets all relevant regulatory requirements, reducing the risk of costly and time-consuming design changes.

Functional zones can be perceived as a spatial allocation for design needs as well in addition to helping ensure regulatory needs. The designer can signal and ensure the items which are in the specific functional zone should fulfil certain requirements.

The ICLL regulations set requirements for opening and closing appliances exposed to green sea pressure. The regulations introduce two functional zones referred to as Position 1 and Position 2. The Marine Safety Committee gives a unified interpretation of the definition of Position 1 and 2 in the circular MSC.1/Circ1534, *MSC (2022)*:

“Regulation 13 – Position of hatchways, doorways and ventilators

For the purpose of these regulations, two positions of hatchways, doorways and ventilators are defined as follows:

Position 1 – Upon freeboard decks and raised quarterdecks, or other exposed decks * lower than one standard height of superstructure above the freeboard deck, and upon exposed deck * situated forward of a point located a quarter of the ship's length from the forward perpendicular that are located lower than two standard heights of superstructure above the freeboard deck.

Position 2 – Upon exposed decks * situated abaft a quarter of the ship's length from the forward perpendicular and located at least one standard height of superstructure above the freeboard deck and lower than two standard heights of superstructure above the freeboard deck.

Upon exposed decks * situated forward of a point located a quarter of the ship's length from the forward perpendicular and located at least two standard heights of superstructure above the freeboard deck and lower than three standard heights of superstructure above the freeboard deck.”

* "Exposed decks" include top decks of superstructures, deckhouses, companionways and other similar deck structures.

The interpretation of the regulations and identifying the location of positions 1 and 2 requires experience and a thorough understanding of the ICLL regulations. This becomes even more complex for ship types where the definition of the freeboard decks is difficult to determine, typically passenger and ro-pax vessels. It would greatly simplify the design and approval process if the position 1 and 2 zones can be defined in the 3D design model.

4.2 Example 1: Compartments

The spatial arrangement of the vessel is a crucial design objective in shipbuilding. It is a prerequisite for fulfilling the mission requirements and the watertight subdivision determines the vessel's survivability. Fig.4 depicts the 3D compartmentation of Hurtigruten “Fridtjof Nansen”.

Fig.4: Fridtjof Nansen 3D model of arrangement (spaces and compartments), Kongsberg Maritime

The schema definition of the vessel arrangement is already part of the published OCX schema, see *Astrup et al. (2022)*. The OCX schema can transfer the full 3D spatial compartment definitions including compartment metadata as purpose, content, filling heights air pipe heights etc. In a later section, we will expand the OCX definition of the compartments to define a generic zone representing a 3D volume or surface.

4.3 Example 2: hazardous zones

Ventilation inlets such as methanol tank outlets can be placed sufficiently far away from danger. This spatial zone will carry on the design intent as no ventilation inlets are allowed in that space, so any design mistakes downstream can be prevented with simple checks, see the illustration depicted in Fig.5.

4.4 Example 3: damage zones

Damage zones have certain requirements for penetration from a stability requirements point of view. Designers can define functional zones according to regulations and can locate penetrations based on this volume and any wrongly placed penetrations can be found with a simple check since that zone will carry its design intent.

Fig.5: Functional zones examples

5. The load line schema

5.1 Extending the OCX schema

The load line schema is defined on top of the OCX schema by using the W3C XML `xs:import` construct, *ImportSchema Example (2002)*. This allows for an easy way of adding any extension to the existing OCX schema as illustrated in Fig.6.

Fig.6: OCX schema building blocks

In addition, the load line schema extension for opening and closing appliances is assigned a dedicated namespace: `ocxeq` separating new entities from any of the referenced schemas.

This offers flexibility in both the development and maintenance of any schema extension as it separates the extensions from the underlying schemas. All the referenced schemas are versioned so any new versions of the referenced schemas will not impact the schema extensions.

Utilising the above principle gives a simple schema representation of the load-line extension with only two level 2 element types:

The `LoadLine` root element has two children element types:

- `ApplianceCollection`
- `SolasPosition`

see also Fig.7.

Fig.7: The load line schema extension

The `ApplianceCollection` contains all the instances of the exported opening and closing appliances, see Fig.9 in section 5.3 for a detailed description for the supported appliances. `SolasPosition1` and `SolasPosition2` represent the ICLL definition of the functional zones referred to as Position 1 and Position 2 in the regulations, *IMO (1968)*, see Fig.8 in Section 5.2 for a detailed definition.

5.2 The schema definition of the functional zones

The proposed load line schema extends the existing OCX 3D arrangement definition to support the general concept of zonal ship design or functional zones. This is done by reusing the existing OCX `Compartment` definition by using the OCX type `ocx:CompartmentFace` to define the functional zone boundaries or surface faces, Fig.8.

Each zone has an attribute `ocxLL:zoneFunction` defining the purpose or function of the zone. The schema defines 7 fixed values of the `zoneFunction`, see Table II. More values can easily be added when needed.

Fig.8: Schema definition of the functional zones

Table IV: zoneFunction values

Element	Description
Load-line	The Position 1 and 2 zones related to the ILLC regulations
Fire zone	Zones with fire protection requirements
Damage zone	Damage zones according to regulations
Gas zone	Zones exposed to hazardous gases
Hazard zone	Zones exposed to hazardous events e.g. dropped objects or explosions
Escape route	Escape routes for evacuation of passengers and personnel
UserDefined	None of the above functions

5.2 The schema definition of the opening and closing appliances

Fig.9: Schema definition of the opening and closing appliances

The authoring application will export the component types used in the 3D design model or mock-up. Each appliance type (Door, Window, Hatch ...) carry a set of common attributes and type-specific elements/attributes. The component geometry can optionally be given in the schema by a reference to an external file in the STEP format with the component geometry. This will allow the receiving application to display components in full 3D.

The properties defined for each appliance type have been determined based on current practice (see Tables I-III) and regulatory requirements.

The schema attributes of the `Door` appliance are listed in Table V.

Element	Description
<code>ExternalGeometryRef</code>	The <code>ExternalGeometryRef</code> element is used to point to an external geometry representation of the parent entity, in this case, an opening and closing appliance (door, hatch, ventilator ...)
<code>SillHeight</code>	The door sill height. Usually measured from the deck to the top of the sill.
<code>applianceTightness</code>	The tightness class of the opening and closing appliance
<code>applianceMaterial</code>	The construction material of the appliance
<code>applianceTypeId</code>	The maker type identification or another type code used for this appliance type
<code>maker</code>	The name of the maker producing the appliance
<code>fireClass</code>	The fire class assigned to the opening /closing appliance
<code>standardReference</code>	The applicable standard, if any
<code>drawingReference</code>	The reference to the maker drawing documenting the appliance type details
<code>hasWindow</code>	Whether the door has a window or not

Similarly, the schema defines the attributes of the window, hatch, ventilator, and side-scuttle appliance types. The 3D representation of typical opening and closing appliances are shown in Fig.10

Fig.10: 3D model of typical opening and closing appliances

6.” Fridtjof Nansen” Case study

6.1 The information flow

Hurtigruten “Fridtjof Nansen” is used in a case study to demonstrate the application of functional zones to a model-based approval process. The information exchanged between the designer and the classification society for the load-line verification and approval is carried out in two exchange rounds, see Fig 11.

Early stage: Functional zones

Later stage: Opening and closing appliances

Fig.11: Model-based transfer of information for the load line approval

6.2 Model-based approval of the functional zones

In the first exchange round the designer transfers the definition of the functional zones to DNV for the review by the classification society illustrated by the leftmost process flow in Fig.11 (`SolasPosition1` and `SolasPosition2` defined by the proposed OCX schema).

When the vessel arrangement has been defined in the designer’s CAD model, the designer will prepare the definition of the functional zones as shown in Fig 12. These definitions can now be exported as an OCX file and transferred to the classification society for review following the model-based information flow described in Fig.11. The classification society will review the transferred OCX file and check if the layout of the functional zones is in accordance with the requirements of the ICLL. The rendering of the transferred OCX definition of the functional zones is shown in Fig.13.

Fig.12: Position 1 and 2 based on ICLL requirements together with tanks and rooms below

Fig.13: Rendering of the OCX export of Position 1 and 2 for Fridtjof Nansen

Fig.14: Model based approval of the functional zone definition by the classification society

After the review, the classification society will provide direct feedback to the designer using the received 3D model as shown in Fig 14. The 3D comments are linked to the 3D model.

The designer will be notified that the classification society has published new comments. The comments can be readily available directly in the designer’s CAD tool.

6.3 Model based approval of opening and closing appliances

The designer can proceed with laying out the opening and closing appliances in the 3D model after the approval of the functional zones by the classification society. The designer will be confident that all the opening and closing appliances are positioned in accordance with the regulatory requirements. Fig.15 shows the positioned opening and closing appliances in position 2 zones in the CAD model.

Fig.15: Opening and Closing appliances inside the load-line functional zones

Fig.16: Typical ventilators and its attributes associated with load line requirements

Fig.17: Watertight door and design intent check by the CAD tool

The CAD system also holds the required attributes for the different appliance types. The designer will have to enter the values associated with that appliance instance, Fig.16. This ensures that the CAD 3D model is the only source for all loadline data.

In the case illustrated in Fig 17, the design intent associated with Position 2 zones is used to check certain attributes of the appliances which are positioned in this zone. In the Position 2 zone, the sill height should not be less than 300 mm according to the regulations. But here the door sill height is 200 mm which is not fulfilling the requirements and therefore highlighted by the CAD tool. By incorporating these simple rules in the CAD system, it is possible to avoid mistakes before the design documentation is sent for approval. In this way, the designer avoids costly rework and delays.

When the designer has completed the layout of all opening and closing appliances, it is time for preparing the load-line documentation for final approval by the classification society. This is now simply done by a press of a button to create an export of all the appliance positions and attributes on the OCX format as indicated by step 3 in the rightmost process flow in Fig 11.

The classification society will review the received OCX model and verify that the opening and closing appliances are correctly placed and fulfil the regulatory requirements. This model-based approval process is illustrated in Fig 18. The current model-based review process by the classification society is still a manual process and to a large extent follows the current drawing-based approval process. However, with the model-based transfer as described in this section there is a huge potential for automating many of the manual verification tasks that must be carried out today.

Fig.18: Model based approval of opening and closing appliances

7. Conclusions and further work

The model-based approval process for loadline requirements outlined in this paper demonstrates well that accompanying functional zones with specific design intents will enhance the approval process. Also, it will cut the time needed to prepare drawings where the model will contain all necessary information providing a “snapshot” of the status to the classification society. An additional benefit of working this way will enable the design to be more accurate and unintentional mistakes to be prevented on time via design intent checks of the models before any submission to class.

The full potential of a model-based loadline approval lies in the possibility to automate the verification of both the position and attributes of all opening and closing appliances. Figure 19 shows a mock-up of an automated loadline verification. Here, the received 3D model is used to create plan views with identification of the functional zones and the position of the opening and closing appliances are shown with symbol marks. All attributes are available in tables and the result of the automated rule checks are displayed. Automation like this will to a large extent replace the time-consuming manual verification tasks today carried out by the approval experts. In the future, such automated services may also be available to the designer/yards and can be implemented directly in the design tools.

Fig.19: Mockup of future automatic load-line verification and reporting

The loadline approval is just one example of the application of functional zones for model-based approval. As stated in Section 4, there are several zonal ship design functions which will benefit from a model-based definition as exemplified in this article. The proposed schema can easily be extended to cover all functional zones relevant to ship design and regulatory requirements

Overall, 3D ship modelling and model-based functional zone definitions can speed up the ship design process by enabling designers to identify and resolve regulatory requirements early on in the design phase, improving the design quality and reducing the likelihood of costly modifications during the construction phase.

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OCX on the Way from Research to Industry Practice

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Abstract

The OCX format was originally defined in a research project and has quickly gained interest from both users and tool vendors in the shipbuilding industry. Now it is on its way from a pure research demonstrator to industry practice. This paper illustrates the current status of the format, which is not only defined by the specification itself. Much more interesting is the format applied in the shipbuilding industry, the support available in IT tools as well as the consortium driving further evolutions.

1. Introduction

The OCX format was developed in the APPROVED program as a means to transfer shipbuilding information between partners in the ship design. The program finished with much more industry impact than seen in other research projects, as those software vendors added support to write and read OCX format to solutions. To keep that momentum after the completion of the research project, the OCX Consortium was founded to promote the use of the format and support further development of the format itself or applications using it.

This paper presents my view on the current situation around the OCX format and some implementation work which is now publically available for free. It takes a look from different perspectives like the development of the format and accompanying documentation, new use cases and software solutions with OCX support.

2. Organization

No matter how formal or informal a format is, some kind of organization is needed as an authoritative source and to foster further development. Well-known examples in the area of standard formats are off course the ISO (STEP, JT), the Khronos Group (Collada, GIFT), or Buildsmart International (IFC). The OCX Consortium was founded in May 2021 to play a similar role for the OCX format. The self-given charter mentions five main goals, <https://3docx.org/>:

1. Increase maritime safety through transparent design documentation and processing of data concerning the design, verification and inspection of ships and floating offshore assets.
2. Support the evolutions of the OCX standard and promote its use in the marine industry.
3. Establish Conformance Classes to approve that the files exchanged by an application are in line with the standard.
4. Act as a source of information on the development and implementation of OCX standard in the maritime industry.
5. Encourage implementation and use of software interfaces according to the OCX standard.

The OCX Consortium was started by the eight partners from the APPROVED project and gained now 31 members. Those members contain most major classification societies and ship-building relevant CAD vendors. Similar to other organizations, users from yards or design offices as well as academia is a bit underrepresented though. The last in-person meeting took place last year in November in Oslo, several interesting presentations could be found on the website.

1.1 Implementor Forum

One major decision in that meeting was to start an OCX Implementor Forum (IF). It is organized similarly to the one run by AFNet, PDES Inc and prostep ivip for the AP242 and JT standards. Fig.1 contains a rough overview of the organisational structure. The users (yards, design offices, classification

societies) are organized in the User Group, their main interest is to get interoperable solutions for their business. They drive the standard's development by requiring new capabilities. The implementor group contains software vendors supporting that format. Their main task is to ensure that their solutions are interoperable, but also to provide new proposals for the further development of the standard. The full members should act as a board to collect the requirements (from the business side) or improvement proposals (already as an implementable, technical proposal) and update the standard if needed.

Fig.1: Roles and interactions in OCX Consortium

In the AP242 IF interoperability plays a major role, there are bi-weekly meetings of the software vendors who are working on three major topics. One is the preparation of test data sets from their respective systems, which are used by the other vendors to check their solutions and vice versa. The second one is the creation of recommended practises documents, which explain how certain aspects should be written or read from a file. The total body of recommended practises documents is now at over 500 pages, see *Hirel et al. (2022)* for an example. The last is to formalize the rules from recommended practices as automated test cases. This allows a fast turnover, as one could check changes using those Schematron rules, <https://www.schematron.com/>, without reaching out to colleagues from other companies. Compared to the long-established interoperability in the AP242 world, the OCX world is still in its infancy. The kickoff meeting happened in mid-February. The proposals for test data, recommended practices and Schematron are published, but no feedback is available yet.

1.2 Resources

The information on OCX is currently concentrated on two publically available websites. The website of the OCX Consortium contains general information on the schema, example data as well as presentations from the meeting in November 2022. The schema itself and the ticket system to collect issues like bug reports or enhancement proposals are managed as a GitHub project, <https://github.com/OCXStandard/>.

The GitHub project is not only used to manage the source data of the project, read the OCX file schema. It also houses an issue management system, where one could find both issues on organization matters like the test data, as well as enhancements to the format itself. Write access to e.g. post an enhancement issue is available to members of the OCX consortium. Compared to the AP242 world, where the information is scattered in 10+ locations and even read access is mostly available only to (paying) members, this offers easy access for anybody interested in that matter.

2. New Use Cases

The original focus of the project was the transfer of vessel design data for approval by a classification society. As always when data is readily available, ideas and needs to use this for other use cases as well. In the long run, this will require enhancing the format, which is the very reason something like the OCX

Consortium is needed. They have to decide, if and how support for additional use cases is added to the format. As of today, some proposals are either voiced or are already backed by an issue managed in GitHub. Fig.2 shows an overview of the use case and their status concerning their readiness. Some of them are already contained in an issue and already for code review, whereas others are still in discussion with yards or software vendors.

As said in *Bitomsky et al. (2022)*, the use case “Transfer Vessel Design” is a major step ahead, but leads a bit to a dead end. All comments created at the classification society are sent back to the yard by mail, issue management system, slides with screenshots etc. This is an established practice, but somehow a media disruption. In GitHub, one finds my proposal for a simple extension to transfer comments associated with any item, including metadata like issuer as well as the viewpoint used by a person at the classification society. The classification societies already collect this information during the review process, so there is nothing to invent here. And many design systems are also able to show comments and render a predefined viewpoint, so adding this on their side is also a feasible task.

Similar ideas are currently circulated in the direction of surveyors or persons performing e.g. thickness measurements on board the vessel. With the current format, they already get a 3D model plus information on the expected scantlings, commenting capabilities are needed for the use case above anyhow. What is further needed in the format, is a way to transfer the task (what to survey or measure), comments on the findings as in the use case above and additional data e.g. on measured wall thickness. Information like thickness measurements is currently not supported by the schema, which leads to the typical choices to enhance an existing format.

The first way is to add specific items and attributes for each use case, in this example a specific attribute value for the measured plate thickness. The problem with this way is obvious when the next request comes to also transfer e.g. coating thickness, which quickly leads to a plethora of attributes. The alternative is to add only one specific item called e.g. *Measurements* and then add a general capability to associate data to it. Other standards like STEP, IFC, or JT offer this capability, as this enhances the usability of a standard for use cases not foreseen yet. A simple example is found in Listing 1 below.

Fig.2: Use Cases discussed or anticipated for OCX

Listing 1: Example using generic data concept

```
<ocx:Stiffener id="STF1" >
  <ocx:Measurements>
    <ocx:Measurement>
      <ocx:NumericData name="webThickness" numericvalue="13.2"
unit="u2" />
      <ocx:NumericData name="flangeThickness" numericvalue="13.2"
unit="u2" />
      <ocx:NumericData name="coatingThickness" numericvalue="22"
unit="u3" />
      <ocx:NumericData name="anyOtherData" numericvalue="42" unit="u0"
/>
    />
  />
```

Listing 2: Example for current point format and proposed compact format

```
<!-- current definition -->
<ocx:EndPoint>
  <ocx:X numericvalue="36000" unit="u2"/>
  <ocx:Y numericvalue="-7208.6661347532763" unit="u2"/>
  <ocx:Z numericvalue="1200" unit="u2"/>
</ocx:EndPoint>

<!-- compact format -->
<ocx:EndPoint coords="36000 -7208.6661347532763 1200 " unit="u2"/>
```

There are also some discussions about using the OCX information as a basis for some work preparation tasks. The contained information is of course not sufficient to cut plates or profiles, but there are other needs in work preparations requiring a simple 3D model available without too much effort. One such case is all kinds of manufacturing simulations. These often need information about the part shape, centre of gravity and sometimes additionally the assembly hierarchy. All but the assembly hierarchy is already found in the OCX file, so e.g. transportation simulations could be run with an out-of-the-box export.

The issue list contains an additional proposal from me to reduce the file size dramatically. All point coordinates are currently transferred in a very flexible, but also space-consuming manner. As shown in Listing 2, each axis has its wrapper element (X, Y, Z) and may use a different unit. A much shorter representation is found in the last line, it uses a compact representation without additional wrapper elements and references only one unit. In reality, all tools I know use the same unit for all three coordinates, the same string representation for a list of doubles is already used for the knot vector. This proposal may sound a bit pedantic, but files using the compact format shrink to less than half.

My driving force is the sheer size of real-world OCX files. They are so large, that programming editors like Notepad++ or Visual Studio Code either stop working completely or at least provide no more syntax highlighting or code folding on the XML. That proposal reduces the problem and costs roughly a day to implement for each vendor. A transition schema could first contain both serialization formats and phase out the lengthy format over the next 2-3 years.

3. Implementations

Currently, existing OCX implementations fall into three categories. Most users depend on OCX support in either their initial or basic design tool to provide the vessel information to the classification society. These are commercial-of-the-shelf (COTS) tools by yards and designers all over the world or additional OCX integration for these tools provided by companies like e.g. AITAC or PROSTEP. A second category contains custom-specific tools, e.g. often the tools implemented by classification societies

themselves. Both categories already existed last year, the freely available OCXReader library added a base library which could be used as a simple converter or base of a viewer.

Table I contains the information currently available and/or planned implementation of OCX interfaces in COTS design tools. It is based on publically available information, I hope to verify and update this with the respective vendors before the conference. On the member's page of the OCX consortium, one additional finds companies providing CAE, integration or visualization solutions.

Table I: Currently known OCX support in COTS design tools

Vendor	Application	Direction	Remark
AVEVA	E3D	Read/Write	
AVEVA	AVEVA Marine	Read	3 rd party PROSTEP
CADMATIC	CADMATIC Hull	Read/Write	
Dassault Systèmes	3DEXperience	Read	3 rd party AITAC
Hexagon	SM3D	Write	
NAPA	NAPA Designer	Read/Write	
SIEMENS	NX	Write	
SSI	ShipConstructor		Rumours
Several Vendors	MCAD	Read	3 rd party PROSTEP

In last year’s paper, we presented our prototype to visualize the OCX format. This prototype did not fully implement the standard, especially in the area of curved panels, but worked as a quick and dirty testbed. Based on that experience, our working student Paul Büchner and I implemented a new solution from scratch. It is based on the open-source CAD kernel OpenCascade and acts as a reader for the OCX format and renders the information into explicit geometry placed into an assembly structure closely related to the OCX format itself.

The OCXReader implementation could be used for free both in commercial solutions as well as for university or private projects. We applied the GNU Lesser General Public License v2.1 to it, allowing using it in both scenarios. It is housed on GitHub (see *Zerbst (2023)*) for easy download and code collaboration. The project’s build setup uses *vcpkg* and *CMAKE* and supports the platforms Linux, Mac OSX, and Windows. The result of the conversion resides in the OpenCascade’s own *OCAF* structure and could be written e.g. as a *STEP* model. This could be used to e.g. visualize it using a standard viewer or perform geometric calculations. An example of such a conversion to *STEP* is found in Fig.3. On the left one has the item structure, and on the right one sees the geometry, also rendered based on the information found in the OCX file.

Fig.3: Output of the OCXReader, showing the item structure on the left and create geometry

Fig.4: Different items created by the OCXReader

Fig.5: Converting OCX to 3D PDF allows on-board usage, e.g. for surveyors

The OCXReader itself supports all major items found in the OCX files. As seen in Fig.4, this includes the contained reference planes, reference surfaces, and most steel items like panels, plates, and stiffeners. A colleague from another shipbuilding software vendor became aware of this project and implemented the cutBy features, which draw both the used cutout contour as well as performing the cutout on panels and plates. Help from other vendors (e.g. to implement compartments or design views) will be welcome. In the long run, we are looking for an IT, shipbuilding, or engineering student to add a viewer application on top of the reader.

PROSTEP as a company offers OCX reading/writing capabilities for tools without built-in support. Import capabilities are available for AVEVA Marine based on the work already presented in *Sieranski and Zerbst (2019)*. Translation of OCX to generic CAD formats allows using the ship structure in common MCAD tools, e.g. as a reference geometry or for visualization. Other work includes e.g. a viewer is currently implemented for a customer based on the 3D PDF, Fig.5. The solution combines the OCX models with information from other sources in the company into one document. This document (Fig.5 shows only the neutral geometry) shows both the geometry as well as metadata as text associated with the geometry. Predefined view ports allow quick navigation in 3D, without the need for long zoom, pan, and tilt actions. The 3D PDF-based solution was chosen to support users working on the vessel, where no or little life connection is available.

5. Conclusions

The transfer of compartment and steel structure in ship design was hindered by a well-supported exchange format. The definition of the OCX standard and its implementation in major shipbuilding tools changed this situation on the technical side within the last few years. Some work remains to add support for more shipbuilding applications or create additional tooling, but this is relatively little compared to the already done work. This work is offered by third-party companies, an open-source solution is available as a building block as well.

The necessary support organization to support the usage of the standard and drive its further development was founded. The implementor forum as a part of this support structure was initiated in Q1 2023, the work on common test data and test rounds has not started yet. Now it is up to the users, to embrace this standard for their daily work e.g. in the exchange with the classification society or for other use cases.

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Operator Guidance Informed by AI-Augmented Simulations

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Abstract

This paper will present a multi-fidelity, data-adaptive approach with a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network to estimate ship response statistics in bimodal, bidirectional seas. The study will employ a fast low-fidelity, volume-based tool SimpleCode and a higher-fidelity tool known as the Large Amplitude Motion Program (LAMP). SimpleCode and LAMP data were generated by common bi-modal, bi-directional sea conditions in the North Atlantic as training data. After training an LSTM network with LAMP ship motion response data, a sample route was traversed and randomly sampled historical weather was input into SimpleCode and the LSTM network, and compared against the higher fidelity results.

1. Introduction

The safety of a ship and its crew in heavy weather and rough sea conditions demands proper operational guidance. Operational guidance is provided in the form of selection of speeds and headings, and is generally based on accessing ship motions response predictions from a pre-computed database or look-up table for a given condition. Operational guidance is an important consideration in the survival of a ship and has been the focus of many International Maritime Organization (IMO) publications, *IMO (1995,2007,2020)*. Recommendations for ship-specific operational guidance has been developed and discussed in the interim guidelines of the Second Generation Intact Stability by IMO, *IMO (2020)*. While these guidelines are certainly useful in design and at sea, they are not comprehensive.

The ocean environment is random and complex. Consequently, a pre-computed database cannot completely capture all ocean conditions potentially encountered. Accordingly, a computationally feasible approach is needed to estimate ship responses for a range of conditions.

A simplified approach for ship motion response predictions typically assumes a unidirectional seaway with a unimodal wave spectrum. However, realistic seaways typically encompass both wind and swell components that are can be delineated in terms of wave directionality and modal frequencies. Bi-directionality and bimodal spectra are common wave characteristics that are suitable for consideration in predictive ship response models.

Multi-directionality has been considered in *Yano et al. (2019)*, where wave radar data were invoked to generate a wave spectrum in simulations of a Ropax ship. By Grim's effective wave and a reduced-order roll equation, the maximum roll angle was estimated at various ship headings and multiple metacentric heights for the given directional wave spectrum. While the maximum roll angle is a useful metric, other seakeeping and structural response parameters are necessary for a more comprehensive investigation of extreme motions and loads.

Levine et al. (2022) described a data-driven model to evaluate predicted ship motions in unidirectional waves with a unimodal spectrum. In this study, data-adaptive Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks were investigated as part of a multi-fidelity approach incorporating Large Amplitude Program (LAMP), *Shin et al. (2003)*, and a reduced-order model known as Simple-Code. An initial assessment of this multi-fidelity approach focused on prediction of ship motion responses in waves. LSTM networks were trained and tested with LAMP simulations as a target, and SimpleCode simulations and wave time-series as inputs. LSTM networks improved the fidelity of SimpleCode seakeeping predictions relative to LAMP, while retaining the computational efficiency of a reduced-order model. The study was expanded in *Howard et al. (2022)*, to limited combinations of bimodal, bidirectional combinations.

In this paper, this data-adaptive approach employing LAMP, SimpleCode and LSTM neural networks is evaluated for prediction of ship motions in bimodal, bidirectional seas during a simulated voyage across the North Atlantic. Simulations are performed based on the David Taylor Model Basin (DTMB) 5415, *Moelgaard (2000)*, in the most common combinations of primary and secondary wave conditions observed in the North Atlantic. Then, random observations of primary and secondary sea states along a prescribed journey are used as input into SimpleCode, LAMP, and the LSTM framework and the seakeeping statistics and time series are compared.

2. Methodology

2.1. SimpleCode and LAMP

SimpleCode is a reduced-order seakeeping simulation tool that can quickly produce reasonable results, *Smith et al. (2019)*. One of the key simplifications in SimpleCode is in the local variation of wave pressure, where the hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov equations can use volume integrals instead of integrating over the surface of the ship, *Weems and Wundrow (2013)*. With pre-computed Bonjean curves, instantaneous submerged volume and geometric center, the sectional hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov forces can be computed efficiently.

LAMP is a higher fidelity simulation tool that considers the 6-DOF forces and moments acting on the ship implemented by a 4th order Runge-Kutta solver in the time domain, *Shin et al. (2003)*. Central to the code is the solution to the 3-D wave-body interaction problem. The perturbation velocity potential is solved over the mean wetted hull surface. Hydrostatic and Froude-Krylov forces are solved over the instantaneous wetted hull surface. Within LAMP, the nonlinearities considered in the solution can be altered through how the model is represented mathematically e.g., including body non-linear hydrodynamics or large lateral motions. The version of LAMP in the current application was LAMP-3. In LAMP-3, approximate body non-linear hydrodynamics with large lateral motions are accounted for. LAMP effectively estimated motions comparable to model tests, *Lin et al. (2007)*.

LAMP is computationally intensive relative to reduced-order SimpleCode. LAMP-3 can run at nearly real-time, though some parameters such as number of wave frequency components, free surface panel definition, and hull offsets can be adjusted and increase the computational effort. For example, generation of a single realization of a 30-minute epoch entails approximately 30 minutes of computational time. In contrast with the same number of frequency components, SimpleCode can run on the order of 5,000 independent realizations of 30-minute epoch data in 30 minutes of computational time, *Smith (2019)*.

From the perspective of fidelity, SimpleCode can produce an approximation to LAMP predictions when tuned radiation and diffraction forces are included, *Weems and Belenky (2018)*, *Pipiras et al. (2022)*. However, a fidelity gap still exists that can be potentially addressed using a data-adaptive machine learning method, *Levine et al. (2022)*, *Howard et al. (2022)*. In this paper, this method is applied to bimodal and bidirectional waves.

2.2. Long Short-Term Memory

An LSTM network, *Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997)*, is a type of recurrent neural network, which incorporates both short and long-term memory based on data-adaptive learning for estimation of a function. These memory effects are stored in weight matrices, which along with other operations, transform input matrices to target output matrices. The following set of equations show the operations that occur in a LSTM layer.

$$f_1 = \sigma(W_{f_1} x^{[t]} + U_{f_1} h^{[t-1]} + b_{f_1}) \quad (1)$$

$$f_2 = \sigma(W_{f_2}x^{[t]} + U_{f_2}h^{[t-1]} + b_{f_2}) \quad (2)$$

$$f_3 = \tanh(W_{f_3}x^{[t]} + U_{f_3}h^{[t-1]} + b_{f_3}) \quad (3)$$

$$f_4 = \sigma(W_{f_4}x^{[t]} + U_{f_4}h^{[t-1]} + b_{f_4}) \quad (4)$$

$$c^{[t]} = f_1 \odot c^{[t-1]} + f_2 \odot f_3 \quad (5)$$

$$h^{[t]} = f_4 \odot \tanh(c^{[t]}) \quad (6)$$

Here, W and U are weight matrixes, b are the bias vectors, $x^{[t]}$ is the input vector at time t , $h^{[t]}$ is the hidden state vector at time t , $c^{[t]}$ is the cell state vector at time t , σ is the sigmoid function, $\tanh()$ is the hyperbolic tangent function, and \odot represents the Hadamard product. The output or target at time t is equal to the hidden state vector at time t , $h^{[t]}$. The weight matrices and bias vectors are progressively adapted during the training process to minimize the specified loss between the training data and test data. Mean-squared error is the loss function to quantify the error between the training and test sets. The formula for the mean-squared error (MSE) is in the following equation, where

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_T(t_i) - y_L(t_i))^2 \quad (7)$$

Here, N is the number of points in the time series; y is the response matrix of the time series for heave, roll, and pitch; subscript T is the target time series, subscript L is the LSTM produced time series; and t_i is the i -th time instant in the time series.

The current framework encompassed three consecutive LSTM layers followed by a dense layer to transform the input into the target output. LSTM inputs were heave, roll, and pitch responses provided from SimpleCode as well as the wave elevation at the center of gravity of the ship at the ordered speed and heading and the corresponding slope of the wave field in the x- and y-directions to account for the bi-directional seas. The target time series were the heave, roll, and pitch motions predicted by LAMP in 6-DOF simulations. For higher fidelity accurate prediction of these vertical degrees of freedom (heave, roll and pitch), the horizontal degrees of freedom (surge, sway, and yaw) were included in the LAMP simulations. Subsequent training of the LSTM network specifically focused on the relevant target outputs for the heave, roll and pitch motions. A series of LSTM networks are trained on a given set bimodal data and then tested on different bimodal systems sampled across the North Atlantic voyage.

2.3. Experimental Set-up

Simulations were performed with the DTMB 5415, Fig.1, Table I, *Moelgaard (2000)*.

Fig.1: Rendering of the DTMB 5415

Table I: Primary parameters of the full-scale DTMB 5415

Lwl	142.0 m	Displacement	9,156.38 t
B	19.06 m	KG, from BL	7.71 m
T	6.51 m	LCG, from FP	72.1 m

To determine the scope of training data environmental conditions, the 100 most historically observed combinations of primary and secondary seas in the North Atlantic during a December were used. The historical records were sourced from Wavewatch III hindcasts run by the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, *Tolman (2009)*. The area defined as the North Atlantic is in Fig.2.

Fig.2: Bounds considered as “North Atlantic” to sample historical wave parameters

For this study, primary spectra characterizing wind-generated waves and secondary spectra characterizing swell were formed from ITTC (International Tow Tank Conference) spectra, *ITTC (2014)*. In addition, a ship speed of 10.0 kts was considered along with primary relative wave headings from 0° to 330° in 30° increments. In this paper, 0° is defined as head seas and 180° as following seas. Secondary spectra wave directions were determined based on the most probable difference between the primary and secondary sea directions.

SimpleCode was set to run in the 3-DOF (heave, roll, and pitch,) configuration while LAMP was configured to run in 6-DOF with a Proportional-Integral-Differential (PID) rudder controller. The difference in configurations between LAMP and SimpleCode can result in different global positions within respective runs due to SimpleCode being restricted in sway and yaw while the controller in LAMP attempts to keep the ordered heading but ultimately includes variations in position. As a result, the simulated ships experience different wave elevations and forces at the center of gravity. The distinction in experienced waves consequently causes phase shifts between the SimpleCode and LAMP time series that may increase as the simulation progresses and affect the LSTM performance. A 6-DOF version of SimpleCode with a similar PID controller to LAMP would mitigate the difference in experienced waves and likely improve performance. In the current structure, each realization was 1920 s (including an initial 120 s wave ramp-up) with a time step length of 0.05 s. In total, 5 realizations were generated for each of the 2,400 combinations of conditions in both SimpleCode and LAMP for training, validation, and testing.

LSTM networks were then trained based on simulations of the most observed North Atlantic in December bi-modal sea states in SimpleCode and LAMP. A network was trained for each of the 12 primary headings. From the 12,000 runs, 50 were randomly selected from each primary relative wave heading for training for each network, 25 were randomly selected for validation, and 25 were selected for testing. Table II details the hyperparameters in the training process.

Table II. Defining hyperparameters of the LSTM framework

Hyperparameter	Value
Time steps, N	18,000
Time resolution factor	9
Hidden state size	150
Number of LSTM layers	3

Once the LSTM network was trained, a Great Circle route between Norfolk, USA and Bergen, Norway was generated. Random samples of primary and secondary seas based on the same historical wave database histogram during the month of December were generated along the Great Circle path. The simulation length for both LAMP and SimpleCode were the same as in the training stage. For each observation along the generated path, five simulations were run in SimpleCode and LAMP for a constant ship speed of 10 knots. The SimpleCode time series were then standardized by the training data statistics run through the trained LSTM network. Histograms of the standard deviation of heave, roll, and pitch along the path for SimpleCode, the LSTM-corrected time series, and LAMP were compared. Additionally, the time series from SimpleCode, the LSTM-correction, and LAMP in the sea state with the largest significant wave height were compared.

3. Results

3.1. LSTM Training

The training and validation realizations for each network were randomly selected from combinations of the 100 most common combinations of primary and secondary significant wave height, primary and secondary modal period, and difference in direction between primary and secondary seas. The training success varied for each of the networks, which were partitioned by primary relative wave direction, as a result of variation in secondary sea heading. Prior to training, the SimpleCode input and LAMP target realizations were standardized by the training data statistics e.g., heave, roll, and pitch standard deviations and means. The training and validation error plot for the primary relative wave direction of 330° over 100 training epochs is in Fig.3. The loss in Fig.3 is the total mean square error between the standardized LSTM output and LAMP for heave, roll, and pitch.

Fig.3: Training and validation error for a relative primary wave direction of 330° over 100 epochs

The training and validation set sizes were limited by a single 4-GB Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) and by the length (19,200 points) of each realization. This limitation was the primary reason for randomly sampling realizations with different parameter combinations so that bias could be reduced without losing accuracy. Still, the not including more combinations of primary and secondary relative wave directions through increase in training and validation set sizes did affect overall performance – especially in cases where parameter combinations varied significantly from the training data set. However, the LSTM still provided an improvement in estimation of statistics compared to SimpleCode.

3.2. North Atlantic Journey Statistical Comparison

The primary goal of this study was to generate statistics for pertinent seakeeping motions in bimodal, bidirectional seaways common in the winter in the North Atlantic for operational guidance. An example

journey was plotted from Norfolk, USA to Bergen, Norway. The route was set through half-degree latitude and longitude grids for which weather data had been collected and was set to be the shortest distance possible, or a Great Circle route. The route is in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Adjusted great circle route between Norfolk, USA and Bergen, Norway

Over the route, primary and secondary wave parameters were randomly selected from historical weather observations from each latitude-longitude grid and the corresponding conditions were run in SimpleCode, LAMP, and through the trained LSTM networks. Although, the random selection of observations does not model the inherent dependence between wave parameters of adjacent/nearby grids, the imposed variation here provides a reasonable initial test of the LSTM networks. The standard deviation from each simulation was estimated over five, 30-minute realizations. The standard deviations from heave, roll, and pitch were tabulated, binned, and counted over the example voyage to provide a summary of the journey. Kernel density estimations of the standard deviation probability density functions (pdfs) for each considered degree of freedom are in Figs.5-7.

Fig.5: Heave standard deviation pdfs from SimpleCode, the LSTM networks, and LAMP

In each degree of freedom, SimpleCode generally over-predicts LAMP while the LSTM networks improve the estimation while generally under-estimating LAMP. In SimpleCode, the larger, more varied responses are likely due to the hydrodynamic forces being concentrated on strictly the presented 3-degrees of freedom. For example, all lateral forces acting on the hull in SimpleCode can only go into producing roll; when in reality, some of the produced movement goes into sway or even yaw.

Fig.6: Roll standard deviation pdfs from SimpleCode, the LSTM networks, and LAMP

Fig.7: Pitch standard deviation pdfs from SimpleCode, the LSTM networks, and LAMP

But since SimpleCode is constrained in the lateral frame in oblique seas, roll is over-estimated and varies widely. The LSTM improves upon SimpleCode in roll by not only moving the most probable standard deviation closer to the most probable LAMP standard deviation, but also in reducing the variation in standard deviation. The estimation of heave and pitch by SimpleCode is generally more accurate but is still larger than the LAMP estimates. Again, the LSTM mostly captures the peak behaviour seen in the LAMP observations and reduction in variation compared to SimpleCode but is generally leads to under-prediction.

Fig.8: Heave time series snippet centered about the largest LAMP heave response.

In Figs.5-7, the LSTM provided an improvement compared to SimpleCode with respect to LAMP in capturing the seakeeping summary. To further test the LSTM, the results from the worst conditions, defined as largest primary and secondary significant wave heights, resulting from the random selection of conditions over the journey were compared to LAMP and SimpleCode. In Figs.8-10, the time series from heave, roll, and pitch from SimpleCode, the LSTM networks, and LAMP are compared for a primary significant wave height of 3.0 m, a primary wave period of 6.5 s, a primary wave direction of 240°, a secondary wave height of 1.5 m, a secondary wave period of 11.5 s, and a secondary wave direction of 330°.

Fig.9: Roll time series snippet centered about the largest LAMP roll response.

Fig.10: Pitch time series snippet centered about the largest pitch heave response.

In Figs.8-10, the LSTM improves in level of response and phasing similarities with LAMP compared to SimpleCode. The LSTM predicted standard deviations from these selected time series compared to LAMP improved with respect to SimpleCode. In roll, the absolute percentage error of the LSTM estimated standard deviation compared to LAMP was 34.7% but it is a significant improvement to the 193% error in the SimpleCode roll standard deviation. The LSTM also generally captured the LAMP peak, which is centered in each time series snippet, in each degree of freedom in both location and magnitude.

4. Conclusion

Accurate predictions of the ship motion statistics are vital for operational guidance. When considering bimodal, bidirectional sea spectra, estimates of the ship response are not simple. Furthermore, generating response statistic lookup tables as functions of the many combinations of parameters sourced from high-fidelity simulations is computationally prohibitive. A data-driven approach to capture the high-fidelity response while taking advantage of lower-fidelity tools can provide a potential answer.

In this paper, LSTM neural networks were trained to improve low-fidelity, 3-DOF hydrodynamic simulations in bimodal, bidirectional seas run by SimpleCode to estimate the 3-DOF seakeeping motions of interest sourced from higher-fidelity 6-DOF hydrodynamic simulations in the same bimodal, bidirectional seas run in LAMP. Networks were trained with the most common combinations of wave parameters in the North Atlantic in December. The networks provided improved estimates of the statistics relative to LAMP compared to SimpleCode. Incorporation of the inherent dependence between the wave parameters of adjacent/nearby grids could help demonstrate the utility of fast SimpleCode-LSTM seakeeping predictions along realistic routes for path planning.

While the current LSTM framework improved upon SimpleCode, the flexibility and accuracy could be increased by expanding the size of the training and validation sets. Running the training on a larger/multiple GPUs or a more optimized set-up would allow for more variation in training and validation data. These more comprehensive training and validation sets would not only improve the network by increasing the amount of data but also general flexibility.

Additionally, a future 6-DOF SimpleCode could enhance the performance of the LSTM. The fuller accounting of force distribution could potentially allow the LSTM to focus on other improvements to reduced-order SimpleCode predictions.

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Towards Refining Related Ferry Operational Patterns with Unsupervised Learning - A Case Study

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Abstract

When retrofitting ferries with batteries the importance of similarity in operational patterns amongst officers is imperative and worthy of investigation. In the optimal world it ought to be virtually impossible to distinguish between said patterns, as we would expect all officers to exhibit rather equivalent operational actions. Previous work has shown the ability to identify several different pattern groups during the maneuvering phase, implying the possible identification of a particular individual or groups of individuals. The pattern groups were found merely using propulsion power - plotted as line graphs; and the use of unsupervised machine learning. In this article we will qualify the findings of the previous work and continue pursuing ground truth and a high degree of robustness with as few parameters as possible.

1. Introduction

Denmark maintains multiple climate goals among which a 70% carbon emission reduction by 2030 compared to 1990. By 2050 Denmark should maintain carbon neutrality by capturing or offsetting at least as much carbon as emitted. The transport sector in Denmark accounts for approximately 29% of the total climate gas emission or 13.5 mil ton CO₂e by 2019, *KF21 (2021)*. Toward 2030 a reduction is expected from road transport while domestic sea transport, including ferries, is expected to remain largely unchanged.

Fig.1: CO₂ emissions per fuel unit and per kWh of Electricity, *DEA (2021)*

One method to reduce the carbon emission from domestic sea transport is a shift of propellant from traditional use of marine diesel to battery or hybrid electric propulsion. Especially the former will eliminate local emissions of both CO₂, PM, NO_x and other substances. CO₂ emission will, depending on the calculation method, be reduced to average for electricity production or down to zero.

According to the Danish Energy Agency, Fig.1, average CO₂ emission for electricity production amounted has decreased from >900 g/kWh to ca. 200 g/kWh over the course of 21 years. With current political goals for increasing wind capacity in Denmark even further, that number may decrease in the future.

1.1 Background

Denmark has a coastline of 8509 km, an area of 42.931 km², which is a coastline-to-area ratio of 0.198, and 391 islands, *Danmarks areal, folketal og kystlinje (2017)*. Naturally Denmark is home to a significant number of domestic ferries ranging from small vessels able of carrying just one car to large HSC catamarans travelling >30 knots, carrying >1000 passengers. In total the fleet of domestic ferries emit approximately 70.000 CO₂e per year, *KF21 (2021)*.

In an effort to provide year-round ferry services to less inhabited islands as well as effective transport links between rural areas, a significant portion of ferry routes are either publicly operated or operated by private companies under government contracts and subsidies. Two such contracts for the links between the islands of Fyn and Als as well as to/from the island of Samsø were awarded in 2022. Both contracts stipulate that electricity must be the propellant, further requiring that the electricity must origin from renewable sources and thus result in 0 g/kWh CO₂ emission, *TM (2023a,b)*.

As a result of these contracts the construction of two new 116 m fully electric ferries have begun in a shipyard in Turkey. The two ferries are intended to be delivered with autonomous systems enabling both autonomous crossing as well as auto docking, *Hovgaard (2022)*. The shift towards more electrically powered ferries on a larger scale in Denmark further inspires the ongoing debate on battery conversion of the ferries LANGELAND and LOLLAND as discussed in *Mikkelsen and Stochholm (2021,2022)*.

1.2 Towards longer harboring intervals

If the company owning the ferries LANGELAND and LOLLAND decides to retrofit batteries, the importance of long, uniformly shaped harboring intervals becomes crucial to make sure there is sufficient time for recharging. As we showed in *Mikkelsen and Stochholm (2021)* harboring intervals vary quite significantly from crossing to crossing, and thus we need to identify the right measures to take to bring harboring intervals to uniformity. One way to achieve more uniformly timed harboring intervals between crossings might be if all operators exhibit similar sailing patterns, which according to the crew is already the expected case. Crew members express an anticipation of a high degree of similarity between sailing patterns. Apparently, some crew members expect differences to be so small that they do not even play a role and instead hold the traffic or weather accountable for the differences. There will of course always be traffic and weather conditions which affect the crossings, and which cannot be avoided.

However, if we disregard these factors, and merely look at the maneuvering phase of the crossing, what can then factually be claimed about maneuvering patterns at this time? How great are the differences within these patterns? Is it possible to identify some kind of common operational style? Do operational styles affect the amount of time in harbor? And could training maybe help this out?

At the time of writing, we do not know, merely looking at line graphs of propulsion data, what constitutes a perfect or even good maneuver, although it is likely and fair to assume that consistency plays a key role. Therefore, comparing the maneuvering phases of the crossings and positively identifying similarity and differences within patterns is the first step towards the definition of a good maneuver, which can then serve as a best practice for training new crew members, or as input to a speed pilot (see Ch.5).

If it is true that all officers exhibit a high degree of similarity in the operational patterns, it ought to be virtually impossible to separate maneuvering patterns amongst officers. *Stochholm and Mikkelsen (2022)* attempted to cluster variations within ferry operational patterns without explicit knowledge of the ground truth, i.e., knowledge of who operated the ferry at a given time or even the number of operators that operated during the investigated period. With the help of unsupervised machine learning we were able to create a prediction of a possible shift schedule, merely by comparing similarities within operational patterns. We have since been given access to the actual shift schedule, Fig.2, and will

compare our initial prediction to the ground truth as well as trying different approaches of getting closer to the ground truth.

2. Analysis

2.1 Reading the shift schedule figures

Table I compares different improvement attempts we have made, but before we look at the comparisons, it is necessary to understand how to read Fig.2 which are the basis for our study. Fig.2 shows two inherent figures side by side. The figure on the left is the predicted shift schedule presented in *Stochholm and Mikkelsen (2022)* our so-called baseline, the figure on the right is what we consider to be the ground truth i.e., it is the actual shift schedule from a randomly selected month of ferry operation. Our prediction is made on the same randomly selected month. The ordinal numbers in the bottom of the figure indicate at what hour the ferry left the harbor in Tårs, but we are clustering the patterns based on the similarity expressed while maneuvering into the opposite located harbor, namely Spodsbjerg. E.g., the second square in the leftmost figure in Fig.2, which has the number “3” attached to it and which is gray in color, represents the crossing from Tårs to Spodsbjerg starting at eight o’ clock in the morning in Tårs, but the actual maneuvering which we study is the maneuvering into the harbor of Spodsbjerg. All the white squares with a “-1” printed on them are times the ferries didn’t operate. It is important to know that the ground truth shows that six different operators have been operating the ferry toward Spodsbjerg during the examined period, whereas the baseline only uses five clusters. The baseline was created without the knowledge of the number of operators in question, which of course will affect the amount of similarity between the two. All improvement attempts succeeding the baseline use six clusters.

Since the baseline shift schedule is based on unsupervised learning, the digits printed on each square are automatically generated every time a new prediction is made. The digits simply specify which individual maneuverings belong together in a cluster, while not specifying any similarity to clusters with the same cluster digit in other figures, and as such, should not be compared across figures. For instance, the turquoise color has the digit “1” assigned to it in the leftmost figure, while the same digit is assigned to the orange color in the second figure, however, this is not indicative of their relationship. The colors on the other hand are exactly to be compared across the figures. The colors are added subsequently to the clusters, so it is possible to visibly identify likeness between figures in order to signify where the highest amount of overlap between prediction and ground truth occurs.

Fig.2: From left to right: 1. Our first attempt at clustering maneuvering patterns *Stochholm and Mikkelsen (2022)* – aka the baseline. 2. The ground truth.

2.2 Observations

We can observe several things from Fig.2. The most apparent observation is probably how easily identifiable the yellow cluster is when comparing baseline and ground truth. If one were to stack the two figures on top of each other, applying a high degree of transparency to the upper one, there would be quite a clear overlap on the yellow squares (instances of maneuverings), while for instance yellow and green wouldn't convey much overlap. It is, however, important to mention that this is not an indication of whether the yellow cluster exhibits a good or bad way to maneuver the ferry, simply that it is different from the way other officers maneuver the ferry while maintaining a high degree of consistency - and consistency *may be* indicative of quality. Another thing to note is the amount of orange and blue in the ground truth image. These two officers have not had a lot of sailing time in the given month. Clustering algorithms may be affected by unbalanced datasets and thereby cluster the maneuvers wrongly. Although there exists a high degree of consensus between the two schedules (especially the yellow and turquoise colors seem to overlap quite a bit respectively), it is still quite difficult to say exactly how identical the two schedules really are merely by looking at them. We will explore this below.

3. Method and Results

3.1 Creating a model

The baseline uses only knowledge of propulsion power and the effect of the angles on the thrusters during the entire maneuvering phase for its representation of what constitutes a maneuvering. Many other factors, such as the number of generators running, could just as well have been added, but we wanted to keep the number of features to a minimum in order to be able to apply the model to other ferries in the future while keeping the model simple. By looking at the angle of direction of the thrusters compared to the direction of the ferry, we can tell whether the thrust is applied for speeding up or for breaking. An example of how we have applied the angles to the thrust can be seen in Fig.3. The result is afterwards mapped to Gramian Angular Fields (GASF+GADF) and Markov Transition Fields (MTF) in order to be able to apply convolutional neural networks on the timeseries data for the extraction of latent spaces as explained in *Stochholm and Mikkelsen (2022)*.

Fig.3: Applying the angles of the thrusters to the line graphs of propulsion power; see *Stochholm and Mikkelsen (2022)* for a more in-depth description.

3.2 Adding single value features

As mentioned above if we want to add more features to the image, they must also be continuous throughout the maneuvering phase, such as the case for the number of generators running. However, according to *Singh et al. (2020)*, convolutional neural networks are very susceptible to color toning, and since our model is based on the abilities of convolutional neural networks, this means there is a possibility of adding single value features to the images by toning the images according to this factor. This could for instance be used to apply the overall fuel consumption for the given crossing as a factor to an otherwise dynamic figure constituted of continuous variables. An example of color toning can be seen in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Example of the same maneuvering with overall fuel consumption toned in the rightmost image

3.3 Advancing toward the ground truth

As could be seen in Fig.2, our baseline model is not completely without fault, so in this section we describe the different attempts we have made in order to close the gap between model and ground truth, still using as few features as possible. Later we will compare the results of the different attempts.

3.3.1 Improvement attempts:

1. **6 clusters.** In our first attempt towards the ground truth, we have increased the number of clusters to six instead of five. The reason for this change is that we now know how many different officers have been operating the ferry during this particular month, and we expect that the correct number of clusters should result in a better prediction. All improvement attempts succeeding this, apply their changes to this decision.
2. **Color Toning.** In our second attempt we have toned in the overall energy profile per crossing as a factor to the GADF, GASF and MTFs, so the image gets darker or lighter depending on the overall energy profile for the specific crossing, compared to the standard images (as shown above in figure 4). The reason for this is that we suspect that there could exist a correlation between fuel consumption and maneuvering patterns. Since our model applies convolutional neural networks in order to identify patterns, we can only add in scalar values through toning of the images.
3. **Window size.** In our third attempt we changed the size of the window considered to be the maneuvering pattern from 10 minutes to 5 minutes in order to zoom in more on the interesting part of the maneuvering. Also, instead of starting the window at a specific coordinate and then adding 10 minutes to it (as done in *Stochholm and Mikkelsen (2022)*), we decided to end the window the first time the ferry reaches a track speed of zero and moving backwards five minutes from there, thereby eliminating the possibility of capturing part of the harboring phase rather than the actual maneuvering phase.
4. **Separate factors.** In the fourth attempt we decided to keep thrust and angles as separate factors in our plot instead of combining them. We created line graphs in which thrust, and angles were separately plotted into a single diagram (as opposed to the other approaches where angles are allowed to affect the thrust diagrams directly as shown in figure 3 above), whereafter they were mapped into two-dimensional GADFs, GASFs and MTFs, just as with the original approach.

3.3.2 First attempt

Fig.5 shows the attempt to apply six clusters instead of five as this should reflect the number of officers operating during the month in question, no other changes have been applied to this figure. Blue and orange clusters are randomly spread out and highly overrepresented when compared to the ground truth, however the data merely represent a single month, which means that not every officer maneuvers the ship an equal amount of time. Blue and orange clusters are not represented as much in the dataset, which gives us less of a possibility to recognize their styles. The clustering algorithm is unaware of this fact, and it therefore has no way of knowing how many crossings to assign to each officer. This, of course,

will skew the results of the other clusters as well, since these will be affected by how the algorithm chooses to cluster blue and orange.

Fig.5: From left to right: 1. Applying six clusters instead of five, 2. The ground truth.

The inherent figures within Fig.2 and Fig.5 can be quite confusing to look at, and it is difficult to visually assess whether the 6-cluster approach in figure 5 is performing better or worse than the baseline shown in Fig.2, and so in order to know how much of an improvement any optimization attempt might add to the result, we have built confusion matrixes for every optimization attempt as shown below.

Fig.6: Confusion matrix of the overlap between clusters in prediction and ground truth – for 6 clusters

The confusion matrix in Fig.6 shows how well the 6-cluster attempt did in relation to the ground truth. The rows represent our predictions, and the columns represent the true labels. A perfect match is if all values end up on the diagonal line. Darker colors mean high degree of coherence, although the scales are different in each matrix, and should not be compared with other matrixes. The turquoise cluster is easily identifiable, since there is a high degree of overlap (many true positives) and few false positives (other values in same column) and also few false negatives (other values in same row), the same is true for the yellow cluster. It is also clear that we assign way too many predictions to the orange and blue clusters as expected when considering Fig.5. The overall impression is that the 6-cluster approach is doing quite well, although there is still room for improvement. We expect that in order to achieve a better result, we could apply the model to a greater amount of data. Besides this, we can also see that turquoise is most often confused with the green cluster; however, the green cluster is only rarely confused

with the turquoise color, and so we cannot deduce from this that the two clusters are similar in their styles.

3.3.3 Confusion matrixes

Instead of showing all the shift schedules for the different attempts we will only show the confusion matrixes, which will give a much clearer possibility of comparison for strengths and weaknesses of each approach.

Fig.7: Confusion matrixes for all the different attempts

What we can immediately notice is that all confusion matrixes seem to be able to identify some clusters well, and usually this refers to the yellow and turquoise clusters, but also gray is occasionally well identified. ‘Color Toning’ and ‘Separate Factors’ seem to bring more confusion to the table and maneuvers with these factors included are not as easily discernable. Note that since the baseline only has five clusters the diagonal is shifted one column sideways.

When looking at the confusion matrix for the ‘Color toning’, Fig.8, it is quite striking that green and gray are often confused (shown by the four red circles). This could indicate some similarity between the two operators especially regarding the amount of energy used on the crossing, since this pattern of inter-cluster confusion is not as easily observable in the other confusion matrixes, and since this is the extra feature added in the present case. It can of course also indicate similarities within the weather for the days green and gray were operating, which affects the amount of energy needed to operate the ferry. Yellow and turquoise are still very clearly discernable from the other clusters.

Fig.8: Confusion matrix for color toning

3.3.4 Calculating the best attempt

In order to figure out which attempts added most value to the results we can calculate Precision, Recall and F1-score.

Precision is the ability to identify only the relevant data points, or mathematically: $PRE = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$

Recall is the ability to find all the relevant cases within a data set, or mathematically: $REC = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
 F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall or mathematically: $F1 = 2 \frac{PRE \cdot REC}{PRE+REC}$

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
orange	0.01923	0.11111	0.03279	9
gray	0.66667	0.27451	0.38889	51
yellow	0.80556	0.67442	0.73418	43
turquoise	0.71429	0.54054	0.61538	74
green	0.42308	0.32353	0.36667	68
blue	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	12
accuracy			0.41245	257
macro avg	0.43814	0.32068	0.35632	257
weighted avg	0.58536	0.41245	0.47537	257

Fig.9: Precision, recall and f1-score for the 6-clusters attempt

Fig.9 shows the calculated scores from the confusion matrix in Fig.6. And while a weighted average precision of 58.5% may not seem like much, remember that by mere chance we would ultimately end up at 16%. Again, it is interesting to look at the yellow cluster, which in and of itself has a precision of 80.6%, and this model performs very well not only on yellow, but also on turquoise and gray.

We can now calculate precision, recall, and f1-score for each attempt. As we can see in Table I, the baseline has the best recall score (in bold font), whereas the 5-minute window approach has the best precision and f1 score (in bold font). However, fewer clusters will often result in better recall, since we are better able to find all the relevant cases we are looking for. So, it is more interesting to look at precision, which tells us how good we are at identifying only the relevant data points. The higher recall also tells us that there are cases that are difficult to separate, meaning, some operators expose similar styles, which is a good thing if the common style expressed is an efficient operation, but that is beyond the scope of this paper to decide, even so in future research it would be interesting to investigate this further for instance by also comparing the value of rounds per minute on the thrusters as well as longitudinal speed of the ferry, since these parameters might help qualify styles.

Table I: Comparison of which attempts have had an effect

Model	Baseline	6 clusters	Color Toning	5-min Window	Separate factors
Precision	0.48003	0.58536	0.44039	0.60758	0.45305
Recall	0.43969	0.41245	0.36965	0.42412	0.42023
F1	0.44889	0.47537	0.38556	0.49129	0.40706

Albeit, the question remains how this relates to pure chance, and for this we apply Cohen's kappa score. Kappa statistics are normalized statistics with values between 0 and 1. Larger values of Kappa indicate better reliability of the classifier. For the same classification task, Kappa statistics can be used more reliably to compare between different models.

Table II: Comparison of Cohen's Kappa score

Model	Baseline	6 clusters	Color Toning	5-min Window	Separate factors
Cohens kappa	0.29643	0.29187	0.22896	0.30938	0.28483

Not surprisingly, the 5-minute window has the highest kappa score, which is suspected since it also did best on the precision and f1.

According to *Landis et al. (1977)* kappa score can be compared to Table III.

Table III: Amount of agreement between attempt and ground truth according to Cohen’s Kappa score

Kappa	Agreement
< 0	No agreement
0.01 – 0.20	Slight agreement
0.21 – 0.40	Fair agreement
0.41 – 0.60	Moderate agreement
0.61 – 0.80	Substantial agreement
0.81-1	Almost perfect agreement

According to the Kappa metric, all our models end up in the fair agreement section, which leaves quite a bit of room for improvement, but still much better than pure chance.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

After being given access to shift schedules, which function as the ground truth of who operated the ferry at a given time, we can conclude that we found what we expected, but not what we were hoping to find. In other words, we expected operators to show distinctions in their maneuvering styles in a way that would make it possible to cluster by style, but we were hoping to find that operators were so identical in their maneuverings that it would be almost impossible to tell them apart. We showed that it is indeed possible to cluster maneuvers using thrust and thruster angles combined – by applying unsupervised machine learning. However, some operators exhibit a much more profound consistency and are much more easily identifiable than others. We don’t yet know if this is a beneficial maneuvering style, only that it is consistent. Furthermore, we showed that some operators were more frequently confused, which might indicate a similarity in styles between operators, although this can also be due to external factors such as weather conditions. We also found that the exact window of operation is very important in order to compare styles.

One of the reasons the identification of maneuvering patterns may be difficult is because operators may swap seats during the crossing, according to the crew members, this happens occasionally. There are many reasons for seat swapping, but one common reason is practice motives, e.g., if an operator needs to practice harboring the opposite harbor of his usual crossing. No one knows how often this happens and it isn’t logged anywhere, but a cautious yet reasonable guess would be that about 10% of the overall number of crossings are affected by seat swapping, but the number could be much higher on smaller datasets. This means that we can’t be fully confident that our ground truth is actually the ground truth. It merely represents the watch schedule as it is saved in the system, which also means we may be doing much better or much worse than first estimated.

Even though color toning has a profound effect on the clustering algorithm’s ability to group similar images, it turns out that this has a negative effect in our case. We may conclude that there is no correlation between the overall amount of energy spent on a crossing and the maneuverability pattern. As it turns out, the sea current is commonly north going which means that operators going towards Spodsbjerg will receive a boost while operators toward Tårs will have to spend more energy going against the current. In our case we have only looked at operators toward Spodsbjerg, but it will be important to keep in mind when scaling up the experiment.

Also, since the blue and orange operators are so underrepresented in the data, it is likely that they affect the results a lot. Therefore, it would be helpful to look at data for a longer period.

5. Future work

Going forward it is anticipated that mapping and analysis of data along with literature review of previous attempts at optimizing energy usage and performance can lead to a comprehensive speed profiling for various sections of the route.

Basically, the route consists of four segments. Going east to west (from Tårs or Spodsbjerg) those segments are:

1. Maneuvering, departure Tårs + Navigation in dredged channel.
2. Shallow water (<10 m), cruising east-south-east.
3. Deep water, cruising east-south-east.
4. Shallow water (<10 m), approach to Spodsbjerg.

Fig.10: Snippet of a chart covering the area with route and shallow water marked

Should the ferries be battery converted, charging time in port is, presumably, essential to the efficient and timely operation of the link. Numerous factors affect the energy consumption during a crossing; wind, current and water depth being paramount, but also traffic and consequent divergence from the shortest route is a factor.

Surface current see a prevailing north bound flow of water at speed between 0.5 to 1.5 kn, or ~0.25 to 0.8 m/s, but currents may reach speed exceeding 4 kn or 2 m/s north or south bound depending on weather conditions and previously passed wind systems. Strong surface currents (>2 kn) may cause significant increase to resistance and drift angles in excess of 10° to maintain course over ground requiring increase in power consumption when travelling against the current. But also constituting a gain when travelling downstream.

Future analysis of consumption data and thruster power and angel setting in conditions with strong currents may shed light on possible effects of accepting a longer crossing distance by following the current at sections with high current speeds, the returning to route over more shallow water where current speeds are usually slower.

Regarding the speed pilot, the hypothesis is that a speed pilot, combined with battery electric propulsion, eliminating the need for selection of number of generators to be operated, can make continuous calculations on required speed and thus frequent adjustments of thruster power. And do so more efficiently than the human operator.

For the speed pilot to perform efficiently a more comprehensive analysis of power consumption correlated with water depth, wind speed and direction and current speed and direction may be needed. It is therefore predicted that several standard scenarios should be identified, in terms of wind and current, and further analyzed to build an algorithm that can interpret aforementioned logged performance data to build a speed profile for the coming voyages. Interviews with crew and live tests may be needed.

However, we believe that the observations made in this paper will positively help the development of such a speed pilot.

<https://www.dmi.dk/strom/>

Fig.11: Example of current prediction indicating 2 knot southbound surface current, strongest over the deep-water section of the route along the coast of Langeland.

The above does not yet consider the density of traffic in the area. Adhering to anti-collision regulation, thus avoiding other vessels does sometimes lead to prolonged voyage distances and thus higher crossing speed and/or delayed arrival time, which after a battery conversion may adversely affect required charging time to maintain state of charge on the batteries.

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Automated Mooring Systems

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Abstract

This paper explores the feasibility of existing automated mooring systems for short-sea container ships and deep-sea bulk ships. The systems in question include vacuum-based, magnetic-based, and robotic arm-based solutions. By evaluating input from users and system suppliers, the study considers the performance of these systems in terms of safety, operation time, efficiency, sustainability, and emissions reduction. The paper also identifies potential challenges associated with the use of automated mooring systems in these contexts. Overall, this study provides valuable insights for stakeholders seeking to enhance the efficiency and safety of mooring operations in the shipping industry.

1. Introduction

The maritime industry has undergone a tremendous change in the past few decades, and technological advancements have played a significant role in improving safety, efficiency, and sustainability. In this context, the development of autonomous ships is seen as a promising solution that can revolutionize the shipping industry. However, achieving a fully autonomous ship requires the automation of all ship processes, including mooring. Mooring is the process of securing a ship to a permanent structure and intended to prevent ship from moving freely on the water. Conventional mooring is mainly manual work using thick ropes, called mooring lines, to secure the ship to bollards on the quay. The heaviest cargo ships may require more than a dozen mooring lines, while smaller ships can be secured with four to six lines. The conventional mooring process poses considerable safety risks to personnel and the cargo, ship, and quay. According to the European Harbour Master's Committee, 95% of the registered mooring injuries are caused by ropes and wires, *Li (2020)*. Large forces acting on the ship due to waves, winds, and currents require the mooring lines to be tight to keep the ship steady, but at the same time, avoid too much tension in the lines. An unsteady ship or large ship motions can cause damage to the cargo, ship, and quay, and cause mooring lines to break, imposing a significant danger on the shoremen. Moreover, the mooring lines must be adjusted due to changing tides and ship drafts, as well as onloading and offloading operations. In addition to the safety risk of conventional mooring, the process is typically time-consuming. For busy ports, reducing the mooring time can increase the turnover. Fast mooring is also beneficial for the ship owners.

The implementation of automated mooring systems in the shipping industry represents a promising opportunity to improve safety and efficiency. Automated mooring systems can eliminate the need for shoremen to engage in dangerous mooring operations, thus reducing the risk of accidents and injuries. Additionally, automated mooring systems can decrease port time and improve vessel turnaround times, leading to potential reductions in operating costs. While there are existing solutions for automatic mooring on the market today, previous studies have only investigated specific types of systems. E.g. *Yan et al. (2022)* reviewed vacuum-based mooring systems, but did not consider other types of automated mooring solutions. This current study seeks to evaluate all available automated mooring systems and assess their suitability for use on both container ships and bulk ships. The findings presented in this paper are based on research conducted by, *Bellingmo and Jørgensen (2022)*.

1.4. Methodology

A literature study has been performed to identify the available automated mooring systems. The system providers of the automated mooring systems have been interviewed to get insight how they work and their applications. This includes the companies Trelleborg, Cavotec, MacGregor, and AutoMooring Solutions (AMS). Furthermore, to get user experience, the ferry operator Torghatten Midt and bulk

ship operator Luossavaara-Kiirunavaara AB (LKAB) have been interviewed. Together, these inputs are used to identify benefits and challenges of the different types of automated mooring systems. Lastly, a case study involving a short-sea container ship and a deep-sea bulk ship is conducted to examine if the automated mooring systems are suited.

2. Existing Automated Mooring Systems

There are three types of commercially available automated mooring systems today: vacuum-based, magnetic, and robotic arm. Vacuum-based and magnetic (suction-based) systems are typically installed on the shore, while robotic arm systems are installed on the ship. This section provides an overview of the existing solutions.

2.1. Vacuum-based

The most common automatic mooring system used is vacuum based. These systems are installed and in operation worldwide. We will discuss three different vacuum-based automatic mooring systems developed by Cavotec, Trelleborg and AMS, respectively.

MoorMaster is an automated vacuum-based mooring system developed by Cavotec, Fig.1, <https://www.moormaster.com/>. This system uses vacuum pads that attach to the ship's hull to moor it. The system can be installed on top of or in front of a quay. The mooring system does not require any mooring lines, and it is remotely operated through a control panel. The maximum suction force of the mooring unit is 200 kN in sway and 100 kN in surge per unit. The vacuum pads can rotate about a pivot point with up to 6° in roll angle. MoorMaster can adjust to different draughts and tides by being installed on vertical rails or by utilizing the stepping feature where the vacuum pads detach and reattach in a new position. The mooring system uses active controls to dampen surge motions. There are some 400 MoorMaster units installed worldwide. MoorMaster is widely used for ferries, general cargo ships, large container ships, and bulk ships. The mooring time for a ferry using MoorMaster is less than a minute, whereas with conventional mooring, it can take 6-8 minutes. For a container ship, conventional mooring and unmooring may take 30 minutes, while with the automated mooring it can take less than a minute, *Tolsgaard (2020)*. The number of mooring units required depends on the ship's characteristics and environmental conditions at the port.

Fig.1: MoorMaster by Cavotec

Fig.2: AutoMoor by Trelleborg

AutoMoor by Trelleborg is another vacuum-based automated mooring system that uses vacuum pads to moor the ship, Fig.2, https://www.trelleborg.com/marine-and-infrastructure/-/media/marine-systems/resources/datasheets/downloads-dam/automoor_v2_1_hires.pdf. This system is installed on the shore side and uses a passive damping technology to limit ship motions in surge and sway, ensuring safe operation in berth during different environmental and berthing conditions. The mooring system includes environmental sensors to adapt to the current environment. AutoMoor can be installed with up to two arms with vacuum pads. The active outreach of the mooring system is 1.45 m, and the vacuum holding capacity is 40 mt using two vacuum pads (2 x 20 mt). The mooring time for AutoMoor is less than a minute, and the unmooring time is less than 30 s. The mooring system is mainly used for ferries

and container ships, for instance, at the Port of Tallinn serving large passenger ferries. There are over 100 installations of vacuum-based automated mooring systems by Trelleborg globally.

Unlike the above-mentioned systems, AMS has developed a vacuum-based automated mooring system series designed to be used in Ship-to-Ship (StS) operations, <https://automooringsolutions.com/rpr/>. However, due to its modularity, it is also possible to use the StS series for conventional mooring operations by installing the system on shore. The StS series uses vacuum pads and has hydraulic telescopic arms that can reach out 12 m and pull the receiving ship into a predetermined distance between 2 and 8 m. An illustration of the AMS vacuum mooring system is shown in Fig.3. The telescopic arms can control mooring forces up to 1000 kN and use active damping technology to limit ship motions in surge and sway, ensuring safe operation in berth during different environmental and berthing conditions. The system is designed to enable mooring of ships without the need for fenders. The mooring system includes environmental sensors to adapt to the current environment.

Fig.3: StS mooring system by AMS

Fig.4: AMS' magnetic mooring system

2.2. Magnetic

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the present market holds a single magnetic mooring system. The magnetic mooring system, developed by AMS, is an automated contrivance that encompasses a magnetic arm equipped with magnetic pads, Fig.4. The magnets present in the system attract two welded plates that are integrated into the ferry's hull. The mooring unit itself is situated on the shore side and exhibits a maximum holding capacity of 1000 kN. Although this magnetic mooring system is not widely adopted, an instance of its implementation is witnessed in the Woolwich ferry located in London. It is noteworthy that the magnetic mooring system used for the Woolwich ferry is fabricated by Mampaey Offshore Industries and AMS is a subsidiary of Mampaey.

2.3. Robotic Arm

Another type of automated mooring system is the robotic arm system. Unlike suction-based systems, robotic arm systems use mechanical arms to secure the vessel to the quay. These arms are typically equipped with hooks or other locking mechanisms that attach to the vessel's mooring points. The robotic arms can be mounted on the quay or on the ship, depending on the specific system's design. Robotic arm mooring is currently in the testing phase and has not been tested in commercial operation yet. However, we will discuss two different robotic arm automatic mooring systems developed by AMS and MacGregor, respectively.

The Rope Picker Robot (RPR) is an automated solution designed by AMS to facilitate the mooring of ships, Fig.5, <https://automooringsolutions.com/rpr/>. The RPR is equipped with a compact hydraulic telescopic arm, which has a stereo camera installed on it. The RPR can place the mooring rope's eye on a selected bollard on shore with the help of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology that recognizes the quay and bollards. Additionally, a self-learning system is integrated to recognize any unidentified

bollards. The RPR has an outreach of up to 15 m, which makes it possible to handle heights between - 4 to 10 m, and the working load is 50-600 kN. Standard winch mooring systems can be used to securely keep the ship moored once the rope is in place. The RPR developed by AMS is a state-of-the-art robotic mooring system that is expected to revolutionize the mooring process.

Fig.5: Rope Picker Robot, AMS

Fig.6: RobotArm, MacGregor

Another automatic mooring system developed by MacGregor is a fully electric seven-axis robotic arm, *MacGregor (2018)*. This mooring system is designed to stretch mooring ropes with loops from the ship and place them around bollards on the quayside using the robotic arm. The robot arm is shown in Fig.6. A camera at the end of the robotic arm is used to detect the mooring lines' location, and the system is equipped with a compensation system to position the robotic arm correctly independent of ship movements. The mooring system developed by MacGregor is installed in the operating autonomous container ship Yara Birkeland, but some synchronization issues prevent it from being used daily. However, they are planned to be operational anytime soon. The Yara Birkeland has two robotic arms, one installed in the bow and the other in the stern. This system developed by MacGregor is another example of a state-of-the-art automated mooring solution that has the potential to transform the mooring process.

3. Benefit and Challenges

Automated mooring systems have gained attention due to their potential benefits compared to traditional mooring solutions. This section present benefits and challenges of using an automatic mooring system. It is essential to understand the benefits and challenges associated with automated mooring systems to make informed decisions on whether to implement them or not.

Table I summarizes benefits and challenges common to all automatic mooring systems. Table II outlines specific benefits and challenges of suction-based mooring systems (vacuum and magnetic). Table III presents the benefits and challenges of robotic arm solutions.

Table I: General benefits and challenges for automatic mooring systems

Benefits	Challenges
<p>Reduced manning: The traditional mooring operations require the involvement of crew members on both the quayside and the ship. However, the use of automatic mooring systems eliminates the need for crew members in these areas, thereby reducing the costs associated with the manpower required for these operations.</p>	<p>Complex: Automated mooring systems complexity poses a challenge as all subsystems need to operate in a coordinated manner for the entire system to function effectively. The system's operation can be compromised by various issues, such as vacuum loss, vacuum release issues, control signal issues, communication losses, latency, and non-consistent behaviour, leading to downtime and reduced trust in the system.</p>

<p>Environment: The use of automated mooring systems minimizes the use of tugs and ship engines during the mooring process, which reduces the amount of fuel needed and therefore the level of CO2 emissions released into the atmosphere. This aligns with the broader global trend towards reducing greenhouse gas emissions and mitigating the impact of climate change, https://www.moormaster.com/ Díaz-Ruiz-Navamuel et al., 2021).</p>	<p>Costly: Automated mooring systems initial cost is often higher than that of traditional mooring solutions. This cost is due to the complexity of the system and the need for specialized components, software, and maintenance. The costs associated with the development of these systems have resulted in a higher price tag compared to traditional mooring solutions. However, the long-term benefits of automated mooring solutions may offset the initial investment, such as reduced crew and operational costs and reduced emissions. Furthermore, with further advancements in technology and increased adoption, the costs associated with automated mooring systems are expected to decrease, making them more accessible to a wider range of users.</p>
<p>Digitalization: Automatic solutions provide significant benefits through traditional digitalization, including fast access to information, increased productivity, improved decision-making, improved security, higher mobility, and automation. The automated mooring systems benefit from digitalization due to the vast amounts of data generated by the systems. This data can be used to optimize operations, predict maintenance needs, and identify potential problems before they occur. The use of automation and digitalization in mooring operations enables operators to monitor and control the system from anywhere, improving overall efficiency and safety (Malak, 2022).</p>	<p>Service availability: The complexity of automatic mooring systems increases the likelihood of system issues and failures, which can often only be handled by specialized system providers. This could result in downtime for the equipment and cause delays for the ships. As automatic mooring systems are not designed for manual intervention, they require higher levels of maintenance support than traditional mooring systems. The need for a specialized service system increases the overall cost of maintenance and operations for automatic mooring systems. Therefore, the advantages of reduced manpower and increased safety must be weighed against the additional cost and complexity of maintaining and servicing automatic mooring systems.</p>
<p>Safety: Automated mooring systems remove the need for crew to be present in exposed mooring areas, which eliminates the hazards associated with rope brakeage and failure. The elimination of manual handling also reduces the risk of musculoskeletal injuries to crew members.</p>	
<p>Monitoring and remote operation: The use of automatic mooring systems enables remote control of mooring operations from a remote operating centre (ROC). This technology allows the operator to monitor the mooring process in real-time and respond quickly to any deviations or malfunctions. However, it also requires robust and reliable communication systems to ensure uninterrupted control of the mooring operation.</p>	
<p>Enable full autonomy: Automatic mooring systems offers potential for fully autonomous transportation operations.</p>	

Table II: Benefits and challenges for suction-based mooring systems

Benefits	Challenges
<p>Stability: An automated mooring system can reduce the ship motions caused by wind, waves, and currents during mooring, thereby improving the ship's stability. This enhanced stability simplifies the loading and offloading cargo operations and reduces the risk of damage to the cargo or the ship's hull.</p>	<p>Hull thickness: Automated mooring systems require a hull thickness of at least 10 mm and should be made of steel to avoid being bent by the suction force. Other hull types such as aluminium, fiberglass, or windows cannot be attached to these systems. While automated mooring restrains most of the motion of the moored ship, the mechanical components of the system can wear out, and the ship must be allowed some movements while moored. The force of the automated mooring system must also not exceed the force acting on the fenders to prevent damage. Furthermore, the hull needs to have a relatively flat surface for the system to attach to. In the magnetic mooring solution, a metallic plate is typically welded into the hull as it requires a thicker hull than the vacuum solution (Yan et al., 2022).</p>
<p>Accurate positioning: Adjusting the ship position after mooring can be achieved with automated mooring systems, providing precise control for accurate lining up of the ship. This feature is particularly useful for ferries that require accurate alignment for the use of land-mounted ganeways or equipment.</p>	<p>Wrong connection point: Automated mooring systems provide advantages in terms of reducing motions in surge and sway, but they do not limit motions in heave, pitch, or roll. When a ship rolls and the mooring is attached high on the hull, the bottom of the ship may exert a force on the quay, which can cause a large moment on the mooring units. To prevent this, the pads should be attached at a suitable height above the waterline, ideally around 2 m, to limit the impact of ship movements on the mooring units.</p>
<p>Shorter dock: Automated mooring systems offer a benefit of enabling the use of shorter docks compared to conventional mooring. The ship can overhang the dock by adding additional automatic mooring devices. This not only saves space but also increases efficiency in the port.</p>	<p>Pre-mooring positioning: Automated mooring systems usually require additional requirements for docking. One of the main challenges is that the ship needs to be precisely positioned at the fenders and at stand-still before the automated mooring system can start. This is because the mechanical arm has a limited outreach of about 2.6 m, which can be extended at an additional cost. In contrast, with conventional mooring, the ship can start mooring from about 5 m away by throwing the ropes to shore. Additionally, with conventional mooring, the ship can simplify the docking and undocking procedure by being attached to a rope in one end of the ship and thrust with the other. Without ropes, this requires that the ship is fully actuated and can dock independently or uses tugboats to assist the docking.</p>
<p>Varying heights: The automated mooring system offers a flexible solution to accommodate the variation in ship draughts caused by cargo loading and unloading, and tide changes. This flexibility is enabled by the installation of the mooring</p>	<p>Crane operations: The use of ship-mounted cranes for cargo handling can cause unwanted roll motion, which can affect the stability of the ship during mooring. This can be particularly challenging in rough weather conditions, as roll</p>

<p>units on vertical rails or the stepping feature of the vacuum mooring systems. Vertical rails allow the units to move above and below the height of the quay depending on the draught and tides, while the stepping feature detaches and reattaches the vacuum pads one by one in a new position to adjust to varying heights. This feature is particularly important in ports with large tidal differences and varying ship draughts, where the flexibility of the automated mooring system can significantly reduce the time and effort needed for docking and undocking of ships.</p>	<p>motion can cause the cargo to shift and lead to accidents. One solution to this problem is the use of active heave compensation systems that can counteract the effects of roll motion. These systems use sensors to detect the motion of the ship and adjust the crane movements accordingly. Additionally, the use of passive anti-roll tanks or stabilizing fins on the ship can also help to mitigate roll motion during cargo handling operations.</p>
<p>Faster: Automated mooring systems provide significant time savings over conventional mooring. An automated mooring system can save up to half an hour for a container ship during mooring, <i>Tolsgaard (2020)</i>. These time savings can be attributed to the faster attachment and detachment process of the automated system compared to manually throwing ropes to the shore. Ships can use the time saved to sail at a lower speed, which reduces operational costs and emissions. The reduced turnaround time due to the automated mooring system increases efficiency and earnings for the ports.</p>	<p>Small ships: For small ships, the mooring system needs to be able to handle the environmental loads that can be very large compared to the weight of the ship. These loads can create large movements on the ship, making it challenging for the mooring system to keep the ship in place. Small ships also tend to have a shallower draft, which can make it difficult for the automated mooring system to attach to the hull.</p>

Table III: Benefits and challenges for robotic arm mooring systems

Benefits	Challenges
<p>Pre-mooring positioning: It is possible to utilize conventional mooring techniques to simplify the docking and undocking procedures by being attached to a rope in one end of the ship and thrusting with the other end.</p>	<p>Object detection: The camera system on the robotic arm must detect and track where bollards, mooring lines and any obstacles are located. Camera systems suffer from typical limitations like high contrast light, darkness, and fog. Alternatively, the exact bollard location must be given as input to the control system of the robotic arm.</p>
<p>Flexible: The robotic arm mooring system is a unique system that does not require quayside infrastructure, making it easy to use at any port. This is because the system is mounted on the ship, and the robotic arm can reach out and attach to the mooring bollard on the quay without requiring any other infrastructure or equipment. This makes it an attractive option for ships that visit different ports with varying infrastructure, as it eliminates the need for port-specific equipment and infrastructure.</p>	<p>Performance: The performance of robotic arm mooring systems is still uncertain due to the lack of extensive commercial testing. The solution depends on the accuracy of the compensation system used to position the arm relative to the ship and the quay. Poor performance of the compensation system could lead to a suboptimal mooring system, causing potential risks for the ship, personnel, and the environment. Therefore, it is important to test and verify the performance of these new mooring systems under different environmental conditions and operational scenarios to ensure their reliability and safety.</p>
	<p>Extra weight: The installation of robotic arms on a ship as part of an automated mooring system results in an increase in the ship's overall weight. As a result, the ship may require more energy to move through the water, which can result in increased fuel consumption and emissions.</p>

	<p>Reduced space: Automated mooring systems can have potential drawbacks as they occupy space on the ship that could be used to carry cargo, and in retrofit cases, it may be challenging to place the robotic arms optimally. This may impact the weight distribution of the ship, which in turn can affect its stability and manoeuvrability. Furthermore, the placement of the robotic arms needs to be optimized to ensure that they can effectively moor and unmoor the ship without damaging it or the dock.</p>
	<p>Varying heights: The range of robotic arm mooring solutions is limited by the distance between the bollard on the quay and the robotic arm installation on the ship. For MacGregor, the longest range is 21 m. If the distance is larger than the range, the ship cannot be moored using the robotic arm. Therefore, varying ship draught and tides can be a challenge for robotic arm mooring solutions.</p>

4. Use Cases

This section discusses the opportunities and challenges of automated mooring for two different types of ships. The first use case examines short-sea containers, while the second use case focuses on deep-sea bulk ships.

4.1. Multiple Ports

Short-sea container ships are often medium sized and commonly used for transportation between multiple ports, including both large and small ports. On the other hand, deep-sea bulk ships are generally larger and mainly operate between major ports with established infrastructure. In large ports with high ship traffic, shore-based automated mooring using suction-based systems may be more cost-effective as the cost per ship is low. However, in small ports with limited port calls, the installation cost of multiple automated suction-based mooring units can be unaffordable. Another important consideration is who bears the cost of the mooring system. With shore-based automated mooring, the ports are responsible for the cost, while with robot arm systems, the ship owner covers the expense. For short-sea container ships, the robot arm system is considered suitable due to the frequent port visits, whereas for deep-sea bulk ships, suction-based mooring is often more appropriate.

4.2. Geared Ship

In some ports, there may be a lack of quayside infrastructure, such as cranes, to handle cargo, which leads to the need for ships to carry the necessary equipment on board, commonly referred to as geared ships. Container ships are often equipped with gears as they visit multiple ports with varying infrastructure availability. Similarly, bulk ships may also be geared as they transport diverse types of cargo. However, geared ships may experience roll motions during cargo loading and unloading operations, posing operational challenges. In this context, the flexibility of the robot arm mooring system in accommodating roll angles becomes advantageous, as it can adjust the robot arm to the desired location within its specific constraints. Vacuum-based mooring systems, in particular, can handle roll angles of up to 6°, which is typically within the operational limits of onboard cranes commonly found on geared ships.

4.3. Draught and Tidal Changes

Mooring operations can also be complicated by changes in draught due to cargo loading and unloading, as well as tidal fluctuations, which is applicable to both deep-sea bulk ships and short-sea container ships. In cases where a container ship is utilizing a robot arm mooring system, the outreach of the robotic arm, typically 21 m, may not be sufficient if the distance between the quay and ship deck is greater. On the other hand, suction-based mooring systems can address variations in draught and tides by installing mooring units on vertical rails or incorporating stepping functionality. This implies that for bulk ships utilizing suction-based mooring, changes in draught and tidal conditions do not pose significant challenges, as the system can adapt to accommodate different scenarios effectively. However, for ships utilizing robotic arms, careful considerations and appropriate measures need to be taken to effectively manage varying draughts and tidal conditions to ensure safe and efficient mooring operations.

4.4. Operational Stability and Service

Automated mooring systems are complex and intricate, requiring seamless coordination among all subsystems to ensure proper functioning of the entire system. A failure in the automation system can result in operational downtime and reduce trust in the system. In case of a failure, specialized services from the system provider may be necessary due to the complexity of the system. For large ports, dedicated service personnel may be readily available in close proximity, thereby minimizing the time required to rectify any potential issues. However, for small ports located in remote areas, the distance to a service team can be substantial, aggravating the impact of a potential failure. Short-sea container ships, which frequently visit such remote ports, are particularly vulnerable to significant downtime in the event of a failure. In contrast, deep-sea bulk ships typically visit large ports where service teams may be in close proximity, minimizing the potential impact of a failure on the operation.

5. Conclusions

This study examined three types of automated mooring systems; vacuum-based, magnetic-based, and robotic arm, and evaluated their benefits and challenges for short-sea container ships and deep-sea bulk ships. For short-sea container ships that frequently visit multiple ports, robotic arm automated mooring systems appear to be the most suitable option. However, it should be noted that these systems are still under development and their operational validation is limited. Alternatively, vacuum-based mooring systems are commercially available and currently employed by some container ships operating between selected ports where infrastructure is available. Nonetheless, both types of automated mooring systems may face challenges in accessing specialized service personnel, particularly at remote ports. On the other hand, deep-sea bulk ships typically operate between large ports, making shore-installed suction-based mooring systems a viable option as these ports are likely to have the necessary resources and infrastructure in place. Automatic vacuum mooring systems have been extensively tested and proven to be capable of accommodating large ships, handling height variations due to draught and tide changes, and functioning effectively under diverse weather conditions, ensuring safe and reliable operation in various maritime environments.

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Procedures for Manoeuvrability Characterization: From Ships to Marine Robots

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Abstract

The work aims at presenting an extension of the ITTC standard procedures, employed for the identification of vessel characteristics and performance, towards marine robotic platforms. An automatic system for the execution of standard manoeuvring procedures is exploited to perform an autonomous data gathering and system identification. Execution of zig-zag, turning circle and pull-out manoeuvres are described and experimental data are reported with respect to the employment of the SWAMP ASV. A subsequent data analysis is performed to obtain a dynamic model that can be exploited for motion estimation and synthesis/adaptation of control schemes.

1. Introduction

The International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC) has developed, starting from the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) manoeuvring criteria, *IMO (2002)*, a set of manoeuvring guidelines for ships designed to provide a standard method for assessing their manoeuvrability in various conditions. The ITTC procedures, *ITTC (2021a, 2017a,b)* for detailed reference, include these manoeuvre tests:

- Turning (circle): the purpose is to measure the ship's manoeuvring spaces, to evaluate both its ability to change course and its ability to carry out emergency manoeuvres to avoid a collision.
- Zig-zag: this manoeuvre tests a ship's ability to change direction quickly while maintaining a steady speed.
- Direct/reverse spiral: this test allows the steering diagram to be plotted by points in order to test ship's dynamic stability.
- Pull-out: this test allows to evaluate the ship's ability to disengage from the evolution
- Stopping: the manoeuvre is performed to test the ability of the vessel to stop in order to avoid collision with an obstacle in its path.

The ITTC manoeuvres are used by ship designers and builders to evaluate the manoeuvrability of new ship designs and by ship operators to evaluate the manoeuvrability of their ships in specific operating conditions, *SIMMAN (2020)*.

In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the application of ITTC manoeuvres to marine robots, such as Autonomous Surface Vessels (ASVs), Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) and Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs). These marine robots are used in a variety of applications, including oceanography, hydrography, surveillance, and search and rescue.

The use of ITTC manoeuvres for marine robots has several advantages. First, they provide a standard method for evaluating the manoeuvrability of marine robots in various conditions. Second, they can be used to optimize the design of marine robots for specific applications. Finally, they can be used to evaluate the performance of marine robots in real-world conditions. In particular, bearing in mind the future vision of marine robots operating in daily maritime traffic, it is crucial to identify the operational

capabilities and limitation in order to guarantee a safe and efficient environment where autonomous agents and manned vessels can coexist.

There are also several challenges that must be overcome in order to extend the ITTC principles to the evaluation of marine robots' manoeuvrability. One challenge is that the ITTC manoeuvres were developed for ships, which have different characteristics than marine robots. For example, ships have a large displacement and a deep draft, while marine robots are typically smaller and have a much shallower draft. Another challenge is that the ITTC manoeuvres were developed for manned ships and models, while marine robots are typically operated remotely or autonomously, using specific NGC (navigation, guidance and control) algorithms. The essential challenge for marine robots, when it comes to integrating ITTC procedures, lies in the lack of vehicle classification and absence of guidelines, which instead are established for traditional ship hulls. In marine engineering and naval architecture hulls are divided in hulls families or systematic series, each series is derived from a mother hull. For every hull of each family there are known features, among which geometry, propulsive performance and characteristics. No such thing exists for marine robotic vehicles. Creating this base knowledge is the main challenge of manoeuvrability standardisation in marine robotics.

In the case of autonomous underwater vehicles (AUV) operating throughout the water column, specific ITTC procedures were developed to identify the characteristics of vertical motion, *ITTC (2021b)*. Autonomous surface vehicles (ASV), on the other hand, can be considered "small vessels", therefore the ITTC procedures can be applied directly to such autonomous platforms, with appropriate adaptations related to the specificities of this type of robotic vehicles.

The aim of this paper is to describe the development of automated procedures allowing the "fast" identification of the manoeuvring capabilities of the specific autonomous agent; the term "fast" refers to the fact that the overall procedure can be executed within minutes to hours, depending on the resolution and degree of accuracy that the operator intends to cover over the operational span of the vehicle as opposed to days (weeks) normally required for such characterisation for traditional ships (military vessels).

Thanks to the intelligence onboard the autonomous vehicle, the system can automatically execute the sequence of required manoeuvres for providing the estimation of navigation performance. The presented work starts with the migration of the standardized ITTC procedures to ASVs in order to assess the feasibility of such manoeuvres and, in case, adapt or add further procedures to characterize different/non-conventional hulls and thrust configurations.

2. Robotic Platforms Today

Autonomous marine platforms currently rely on consolidated technology; although new materials, alternative hulls and propulsion concepts and innovative control systems are still pacing the design of brand-new prototypes, the industrial sector has exponentially increased the production of commercial autonomous vessels. Then marine robotic fleet designed and built by CNR-INM are shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Different robotic platforms designed by CNR-INM: ASV SWAMP (left), ROV/AUV Proteus (centre), ROV/AUV e-URoPe (right)

The ASV SWAMP (Shallow Water Autonomous Multipurpose Platform), Fig.2, *Odetti et al. (2020)*, *Bibuli et al. (2022)*, is an autonomous catamaran with double-ended hulls, providing increased stability, smaller draft with higher payload. SWAMP is characterised by enhanced manoeuvring in narrow space and shallow water thanks to the bespoke thrusters flushed with the hull. Achieving good stability was the main driver in the choice of the catamaran shape since payload elements, like sonars used for mapping the sea bottom, request for stable platform with minimised motions. The need for a wide payload area suitable for modularity and re-configurability, *Pellegrini et al. (2023)*, shaped the design of SWAMP. The main idea behind the choice of double-ended hull was the possibility of coupling this solution with the adoption of four azimuth thrusters to be adequately manoeuvrable also in restricted and perturbed waters. Modularity was one of the main ideas behind the design of this autonomous surface vessel. Every hull is composed of various transverse sections of lightweight foam whose number or shape may be modified in function of the actual needs. In this way, the geometry of the hull may be modified to increase the volume and reduce the immersion or to augment stability or to reduce the drag or in function of other operational requests. This concept also allows thinking of the hull as a modular structure where propulsion units, batteries in a various number, sensors and payloads may be positioned or removed from the hull. The vehicle is constituted by the two mono-hull vehicles and the two connection bars. Payload like winches, samplers, sensors, landing pads, etc.; can be installed on the payload deck. The final weight of the entire catamaran structure is 35 kg.

Fig.2: ASV SWAMP general layout with measures

3. Automated ITTC Manoeuvres Execution

This section describes the manoeuvrability test plan for the autonomous surface vehicle SWAMP, adapted from the standard manoeuvrability tests (IMO and ITTC). To this end, some standard manoeuvrability tests of ships and how these were adapted to the SWAMP case, *Ferretti et al. (2022)*, are described in the following.

Most manoeuvring tests start from a straight course condition with as steady as possible values of heading, speed, rpm, and rudder angle or corresponding (pod angle, water-jet steering nozzle angle, etc.). Straight-line speed runs should be carried out in order to find the propeller rpm corresponding to the desired test speed. The most common tests are those referred in IMO Resolution MSC.137(76). The test is initiated by the order to the steering system to execute the actual test.

The procedure reported in the following has to be suitably adapted to the specific autonomous platforms since, for instance, they refer to rudder angles, but the ASV SWAMP is equipped with azimuth thrusters and no rudder is present; thus, in this case, the rudder angle is considered as the azimuth angle applied symmetrically to each thruster pod. The value of the propeller rpm has, for the SWAMP platform, to be intended as the revolution rate of each thruster pump.

The innovative contribution of this work is the completely automated execution of the manoeuvre set, that is autonomously managed by the control architecture onboard the robot. The manoeuvre list, with the specific parameter settings e.g. rpm, azimuth angles, number of circles, etc.; are pre-compiled by the operator and fed to the system. Additional information such as the georeferenced center of the operational area and the main north-referenced direction for the platform motion (in particular for the zig-zag manoeuvres) are also defined. Thanks to the latter information set, the automatic system can compute a number of waypoints that the platform will track prior to each manoeuvre, in order to execute each manoeuvre always at the same (practically) identical initial conditions. In particular, the system executes the following set of operations in preparation of each manoeuvre:

1. The vehicle moves to the initial waypoint, the “entrance” of the operational area;
2. The vehicle moves to a second waypoint in order to get aligned along the main direction of the manoeuvre (the orientation of the zig-zag motion or the tangent line to enter into the turning circle);
3. The vehicle moves to a third waypoint (on the same line connecting the first and second waypoints), setting the intended rpm/speed required for the specific manoeuvre;
4. The manoeuvre execution is activated;
5. If zig-zag – the manoeuvre is ended when 3 complete oscillations (3 on starboard side and 3 on port side) are achieved.
If turning-circle – the manoeuvre is ended when 3 complete turns are achieved;
6. Only for turning-circle – when the turning is completed, a pull-out manoeuvre is commanded, requiring the platform to proceed at constant rpm and zero rudder/azimuth angle for 30 seconds;
7. The manoeuvre is completed and the related data are logged. If other manoeuvres are scheduled, the execution loop starts again, otherwise the automatic procedure is completed and the vehicle will stop standing by for further commands from the operator.

3.1 Turning circle and Pull-out test

The Turning Circle (TC) test is generally started with a hard over rudder angle (generally 35° starboard and portside) and finished by a pull-out by putting the rudder back to neutral angle after completing the turning test, i.e.; after reaching a steady yaw rate. The ship is kept on the circular path for at least one and a half turns (540°), but it is better if at least two turns (720°) are covered, so that the recorded values can be corrected considering the deviations caused by the current and the wind.

For the TC tests, the following parameters should especially be taken into account:

- initial forward speed(s) u
- initial propeller rate(s) of rotations n
- ordered steering device angles δ

The values set during the turning circle tests are summarized in Table I; each trial ends with a pull-out manoeuvre.

Table I: Turning circle and pull out: combinations of azimuth angles and thruster speed during test

Azimuth angle	Thruster speed
$\pm 20^\circ$	1200/1600 rpm
$\pm 30^\circ$	1600 rpm
$\pm 40^\circ$	1600 rpm
$\pm 50^\circ$	1600 rpm
$\pm 60^\circ$	1600 rpm

(*) TC test correspond to $3 \times 360^\circ + \text{pull out}$

Fig.3 reports the normalized vehicle position (x/L and y/L) plot during the execution of a set of port side turning circle tests at 1600 rpm, corresponding to about a $U = 1$ m/s. The motion of the circles centre (measured data), thus indicating the presence of sea current or wind, that has been estimated to correct

the data and identify the ideal (but not perfect) manoeuvre in calm water, allowing insight of the manoeuvrability behaviour of the model, e.g.; Fig.4 shows the tactical diameter (TD) as a function of the azimuth angle δ , including the expected value (EV) and the standard deviation (SD) over three turns.

Fig.3: Example of data acquired (measured) and corrected (due to sea current) during port side turning circle test at 1600 rpm varying the azimuth angle

Fig.4: Tactical diameter TD as function of azimuth angle for port side turning circle test at 1600 rpm

At the end of each TC test, a Pull-out manoeuvre is executed by going back to the steady course rudder angle after a short execute of the rudder (some 10°) to port and starboard side.

With a deeper look into the turning-circle data, as well as in the pull-out manoeuvre, it is possible to notice a biased motion on the port side of the vehicle, Fig.3. This behaviour highlights an asymmetry in the platform configuration, resulting in a corrupted motion characteristic.

3.2 Zig-zag test

The first two overshoots should be accomplished when possible. These tests are conducted to port and starboard. The zig-zag (ZZ) manoeuvre is obtained, starting from a straight course travelled at constant speed with the rudder at the neutral angle, bringing the rudder to a predetermined rudder angle $+\alpha_0$ to starboard and keeping it in this position until the ship rotates the heading by a predetermined angle $+\delta_0$ (defined as the angle between the guideline reached and the guideline held at the entrance to the manoeuvre and indicated as ship heading), after which the rudder is rotated to the opposite side by the same amount ($-\alpha_0$) and leave it in this position until the ship responds to the rudder with a heading variation, again measured with respect to the straight-line entry course, equal to $-\delta_0$. The bar angles are obviously referred to the neutral bar angle. The procedure, repeated at least five times to stabilize the manoeuvre, test the test conditions and collect additional data, is characterized by the choice of the two angles (α_0, δ_0), and is indicated by the abbreviation α_0/δ_0 . Usually, even if not established by the rules, the first approach is made to starboard to verify the behaviour of the ship to the need to disengage from another ship that crosses in the opposite direction. The IMO has standardized $10^\circ/10^\circ$ and $20^\circ/20^\circ$ zig-zag manoeuvres, to evaluate the behaviour of the ship at a medium and high rudder angle. In particular, the former is recommended because it provides useful information for assessing course stability. It tests manoeuvrability for medium-small rudder and turn angles, closer to the usual course control angles. For large ships, it is also recommended to carry out the zig-zag manoeuvres with angles of 15° and 25° .

The modified zig-zag manoeuvre test is used to express course-keeping qualities in conditions like actual operations characterized by small heading changes and rudder values. The test procedure for a modified zig-zag manoeuvre is the same as for zig-zag manoeuvre, but the execute heading angle is chosen to be as small as 1° , the rudder angle being 5° or 10° , *ITTC (2017b)*.

Following parameters should especially be taken into account:

- initial forward speed(s) u
- initial propeller rate(s) of rotations n
- ordered steering device angles δ and heading angle ψ (δ/ψ , i.e.; $10^\circ/10^\circ$ or $20^\circ/20^\circ$)
- turning speed of steering device

The values set during the zig-zag tests are summarized in Table II. Fig.4 shows an example of normalized ship trajectories conditional to azimuth angle at 1600 rpm. For the same test set, the thruster heading (mean value of the four thrusters) is compared to the yaw angle in Fig.5, providing an insight of the ZZ overshoots.

Table II: Zig-zag test: combinations of values for azimuth angles/heading and thruster speed

Azimuth angle / Heading [deg]	Thruster speed
$10^\circ/10^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$15^\circ/15^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$20^\circ/20^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$25^\circ/25^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$30^\circ/30^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$40^\circ/40^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$50^\circ/50^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm
$60^\circ/60^\circ$	800/1000/1200/1400/1600 rpm

(*) 6 angle changes for each test

Fig.4: Example of data acquired (measured) zig-zag test at 1600 rpm varying the azimuth angle

Fig.5: Example of data acquired during a zig-zag test: thruster heading vs yaw angle at 1600 rpm

6. Data analysis

A practical dynamic model of the platform has been derived from the acquired data. The form of the model is the one usually employed for control design purpose and described as follows:

$$I_r \dot{r} = k_r r + c_{r_u} r |u| + c_{r_v} r |v| + b_r \delta \quad (1)$$

r is the yaw-rate, u and v the surge and sway velocities, δ the azimuth angle, I_r the moment of inertia, k_r the linear drag term, c_{r_u} and c_{r_v} the cross-velocity drag terms, and b_r the input interface term.

Since the moment of inertia is known and equal to 7.58 Kg/m^2 , it is possible to estimate the unknown drag and input interface terms through a left pseudo-inversion operation:

$$\frac{1}{I_r} \begin{bmatrix} k_r \\ c_{r_u} \\ c_{r_v} \\ b_r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{r} & \underline{r} |\underline{u}| & \underline{r} |\underline{v}| & \underline{\delta} \end{bmatrix}^{\#} \dot{r} \quad (2)$$

where the underlined terms represent the measurement vectors. The four terms have the following values reported in Table III.

Table III: Values of the dynamic model parameters

k_r	-13.5227
c_{r_u}	7.2526
c_{r_v}	2.6854
b_r	3.9683

The calculated parameters are then used to estimate the dynamic behaviour of the platform by integrating over the time the dynamic equation (1). This procedure has been performed both for the zig-zag manoeuvre, the result is depicted in Fig.6, and for the turning circle followed by the pull-out phase, reported in Fig.7. In both the experiments it is possible to notice the superimposition of the estimated signal with respect to the actual measure.

The model identified can be furtherly employed for the synthesis of guidance and control loops, where possible deviation of the parameter values from the actual ones (due to changing operational conditions and measurement errors) can be mitigated by means of adaptive control schemes, as for instance reported in *Bibuli et al. (2020)*.

Fig.6: Platform motion estimation during the zig-zag manoeuvre

Fig.7: Platform motion estimation during the turning circle manoeuvre

7. Conclusions

The ITTC manoeuvres are a valuable tool for evaluating the manoeuvrability of ships, and there is growing interest in extending these manoeuvres to marine robots. However, there are several challenges that must be overcome in order to extend the ITTC manoeuvres to marine robots, such as the differences in characteristics and operation between ships and marine robots.

Extending such process to autonomous robotic platforms allows the automatic execution of the manoeuvring procedures in a repeatable and consistent framework, allowing a fast identification of the main characteristics of the platform, including the self-adaptation of navigation, guidance and control schemes. Such a fast procedure is of great support in marine robots exploitation, since their payload and configuration can significantly change over time because of the specific operational requirements.

This work represents a first step in the direction of standardisation of ship procedures with the aim of including robotic technology in the framework of marine traffic regulation, in the future view of collaborative manned and unmanned vessel cooperating together.

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Parametric Modeling, CFD Simulations, DoE and Machine Learning for the Design of a Planing Boat

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Abstract

A pilot boat was developed as part of a European R&D project. CAESES[®] was employed to create fully-parametric models of both the bare hull and tunnels. Simcenter STAR-CCM+ was coupled to CAESES and applied for free-surface RANS simulations at planing mode, including propellers via actuator discs. Results from a design-of-experiment (DoE) for 18 geometric parameters were taken as input to train a machine learning (ML) model for rapid design processes on both integral quantities and flow fields. The paper will give an overview of the project, parametric models, and CFD simulations, and will explain the creation of a Reduced-Order Model (ROM), its accuracy, and possible use cases.

1. Introduction

An 11m-pilot boat was designed and optimized as part of the research and development project AutoPlan (www.auto-plan.net) funded within the MarTERA program of the European Union. The fast monohull was developed by UZMAR (Turkey) for planing conditions at a design speed of 27.5 kn for a displacement of 9.5 t, featuring two tunneled propellers with conventional shaft lines, brackets and spade rudders, Fig.1, Table I.

Fig.1: 11m-pilot boat in calm water at 27.5 kn (SkyView in CAESES with simulated wave field taken from Simcenter STAR-CCM+)

Table I: Boat's main dimensions

Parameter	Symbol	Full-scale	Model-scale	Units
Length over all	L_{OA}	11.058	3.364	m
Beam	B	3.5	1.065	m
Design displacement	Δ	9.5	0.267	ton
Draft	D	0.611	0.186	m
Longitudinal center of gravity from AP	LCG	4.945	1.504	m
Vertical center of gravity from base	VCG	0.7	0.213	m
Design speed	V	27.5	15.168	kn
Froude number	F_n	1.358	1.358	–

The Process Integration and Design Optimization (PIDO) environment CAESES[®] was used to create fully-parametric models of both the bare hull and the tunnels. High-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations were undertaken with Simcenter STAR-CCM+. They consisted of RANS simulations with free heave (negative sinkage) and pitch (positive trim bow up), including the viscous free surface. Propulsion was captured via an actuator disc model, taking propeller thrust as an objective.

Simcenter STAR-CCM+ was coupled to CAESES and various design-of-experiment (DoE) and simulation-driven design (SDD) campaigns were run, *Harries et al. (2023)*. Subsequently, a Sobol sequence with 89 quasi-randomly produced samples was utilized for a design space of 18 geometric parameters to create a Reduced-Order Model. The data set, i.e., geometric variants, corresponding flow fields, and integral values, was taken to train a machine learning (ML) model, employing NAVPACK.

This opens up a variety of new possibilities of collaborative design work, e.g., *van den Boogaard et al. (2022)*. In addition to predicting scalar quantities such as thrust and drag, field quantities (e.g., pressure distribution, wave field) and sensitivities can be determined from the ML-model within seconds. This enables engineers and designers to work together interactively and evaluate many scenarios on the fly without having to wait for new CFD results. Particularly for high-fidelity simulations the CFD response time often prohibits rapid evaluations. For the pilot boat CFD simulations typically took 60 to 70 CPU hours per variant so that even on a good cluster any new variant would need quite a while to finish, i.e., definitely more time than it takes to drink a good cup of coffee.

This paper will give a short overview of the parametric models, and the CFD simulations. It then explains the creation of the ML-model, its accuracy, and possible use cases. For details of the AutoPlan project, a thorough discussion of the parametric modeling approach, a comprehensive coverage of the set-up and validation of the CFD as well as a presentations of various simulation-driven design campaigns the reader is referred to *Harries et al. (2023)*. Meanwhile, the focus of this paper is the creation and application of the Reduced-Order Model (ROM).

2. Parametric models within CAESES[®]

In order to undertake SDD campaigns but also to generate the finite sets of input to ROMs a meaningful definition of the design task, in particular of the geometry, is of paramount importance, *Harries (2020)*, *Harries and Abt (2019)*. For both it is crucial to come up with design spaces of reasonably low dimensionality, say less than 20 if possible, definitely less than 50 to be of practical relevance. Otherwise, Richard E. Bellman's curse of dimensionality kicks in, meaning that a prohibitively large number of samples would be needed to capture the cause-and-effect of input and output data, respectively.

Consequently, a sophisticated parametric model needed to be developed for the monohull. The design favored by the shipyard leading the AutoPlan project followed a classic layout: Deep-V bow region, spray rails, flattened stern region, large propellers mounted to shaft lines supported by brackets and housed within tunnels plus spade rudders. While the propellers, shaft lines, brackets and rudders were provided as a package by an internationally recognized supplier, the hull itself was developed and analyzed jointly by several of the project partners, primarily UZMAR, the Technical University Berlin, SVA Potsdam and FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS.

Two fully-parametric models were built within CAESES[®], one for bare hull and another one for the tunnel. Bare hull and tunnel were then merged to form the planing boat.

2.1. Bare hull

The modeling approach taken for the bare hull follows the one presented in *Albert et al. (2016)*. In principle, a set of longitudinal curves define the boat from stern to stem. These longitudinal curves provide the inputs to sections. As elaborated in *Harries et al. (2015)*, the longitudinal curves together with the building pattern, here in transverse direction for the sectional curves, form a sophisticated

sweep surface, called a MetaSurface in CAESES®, Fig.2. The longitudinal curves as shown in Fig.2(A) were fully (and only) defined by parameters which, as a consequence, completely determine all surfaces presented in Fig.2(B). Without any need of interactive work the bare hull can be produced and any change of parameter settings would result in a variant that is topologically speaking identical yet different in geometry. For an elaboration see *Harries et al. (2023)*.

Fig.2: Perspective view of bare hull without tunnels (MetaSurface in CAESES®)

2.2. Tunnel

The tunnel was defined separately and independently of the bare hull, using a Gordon surface as depicted in Fig.3. Essentially, the tunnel is determined by three longitudinal curves, i.e., an inner rail, an outer rail and a top contour as shown in Fig.3(A). These longitudinal curves are utilized to compute interpolating arcs at several positions of importance as depicted in both Fig.3(A) and (B). The resulting surface is given in Fig.3(B). It smoothly interpolates all arcs in transversal direction and, additionally, the rails in longitudinal direction. Changing the rails and/or the top contour parametrically leads to different shapes of the tunnel surface. More details can be found in *Harries et al. (2023)*.

(A) Three longitudinal curves (blue), defining the tunnel

(B) Gordon surface (green), generated by interpolating a set of arcs (black) and the two rails (blue)

Fig.3: Parametrically defined tunnel geometry

2.3. Assembly, parameters and variations

The bare hull and the tunnel represent a set of surfaces and a single surface, respectively, which need to be brought together to form the final geometry. To this end both the bare hull and the tunnel are converted into solid models and subsequently assembled via a Boolean operation. Mathematically, the tunnel is subtracted from the bare hull. The result is depicted in Fig.4. Again, details are discussed in *Harries et al. (2023)*. It should be noted that for the actual simulations of the flow field further components are added, namely the shaft lines and the brackets while the propeller was idealized via an actuator disc (not shown here). The spade rudders were omitted though.

Fig.4: Assembly of bare hull and tunnel (zoomed in at the stern)

Table II summarizes the 18 free variables that span the design space. It should be kept in mind that the parameter model comprises many more parameters which, however, are kept constant here, e.g., the length of the boat. Therefore, the 18 free variables are the subset chosen to modify the bare hull and the tunnel for the design and optimization of this particular pilot boat. Fig.5 shows a series of four variants generated by quasi-randomly changing all free variables within the bounds summarized in Table II.

Fig.5: Some variations of the assembled bare hull with tunnel (screenshot from CAESSES Design-Viewer)

Table II: Free variables with bounds

^ Design Variables						
	Design Variable	Lower	Value	Upper	Active	
1	angleLongAtTransom	0	0	15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2	angleOpeningAtTip	30	35	70	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
3	angleTongue	0.1	6	10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4	areaModCurvedTop	-0.1	0.095	0.1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5	asymAft	-0.05	-0.05	0.05	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
6	asymFor	-0.1	-0.03	0.1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7	lowerTransom	0	0.025	0.075	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
8	parallelFor	0.05	0.1	0.1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9	parallelAft	0.05	0.075	0.25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
10	tipRelPosX	0.225	0.24	0.262	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
11	relHollownessAtKeel	0	0	0.05	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
12	relHollownessAtStern	0	0	0.1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
13	rocker	0	0	0.17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
14	deadriseAtTransom	12	19	25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
15	railInnerTanFwd	-60	-45	-32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
16	railWidthAtTransom	0.04	0.08	0.1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
17	railInnerYrelAtTransom	0.85	0.9	0.95	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
18	railInnerYrelAtyMax	1	1.02	1.02	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

3. CFD simulations

The parametric model built within CAESES[®] as described above was used to automatically generate hull variants to be analyzed by means of high-fidelity CFD. The flow field about the pilot boat was computed via RANS simulations in Simcenter STAR-CCM+. The objective was to minimize propeller thrust modeled using a virtual disk propeller method on the basis of propeller open-water results provided by the propeller manufacturer.

This section gives an overview of the CFD simulations. Details are given in *Ahmed (2022)* and *Harries et al. (2023)*. Starting with the numerical set-up and the appropriate choice of mesh size, a comparison is drawn with the available experimental data to validate the CFD simulations. In the end, the employed simplifications are presented which yield a good compromise between fast and reliable simulations.

3.1. CFD set-up

Simulating planing vessels using CFD is often challenging as it requires rather fine temporal and spatial discretization. This is due to the large dynamic change of heave (sinkage) and pitch (trim), resulting in large mesh motions, associated with the working principle of high-speed planing boats. To address this issue, an overset grid technique for the hull along with a free surface adaptive mesh refinement was used. Fig.6 illustrates the structured overset grid around the vessel, featuring prism layers near the wall to capture the boundary layer nicely. A wall value $y^+ \approx 70$ was chosen in conjunction with a wall function approach and a realizable $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model. All simulations were done at model-scale.

Total Number of Cells Overset Region: 790464

Fig.6: Structured overset mesh, including the hull geometry at an initial time step

The overset mesh is surrounded by a background mesh which moves along with the hull so that the overset mesh is always located at the center of the background domain. The mesh is gradually coarsened from the overset mesh to the outer regions of the background mesh. The overset algorithm allows transferring mesh motions between domains. With the grid coarsened in the regions that are far away from any mesh motion, a good compromise can be achieved between accuracy and speed. Fig.7 presents the overset mesh surrounded by parts of the background mesh. It also shows the results of adaptive mesh refinement (AMR).

The background domain uses a wave forcing approach to artificially dampen the wave motion near the outer boundaries of the domain. Alternative to the wave forcing approach would be to employ a very long mesh downstream of the vessel so as to reduce reflections from the outlets. Reflections would cause numerical instabilities in the solution. The wave forcing approach gives a reasonable size mesh with a much smaller number of cells in the background domain. Discretization strategies and numerical set-up are explained with many details in *Harries et al. (2023)* and can be summarized as follows:

- Symmetry is utilized along the centerline of the vessel, i.e., only half of the domain needs to be taken into account.
- A segregated fluid solver for incompressible fluids and a semi-implicit pressure linked equations scheme (SIMPLE) are employed.
- A Reynolds-Averaged-Navier-Stokes (RANS) based realizable k-epsilon model with wall function approach is chosen to account for turbulence.
- A volume-of-fluid (VOF) scheme to capture the free surface using a high-resolution interface capturing scheme (HRIC) is employed.
- VOF slip-velocity method as described in *Wheeler et al (2021)* is utilized to remove numerical ventilation.

Fig.7: Overset mesh and parts of the background mesh along with regions of mesh refinement

For any CFD set-up, a good choice of mesh size plays a significant role in getting reliable yet fast solutions. Grid convergence studies were undertaken by varying the total number of cells between 0.4 and 5.7 million. Due to the overset algorithm, the mesh sizes in the overset and background region are varied via a so-called “refinement ratio” R as described by *Xing and Stern (2010)*. Background and overset meshes are varied according to $L_{pp}/(5 \cdot R)$ and $L_{pp}/(100 \cdot R)$, respectively. Here L_{pp} is the length of the boat between perpendiculars at model-scale with 3.364m. R values are given in Table III. For the best compromise between computational cost and convergence of the solution Mesh 4 was selected.

Table III: Grid convergence history

Name	Base Size		Total # of cells	Time hours	Refinement ratio R	Heave cm	Pitch Deg	Drag N
	Back-ground M	Overset M						
Mesh 1	1.35	0.065	408676	1.22	1 / 2	10.581	4.9867	526.36
Mesh 2	0.95	0.050	831152	2.21	$\sqrt{2} / 2$	10.727	5.1095	569.42
Mesh 3	0.67	0.035	1755600	3.79	1	10.498	5.0044	535.57
Mesh 4	0.48	0.025	3661000	5.20	$\sqrt{2}$	10.667	5.1003	520.56
Mesh 5	0.40	0.020	5745000	10.2	2	10.679	5.1430	519.27

Grid Convergence Index (GCI) and Richardson extrapolation (Factor of Safety Method) given by *Xing and Stern (2010)* were utilized to quantify the uncertainty in the grid size. Mesh 3, 4 and 5 were taken for this analysis and both indices were found to be within 5%, with maximum deviation in pitch of about 4.6%. The grid uncertainty in drag and heave turned out to be less than 1% using both methods. For details, again, see *Harries et al. (2023)*.

3.2. Comparison to experiments

The numerical set-up as described in the previous section was used, to start with, to run resistance simulations in Simcenter STAR-CCM+. The simulations were performed at various speeds and compared against towing tank data available from experiments (EXP) conducted at the Technical University Berlin as one of AutoPlan’s partners. At the design speed of 27.5 knots, the resistance from CFD turned out to lie within 1% of EXP while the absolute difference in heave and pitch were 1.1 cm and 0.88°, respectively. In the simulations, drag is monitored as a horizontal force experienced by the vessel and the running attitude (pitch and heave) are calculated around the boat’s center of gravity (CoG) as given in Table I. To make a closer comparison of the simulations and experiments, the shaft and the bracket were added to the bare to reflect the experimental studies.

Table IV: Validation of resistance Tests against experiments

F_n	$F_{n\triangledown}$	F_{nB}	V	EXP			CFD		
				Heave	Pitch	Drag	Heave	Pitch	Drag
-	-	-	Kn	Cm	Deg	N	Cm	deg	N
0.26	0.49	0.46	5.29		0.28	80.91			
0.68	1.28	1.21	13.75		3.46	318.19	0.90	3.28	316.90
0.82	1.54	1.45	16.50		3.65	362.06	2.95	3.87	362.56
0.95	1.80	1.69	19.25		3.92	403.47	5.17	4.58	411.99
1.09	2.06	1.93	22.00		4.27	447.43	7.63	5.12	452.43
1.22	2.31	2.17	24.75		4.34	481.70	9.41	5.19	485.82
1.36	2.57	2.41	27.50	9.53	4.22	521.54	10.67	5.10	520.14
1.50	2.83	2.66	30.25		4.19	560.32	11.61	4.95	556.39

Table IV compares the values of the drag and running attitude for both experiments and simulations. Fig.8 shows the drag for various speeds. The numerical set-up was able to capture drag at different speeds within 1% of uncertainty against experimental data. However, the objective for design and optimization is taken as the propeller thrust. Hence, after comparing and validating various cases for resistance the studies were extended to validate a particular case of propulsion test, using body force propeller method, *Ahmed (2022)*.

3.3. Fast and acceptable simulations

A validated numerical set-up with an appropriate mesh size as presented above can be further extended to speed-up simulations further. It needs to be kept in mind that both optimizations and data generation for ROMs require running many CFD simulations to calculate the objective. In this section, the focus is therefore put on how to further decrease the turnaround time for each individual CFD simulation by introducing further simplifications and advanced numerical techniques. In doing so, a significant decrease in the computational time of overall optimization process could be realized.

The simplification steps involve removing the appendages, accepting a coarser mesh, and adapting the numerical set-up to accelerate convergence. In the context of optimization, the relative ranking of the designs for DoE has more importance than the actual (accurate) prediction of the objective for each variant. In principle, the idea is to find the best performing design out of many and to compare the relative improvement in the design performance against the baseline. To do so, two studies independent of the previously shown results were carried out and drag values are compared for a set of designs:

- The appendages add resistance, requiring additional thrust, without effecting the flow field drastically. In contrast, for a simulation it takes almost double the amount of time to resolve the appendages due to the fine mesh resolution needed. Thus, the appendages are omitted for the DoE. A visual comparison of the design rankings for this case is given in Fig.9. The results encourage to leave out any appendages for the majority of simulations. With the exception of designs 1 and 2 that lie very close other to each to begin with, the ranking is nicely maintained.

- The mesh size could be again coarsened, and Mesh 2 was taken instead of Mesh 4. Several arbitrarily chosen designs were tested using both meshes and the ranking with respect to the objective function is compared in Fig.10. Both meshes give the same ranking, thus Mesh 2 can be accepted for a large DoE.

Fig.8: Validation studies for the overall resistance at various speeds

Fig.9: Effect on the objective function (Thrust) for geometry with and without appendages

For the numerical set-up the following additional options were chosen:

- A dynamic overset grid with combination of adaptive mesh refinement and forcing zones.
- Implicit multi-step transient time steps for faster convergence in Simcenter STAR-CCM+.
- Sinusoidal ramp up of the velocity from rest position to design speed with larger time steps; observing a maximum acceleration of 1 g the ramp up time was 0.8 sec, the final design speed being 27.5 kn at full-scale and $V_M = 7.802$ m/s at mode-scale.
- An adaptive time-step to target Courant numbers up to 5 for the acceleration phase (reaching design speed from rest) and less than 0.5 for the steady-state during the final steps.
- Artificial damping of the motion of the vessel to reach steady state at shorter solution times, avoiding oscillations due to the acceleration of vessel.

By using these strategies, individual simulation time could be reduced from 8 h per variant to 2.5 h on a cluster with 32 cores and 80 GBs of RAM. With this set-up, many simulation-driven design campaigns were undertaken, *Harries et al. (2023)*. Despite the significantly reduced computational time for each CFD run, the generation of a DoE with valid 89 variants still took almost 250 h. The computational costs add up and, consequently, one should make good use of the data as much as possible.

Fig.10: Effect on the objective for Mesh 2 and Mesh 4

4. Machine learning (ML)

Using valuable simulation data from the Design of Experiment (DoE), a Reduced-Order Model (ROM) is trained which allows the real time prediction of new geometries, flow fields and scalar performance values. Typically, such a process is divided into a so-called offline and an online phase. During the offline phase, the required number of CFD solutions are computed and the ROM is created. This process may take a significant amount of time, depending on the use case, the number of CFD solutions and the grade of parallelization as described in the previous section. In the online phase, the ROM then provides predictions of the flow field for a previously unknown combination of parameters within a fraction of a second. This, naturally, offers a lot of benefits.

4.1. Design-of-Experiment (DoE)

The dataset at hand consists of 89 samples, generated using a Sobol sequence with 18 parameters. A Sobol sequence typically gives some advantages over a full factorial sampling. It requires a smaller sample size, achieves a more uniform coverage of the design space, is adaptable to different sampling strategies, and is less sensitive to input order compared to full factorial sampling. Furthermore, a Sobol sequence can be extended without compromising the quasi-random distribution of variants should additional data be needed. These advantages make it efficient and accurate for exploring design spaces in numerical simulations, experimental campaigns and for the training of machine learning models.

It is important to mention that the numerical set-up to simulate the flow field of a planing boat is quite different to a set-up for conventional vessels. For a displacement ship it typically contains a fixed domain with incoming fluid (2-DoF approach) while sinkage and trim are iteratively adjusted to capture the equilibrium. Here, for the planing boat, a moving overset mesh and a background domain (3-DoF approach) were chosen. Both domains move in horizontal direction in excess of 60 to 80 m, depending on the convergence history of the solution. Thus, before generating a Reduced-Order Model, an additional pre-processing step is needed: The different hulls and their associated flow fields have to be translated from their final solution at convergence to a common reference position to enable the mapping of the results onto a consistent visualization mesh.

4.2. Generation of a Reduced-Order Model (ROM)

Reduced-Order Models have evolved from being a niche area of research to becoming widely adopted tools in industry over the past few decades. These models, which analyze how quantities of interest change with parameter variations, provide invaluable insights in diverse fields of science and engineering, *Barber et al. (1996)*. Typically built on parameterized data from full-order models, such as CFD simulations for aero- and hydrodynamic problems, ROMs find applications in optimization,

uncertainty quantification, inverse design, data fusion, interactive data visualization, and as boundary conditions for accelerating CFD simulations, *Brink-Spalink et al. (2001)*, *van der Maaten et al. (2009)*, *Han et al. (2012)*.

In the application presented here, the chosen order reduction method for CFD solutions is proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), *Barrault et al. (2004)*, also known as principal component analysis (PCA), *Narayanan et al. (2010)*.

Coupled with an interpolation method for modeling the ROM coefficients (ROM+I), this approach enables CFD predictions for desired parameter combinations, opening avenues for diverse applications. Common interpolation models used include radial basis functions (RBF), *Bui-Thanh et al. (2003)*, and Kriging, *Brooks et al. (2017)*. Furthermore, here a surrogate model (Kriging) is incorporated to predict scalar output values, such as thrust, drag, or pitch, which subsequently serve as key performance indicators.

4.3. Validation of the ROM

For the validation of the prediction, it is strongly recommended to use “unseen” data which is not involved in the training phase of the model at all. It is possible – and often done – to just leave one simulation out of the training and then predict it from the model. This is the so-called “Leave One Out Cross Validation.” However, here the complete Design-of-Experiment was utilized for the training and several new variants were subsequently simulated for evaluation, using the same numerical set-up as described in section 3.

These new samples were not randomly chosen; but could have been of course. Instead, they represent interesting design scenarios which will be discussed in more detail in section 5. In this way, the new variants not only allow validation but also serve to showcase nice ways to benefit from the ROM during interactive design processes without any need to launch (and wait) for further CFD simulations.

5. Application of the Reduced-Order Model (ROM)

Maritime engineering projects involve complex design considerations that require coordination between different disciplines such as hydrostatics and stability, hydrodynamics and power consumption, structural engineering and safety and economics. Traditional design processes often involve delays in decision making due to time consuming serial iterations and challenges in integrating inputs from various disciplines. This can be overcome by surrogates within design synthesis, enabling to run comprehensive simulation-driven design campaigns, e.g., *Harries et al. (2019)*, *Papanikolaou et al. (2020)*.

However, if the simulation data is additionally used to train a Reduced-Order Model, this bears the potential to speed-up design processes by even facilitating interactive design between different disciplines. Fast and accurate predictions of flow fields and geometries enable rapid decision making interactively without any need to postpone to the next meeting, allowing for many iterations on the fly. These capabilities of machine learning models can result in more efficient and optimized product designs, leading to improved performance, safety, and sustainability of maritime assets. Instead of utilizing series data in a conventional way by just getting two or three outputs, say for resistance and propulsion, for a handful of inputs, design teams can produce their own series and then retrieve both numerical and visual results interactively.

5.1. Optimization based on ML-model (ROM + Surrogate)

For the sake of argument, the resulting ML-model from the DoE was employed to optimize the planing boat within the following design scenarios:

- Generate the hull with minimum thrust at 27.5 kn,

- Generate the hull with minimum thrust but with a moderate pitch angle lower than 3.5° (treated as an inequality constraint),
- Generate the hull that yields minimum wave height 1m off the boat’s center plane (at model-scale, corresponding to 3.29 m at full-scale).

In addition, some unusual configurations were also considered to understand the behavior at further extrema:

- Generate the hull that needs maximum thrust (this, naturally, is not a common design request),
- Generate the hull that yields maximum heave.

Finally, a design optimized for lowest thrust at 27.5 kn within a classic SDD campaign was chosen to compare results with. It is the so-called “5th optimized design” described in *Harries et al. (2023)*.

To find the above-mentioned scenarios, a Kriging model was used that correlates the input parameters with the scalar results, adopting the workflow depicted in Fig.11. Since the optimization on the target variables takes place exclusively on the ML-model, it is possible to use a constrained differential evolution algorithm with very many evaluations. The optimization of one configuration and the subsequent flow field prediction only takes about one to two seconds. Consequently, the user – be it a naval architect, a structural engineer, a designer or the future owner – receives the full two-phase solution including flow fields, scalars and the corresponding geometry instantaneously.

Fig.11: Schematic workflow for the model usage

Table V: Scalar predictions

Objective	Thrust (CFD)	Thrust (Prediction)	Deviation for thrust	Heave (CFD)	Heave (Prediction)	Pitch (CFD)	Pitch (Prediction)
Min thrust	393.4	399.8	1.63%	0.104	0.116	-4.5	-4.5
Max thrust	525.2	526.4	0.23%	0.064	0.049	-2.3	-2.2
Min thrust at a moderate pitch angle	422.0	427.0	1.18%	0.083	0.094	-3.4	-3.5
Max heave	441.8	418.8	-5.21%	0.111	0.129	-4.8	-4.6
Min wave	514.2	501.0	-2.57%	0.065	0.063	-2.4	-2.6
5 th opt. design	390.4	388.8	-0.41%	0.102	0.107	-4.2	-4.5

In Table V, the prediction of the scalar quantities is compared with the simulation result for each of the selected configurations. Although there are slight deviations, the predictions for thrust, heave and pitch are very close to each other. For thrust the maximum error is 5.2% of the results from the corresponding CFD simulations. For the prediction of the 5th optimized design taken from *Harries et al (2023)*, the

values, especially for the thrust, are nearly identical with an error below 1%. Note that none of the designs formed part of the DoE and of the building of the ML-model.

5.2. Evaluation of the prediction quality for unseen data

Figs.12 and 13 compare wave patterns for the configurations with minimum and maximum thrust.

Fig.12: Wave fields for the prediction from the ML-model (upper part) and the corresponding CFD simulation (lower part) for the boat giving minimum thrust

Fig.13: Wave fields for the prediction from the ML-model (upper part) and the corresponding CFD simulation (lower part) for the boat needing maximum thrust

Both show good agreement between CFD simulations and ROM predictions aft of the boat. The deviations at the bow are caused by the complex CFD set-up which maps running attitude in the domain via a dynamic mesh with several overset regions. However, the overset region near the bow was not included in the training of the ML-model, which was exclusively trained on the coarser background mesh.

By comparing the wave cuts at a transversal position of 1m away from the hull’s center plane (measured at model-scale), a good agreement between prediction and actual CFD results can be observed, see Fig.14. It depicts the prediction of the volume field, represented by an isoline for the volume fraction of air at 0.5. Note that the wave cuts are scaled twenty times in vertical direction for better visibility.

Furthermore, the Reduced-Order Model demonstrates a high level of accuracy in predicting field values like the dynamic pressure on the hull’s wetted surface. This is shown in Fig.15 for the boat giving minimum thrust. The propulsion system (not shown in Fig.15) and the resulting trim and rise create complex pressure distributions that are very well captured and represented by the ML-model. Again, the field values did not form part of the ROM but, instead, are pure predictions.

Fig.14: CFD simulation (wave cut in black) and prediction from the ML-model (wave cut in red) for the waves generated by the boat giving minimum thrust (wave cuts scaled vertically by 20)

Fig.15: Dynamic pressure on hull for the prediction from the ML-model and CFD simulation for the boat giving minimum thrust

5.3. Interactive design work

Optimizing for a single objective is not always practical since real-world situations often require finding compromises. Thus, understanding which of the free variables influence performance the most becomes advantageous when multiple requirements need to be met. This information can provide a decisive benefit when identifying trade-offs.

These sensitivities are inherent in the model and can be studied for all input parameters as shown in Fig.16. For the pilot boat, two parameters were particularly crucial for the thrust, showing by far the largest impact. They are followed by another two parameters that have tangible influence. Conversely, many parameters do not change the thrust so much, offering flexibility to the designers in meeting additional requirements without causing significant increase of the required thrust.

Fig.17 illustrates sensitivities for thrust on the hull of boat. Working with these sensitivities by modifying the hull shape interactively is also a viable option. The sensitivities on the surface in Fig.17 can be interpreted as follows:

- **Blue** regions: If you push the shape of the hull inwards, normal to the surface, the required thrust decreases.
- **Red** regions: Vice versa, if you pull the shape of the hull outwards, again normal to the surface, the required thrust increases.

It should be noted that these sensitivities correspond to sensitivities that an adjoint simulation would produce, albeit at the cost of only one additional adjoint simulation once the CFD results for the baseline are available, *Harries and Abt (2019)* for an elaboration of adjoints. Meanwhile, here the ROM was fed with the simulations of a comprehensive DoE. Still, this brings about additional insight at practically no extra cost and without the need of an adjoint solver.

Fig.16: Parameter sensitivities with regard to the thrust

Fig.17: Surface sensitivity regarding the thrust as an objective (**blue** regions: push inward to lower required thrust, **red** regions: pull outward for lower thrust)

6. Conclusions and outlook

Parametric modeling, CFD simulations, Design-of-Experiment and machine learning are presented for the design of a planing boat. Based on high-fidelity CFD simulations using Simcenter STAR-CCM+, a significant number of variants were analyzed. The high quality of the CFD was validated by means of comparisons to experimental data. The variants were generated by running a Sobol sequence for a set of 18 geometric parameters that control the hull shape as modeled within CAESES®. 89 variants were utilized that reflect quasi-random changes to the bare hull and the tunnel. The parameters, the resulting shapes, their corresponding flow fields along with integral results such as the thrust required to run each of the variants at 27.5kn were utilized to build a Reduced-Order Model with NAVPACK.

Several new designs were generated by applying the ROM. These designs are representative of meaningful design situations. They also served to judge the quality of the ROM. For thrust differences between predictions and CFD simulations range within $\pm 5.2\%$ of the CFD results taken as the benchmark. Thrust as the driver for the optimization of the pilot boat was predicted from the ROM with an error of about -0.4% when studied for an optimized design that had been previously identified within a sophisticated SDD campaign. Moreover, it turns out that there are very nice correlations for wave fields and pressure field, too. Keeping in mind that optimizations often lie at some of the bounds of the free variables and that 89 variants is not a very large set of variants for an 18-dimensional design space to begin with, these are believed to be very encouraging results.

Two scenarios of interactive work are proposed: One, in which an optimization is triggered that returns a variant for a flexibly formulated task within minutes and without need for additional simulations. Another, in which interactive design work is supported by showing the parameters that have the highest influence and by displaying sensitivities that guide a design team in its options to modify the hull without sacrificing performance or with the aim of making it even better. These constitute rapid design processes and excellent new ways to benefit from CFD.

The computational cost associated with any large-scaled investigation is significant. This is naturally regarded as a limitation. Machine Learning (ML) based optimization such as Reduced-Order Modeling (ROMs) and surrogates to calculate the objectives can help to distribute such an investment over many projects and over the years. The models can be trained based on available results from previous DoE but also from dedicated numerical series deliberately set up by a design team upfront for the purpose of harvesting the data when needed and when working under time pressure.

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Enable the Best Shipbuilding Toolset

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Abstract

IT tools for CAD and PLM have been firmly established in the shipbuilding process for some time. Without them, it would be impossible to deliver the size and complexity of today's ships within a reasonable time and budget. When selecting IT tools, various factors such as capabilities, costs, or even yard preferences should be considered. Furthermore, it should be clarified whether choosing a toolset from one vendor or a selection of tools from multiple vendors is beneficial. This paper presents the two approaches with their advantages and disadvantages and discusses how the integration between different tools influences this decision.

1. Introduction

Ships are complex and one-of-a-kind products, made from hundreds of thousands to millions of parts and components. This requires a wide range of disciplines, such as naval architecture, electrical engineering, or mechanical engineering to work together. But also, more general disciplines such as purchasing or project management are not to be neglected. As a result, the development and production process is equally, if not more, complex than the ship itself. Even sister ships do not facilitate this process, as their designs may differ and are usually manufactured under different conditions. To cope with this complexity and effort, IT tools have become a crucial part of the shipbuilding process. In this regard, a critical capability for shipyards is to create highly integrated and simultaneous cross-discipline designs in order to be competitive. To meet this requirement, it is of great importance to choose the right toolset. Furthermore, the choice of the right tools has a great impact on the effort required to design and manufacture a ship, the flexibility in case of changes, and the time required to manage the entire process.

This leaves us with the question, of how to choose the right tools for a shipyard with all the choices on the market today? And how to make sure they are working together as a toolset? This paper focuses on different aspects of finding the right tool and presents two approaches to enable the best toolset.

2. Choosing tools

Fig.1: Example of factors, that influence choosing a tool

To find the most suitable tool, several aspects should be taken into consideration, Fig.1. First, it should be clear which use cases need to be covered by the tool. In most companies, the tools can be divided into three basic capabilities. There are authoring tools where data and information are generated. In shipbuilding, these often are specialised CAx applications for the ship hull, outfitting, mechanical or electrical design. Another class of tools is PDM / PLM systems where capabilities such as CAx data management, document management, various PLM processes, and the E-BOM can be mapped. Furthermore, there are ERP systems with which capabilities such as master data management, material management, finance accounting or manufacturing resource planning. To summarize, tools can be used by single or multiple domains and during single or multiple phases of the shipbuilding process, *Grau et al. (2019)*. Also, a tool can be used in a dedicated phase of the ship development process or in multiple phases. Fig.2 shows an outline as an example of how various tools could be used in the ship design process by the different departments.

For all these different tools it is important to define the exact requirements and use cases, that they could fulfil. By knowing exactly the requirements of the tool, it is possible to effectively find the tool that is best suited for the shipyard. In practice, when choosing a tool, all the requirements are rarely known in detail. However, efforts can be made to determine them as accurately as possible.

Fig.2: Different tool types during the ship development process

Another factor is to estimate how high the total cost of ownership is. Therefore, various aspects must be taken into account. One of the aspects is whether the system is purchased once, or a subscription model is offered by the vendor. Also, the license model must be factored in and must fit the use cases and the company. Furthermore, all implementation and customizing efforts must be considered.

One critical decision is the vendor of the tool. Size and market position can play a role when assessing whether the vendor can and will provide the software in the long term. Furthermore, it should be investigated on which customers and industries the vendor is focused and if this matches the shipyard. Generally, it is always positive if the vendor can already show successful references in the industry.

As the digital continuity and traceability of data get more important in industries, also the compatibility of tools is an essential factor to consider. There are two different approaches to dealing with this matter to form a compatible toolset, *Grau et al. (2019)*:

- Best-of-suite approach. Purchase all tools from the same vendor because they provide support for all design phases and a seamless data model.
- Best-of-breed approach. Purchase the best tool available on the market for a certain task, knowing that the integration with the surrounding it-tools needs to be implemented.

2.1 Best-of-suite Approach

Purchasing all tools from the same vendor has some main benefits. First of all, the vendor promises to provide an integrated tool suite that has all interfaces already implemented. Use Cases, like handing over data between different tools or from one design phase to another, should work out-of-the-box. If an integration problem appears, the expectation is that it is solved by the vendor sooner or later. Also, by using one common design process, data model, product structure, geometry, and metadata (weight, planning data, ...) during the whole shipbuilding process the effort in design and management can be reduced. At the same time, this is the foundation for always having a correct database of design data. These capabilities enable cross-discipline use cases to also work out-of-the-box and more efficiently.

If this approach is preferred, the choice lies with one of the major vendors, who provide tools for different capabilities and requirements. Therefore, not all tools fit perfectly for all required use cases. This can result in the need to customize tools and the hazard of obstructing the standard interface and function.

Even if all internal interfaces are provided by the system and the vendor, interfaces for collaboration partners still need to be created. Which is a core requirement for a successful shipyard today. For example, in an interview with PROSTEP AG in 2017, Dr. Jan Meyer (CEO Meyer Werft) explained that Meyer Werft purchases between 75 and 85%, of the added value from suppliers of turnkey packages and services, *Wendenburg (2017)*. This requires intensive collaboration, and it is not possible to get all parties to use the same systems.

2.2 Best-of-breed Approach

The best-of-breed approach is the other way around. The best tools available on the market for a certain task are chosen, knowing that the integration with the other tools in the system architecture needs to be implemented. This gives the opportunity to select tools, that perfectly support use cases, which can only be found in each specific department.

There are additional advantages to using individual tools. It enables more independent handling of the tools, e.g. to keep up with the development progress of one tool without having to update other tools as well. Another important aspect is the possibility to select tools more easily and to avoid (costly) "vendor lock-in" situations. One gets the opportunity to choose cheaper tools, although the cost factor for integration is not negligible.

All in all, this approach enables to choose the toolsets more freely and fitted to the shipyard's needs. Otherwise, it requires implementing several tool-to-tool interfaces, to have a toolset that can handle multi-tool and multi-discipline use cases. However, integrations can never be completely avoided. Therefore, it makes sense for a company to build up its own integration competencies in-house anyway.

2.3 Interfaces

To take the flexibility of a best-of-breed approach, it is therefore important to understand the requirements to create or rethink solutions for the new or existing integration use cases. To avoid failure, it is therefore advisable to first analyse the situation in detail. For starters, analysing the information flow in the scope can identify the business objects and information that need to be transferred from one tool to another. This analysis can also be used to determine the frequency and amount of data required to be exchanged. This aspect influences if an interface needs to be automated and the effort of implementation. For example, with a daily transfer of thousands of parts, a pure manual solution is unreliable and will become too costly in the long run.

Once these factors have been determined, the tools that need to be connected can be identified. In some cases, this may be more difficult than expected, as the information needed to run the interface may be distributed across multiple sources. Once the sources of information have been identified, it is necessary to decide in which direction the transfer will occur. There are three different possibilities for the transfer. First of all, there are transfers in which the information must be transferred only in one direction. Other

use cases require that data is transferred back and forth. Then a bidirectional interface is needed. The third option are use cases where the data being transferred back and forth is so different that it is easier to process it as two separate unidirectional interfaces.

The next aspect to consider with an interface is the level of detail that is required for the data to be transferred. This generally results in four different levels of data transfers in shipbuilding, Fig.3. These differ in the semantics and also the effort of implementation, *Bitomsky et al. (2022)*.

Fig.3: Integration levels in shipbuilding, *Bitomsky et al. (2022)*

2.4.1 Level 0 - Database Tables & Records

Level 0 focuses only on transferring simple metadata like numerical and text attributes in tables or records from a source to a target tool. Usually, this level contains a low degree of semantics, but typically a fairly large number of data records.

2.4.2 Level 1 – Attributes and Structure

In Level 1, the product structure is transferred additionally to metadata to a target tool. This level is often found in the interface from design tools to ERP or MES. An example of transferring metadata is integrating AVEVA Marine with HEXAGON SPx. As a design tool AVEVA Marine is used for the detailed design and the organization of the production-related items is done in HEXAGON SPx. From the as-designed bill of materials created in AVEVA, it is possible to organize an as-planned bill of material and associated work orders in the MES system HEXAGON SPx. Most tools provide an out-of-the-box interfaces for use cases like this. Therefore, the challenge is to achieve the desired level of automation.

2.4.3 Level 2 – Geometry Representation

Level 2 integration adds geometry representations to the transfer. These geometry representations do not contain the full set of 3D information, e.g. the type and parameters of cut-outs applied on a plate,

but only its final geometrical shape. It is quite common in shipbuilding to use at least two different CAD systems for different design disciplines for example different tools are used for shipbuilding steel and outfitting design. When it comes to inter-domain exchange, most of the time it is an event-driven exchange of updates of geometry as well as metadata between two systems. This provides for instance both steel and equipment designers with the complete reference geometry and metadata of the opposite disciplines. It allows to perform clash analysis in their tool and to use normal change management as parts can be identified based on the available metadata.

We implemented such a solution at a customer who uses 3DEXPERIENCE from Dassault Systèmes for steel, deck outfitting, and architectural design together with CADMATIC for routing disciplines like piping, HVAC and cable trays. This use case has usually quite imposing magnitude of transfers. Today’s designs for example cruise ships easily contain millions of parts and the transfer of outfitting parts for reference purposes into the steel structure involves about 2.5 million parts (and vice versa). The design process depends on up-to-date reference data, so this process must be closely monitored to ensure that no collisions occur, *Grau et al. (2019)*.

2.4.4 Level 3 – Native Model Data

The most complex level is the transfer of the native data model. Here, the goal is to achieve a data quality when transferring the data into the target system as if the data had been created there in the first place. To perform this, it requires a high level of know-how about both tools involved in the transfer. The alternative to this transfer is to redesign the model or use inaccurate geometries.

This occurs for example if an early 3D hull design model hull surface is handed over from a tool like NAPA Designer which is used for stability calculation to a steel design tool like AVEVA Marine. As a result, it is possible to proceed seamlessly with the basic and detailed design in AVEVA Marine based on the design carried out in NAPA Steel. To be able to reach the desired quality of data, the complete steel model is exported from NAPA. This includes both the geometry and metadata as well as topology information, *Grau et al. (2019)*.

Fig.4: Result of a native data model transfer, *Grau et al. (2019)*

3. Observed Market Situation

Over the past 10 years, we as PROSTEP AG have been able to make various observations regarding the shipbuilding market. The major challenge facing shipyards and their suppliers is the efficient provision and continuous use of information in all phases of the ship's lifecycle, from development to production and ongoing operation. To address this, the shipyards had different strategies.

For example, Damen Shipyard Group started using the best-of-suite approach in 2016 by further establishing the 3DEXPERIENCE platform from Dassault Systèmes in the company. For every new ship, the "single source of truth" should be available for all stakeholders, *Dassault Systèmes (2020)*.

The Meyer Group, on the other hand, has decided in favour of a multi-CAD strategy as part of the harmonization of the heterogeneous IT system landscapes at the various shipyard locations, and therefore also in the best-of-breed approach. At all yards, the hull and architectural areas are modelled using CAD system CATIA V6, while the shipbuilding-specific CAD system from CADMATIC OY is used for the mechanical engineering equipment. This created an interface between two CAD systems where native data must be synchronized on a regular basis. This project is supported by PROSTEP AG. *Grau (2018)* In an interview with PROSTEP AG in 2017, Dr. Jan Meyer (CEO Meyer Werft) explained that they need to be multi-CAD capable in order to migrate to a more modern and homogeneous CAD/PLM environment. Multi-CAD capability is of strategic importance for their future CAD/PLM architecture because they also need to integrate their supplier base with their heterogeneous CAD environments, *Wendenburg (2017)*.

Also, other shipyards were able to significantly shorten their engineering time by opening up to other CAD or PDM systems and following a best-of-breed approach.

Furthermore, an increased focus on digital continuity and the associated interface problem can also be observed among vendors. On one hand smaller vendors that only cover one basic capability have joined forces. For example, CADMATIC and CONTACT Software just released their cooperation a few months ago. With this partnership, the aim is to provide shipyards with optimum support for digitization along the entire lifecycle of shipbuilding projects in the future from design and engineering, through prefabrication and production, to maintenance and operation, *CONTACT Software (2023)*. Also, AVEVA and ARAS announced their collaboration in 2022, *AVEVA Solutions (2022)*. On the other hand, large vendors expand their capabilities by buying other solutions. For example, Siemens Digital Industries Software has expanded its capabilities in marine design and engineering with the purchase of FORAN marine design in 2021, *Siemens Digital Industries Software (2021)*. This means that Siemens has a wider choice of tools for shipbuilding and can offer more when choosing the best-of-suit approach.

4. Conclusion

There are several factors to consider when determining the best shipbuilding toolset for a yard. It is always an individual decision that cannot simply be transferred. In principle, the better the use cases and framework conditions are known, the more suitable the tool can be chosen. One of the major choices that should be made is whether to choose the best-of-suit or the best-of-breed approach. In any case, thought must be given to interfaces. In the best-of-suit approach, this mainly concerns interfaces to partners. In the best-of-breed approach, it is an essential part of making the toolset efficient and reliable. When faced with these interfaces there are different integration levels to consider, which vary in terms of complexity and realization effort.

We are always supporting shipyards by dealing with integration use cases to enable the best toolset for them. That's why we not only providing bespoke solutions for the shipbuilding industry, but we are also increasing our range of tailored solutions. PROSTEP's digital enterprise platform OpenPDM Ship provides integration made from standard products. We support a whole range of PLM (e.g. ARAS, Enovia, Teamcenter, etc.) or ERP systems (e.g. IFS, SAP, etc.) in addition to shipbuilding specific CAD systems. Those are also bases for native level integration for systems like AVEVA Marine, CADMATIC, or NAPA. To connect the various systems to OpenPDM, connectors are available as maintained standard product components. Each connector provides read and write access to the connected system using interfaces provided by the system vendors. On their backside, all connectors share a common interface to provide PLM data into the OpenPDM platform in a normalized format while maintaining the proprietary data semantics.

Fig.5: OpenPDM Ship, Bitomsky et al. (2022)

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Elevating Maritime Design to a Higher Level with Advanced Engineering Simulation

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Abstract

Engineering simulation is emerging as the new global tendency in Maritime as the human impact on the environment is the latest challenge of all industry. Computer Aided Engineering is already established in other industries as it facilitates research and innovation while reducing the cost of the overall product cycle. Starting from basic analyses like static, durability and fatigue, underwater vibrations and water resistance reduction, to design optimization, simulation engineering can improve the efficiency and structural strength of the final product. This study shows a use case of ship industry CAE applications in various stages of the product development.

1. Introduction

According to statistical reports the global offshore wind turbine (OWT) installation capacity reached 54.3 GW by the end of 2021, while it needs to be increased significantly by 2050 in order to achieve net zero. However, an overall environmental impact of wind energy exists, even though is miniscule in comparison to fossil-fuel energy. Hence, it is imperative to investigate the damage mechanisms and ensure the lifecycle of the offshore wind turbines with improved efficiency, by utilizing advanced engineering simulations.

This study focuses on a 5MW wind turbine supported by a monopile and its structural performance under various sea state loading in a fatigue analysis. In general, the OWTs are subjected to wind and wave loading, with wave loading being the dominant source of extreme loads for the structure. Even though the wind loading could be ignored, the performance of the structure will be examined under both wave and wind loads in this study. The loads are calculated based on available meteorological data of a site and assumed to be in the same direction as a likely worst case scenario.

The OWT is modelled with ANSA pre-processor to generate a structural and CFD mesh for further analysis. The fluid analysis is performed with ANSYS Fluent to extract the pressure loads of each sea state. The resultant pressures are then applied to the structural model to run a static analysis and retrieve the stresses induced by the wave and wind loading. EPILYSIS solver is used for the static analysis, while the stress induced by the structural vibrations of the environmental variables is processed with META post-processor.

Finally, a fatigue analysis is performed for a set of sea states according to their probability of occurrence, to estimate the fatigue damage. The damage is mainly driven by the bending stresses caused by the vibrations due to wind and wave loads, during the service life of the OWT in non-operational condition. The fatigue analysis is performed with the FATIQ tool of the BETA CAE software suite.

1.1. Model configuration

The model is based on the 5-MW NREL offshore wind turbine mounted on a monopile, installed in 20 m water depth. The nacelle of the considered turbine has a mass of 240,000 kg, while the total mass of the rotor and blades is 107,000 kg. The rotor, wind turbine blades and nacelle are modelled as a lumped mass of 347,000 kg. The tower and monopile are modelled as being made from a medium grade structural steel with Young's modulus of 210 GPa, yield stress of 385 MPa and density of 8500

kg/m³. The density value is increased above steel's typical value of 7850 kg/m³ to account for paint, bolts, welds, and flanges that are not accounted for in the tower thickness data. The monopile is fixed to the mudline ignoring the soil-structure interaction.

2. Modelling

2.1. Geometry handling

CAD data are imported in ANSA as neutral files (.step), Fig.1. The geometry of the model is checked, and existing topological errors are automatically identified and fixed. Additional information of the CAD data such as materials, thicknesses, model hierarchy, scanting information etc. are extracted from an .xml file of the CAD model.

Fig.1: Imported geometry

2.2. Mesh representations generation

FE representation of the model is needed for both structural and CFD analysis. The process is automatic and performed by a special tool, the Batch Mesh Manager tool of ANSA. The mesh characteristics and quality criteria are predefined for each part of each model, depending on the type of the solution. In order to generate a good quality mesh, free of violating elements, limit values are defined according to various solver criteria.

All settings (mesh parameters and quality criteria) within the tool define a meshing scenario that can be saved and reused for different models. Each scenario can apply different mesh parameters on different parts of the model.

Details such as holes and flanges handling are specifically defined according to the specifications of the analysis.

2.2.1. Structural mesh

The rotor, blades and nacelle are represented by a lumped mass and therefore excluded from the meshing process, Fig.2.

Fig.2: FE representation of the rotor, blades and nacelle

The tower and the monopile are meshed with a uniform element length, Fig.3, at first and then the monopile, up to the airtight deck, is refined for extra accuracy of the results, Fig.4. The mesh parameters and quality criteria of the coarse mesh are presented in Table I, while the ones of the finer mesh of the monopile, in Table II.

Fig.3: Uniform coarse mesh

Fig.4: Monopile mesh refinement

Table I: Coarse Mesh settings

Mesh Parameters	
Elements type	First order quads
Global Element Length	0.35 [m]
Quality Criteria	
Skewness (Nastran)	30
Aspect ratio (Nastran)	3
Warping (IDEAS)	10

Table II: Monopile Fine Mesh settings

Mesh Parameters	
Elements type	First order quads
Local Element Length	0.13 [m]
Quality Criteria	
Skewness (Nastran)	30
Aspect ratio (Nastran)	3
Warping (IDEAS)	10

By running the meshing scenario, the mesh is automatically created and quality improvement is applied to fulfil the pre-defined quality criteria.

2.2.2. CFD mesh

The CFD mesh is also generated with the Batch Mesh Manager tool. The boundary layers are created around the structure's model and around the sea surface, towards the seabed and sky, Fig.5. The mesh

settings of the CFD surface mesh are presented in Table III, the CFD volume mesh settings in Table IV and the ones of the Layers in Table V. The quality criteria of the volume mesh are applied also to the layers.

Fig.5: CFD mesh

Table III: CFD surface mesh settings

Mesh Parameters	
Elements type	First order tria
Growth rate	1.2
Maximum length	5 [m]
Quality Criteria	
Skewness (FLUENT)	0.5
Warping (IDEAS)	20

Table IV: CFD volume mesh settings

Mesh Parameters	
Elements type	Tetra rapid
Maximum growth rate	1.2
Maximum length	5 [m]
Max. skewness	0.9
Quality Criteria	
Skewness (FLUENT)	0.92
Warping (IDEAS)	70
Max angle pentas(FLUENT)	0.92
Max angle hexas(FLUENT)	0.92
Minimum volume	1.E-17
Growth ratio(ANSA)	50

Table V: CFD layer settings

Layer Parameters		
First height	0.1	Absolute Y+
Growth factor	1.2	constant
Number of layers	15	
Quality criterion		
Layers quality		1.01

3. FEA Analyses

3.1. Wind and Wave loading

Wind and wave loading of the model are based on environmental data at the Fuhai area of Taiwan. The probability distribution against significant wave height is assumed to be a truncated normal distribution. The wind range investigated is 0-5 m/s, while data of other wind ranges are not taken into account. The significant height of the waves varies from 0.5-3.5 m. Table VI presents the various sea states and their probability distribution. Due to lack of information on wave direction, these conditions are set as unidirectional, aligned with the orientation of the foundation. This simplification is based on the notion that the load facing normally the model usually imposes the largest amount of energy on the structure and is considered the essential load case in preliminary design.

Table VI: Sea states for wind speed 5m/s

Sea State	U_w [m/s]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	Prob.%
1	5	0.5	6	63.7
2	5	1	6	26.0
3	5	1.5	6	7.5
4	5	2	6	1.6
5	5	2.5	6	0.8
6	5	3	6	0.2
7	5	3.5	6	0.2

3.2. CFD analysis

The model with the CFD mesh representation is solved with ANSYS Fluent for various sea states as described in section 3.1. The method followed is the Volume of Fluid method, using the boundary conditions of open channel. The standard k- ω turbulence model is used with standard Wall functions. The analysis is considered as transient with a timestep of 0.5 s and a total of 3000 timesteps. ANSYS Fluent calculates the gauge pressure, while the atmospheric pressure is added to extract the absolute pressure, later on used as loading for the static analysis. Since the simulation is transient, the maximum pressure of the last 200 timesteps is selected in order to examine the worst case scenario. Representative pressure results of sea state 3 are shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6: Relative static pressure on model in [Pa]

3.3. Static analysis

3.3.1. Mapping wind and wave loads

The pressure loads induced by the wind and wave for each sea state, are mapped on the structural model to calculate the stresses on the monopile automatically with the map tool of ANSA. The analysis is divided into eight subcases; one for the calm sea state and one for each sea state with wind. The calm sea state is considered the initial state of the model. The loads applied on the monopile walls of this state are the external and internal pressure from the sea water, Fig.7. These loads are created automatically in ANSA by specialized tools. The internal loads are created by identifying closed volumes and applying pressure of a liquid with the provided properties up to a selected level. The tool for the calculation of the external loads takes into account the mean sea level, the mudline and the properties of the sea water.

Fig.7: Calm sea state loads

The mapping tool is then utilized to map the pressure loads of the sea states, as calculated from the CFD analysis, on the structural mesh, Fig.8. The pressure varies from ~1-3 bar for all seven sea states.

Fig.8: Mapped pressure (MPa) for H_s (i) 0.5 m, (ii) 1 m, (iii) 1.5 m, (iv) 2m, (v) 2.5 m, (vi) 3 m, (vii) 3.5 m

The mapped pressure of all states is converted to pressure loads according to EPILYSIS keywords, in order to setup the subcases for the structural analysis automatically, Fig.9. The boundary condition of the model is the fixed end of the monopile at the mudline (Figure 10) while the rest of the model can move freely.

Fig.9: Pressure loads on monopile

Fig.10: Monopile fixed end mesh (left) with SPC1s (right)

Fig.11: Mapped pressure (MPa) for H_s (i) 0 m, (ii) 0.5 m, (iii) 1 m, (iv) 1.5 m, (v) 2 m, (vi) 2.5 m, (vii) 3 m, (viii) 3.5 m

3.3.2. Static analysis results

The model was solved with EPILYSIS version 23.1.0. The results are presented in META post-processor. The maximum Von Mises stresses developed on the model are located mainly on the monopile region and are lower than the yield stress of steel. High stress concentrations occur near the fixed end. The stress distribution is shown in Fig.11. The maximum displacement of the tower does not exceed 0.5°.

3.4. Fatigue analysis

The structural analysis ensures the structural integrity of the model under various loading conditions while these are considered constant. However, failure may still occur due to material fatigue, during the service life of an OWT, since the wind and wave loads are periodic phenomena. Consequently, fatigue analysis is performed in time domain with the FATIQ tool of the BETA CAE software suite to investigate the damage of the structure.

The resultant stresses from the static analysis are the fatigue analysis input. The material of the model is S355 steel with a yield stress of 385 MPa, ultimate strength of 490 MPa, according to the thicknesses of the parts, while the fatigue strength coefficient is 952.2 MPa and the fatigue strength exponent -0.089. Fatigue events are created to represent the oscillating loads caused by the wind and waves. Each event alters the pressure on the monopile from the calm sea state to the maximum of the relative wave. The cycles of each event are determined according to the probability of each wave's occurrence. Fatigue life is calculated using the Rainflow algorithm which reveals weak areas of the structure over the years. The fatigue damage for each sea state is presented in Table VII, while the total damage of the sea states for a wind speed of 5m/s is 1.24×10^{-5} . Fig.12 shows the fatigue results for each sea state as plotted in the FATIQ tool.

Table VII: Fatigue damage for each sea state

Sea State	U_w [m/s]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	Damage
1	5	0.5	6	9.39×10^{-6}
2	5	1	6	1.85×10^{-6}
3	5	1.5	6	4.08×10^{-7}
4	5	2	6	4.9×10^{-9}
5	5	2.5	6	1.12×10^{-8}
6	5	3	6	3.23×10^{-8}
7	5	3.5	6	7.3×10^{-7}

Fig.12: Fatigue results in FATIQ

4. Future work

The accuracy of the calculated fatigue damage can be further improved when considering more sea states and fewer simplifications. The environmental data of the site include information on more sea states with wind speed up to 25m/s. Even though the extreme wind and wave conditions probability is very low, they should be taken into account to conclude to more accurate results on the structure's fatigue damage. Furthermore, multi-directional and wind-wave misalignment load cases should be evaluated. Additionally, including the rotating blades in the CFD analysis to predict the drag forces and the air flow around the tower area could be considered to improve the accuracy of the load distribution.

Moreover, the monopile-soil interaction has a great effect on the fatigue life of offshore wind turbines as it contributes to the structure's damping, which is mostly comprised of aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, structural and soil damping, in addition to dampers installed in the tower. Soil damping is more important in parked/non-operational conditions, while it has been found to influence greatly the OWT fatigue life and therefore, should also be investigated.

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A Decoupled Approach to AI-based Design and Optimization of the Delft Systematic Yacht Hull Series

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Abstract

Current strategies for hull resistance optimization involve parametrizing a series of geometries; surrogating the relationship between parameters and resistance from Experimental Fluid Dynamics (EFD) or Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD); and optimizing the surrogate to retrieve the optimal design. This approach requires extensive computational efforts, costs, and time. Ideally, instead of building a new database for each parametrization, we would leverage historical data. Therefore, we propose to decouple the parametrization from the input to the surrogate model and show how our decoupled approach can develop surrogates able to match the performance of CFD models and optimize hull resistance.

1. Introduction

Optimizing vessel hull resistance is an essential aspect of the design process, *Feng et al. (2018)*, *Harries and Abt (2019)*. Minimizing hull-form resistance is crucial not only for enhancing performance but also for reducing the environmental impact of motorized vessels, *Armstrong (2013)*. However, achieving this objective requires exploring a broad and multidimensional design space, *Maisonneuve et al. (2003)*, which is not an easy feat given the complexity of the representation space, *Skinner and Zare-Behtash (2018)*.

Current methods for optimizing vessel hull resistance require a significant amount of time and computational resources, *Zheng et al. (2023)*, *Campana et al. (2006)*, *Temarel et al. (2016)*. Traditionally, Experimental Fluid Dynamics (EFD) has been used to determine hull resistance, *Gerritsma et al. (1989)*, *Keuning and Sonnenberg (1998)*, *Keuning and Katgert (2008)*, but constructing scaled models and conducting tests is labor-intensive. Hence, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has become a more popular approach, as it is faster and still very accurate, but it is still computationally expensive when assessing numerous designs, *Feng et al. (2018)*, *Guerrero et al. (2018)*, *Coppedè (2019)*, *Niklas et al. (2019)*, *Miao and Wan (2020)*, *Casalone et al. (2020)*, *Zhang et al. (2021)*, *Liu et al. (2022)*.

When it comes to optimizing the design of a vessel hull, assessing the performance of many different candidate designs is required, *Biliotti (2011)*. Relying on CFD results is impractical due to the computational requirements, *Zheng et al. (2023)*, *Campana et al. (2006)*. Hence, recently, Artificial-Intelligence (AI)-based approaches are attracting the attention for their ability to accurately surrogate complex experimental (EFD), *Fahrholz (2022)*, or numerical (CFD), *Feng et al. (2018)*, *Guerrero et al. (2018)*, *Coppedè (2019)*, *Niklas et al. (2019)*, *Miao and Wan (2020)*, *Casalone et al. (2020)*, *Zhang et al. (2021)*, *Liu et al. (2022)*, procedures. These approaches are based on a historical collection of inputs and outputs, which are computationally expensive to construct but computationally inexpensive to use. Consequently, AI-based surrogates can be directly incorporated into a human-driven optimization loop, reducing the computational requirements between design iterations. They can also be used in developing a fully automated optimization loop that requires minimal human intervention, enabling the exploration of a wider design space, *Harries and Abt (2019)*.

The current approach to vessel hull resistance optimization involves a combination of human experience and AI, *Feng et al. (2018)*, *Guerrero et al. (2018)*, *Coppedè (2019)*, *Niklas et al. (2019)*, *Miao and Wan (2020)*, *Casalone et al. (2020)*, *Zhang et al. (2021)*, *Liu et al. (2022)*. Firstly, parametrizing a series of and defining the parameters ranges using one of several approaches that exist in the literature (Section

2). Next, a surrogate of the relationship between parameters and resistance from Experimental Fluid Dynamics (EFD) or Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is built, which allows estimating the resistance for a new parameter configuration at a fraction of the time, computational, and financial requirements of the CFD. Lastly, the surrogate is exploited by an optimizer to search for the optimal parameters configuration in the parameters ranges, to retrieve the associated optimized geometry. Resistance is one of the key design optimality conditions (e.g.; resistance at high and low speed), therefore, multiple optimal solutions are retrieved according to the Pareto front, *Burachik et al. (2022)*.

The current approach is limited in a number of ways. Firstly, there is a need for human supervision in geometry parametrization and optimization because the parametrization needs to satisfy multiple functional requirements: (i) be informative enough to allow for the prediction of the resistance; (ii) be homomorphic; and (iii) be synthetic and intelligible enough to allow for interpretation and test (e.g.; for physical plausibility). Ideally, human intervention should be limited during optimization because the parametrization and surrogate should be accurate and physically plausible enough to not find unfeasible, physically implausible, or degenerate solutions. Secondly, there is a need for extensive computational efforts (for CFD), costs (for EFD), and time (for both CFD and EFD) to build the dataset for surrogation. Ideally, we would rely only on previous CFD and EFD and not require new efforts for each investigation. Finally, there is a limited ability of this approach to work beyond the specific setting such as changes in the family of geometry or extrapolation outside the parameter ranges, *Feng et al. (2018)*, *Guerrero et al. (2018)*, *Coppedè (2019)*, *Niklas et al. (2019)*, *Miao and Wan (2020)*, *Casalone et al. (2020)*, *Zhang et al. (2021)*, *Liu et al. (2022)*.

We propose a new approach to vessel hull optimization that addresses the limitations of current methods. It involves a parametrization that can cover a wide range of geometries which is homomorphic and requires minimal human intervention because it can be used for all designs around the 6 parent hulls of the DSYHS, reducing the need for repeated parametrization. Next, to simplify the parametrization phase even further and reduce the need for human intervention, we have decoupled the process of defining the hull geometry from the process of defining the AI-based surrogate parameters and predicting the hull resistance. Our approach involves using the Nautilus code, <https://github.com/mai-lab-tud/nautilus>, which can automatically extract a range of features that are informative enough to predict hull resistance across multiple parent hulls while remaining physically plausible, *Fahrnholz (2022)*. This decoupling is a key aspect of our approach, as it allows us to create a rich and informative feature set without the requirement of homomorphic parametrization. Instead, the geometry parametrization can focus solely on the optimization parameters, thus simplifying the optimization step and minimizing the need for human intervention, particularly when new parent hulls need to be covered. As a result, our approach has simplified a complex and constrained problem into two simpler ones.

Thanks to the decoupled approach to the parametrization, covering multiple parent hulls, we can train AI-based surrogates based on the existing EFD of the DSYHS and we do not additional EFD or CFD. However, CFD was necessary to ensure that the surrogates were physically accurate and reliable. This step allowed us to validate the surrogates and ensure their suitability for real-world applications.

To test the proposed decoupled approach, we first show the effectiveness of the proposed AI-based surrogate by testing it in an extrapolation scenario: removing part of the EFD during the surrogate training phase and using those data for testing purposes. Then, to validate the proposed optimization approach, we tested the AI-based surrogate that was trained without knowledge of variations of a particular parent hull and explore geometric parameters $\delta\%$ larger than the ones covered by the DSYHS. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant related works; Section 3 describes the available data; Section 4 outlines the proposed methodology; Section 5 contains the results; and finally, Section 6 concludes the work.

2. Related Work

This section summarizes the related works describing the parametrization, sources of data, data

validation, AI-based surrogation, optimization approach, results, and validations for physical plausibility of each of the relevant works.

Huang and Yang (2016) optimized a Series 60 hull using 7 design variables to parametrize the hull. An initial population of 210 geometries was evaluated using a Steady Ship Flow solver based on the Neumann-Michell theory, which was validated against literature data. A Radial Basis Function based surrogate for resistance was constructed and incorporated into a Multi-Objective Artificial Bee Colony optimization framework. Although statistical validation for the surrogate was not reported, a visual comparison of the real versus predicted resistance using scatter plots showed good agreement between the surrogate and the original model. The optimization was subject to a displacement change constraint of 1%, and results indicated an 8% reduction in total resistance at a Froude number of 0.27. The findings were validated using a high-fidelity approach, Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes based CFD tool.

Feng et al. (2018) optimized an offshore aquaculture vessel using a combination of CFD and EFD. The hull was parametrized using FFD with 9 design variables, and 300 geometries were evaluated using a CFD model validated against EFD data. The authors proposed a Support Vector Regression-based surrogate coupled with the NSGA-II optimizer to minimize total resistance and wake flow at the design speed. The surrogate showed a good agreement with the original model, and the optimization results showed reductions of 1.6% and 18% for total resistance and wake flow, respectively. The optimized hull design was validated via EFD, confirming the reduction in total resistance and wake flow.

Guerrero et al. (2018) optimized the design of a bulbous bow by parametrizing it with 6 design parameters using FFD. They evaluated a small number of geometries (25) using high fidelity CFD at 5 different Froude numbers. The CFD was validated against EFD with two levels of mesh coarsening and showed a maximum deviation of 5.6%. The authors then developed a Kriging based surrogate and used it with a NSGA-II optimizer to identify the 5 best geometries. Results showed that 3 geometries had unsatisfactory performance, while the remaining 2 demonstrated a reduction in total resistance of approximately 6-7%.

Tahara et al. (2011) employed a parametrization for a twin-skeg fishing vessel using 6 dimensionless design variables. They used a CFD approach validated through a mesh-coarsening procedure with 3 levels of grid refinement, resulting in a dataset of 54 simulations. A Kriging based surrogate was constructed with a Coefficient of Determination of approximately 0.95. The surrogate was coupled with a NSGA-II optimizer to minimize total resistance at 4 different velocities between 9 and 12 knots. The optimal model resulted in a 5.6% reduction in total resistance at the design speed of 11.3 knots, which was validated using the CFD model.

Coppedè et al. (2019) optimized the KCS using FFD parametrization and 6 design variables. A high-fidelity CFD model was used to evaluate the performance of 120 geometries at a fixed Froude number of 0.26. The mesh was validated using a mesh coarsening procedure with 1.5M cells and compared to EFD data from the literature. A Response Surface Model surrogate was constructed and statistically validated with Leave One Out method, showing a Coefficient of Determination of 0.97 and a Root Mean Square Deviation of 0.05N. The NSGA-II optimization framework was used to minimize the total resistance with a constraint on a 1% change in displacement. The results, validated with CFD, showed a reduction of 0.32N in total drag.

Miao and Wan (2020) optimized the KCS at 2 speeds using FFD parametrization with 5 design variables. They employed a Neumann-Michell coupled with Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes CFD approach validated with EFD to generate an initial population of 40 geometries evaluated at both speeds. A Gaussian Progress Regression based surrogate was developed, and although no statistical validation was reported, the scatter plots of real versus predicted resistance indicated good agreement between the surrogate and the CFD approach. They then used a NSGA-II optimizer to minimize resistance, resulting in 9.24% reduction at design speed (Froude number 0.26) and a 4.99% reduction at Froude number 0.2. *Zhang et al. (2021)* utilized FFD parametrization with 2 design variables to optimize a Wigleyship. A panel-based CFD approach was employed to evaluate the wave making coefficient at a Froude number

of 0.35 and validated against CFD data from literature. They developed a Deep Belief Neural Network based surrogate, which showed a Coefficient of Determination of approximately 1. The authors then used a Quadratic Lagrangian based Non-Linear Programming optimizer coupled with the surrogate to minimize the wave making coefficient at Froude numbers between 0.28 and 0.36. The optimal model demonstrated a 12% reduction in the wave making coefficient and was later validated using a CFD model, showing an uncertainty of 5%.

Mittendorf and Papanikolaou (2021) optimized a catamaran using a parametric model consisting of 6 design variables. They evaluated 2000 geometries using a panel-based CFD model that was validated against high fidelity CFD results from literature. The authors developed and statistically validated three different AI-based surrogates: Gaussian Process, Support Vector, and Multi Adaptive Splines. The Multi Adaptive Splines based surrogate had the highest Coefficient of Prognosis (0.81), so it was coupled with the NSGA-II optimizer to minimize vessel resistance at five different speeds. Two optimal hull designs were validated against both low fidelity and high fidelity CFD. For one hull, the panel-based CFD predicted a decrease in resistance, but the high fidelity CFD actually showed an increase. For the other hull, both low and high fidelity CFD predicted a reduction in resistance.

Liu et al. (2022) used a FFD and spline-based parametrization approach with 5 design variables for the DTMB-5415 hull. They employed a combination of Neumann-Michell and Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes CFD models to estimate the coefficient of resistance for 50 and 30 geometries, respectively. The mesh was validated through a coarsening procedure, and the CFD models were validated using experimental data from the literature. To improve efficiency, the authors proposed a Kriging-based surrogate which was statistically validated, demonstrating an Average Absolute Error of 0.29, a Maximum Absolute Error of 1.93, and a Root Mean Square Error of 0.45. The surrogate's accuracy improved with the addition of high-fidelity samples. The authors applied a Genetic Algorithm to optimize the resistance at a Froude number of 0.28, resulting in a reduction of resistance between 2% and 5%.

3. Available Data

In this section we will describe the data that we will exploit in this study. We leverage the DSYHS database (available upon request to the Delft University of Technology Ship Hydromechanics Laboratory), *TUD (2021)*.

The DSYHS database contains the hull Series 1 \div 7 ($S_1 \div S_7$) note that S_5 is not present in the database. The 6 series are in model scale. Table I shows the boundaries of the hulls in the DSYHS. From these 6 Series there are 54 different derived geometries G . Each G has the total resistance R_t retrieved over a range of speeds v via EFD. The total number of samples is 702.

Table I: Boundaries of the hulls in the DSYHS.

Series	Geometries	Length [m]	Breadth [m]	Depth [m]	Volume $\times 10^{-3}$ [m ³]	Draft [m]
S_1	22	1.94 \div 2.30	0.51 \div 0.68	0.29 \div 0.36	37.60 \div 37.61	0.13 \div 0.15
S_2	6	2.31 \div 2.35	0.50 \div 0.66	0.23 \div 0.35	37.53 \div 37.60	0.11 \div 0.15
S_3	11	2.28 \div 2.40	0.48 \div 0.80	0.20 \div 0.28	37.53 \div 37.53	0.11 \div 0.11
S_4	9	2.09 \div 2.38	0.37 \div 0.74	0.27 \div 0.34	30.92 \div 37.53	0.11 \div 0.12
S_6	3	2.42 \div 2.43	0.66 \div 0.66	0.30 \div 0.35	30.92 \div 30.92	0.12 \div 0.12
S_7	3	2.51 \div 2.57	0.38 \div 0.45	0.21 \div 0.33	30.92 \div 30.92	0.12 \div 0.12

The geometries contained in the database are parameterized by hydrostatic coefficients, see Table II for details. Note that, for any geometry, the parameters reported in Table II can be retrieved using the Nautilus code.

Table II: Hydrostatic coefficients to parametrize the geometries.

Parameter	Symbol	Parameter	Symbol
Length of waterline	L_{wl}	Area of cross-section	A_x
Breadth of waterline	B_{wl}	Wetted surface area of canoe body	S
Draft of canoe body	T	Block coefficient	C_b
Volume of canoe body	∇	Midship area coefficient	C_m
Longitudinal center of buoyancy	LCB	Prismatic coefficient	C_p
Longitudinal center of flotation	LCF	Waterplane area coefficient	C_w
Area of waterplane	A_w		

4. Methodology

In this section, we will describe the proposed methodology. Section 3 already focused on the available data, while the following aspects of the methodology will be the subjects of this section:

- the development of the surrogate to estimate R_t based on the parameters reported in Table II that can also be retrieved with Nautilus for any hull geometry (Section 4.1);
- the validation in an extrapolation scenario and the physical plausibility against CFD of the surrogate (Section 4.2);
- the homomorphic parametrization of the hull and the parameters range and constraints generating the parameter space (Section 4.3);
- the optimization framework which searches in the homomorphic parameters space simultaneously optimizing R_t for both a high v^{High} and low v^{Low} and verification of the physical plausibility against CFD (Section 4.4).

4.1. Surrogate Development

Predicting R_t based on the parameters reported in Table II and the velocity v can be mapped to a typical regression problem by Machine Learning, *Shalev-Shwartz and Ben-David (2014)*. In this paper we will leverage on a Machine Learning model coming from the Kernel Methods family called Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR), *Shawe-Taylor and Cristianini (2004)*. In KRR we chose to rely on the Gaussian kernel for the reason described in, *Keerthi and Lin (2003)*, and then the regularization hyperparameter λ and the kernel coefficient γ need to be tuned. We have defined the hyperparameters' search space as $\lambda : \{10^{-6}, 10^{-5.8}, \dots, 10^3\}$ and $\gamma : \{10^{-6}, 10^{-5.8}, \dots, 10^3\}$. The performances, in terms of accuracy, will be measured in accordance with different metrics: three quantitative (the Mean Absolute Error - MAE, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error - MAPE, and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient - PPMCC), *Naser and Alavi (2021)*, and one qualitative (the scatter plot actual versus predicted value), *Sainani (2016)*.

4.2. Surrogate Validation and Physical Plausibility

In this work, we will use an extrapolation scenario based on the intrinsic hierarchy of the dataset to allow us to understand the extrapolation capability and robustness of the models described in the previous section. Specifically, the LOSO scenario is where we remove all the EFD corresponding to a particular series (all variations of a particular parent hull) and will test the extrapolation ability of the model in terms of series, namely, to estimate the resistance for a series never observed before in the dataset, Fig.1.

Note that, the LOSO scenario is an interesting and useful test because, in practice, what we want to do is to generate geometry for a new, previously unexplored series, and this is precisely the scope of the LOSO scenario: we try to infer something for a new series that was previously unexplored.

Fig.1. Visual representation of the LOSO extrapolation scenario that we investigated in this work

For what concerns assessing the final performance we used the principal of the extrapolation scenario to split the data into Training D_n and Test T_t sets. Then we used D_n to both train the model and select the associated best hyperparameters and use T_t to assess the performance. For tuning the hyperparameters (λ and γ) we used the same extrapolation principal to split D_n into Learning L_l and Validation V_v sets, then we chose the hyperparameters configuration that, when trained on L_l , performed the best on V_v .

To ensure the physical plausibility of the proposed surrogate, we leveraged a state-of-the-art CFD model. For the DSYHS, EFD have been carried out by means of a large experimental campaign carried out at the Delft University of Technology towing tank and for this reason, they possess some level of uncertainty that cannot be removed. Therefore, to measure the quality of our surrogate we need to compare its performance against a baseline which, in our case, is a state-of-the-art CFD model.

The CFD model for assessing the hull resistance was developed in Star CCM+ (a state-of-the-art commercial package). The domain was created with the depth under the vessel greater than twice the draft, the length after the vessel was longer than twice the length of the vessel, and the width of the domain was 50% larger than the length of the vessel. To reduce computational demand, only half of the problem was simulated to assess the hydrodynamic performance. The CFD model used a finite volume viscous RANS solver with the $k-\omega$ shear-stress turbulence model with wall functions. The volume of fluid technique was used to establish a free surface in the solution. The vessel was allowed two degrees of freedom (sink and trim), which is in line with the original experimental campaign. The simulation time-step was 0.001 s and the total time simulated was 60 s then the solution was taken as the time averaged response over this period. We validated the CFD against the original EFD results for a number of geometries to ensure it could be used for the physical plausibility of the AI-based surrogate and a mesh coarsening procedure was carried out with $3 \cdot 10^5$, $9 \cdot 10^5$, and $3 \cdot 10^6$ cells respectively to ensure there was grid independence. The highest fidelity mesh with $3 \cdot 10^6$ cells was used to gather the results in Section 5. Fig.4 shows the mesh which included a surface mesh refinement on the vessel hull and on the boundaries of the domain in addition to volume mesh refinements around the hull, wake, and free surface.

Fig.2: The CFD mesh in Star CCM+

4.3. Hull Parametrization and Parameters Range

In this section, we will describe the adopted homomorphic parametrization, together with the associated parameter range, that will be leveraged during the optimization phase (Section 4.1) to search for the best hull. Following the proposed decoupled approach, this parametrization is independent from the one used to build the surrogate (Section 4.4).

A parametric model for a sailing yacht hull was developed in Siemens NX relying on 32 parameters. The parameters shape the hull by controlling the location of control points on B-Spline curves that shape the hull surface. This parametrization allows for the parameters to be modified independently and ensures homomorphy. Constraints were imposed on the model geometry to ensure G0 and G1 continuity at the intersection between adjacent splines to help with feasibility. Additionally, the G2 continuity was applied to ensure a smooth surface was retrieved from the model. Fig.3 shows the 32 parameters and a cross-section of the mid-section, the isometric view of the hull, and a planar view of the hull. Parameters denoted with an x or z define features in the xz plane and parameters denoted with y define features in the xy plane. The parameters preceded by P refer to the B-spline control points in the yz plane.

For the parameters ranges, they have been designed following the principle of first searching for the minimum and maximum value in a specific series S_i , i.e.; the series that we want to optimize (see Section 4.4). Then we increased that range by $\delta\%$. This extrapolation is because, in practice, we want to generate a geometry for a new, previously unexplored series rather than restrict ourselves to pre-existing designs. In the experiments, we will show that the $\delta = 30\%$ is the threshold at which the framework will begin to return physically implausible solutions.

Fig.3. The parametric model created in Siemens NX

The parameter ranges extracted from the DSYHS database are reported in Table III. The proposed homomorphic parametrization does not suffer the limitations of the current approaches and is able to parametrize the DSHYS database and beyond (i.e.; up to $\delta\%$ of the DSHYS).

Table III: Ranges for the geometric parameters extracted from the DSYHS database (in mm)

Parameter	Range	Parameter	Range	Parameter	Range	Parameter	Range
X_{Bow}	[1650, 2200]	Y_{Mid}	[173, 371]	P_{Entr}^{y1}	[6, 43]	P_{Run}^{y1}	[72, 274]
Y_{Bow}	[1, 62]	Z_{Mid}	[-97, 4]	P_{Entr}^{z1}	[31, 85]	P_{Run}^{z1}	[28, 79]
Z_{Bow}	[156, 355]	X_{Run}	[-200, 50]	P_{Entr}^{y2}	[12, 71]	P_{Run}^{y2}	[128, 307]
Z_{Max}	[196, 364]	Y_{Run}	[146, 327]	P_{Entr}^{z2}	[60, 165]	P_{Run}^{z2}	[64, 163]
X_{Entr}	[1600, 2050]	Z_{Run}	[29, 180]	P_{Mid}^{y1}	[154, 349]	P_{Stern}^{y1}	[9, 248]
Y_{Entr}	[18, 97]	X_{Stern}	[150, 400]	P_{Mid}^{z1}	[63, 121]	P_{Stern}^{z1}	[4, 71]
Z_{Entr}	[22, 179]	Y_{Stern}	[26, 292]	P_{Mid}^{y2}	[166, 368]	P_{Stern}^{y2}	[17, 273]
X_{Mid}	[800, 1050]	Z_{Stern}	[38, 282]	P_{Mid}^{z2}	[127, 244]	P_{Stern}^{z2}	[7, 139]

4.4. Optimization Framework

In this section we will present the proposed approach to the search for the best hull in a series S_i , in terms of the best R_t at v^{High} and v^{Low} , in line with the referenced works, leveraging the parametrization described in Section 4.3 and the surrogate described in Section 4.1.

It is not a fair trade-off between the resistance R_t and the volume of the hull ∇ , i.e.; zero resistance will correspond to having no submerged body. Therefore, we will optimize for the relative resistance to the submerged volume ($\frac{R_t}{\nabla}$). Additionally, the optimization problem is subject to a constraint on the bounds of the volume ∇_l and ∇_u for the lower and upper bounds respectively. ∇_l and ∇_u have been set by searching for the minimum and maximum volume in a specific series S_i because we aim to optimize the geometry of a hull that fits within a particular series and conforms to the same volume constraints. Therefore, we can formalize the problem as a single objective one using the weighted sum, *Emmerich and Deutz (2018)*, of the different objectives as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{p}} \lambda \frac{R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{High})}{\nabla(\mathbf{p})} + (1 - \lambda) \frac{R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{Low})}{\nabla(\mathbf{p})} \\ \text{s. t. } \quad \nabla_l \leq \nabla(\mathbf{p}) \leq \nabla_u \\ \mathbf{p}_l(\delta) \leq \mathbf{p} \leq \mathbf{p}_u(\delta) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the vector of the 32 parameters of the homomorphic parametrization of Table III, $\mathbf{p}_l(\delta)$ and $\mathbf{p}_u(\delta)$ are their lower and upper bounds of the parameters as a function of δ , $\nabla(\mathbf{p})$ is the volume of the hull we want to optimize as a function of \mathbf{p} estimated using the Nautilus code, ∇_l and ∇_u are the upper and lower bound of $\nabla(\mathbf{p})$. Finally, $R_t(\mathbf{p}, \cdot)$ is the total resistance as a function of \mathbf{p} and the velocity (computed at v^{High} and v^{Low}) estimated via the surrogate described in Section 4.1 but where \mathbf{p} induces the geometry and Nautilus estimates the quantities of Table II that (along with the velocity) are the inputs of the surrogate. Instead, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ defines the importance of the different objectives, i.e.; for $\lambda \rightarrow 1$ $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{High})$ is more important than $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{Low})$ and vice-versa for $\lambda \rightarrow 0$. Solving Problem (1) for different values of λ allows us to obtain the Pareto frontier in a computationally efficient way, *Emmerich and Deutz (2018)*.

Problem (1) is a non-linear and non-linearly constrained optimization problem. To solve this we can exploit a number of different approaches. However, according to the literature on the subject, *Feng et al. (2018)*, *Guerrero et al. (2018)*, *Coppedè (2019)*, *Miao and Wan (2020)*, *Liu et al. (2022)*, we opt for the Evolutionary Algorithm (EA) as it showed to be the best approach for this class of problem. We relied on an EA-based optimization framework built in MATLAB which is a variant implementation of the NSGA-II Genetic Algorithm. Moreover, we customize the optimizer by adding a multi-start approach, running the algorithm multiple times keeping the best solution found in the different starts. For the sake of repeatability. Table IV reports the parameters' set that empirically produced the best results in the paper.

Table IV: Parameters for the optimization

Algorithm	MATLAB Function	Parameter	Value
EA	ga	PopulationSize	5000
		MaxGenerations	200
		CrossoverFraction	0.8
		EliteCount	1
		Multi start (manually implemented)	10

Considering the last task, which is the verification of the physical plausibility against CFD we first need to specify a definition for physical plausibility. In this work, we a geometry to be physical plausible when the optimizer finds non-degenerate geometries that, when tested, will not exhibit $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{High})$ and $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{Low})$ far away from the performance inferred by the optimizer. However, it may also be the case a geometry is physically implausible and there are two main reasons for this to happen

1. $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{High})$ and $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{Low})$ inserted in Problem (1) are not the real resistances but a surrogate characterized by no infinite precision and limited extrapolation abilities (this has been already tested in Section 4.2). Consequently, during exploration, the optimizer may be induced into false minima by the imprecision and the extrapolation limitations of the surrogate;
2. the parameter space defined by $\mathbf{p}_l(\delta)$ and $\mathbf{p}_u(\delta)$ namely by δ is too large, requesting the optimizer to search within a parameter space that has more risk of imprecise extrapolation of the surrogate.

For this reason, analogously to what has been done for the surrogate in Section 4.2, we will test the geometries found by the optimizer with the Star-CCM+ package checking the deviation between the $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{High})$ and $R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{Low})$ estimated with the surrogate model and the CFD. The CFD simulation is the same one reported in Section 4.2.

5. Experimental Results

In this section, we will report the results of applying the methodology described in Section 4 to solve the problem faced in this work using the data described in Section 3. In Section 5.1 we test the quality of the AI-based surrogate model in the LOSO extrapolating scenario and then validate the physical plausibility of the results against the CFD. In Section 5.2 we tested the quality of the proposed optimization framework on a particular series of the DSYHS showing that we can improve the current geometries with new designs that we tested using CFD to verify their physical plausibility. All experiments have been conducted on DelftBlue, *Delft High-Performance Computing Centre (2022)*.

5.1. Surrogate Models Validation and Physical Plausibility

In this section, we will report the performance of the surrogate models described in Section 4.1 using the validation approaches described in Section 4.2 in the extrapolation scenario. Table V reports, for the KRR in the LOSO scenario, the different metrics of accuracy (MAE, MAPE, and PPMCC) for each of the series. Instead, Fig.4 reports, for the KRR in the LOSO scenario, the scatter plot for each of the series.

Table V: LOSO Scenario for each of the series using the KRR algorithm

Series	Accuracy		
	MAE [N]	MAPE [%]	PPMCC [-]
S_1	3.47 ± 0.94	1.26 ± 0.29	0.99 ± 0.00
S_2	3.13 ± 1.85	0.61 ± 0.24	0.99 ± 0.02
S_3	3.13 ± 1.85	0.62 ± 0.35	1.00 ± 0.00
S_4	2.28 ± 0.49	0.88 ± 0.17	1.00 ± 0.00
S_6	0.86 ± 0.38	0.49 ± 0.11	1.00 ± 0.00
S_7	0.62 ± 0.18	0.37 ± 0.15	1.00 ± 0.00
Average	1.83 ± 1.07	0.11 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.00

From Table V and Figure 4 it is possible to observe that the surrogate performs better on some series than on others. This is due to several reasons

- the performance of the surrogate decreases at higher speeds as less experiments have been performed at higher speeds. As a matter of fact, for S_1 , S_2 , and S_4 , the poor performance is exhibited around Resistances in the range from 40–100N, Figs.4a, 4b, and 4d;
- the poor performance for S_1 as the LOSO (Figure 4a) is related to the fact that there are significantly more geometries in this series than in any other (22 out of 47 geometries according to Table I). Consequently, when we check S_1 in the LOSO scenario, we have very few geometries to learn our model.

Let us continue this section with the test of the physical plausibility of the surrogate. For this test we have decided to focus on S_4 as the LOSO as this is the series that exhibits approximately the average performance of the surrogate in the LOSO scenario (i.e.; it is not the most challenging nor the simplest series to predict but is an average to challenging one. Since reporting all the geometries is not meaningful, we have decided to report the physical plausibility for the best and worst geometries in this series in Fig.5.

Fig.4: The scatter plots of each series as the LOSO

Fig.5: The Physical Plausibility of the best and worst geometries with S_4 as the LOSO

5.2. Optimization Framework Validation and Physical Plausibility

At this point, we have empirically shown that the proposed parametrization and the surrogate are able to work well also in extrapolating scenarios matching the performance, in terms of accuracy and physical plausibility, of state-of-the-art CFD models at a fraction of their computational requirements.

In this section, we will leverage this surrogate in the optimization framework and validate its performance by means of the approach described in Section 4.4.

For the same reason as Section 5.1, we selected to use S_4 as the target series to optimize and the model with S_4 as the LOSO as the surrogate. For S_4 the $\mathbf{p}_l(\delta)$ and $\mathbf{p}_u(\delta)$ are reported in Table III while $\nabla_l = 19 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ and $\nabla_u = 48 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$. We reported the results for different values of $\delta \in \{10, 20, 30\}\%$ and $\lambda \in \{0, 0.1, \dots, 1\}$ linearly interpolating between this value. Fig.8 reports the Pareto frontier ($\frac{R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{High})}{\nabla(\mathbf{p})}$ on the x-axis and $\frac{R_t(\mathbf{p}, v^{Low})}{\nabla(\mathbf{p})}$ on the y-axis) for different values of λ and δ together with the EFD data and the CFD validation as just described. Additionally, Fig.9 reports a comparison of the body plans for the baseline geometry belonging to S_4 and the optimized ones with $\lambda = 1$ and $\delta \in \{10, 20, 30\}\%$. Setting $\lambda = 1$ implies that we prefer to minimise the resistance at v^{High} , representing a typical velocity for high-speed operations where we should observe the most significant differences in optimal performance.

From Figs.6 and 7 we can observe that

- with a small δ (Figure 6a, $\delta = 10\%$) the proposed framework and surrogate can find geometries that match S_4 without any a-priori knowledge of this series. However, it is worth mentioning that the geometry found by the optimizer (Figure 7a), is different to the original S_4 hull. This is because the optimization problem is simplified, and does not take into consideration all of the realistic constraints that impact the design of a hull (e.g.; stability and seakeeping);
- with a larger δ (Fig.6b, $\delta = 20\%$) the proposed framework and surrogate can remarkably exceed, according to the surrogate, the performance of the original S_4 . However, when the performance is checked (using CFD) we find this is a bit optimistic. Also, there is a difference with the geometries (Fig.7b) as they start to enlarge;
- with an even larger δ (Fig.6c, $\delta = 30\%$) the proposed framework and surrogate, can even more remarkably exceed, according to the surrogate, the performance of the original S_4 . However, when the performance is checked (using CFD) we find this is just a numerical artefact due to the extrapolation limits of the surrogate. In fact, when using the CFD we find there is a reduction of this performance that brings us back to the gain found when δ was smaller. Note that in this case the geometry, Fig.7c, is quite similar to the case of $\delta = 20\%$, Fig.7b.

Fig.6: The Optimization Framework and Physical Plausibility for S_4 with $\delta \in \{10, 20, 30\}\%$ and $\lambda \in \{0, 0.1, \dots, 1\}$.

Fig.7: The body plans for the baseline geometry (blue) belonging to S_4 and the optimized ones (orange) with $\delta \in \{10, 20, 30\}\%$ and $\lambda = 1$.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we tackled the problem of vessel hull resistance optimization, which is crucial for achieving optimal performance and reducing environmental impact. We first reviewed the current literature and found that the existing approach mostly relies on a mix of human experience and AI-based surrogates. We identified several limitations of the existing approaches, including the need for human intervention in geometry parametrization and optimization, extensive computational efforts and costs, and limited ability to work beyond the specific settings. To overcome these limitations we proposed a decoupled approach to AI-based design and optimization of the Delft Systematic Yacht Hull Series. We showed that the AI-based surrogate can be trained on the existing DSYHS dataset, without new CFD or EFD customized for this problem, and match the performance of CFD models even in extrapolating conditions, with physical plausibility and minimal human intervention. We also validated our approach to developing AI-based surrogates in extrapolating conditions with statistical methods using the DSYHS dataset and for physical plausibility using CFD models. Finally, we demonstrated the effectiveness of our proposal by showing that it is possible to optimize the hull resistance by exploring geometric parameters beyond the boundaries of the DSYHS.

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Numerical Simulation of Sea Spray Events in Extreme Weather Conditions

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Abstract

To predict the rate of ice formation on marine structures, the mass and location of impinging sea-spray must be determined. Since different droplet sizes have vastly different trajectory paths, the mass flux of the spray cloud must be expressed as function of droplet size. A valid model for this relationship does not exist for spray generated by a vessel moving through a wave. Using data (previously) collected from a U.S. Coast Guard vessel in the Bering Sea, droplet size, quantity and weight contribution were extracted for a series of vessel-wave interactions. The total wind- and sea-spray flux impacting the vessel were determined by numerical simulation using Newton's Second Law of Motion and velocity fields generated using Computational Fluid Dynamics. Results of a fishing vessel test case can later be utilized to analyse topside ice formation.

1. Introduction

As vessels venture into extreme weather conditions, it is imperative to understand the effect and quantity of green water and weather spray that impact the vessel. Combined with the effects of large swells, strong winds, and low temperatures, the effects can be catastrophic.

Two recent vessel casualties involving icing on commercial fishing vessels demonstrate these tragic effects. In 2017, the fishing vessel 'Destination' sank with the loss of all crew onboard. Two years later, the vessel 'Scandies Rose' sank with five fishermen perishing and two survivors, *National Transportation Safety Board (2022)*. Both casualties were attributed largely to vessel icing in extreme weather conditions. Both vessels also had crab pots onboard, a meshed fishing structure. Attempts to understand icing on these structures were frustrated because current icing models only consider solid structures, which have different parameters for icing than a meshed structure like a crab pot – both in quantities of impinging water and in heat transfer coefficients associated with ice formulation.

Attempts to quantify icing on vessels carrying crab pots has not been performed. While icing models exist for vessels and Mobile Offshore Drilling Units (MODUs), primarily in the North Sea, the casualties of 'Destination' and 'Scandies Rose', along with the 12 lives lost, highlight the urgency and importance of the problem to both commercial mariners and the environment.

2. Approach

To properly predict icing on a fishing vessel, the mass flux of water striking the crab pot stack must be determined. Fig.1 illustrates the entire ice accretion problem, from initial spray generation to vessel stability analysis with icing.

Fig.1: Flow chart of icing model

The model is divided into four subsections:

1. Droplet trajectory
2. Water mass flux
3. Ice accretion or ice flux
4. Stability impacts

The droplet trajectory model was completed for the on-scene weather conditions experienced during the ‘Scandies Rose’s’ final voyage, *DeNucci and Brahan (2022)* and validated against previous results, *Dehghani et al. (2016)*. The velocity flow field was modelled using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and integrated into the droplet trajectory model. This approach allowed localized wind velocities to influence the flight path of droplets with greater precision.

The water mass flux model is presented in this paper. After validating the droplet trajectory model, the quantity of water originating from both vessel-wave interactions and from wind-generated spray is determined. Combined with the droplet trajectory results, a model is presented to determine the mass flux on the crab pot stack – both on a macro and micro scale.

Once the mass flux is known on a local area, a nodal analysis of icing will be possible on the crab pot stack, and a stability analysis can be performed yielding further understanding of the effects of extreme weather on the overall vessel stability.

3. Droplet trajectory model overview

As droplets move over marine platforms, the larger droplets tend to fall out of spray clouds because of gravity. However, there is a balance between gravity and wind so that larger droplets remain in the cloud at higher wind speeds and smaller droplets are affected more by the velocity flow field; therefore, all droplet sizes present in spray should be modelled, *Dehghani-Sanij et al. (2017)*. This is especially important for commercial fishing vessels, as risky icing events occur typically occur at high wind speeds.

3.1 Equations of motion

Water droplets in the air are subject to both gravity and drag forces. Newton’s second law for droplet motion, shown in Eq.(1), includes terms for body, drag, and added mass forces:

$$m_d \frac{dV_d}{dt} = \rho_d \forall_d g - C_{dr} \frac{\pi D^2}{8} \rho_a |V_d - V_a| (V_d - V_a) + \rho_a \forall_d C_{ad} \frac{D(V_d - V_a)}{Dt} + \rho_a \forall_d \left(\frac{DV_a}{Dt} - g \right) \quad (1)$$

where m_d is the mass of the droplet, t is time, V_d is droplet velocity, V_a is air velocity, ρ_d is water density, \forall_d is droplet volume, g is gravity, C_{dr} is drag coefficient, D is droplet diameter, ρ_a is air density, and C_{ad} is the added mass force coefficient.

The longitudinal (x), transverse (y) and vertical (z) particle velocity and acceleration equations are derived from Eq.(1) and shown as Eqs. (2) – (4).

$$\dot{x} = \frac{dx}{dt} \quad \ddot{x} = -\frac{3C_{dr}}{4D(\gamma+C_{ad})} (\dot{x} - U_x) \sqrt{(\dot{x} - U_x)^2 + (\dot{y} - U_y)^2 + (\dot{z} - U_z)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{y} = \frac{dy}{dt} \quad \ddot{y} = -\frac{3C_{dr}}{4D(\gamma+C_{ad})} (\dot{y} - U_y) \sqrt{(\dot{x} - U_x)^2 + (\dot{y} - U_y)^2 + (\dot{z} - U_z)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{z} = \frac{dz}{dt} \quad \ddot{z} = \left(\frac{1-\gamma}{\gamma+C_{ad}} \right) g - \frac{3C_{dr}}{4D(\gamma+C_{ad})} (\dot{z} - U_z) \sqrt{(\dot{x} - U_x)^2 + (\dot{y} - U_y)^2 + (\dot{z} - U_z)^2} \quad (4)$$

The wind velocities, U_x, U_y, U_z , were generated using a CFD flow analysis. The crab pots were modelled as porous surfaces using the Darcy-Forchheimer Law, *DeNucci and Brahan, (2022)*.

Fig.2 illustrates the resulting airflow across the ‘Scandies Rose’ as it accelerates to a speed of 8 knots. One interesting observation is the velocity stall at the starboard bow quarter of the vessel where there is a sharp decrease in wind velocity.

Fig.2: Airflow over the deck of Scandies Rose at 2, 4, 6 and 8 knots. Red indicates areas of higher velocity flow fields, blue slower velocity flow fields.

4. Spray trajectories

Waves and wind generate marine sea spray. Wave-generated sea spray occurs during vessel-wave interacts while wind-generated spray is caused by the wind interacting with the free surface. Although the mass flux from the wind-generated spray is much less than that of the wave-generated, the droplets formed by wind-generated spray are much smaller and have different trajectories, thus forms ice in different locations on the vessel. To accurately predict the amount and location of ice, both sources of spray must be considered.

4.1 Wave spray trajectory

Wave-generated spray is the primary source vessel icing, *Lozowski (2017)*. Every time a wave is encountered, spray is generated from the vessel impacting the wave. However, not every wave generates this spray; for a fishing vessel, every other wave causes the vessel to generate spray from impact, consistent with that of a fishing trawler *Zakrzewski (1987)* and from video images of ‘Scandies Rose’ in a significant sea state, *Mrjonvan (2010)*.

The spray, in the form of a thin liquid sheet is assumed to start at the bow and develop symmetrically along both sides of the vessel to a distance, x_e , which is approximated by *Lozowski et al. (2000)* in Eq.(5):

$$x_e = 2.0h_s + 0.04v_{sw}^2 - 10.0 \quad (5)$$

where h_s is the significant wave height. The vessel speed relative to the waves, v_{sw} , is given by Eq.(6):

$$v_{sw} = \frac{g}{2\pi} \tau_w + v_s \cos(\pi - \alpha) \quad (6)$$

where τ_w is the significant wave period, v_s is vessel speed, g is gravitational acceleration and α is the angle between the vessel heading and the wind-wave direction.

To visualize the droplet trajectories, simulations were conducted to generate spray as waves struck the bow of the ship. Bow and flare angels were interpolated as a series of points to accurately capture the hull geometry of ‘Scandies Rose’. Table I shows the initial conditions used in the spray trajectory simulation.

Table 1: Wave spray trajectory initial conditions

Variable	Value
x -position	$18.85 - x_e$ m
y -position	Within 0.5 m of beam
z -position	0 – 3.82 m
Droplet diameter	250 – 1800 μ m
Droplet initial velocities	Assigned by droplet size \pm 20%
θ	$0^\circ - 90^\circ \pm 5^\circ$
φ	$70^\circ - 90^\circ \pm 5^\circ$

The droplets were initiated from a series of points representing the wave. Spray was varied in the x , y , and z directions. This variation is important because video from ‘Scandies Rose’ shows waves cresting at different heights depending on both their size and shape, *Mrjonvan (2010)*. The wave was partitioned so that droplets could be initiated along the length of the wave in the x -direction. In the y -direction, droplets were randomly positioned within 0.5 m of the beam. In the z -direction, droplets originated from the free surface to the wave height of 3.82 m. Additionally, water droplets were randomly positioned between the edge of the beam and 0.5 m from the beam. This, along with varying the injection angles, allowed for some variability in the initial spray, as could reasonably be expected. Simulations varied the most common droplet sizes present in high latitude sea spray in step sizes of 50 μ m, *Ryerson (1995)*, *Andreas et al. (2010)*.

Fig.3 shows the droplet trajectory paths from the wave-interaction simulation. The smaller droplets are carried with the velocity field, while the larger droplets’ inertial terms limit the effect of the flow field on their trajectory.

Fig.3: Spray trajectory across the vessel

4.2 Wind spray trajectory

Although wind-generated spray is a smaller proportion of mass flux the vessel encounters, it was modelled nonetheless. *Jones and Andreas (2012)* show that droplets in the air from the interaction of wind and the free surface are much smaller than those generated by vessel-wave interaction. Initial droplet initiation positions were varied in a fashion like the wave-generated spray. Table II shows the initial conditions and parameters used for the wind-generated spray.

Table II: Wind spray trajectory initial conditions

Variable	Value
<i>x-position</i>	30 – 4 m
<i>y-position</i>	-10 m
<i>z-position</i>	0.5 – 8 m
Droplet diameter	5 – 205 μm

Simulations showed that the initial velocities of the wind-generated droplets were irrelevant, due mainly to the smaller droplet diameters. Within a few time steps of the simulation, the droplets traveled at a nearly identical velocity as the wind profile determined by the CFD analysis. The droplets present in the wind-generated spray are much smaller than those in the wave-generated spray and have little inertia making them subject to the air flow field.

These parameters and sizing steps created over 40,000 individual droplets for both wind- and wave-generated spray simulations. To model each individual droplet emanating from the free surface would not be feasible because the number of droplets in the spray cloud are on the order of 10^5 to 10^6 droplets in 1 m^3 for wind-generated spray which accounts for only about 7% of total spray flux, *Kulyakhtin and Tsarau (2014)*. Therefore, a mass flux analysis was conducted, and each droplet represented all droplets originating from an area of the wave-generated or wind-generated spray.

5. Sea-spray mass flux per unit area ($\text{kg}/\text{m}^2\text{s}$)

Typical relative icing frequencies on fishing vessels, according to the source of impinging liquid, are as follows: spray alone (90%), spray with simultaneous atmospheric icing (7%), atmospheric icing alone (3%), *Lozowski (2017)*. The total amount of mass flux of seawater spray reaching an object located on a marine structure per unit area and unit time for wind spray and sea spray is obtained in Eq.(7), *Chaine and Skeates (1974)*, *Paulin (2008)*:

$$\dot{M}_{w,t} = B_s E U_{rs} [\omega(z)_{wind} + \omega(z)_{wave}] \quad (7)$$

where B_s is the shape coefficient, E is the collision efficiency. U_{rs} is the magnitude of the wind velocity relative to the structure; the method presented in this paper finds this value through CFD analysis. ω is the liquid water content (LWC), a measure of the mass of the water in a spray cloud per unit amount of dry air.

While Eq.(7) is appropriate for a water content analysis, it neglects the geometry of the crab pot stack which is essential in this problem. If the droplet intercepts the crab pot stack, represented by a plane, it is counted as a ‘‘hit’’ to the crab pot stack and the mass associated with the droplet is added to the total mass flux term. Therefore, the shape factor and collision efficiency term can be dismissed as it is captured in the formulation of the problem.

5.1 Wind-generated sea-spray

To compute the liquid water content (LWC) in wind-generated sea spray, an approach proposed by *Jones and Andreas (2012)* was employed because their approximation considers wind speed, droplet size, significant wave height, and height above free surface – all parameters which affect the LWC. Eq.(8) shows the LWC in wind-generated sea spray for wind speed greater than 19 m/s:

$$\frac{d\omega(r,z)}{dr} = \rho_w \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \right) \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^{-\frac{v_g(r)}{ku_* f_s} \frac{30U_{10}^4}{r}} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\ln \left(\frac{r}{0.3} \right)}{\ln 4} \right]^2 \right) \quad (8)$$

where r is the droplet radius, ρ_w the density of seawater, k the Von Karman constant, f_s the slip factor, u_* the friction velocity and h the height which is specified as the upper limit of the source region for

spray droplet generation ($h = 0.5h_s$ where h_s is the significant wave height). The fall velocity, shown in Eq.(9), is provided by *Andreas (1990)*:

$$v_g(r) = \frac{2r^2g}{9\nu_a \left[1 + 0.158 \left(\frac{2rv_g}{\nu_a} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \right]} \left(\frac{\rho_w}{\rho_a} - 1 \right) \quad (9)$$

where g is the acceleration of gravity, ν_a is the kinematic viscosity of air and ρ_a is the air density.

By numerically integrating Eq.(8), the mass flux from wind-generated spray, \dot{M}_{wind} , can be explicitly calculated. Since, this approach relates the size of droplets to each individual droplet's weight contribution to the overall spray cloud, one droplet could be released into the air representing the overall weight contribution in each volume of air attributed to that size of droplet. This reduces simulation costs, as there are tens of thousands of water droplets within a cubic meter of air at any given time. *Kulyakhtin and Tsarau (2014)* identify each droplet simulated as a "parcel" of droplets or mass. This approach was used in this paper for both the wind and wave-generated sea spray to decrease the amount of computational time required.

5.2 Wave generated sea-spray

Kachurin et al. (1974) proposed a simple formula for LWC as a function of wave height. While *Borisenkov and Pchelko (1975)* obtained an empirical formula for the vertical distribution of LWC for a fishing vessel in the Sea of Japan using the height above deck of the vessel, it is only applicable to fishing vessels under limited sea conditions. *Horjen and Vefsnmo (1984)* and *Brown and Roebber (1985)* derived computer formulas specifically for offshore structures using both the significant wave height and the height above over the mean seawater level to calculate the LWC. *Zakrzewski (1986)* improved the LWC for a fishing vessel by incorporating the wave height and vessel speed relative to the waves.

To calculate the vertical distribution of LWC in the spray for the ship, *Lozowski et al. (2000)* expressed Eq.(10) based on results from *Zakrzewski (1986)* for a single spray event.

$$\omega(z) = 6.1457 \times 10^{-5} h_s v_{sw}^2 e^{\left(-\frac{(z-H_{bow})}{1.82} \right)} \quad (10)$$

where H_{bow} is the height of the bow above the surface level.

The duration of the spray event, Eq.(11), given by *Zakrzewski (1987)*:

$$\tau_s = \frac{c v_{sw} h_s}{U_{10}^2} \quad (11)$$

where c is an experimental constant which depends on both the dimensions and configuration of the vessel hull, *Zakrzewski (1987)*. *Lozowski et al. (2000)* report that the parameter c is 10 for a USCG patrol vessel when it is assumed that a spray even occurs for every fourth wave collision. *Zakrzewski (1987)* suggests that the parameter c is 20.62 for a fishing vessel which experiences a wave generated spray every second wave collision. The analysis presented in this paper assumes c is 20.62. Eq. (12) is later used to determine the number of wave encounters which generate spray within the simulation period.

Combining and integrating Eqs. (10) and (11) yield a total mass flux of water from the vessel-wave interaction per wave event, shown in Eq.(12):

$$\dot{M}_{wave} = \tau_s x_e U_{rs} \int \omega(z) dz \quad (12)$$

While Eq.(12) yields the total mass flux per wave event, it does not relate the mass flux to droplet size. This is critical for simulation purposes because different droplet sizes have vastly different trajectories due to their varying inertial terms and relative sensitivity to the velocity field. As such, a relationship between droplet size and percent contribution to mass flux is critical to accurately determine the location of ice accretion.

A mathematical model relating droplet size to mass flux does not exist for spray generated by a vessel moving through a wave. However, correlation between droplet size and mass flux were determined using data from experiments aboard the U.S. Coast Guard Cutter (CGC) ‘Midgett’. Ryerson (1995) measured droplet size and quantity as percentages of the spray cloud as the ‘Midgett’ transited the Bering Sea in February, Fig.4a. This data was then related to the mass of a droplet based upon its size. For example, if 10% of the droplets in the spray cloud were of a certain size range (by radius), the overall percent contribution to the total mass flux from droplets within that range could be computed by calculating the mass of droplets within that range, Fig.4b. The total mass flux from one wave was then solved using Eq.(13). By integrating the data in Fig.4b with respect to droplet radius for a given droplet range, one droplet could represent a percentage of mass from the wave-generated spray.

Fig.4: (a) Droplet concentration percentage vs. droplet radius as presented in Ryerson’s 1995 study on ‘CGC Midgett’ (b) integrated data to plot the weight contribution percentage vs. droplet radius.

This effectively relates the mass in the spray cloud to droplet size in the cloud formed from vessel-wave interaction. Although large droplets do not make up the bulk of the droplets in the spray cloud, Fig.4b shows that most of the mass in the cloud due to vessel-wave interactions is due to the largest droplet sizes. 80% of the spray cloud weight is carried by droplets only 10% of the total number of droplets, or those droplets greater than 250 micrometres in size.

With this relationship, the wind-generated and wave-generated spray can now be modelled as droplets representing a parcel of mass. Droplets released from the locations described in Tables I and II now had an overall mass associated with them, representing a percentage of the overall spray flux from the waves and wind.

6. Simulation results

For the preliminary, static analysis onboard ‘Scandies Rose’, one hour was selected. It may later be important to determine an hourly icing rate. The mass fluxes were combined to determine total mass generated from both waves and wind by Eqs. (13) and (14):

$$M_{tot} = n_{waves} A_{grid} \dot{M}_{wave} + t_{sim} A_{grid} \dot{M}_{wind} \quad (13)$$

$$n_{waves} = \frac{t_{sim}}{P_w} \quad (14)$$

where n_{waves} represents the number of wave events encountered by the vessel within the given simulation period, t_{sim} is the simulation time in seconds, and A_{grid} is the grid area where wind- and wave-generated spray originates.

The wave encounter interval, P_w , is shown in Eq.(15), *Aksyutin (1979)*:

$$P_w = \frac{1.56\tau_w^2}{v_{sw}} \quad (15)$$

The crab pot stack was modelled as a series of planar surfaces and marked where a droplet intercepted or “hit” the crab pot stack. Fig.5 illustrates locations where the droplets struck the boundaries of the crab pot stack or deck.

Fig.5: Locations indicating where a droplet hit the outer edges, and vertical boundaries of the first rows of crab pots from the wave-spray simulation. Blue indicates the extreme edges of the crab pot box, orange is the first vertical boundary of crab pots, yellow is the second boundary, and purple indicate strikes of the deck.

While Fig.5 identifies the location where a droplet has hit the crab pot stack, it does not indicate the mass of the droplet nor the mass of the parcel that the droplet represents. For later simulations, the mass of the parcel needed to be tracked to identify the localized mass flux to the crab pot stack. Next, the mass of the parcel was traced and then deposited on the crab pot stack.

6.1 Parcel striking crab pot stack

The mass of water accumulating on the outer starboard edge of the crab pot stack needed to be tracked and obtained from the droplet hits identified in the simulation results presented in Fig.5. This was accomplished by depositing some mass of the parcel on the crab pot stack.

DeNucci and Brahan (2022) determined that a crab pot has a porosity, γ , of 0.905, i.e., surfaces are over 90% porous. While a given droplet may strike the outer plane of the crab pot stack, another droplet may or may not hit the crab pot structure (tubing or netting). Given such a large porosity, it is in fact very likely that the water droplet will not hit and continue to flow through the crab pot. However, one droplet represented a parcel of mass and many times the number of droplets of that size originating from both the wave and the air. Therefore, it was assumed that $(1 - \gamma)$ or 9.5% of the mass of the parcel was deposited on the starboard boundary of the crab pots when that droplet intercepted the starboard edge of the crab pot plane. While the simulation could track all the crab pot boundaries, the extreme edge was only modelled as a proof of concept for this paper. In any case, the outer, starboard edge is most interesting; this is where ice begins to accrete.

With each “hit” of the outer starboard plane of the crab pot stack, the appropriate mass as a function of porosity was added in that location for later heat transfer or icing analysis at that node. Fig.6 displays

the mass flux concentration of the wave-generated sea spray while Fig.7 displays the mass flux concentration from the wind-generated spray.

Fig.6: Plot of water flux ($\text{kg/m}^2\text{-wave}$) for the side of the crab pot stack after one wave encounter for wave-generated sea spray. Largest magnitudes are $9 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{-wave}$. The wave spray period is $\sim 4 \text{ s}$.

Fig.7: Plot of water flux ($\text{kg/m}^2\text{-s}$) for the side of the crab pot stack for the wind-generated sea spray. Largest magnitudes are $0.08 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{-s}$. This spray is continuous given the weather conditions.

The total mass originating from wind and waves was found to be over 350 MT/hr given the weather conditions and relative course and speed to the oncoming waves. The total mass hitting the starboard side of the crab pots was determined to be 21.75 MT/hour. The remaining mass either flowed through the starboard edge of the crab pot stack or missed it entirely. Additionally, Fig.6 shows that most of the incoming water flux hits the forward starboard portion of the crab pot stack, giving mass to the droplets analysis shown in Fig.5.

7. Conclusions

The mass flux into the crab pot stack from the wave-vessel interaction and air free surface interactions during the weather conditions ‘Scandies Rose’ encountered are an intermediate step toward the final calculation of the icing on the crab pot stack, but conclusions can still be drawn from the results presented. The contribution of the incoming mass of water from the vessel-wave interaction is much larger than that of the wind-generated spray. However, the wind-generated spray is not insignificant and should still be accounted for when analysing the mass flux of water incoming to the crab pot stack that is available to form ice. Figs.6 and 7 show that the water hits the crab pot stack in differing locations; therefore, both sources must be factored into the icing model. Due to the highest concentrations of incoming water flux, the starboard, forward portion of the crab pot stack can be expected to accrete ice at the fastest rate.

While Fig.3 highlights the fact that many water droplets originating from the wave-generated sea spray miss the vessel entirely, most of the mass is carried by the largest droplets. Fig.6 shows this, as the largest mass fluxes occur in areas where the largest water droplets are hitting the crab pot stack as they are less prone to the effect of the wind.

8. Future work

Now that the mass flux into the side of the crab pot stack has been found from both the wave-generated and wind-generated spray, the values can be incorporated into a heat and mass transfer model of the crab pot stack to conduct an icing analysis.

However, there are limitations to the model presented. First, it only models the outer starboard plane of the crab pot stack. A future model could incorporate the front of the stack along with the intermediary vertical and horizontal planes. The droplet presented represents a parcel of mass representing thousands of other droplets which can be deposited at the various locations throughout the journey. Fig.5 highlights the fact that a simulated droplet can impact multiple locations along its journey, leaving $(1 - \gamma)$ of water behind.

Additionally, one droplet, most notably a droplet originating from the wave-generated spray, represents many thousands if not millions, of droplets about that are approximately the same size. While there is some comfort in that there are over 40,000 droplets released during the simulation, the number of droplets simulated are a tiny fraction of the over 350 MT/hr of weight they represent. Additional simulations could provide more fidelity to the results.

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3D Mapping of Underwater Hulls for Robotic Guidance

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Abstract

This paper gives an overview of describing hull surfaces, with a special focus on re-creating existing hulls where the original hull design description is not available in digital format. Key technologies are parametric hull descriptions and 3D scans. It is recommended to use dedicated service providers for the task.

1. Introduction

The shipping world is striving towards a sustainable future, not just on decarbonization, but also on many other aspects. One of these other aspects is biofouling management with the focus on preventing the spread of aquatic invasive species. Both decarbonizing shipping and biofouling management tie in with hull cleaning. If we further add the desire to eliminate release of paint particles (including microplastics) and biocides in the hitherto dominantly popular self-polishing copolymer (SPC) coatings for ships, a logical conclusion is predicting a mechanical era of hull management using, e.g., robotic cleaning of large surfaces coated with non-biocidal paints and ultrasonic protection for niche areas, *Bertram (2020,2022)*.

The rapidly evolving field of robotic hull cleaning comes with many detail issues that need to be addressed on the way to technically and economically mature solutions. 3D hull descriptions are an example, where such descriptions would be useful for:

- Mapping - Underwater inspection and cleaning robots should cover the hull completely, but with minimal overlap. Especially when envisioning team robotics, a common ‘map’ of the ship is a base for efficient robotic path planning. This applies particularly for crawler robots, Fig.1, but to some extent also to free-floating robots that follow the hull keeping a short distance to it, Fig.2.

Fig.1: Hull Skater crawler robot, source: Jotun

Fig.2: Seasam free floating robot, source: Delair

- Reporting – Ships are 3D objects. Reporting benefits from intuitive 3D maps where findings can be attached as text and/or images. Industry practice is using simple generic sketches, where divers mark findings qualitatively, Fig.3 (left). *Guéré and Gambini (2021)* present already and improvement, appropriate for digital inspection and reporting purposes, albeit still based on 2D schematic displays, Fig.3 (right). Using 3D models with very intuitive marking of findings on such a 3D map, similar to Google map pins, has been successfully used e.g.,

for ship structural hull condition monitoring, Fig.4, *Cabos et al. (2010)*. This approach has been implemented for years in DNV's ShipManager software, <https://www.dnv.com/services/hull-integrity-and-ship-maintenance-software-shipmanager-hull-1531>. *Cabos et al. (2017)* envision even wallpaper mapping of drone inspection images on the 3D model to allow viewing in Virtual Reality, Fig.5.

Fig.3: Manual 2D sketches (left) have progressed to digital 2D displays (right), source: Notilo+

Fig.4: DNV's ShipManager (Hull)

Fig.5: Vision of drone-based images mapped on 3D model and viewed in VR, *Cabos et al. (2017)*

But most of the time, ship owners do not have any hull description for their ships. This problem occurs also for other applications, e.g. for hull condition assessment schemes, *Cabos et al. (2008)*, and trim optimization, *Hansen and Hochkirch (2013)*. “One of the issues of creating the hull models for existing ships is the eventual lack of information. Whenever the only data available are the drawings available onboard the ship, the model must be developed from a reduced set of data and also in a short period of time [...] [T]he simplified model should be [...] developed from the information on the drawings commonly existing on board the ship, such as the general arrangement, body plan, docking plan, midship section, shell expansion, transverse and longitudinal bulkhead.”, *Cabos et al. (2008)*.

There are two key reverse engineering techniques to recreate CAD (computer aided design) descriptions for existing ship geometries, namely parametric hull design techniques, e.g. *Harries (1998)*, *Veelo (2004)*, and 3D scanning. These will be described in more detail in the following.

2. Hull description options for re-creating existing hulls

2.1. CAD surface descriptions

When re-creating an existing hull, the aim is to come up with a mathematical representation that is close to the ship as designed, built or in service. The purpose of the reverse engineered description is not to replicate the ship for reproduction in another shipyard, but rather to make the geometry digitally available for (i) high-fidelity hydrodynamic analyses, e.g. as needed for trim optimization, performance monitoring and advanced weather routing, and (ii) for services such as cleaning, inspection and reporting. The former requires an accurate model while the latter can accept a coarser approximation.

In general, for the re-creation of geometry, the same mathematical methods are used as for the original generation of ship hulls, propulsion systems, propellers, rudders etc. at the design stage. Both a designer and an engineer tasked with re-creating the hull would use so-called boundary representations (BReps) as offered within major Computer Aided Design systems (CAD) such as CAESES, Catia, NAPA, NX, Pias, Rhino, etc. In these systems curves are typically established from point data, for instance, points to be interpolated or points with which a curve is associated as for B-splines, *Piegl and Tiller (1995)*. Surfaces may also be generated by means of point data, for instance, via the vertices of a B-spline's defining polyhedron.

Typically, ship hull surfaces are generated via sets or meshes of curves, Fig.6. A hull mesh may comprise intersecting curves in different dimensions, such as sections, waterlines, diagonals etc. These curves need to be defined before they serve as input to surfaces. Setting up curves and surfaces manually from point data is rather tedious. Moreover, it calls for skillful interactive work by an expert familiar with the CAD system at hand. This is quite costly. Typically, several days of work are required.

Fig.6: 2D hull information can be combined to 3D hull description

An alternative approach to curve and surface modeling is to utilize sophisticated parametric modeling. Here, the geometry of interest is described using a reasonably small set of parameters that serve as high-level descriptors. Typically, a hull form can be sufficiently defined by 30 to 50 parameters as soon as the topology has been selected, *Harries (1998,2010)*. Parametric ship hull models are tailored to specific ship types, using key differentiators such as:

- number of hulls, i.e. monohull, catamaran (possibly SWATH), trimaran, etc.
- type and number of the propulsors, i.e. classic propeller, ducted propeller, Voith-Schneider propeller, podded drives, etc.
- type of aftbody, i.e. single integrated skeg, twin-skeg, etc.
- type of forebody, i.e. straight stem, integrated bulbous bow, etc.

Re-using such tailored macro-models for a suitable ship hull can bring about a CAD definition within just a few hours of work. Information for the required parameters can be retrieved from

- General Arrangement plans (main dimensions, center plane contour, deck contours, amidship contour),
- Steel plans (some further cross section contours over the length of the ship)
- hydrostatics tables/stability book (longitudinal center of buoyancy and displacement volume at various drafts),
- selected measurements and photographs, e.g. from dock stays,
- scans,
- and even from educated guesses, e.g. from similar ships where actual or re-engineered hull descriptions exist.

Fig.7 gives an illustration of a parametric model of the forebody of a container carrier. Similarly, Fig.8 shows a parametric model for a conventional propeller for which even fewer parameters are needed to establish a mathematically closed definition. For further examples and animations see <https://www.caeses.com/industries/marine/>.

Fig.7: Parametric form description for containership hull (as implemented in CAESSES)

Fig.8: Parametric form description for propeller (as implemented in CAESSES)

Details of various parametric modeling techniques are given in *Harries et al. (2018)*. For a general understanding it may suffice to point out the decisive difference between a standard CAD approach – as would be used in an interactive re-creation process of a ship – and its parametric counterpart: In the standard approach the curves and surfaces are produced first from which important characteristics of the shape, e.g. the displacement, the area of the design waterline etc., are derived, while in the parametric approach the process is turned around, i.e., the desired characteristics are compiled and, subsequently, the curves and surfaces are computed accordingly.

2.2. 3D scanning

The prime application for 3D scanning inside ships are retrofit projects. The state of the art is very mature, allowing to import 3D scanned point clouds directly into widely used CAD software, *Blom and Czapla (2021)*. Laser scans on ships can be combined with photographic color information to create realistic 3D models which look like the real ship, but allow also extracting geometrical information such as quantifying space and distance between objects, Fig.9.

Fig.9: Laser scans (top) can be combined with photos to create realistic 3D representations (bottom), source: Blom Maritime

Scanning ship hulls from the outside in drydocks is similarly straightforward; however, in-water scanning of ship geometries is much more complicated, due to the relative motions between underwater robots carrying scanning devices and ships (which move due to natural waves always present). Using self-referenced underwater color laser scanners, this problem can be solved, Fig.10, and highly accurate underwater scans are also possible, with resolution of 0.01 mm on crawling robots and 0.5 mm on free-floating robots, *Paranhos (2020)*.

Fig.10: 3D underwater scanning can reproduce accurate as-built/as-is reproductions of hull geometries, source: Kraken Robotics, Kroes Marine Projects

Naturally, both parametric hull design and 3D scanning can be combined in order to increase the level of accuracy of producing a geometric twin and to cover blind spots not accessible (or not accessed) by the laser when scanning, respectively.

3. Conclusions

Various reverse engineering approaches to recreate ship geometries exist and some have reached industry maturity, most notably

- parametric hull descriptions using naval architectural parameters to describe the hull;
- 3D scanning which by now is also possible under water

As the involved processes require special software and know-how, and as they are only performed once for each ship, the reverse engineering tasks should be outsourced to dedicated service providers.

Finally, using such recreated hull and propeller geometries for purposes such as trim optimization, Condition Assessment Schemes, or biofouling management activities does not violate the intellectual property of shipyards, as the recreated approximation is not used to create products made by the shipyard.

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Digital Twin for Evaluation of Emission Reduction by Novel Technologies

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Abstract

This paper presents a development of a digital model for a bulk carrier, developed within the CHEK project. The results of resistance and propulsion simulations and energy simulations, including the impact of advanced energy saving technologies, are presented. An overview of CAPEX and net present value calculation methods is provided. Such a digital model can then be transformed into a digital twin which will offer numerous efficiency gains during ship's operational life.

1. Introduction

Digital Twins is one of the buzziest and hottest topic and seen as a key prospect for the progress in the marine sector. The digital twin is a software model that can be used for simulation of scenarios. The following definition can be found in Wikipedia - Digital Twin is "real-time digital replica of a physical device". Another definition is given by *Fonseca and Gaspar (2021)*, where the Digital Twin is "a digital asset that simulates the behaviours of a physical counterpart". According to Google Scholars, there are over 61,000 publications containing the phrase "Digital Twins ships". *Bekker (2018)*, *Bekker et al. (2019)* outlined what should be measured and analysed for the Arctic research vessel for the proposed digital twin. Using a simulation model based on a neural network, *Coraddu et al. (2019)* estimate the speed loss caused by marine fouling. A digital twin for monitoring of structural fatigue is presented by *Vanderhorn et al. (2022)*.

The subject is no longer being dealt with exclusively by the scientific organisations but is also starting to become part of the development work of shipyards and design offices. This article is an example of the application of the digital twin idea for modelling ship energy consumption in a design office.

Decarbonising shipping can be technically divided into three main categories: optimising operations, improving, and optimising design and equipment, and low-carbon fuel alternatives. Digital twins based on measured system data are often proposed as a technical tool for shipping decarbonisation, at least in the context of energy savings and maintenance of good operational efficiency. A digital twin of a ship can be created using measured data from the operating vessel. However, we should focus on optimising the ship from the early concept design phase if we want to have the greatest possible impact on the overall performance of the ship. This is also the time to ensure that the necessary capacity for future sustainable fuels is available on board the vessel.

It is therefore possible to focus on cost-effective technical ship optimisation, such as system sizing and optimisation of machinery, hull, and propulsion systems, as early as possible in the ship's life cycle by creating a digital representation of the ship. The creation of digital ship models in several "generations" is a pragmatic way to combine the development of the ship's environmental performance in the traditional ship design phases from conceptual design through basic and detail design and ship construction, followed by the operational phase.

Fig.1 above provides a simplified illustration of how a digital thread for a ship can be understood, first considering several generations of digital models when designing. It is important to note that the operational data of the existing ships, which are a relevant reference for the design of the new ship, provide a useful input for the design. These feedback loops are shown by a blue arrow. The digital models generated during the design phase can be used for the digital twin of the ship by calibration with measured operational data, but the interface between design models and "digital twin" models needs to be defined separately if the same party is not responsible for both the digital design models and the digital twin.

Fig.1: Digital thread

The approach to the idea of Digital Twins in the CHEK project is based on 3 levels, Fig.2:

- Simulation Model Calibration
- Digital Prototype ver. 1.0
- Digital Prototype ver. 2.0

Fig.2: Process of energy simulations evolution from historical model to Digital Prototype

The first level of our approach is model calibration. The purpose of the first part is to create the first simulation model of the ship using only the historically measured profile data as operational input and to calibrate the components within the simulation model in terms of the main power-consuming and producing groups with the measured data. The variables calibrated at this stage of the simulation are mostly those that are not the focus of detailed optimization in the CHEK project and are also used as input in the other stages of the simulation, at least initially. The fuel consumption tolerances of the main engines or the heat and power loads for the case ships are examples of such variables. These variables may evolve throughout the project and digital modelling.

Fig.3 shows in more detail the process of getting to the level of being able to create a 'digital prototype v2.0'. The process appears to be linear. However, there are feedback loops. For example, a sail-

equipped bulker will be more likely to follow favourable wind conditions. A conventional bulker, on the other hand, will try to avoid rough weather and minimise the route length between destination.

In this article, we present the activities of the Digital Prototype 2.0. Based on the hull forms we developed, an estimation of shaft power was carried out for the technologies presented. The first step was to prepare the weather for each sailing point resulting from the proposed route. Fig.4 shows the data extraction algorithm for each point based on the Copernicus databases, *MOI (2015,2018)*.

Fig.3: Separation between energy efficiency entities

Fig.4 Algorithm for extraction and processing of data for added resistance

Based on the weather profiles, in a second step the ship's resistance was estimated. Calm water resistance was calculate using Siemens StarCCM+ and reference model test. Additionally, the power required was determined in the same level. Furthermore, calculations were carried out to estimate the effect of the sails on increasing the thrust. The effect of hull roughness on resistance was also investigated. Added resistance generated by wave are calculated using the *ITTC (2014) STAwave1*, *ITTC (2014) STAwave2* methods and direct calculation in Ansys Aqwa. All calculations in the second level are performed for a particular point in time and space. Based on the results from the second level, averaging was carried out according to the length of the individual route sections. These two levels are part of DeltaSeas model.

Based on the results from the hydro and energy parts, the economic parameters were determined. The most important economic parameters determined in this section are Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and net present value (NPV).

2. Bulker description, new technologies and routes

The article presents the idea of a digital twin of a Kamsarmax-type bulk carrier ship. The main characteristics of the ship are given in Table I. A base bulk carrier hull form and its variants are developed from this data.

Table I: Basic particulars of Kamsarmax bulker carrier

LOA	229.00 m
LPP	225.06 m
Breadth	32.26 m
Deadweight and draft	80962 MT at 14.475 m
MCR and rpm	8880 kW at 86.5 rpm
Laden- service speed and shaft power	14 knots at 80% MCR
Laden- economical speed and shaft power	12.3 at 45% MCR

During the CHEK project we tested various technologies to minimise emission and maximize energy efficiency of the bulk carrier. These included:

- sails
- air lubrication
- antifouling system
- gate rudder
- changing propulsion train
- hybridization
- electrification

In this article we present results for first three technologies.

The assumption is that the ship has two sails areas as part of the propulsion system. A 4DOF analysis of the ship's motions and a force balance optimisation routine to determine the vessel's yaw, heel moments, thrust and leeway is essential to predict the savings from sail-assisted propulsion accurately.

In order to reduce friction resistance, the air lubrication system is designed so that the air carpet spreads out and covers the flat bottom. By simply using a percentage reduction in the final shaft power requirement, the effect of air lubrication is taken into account. Drift and yaw generate by sails would also have an impact on the performance of this technology.

The six routes shown in Table II were used to assess the impact of the different technologies.

Table II: Routes

	Departure	Arrival	Via	Length
A	Brazil	China	Cape of Good Hope	11220 nm
B	China	Australia (Newcastle)		4812 nm
C	Australia (Newcastle)	Brazil	Cape Horn	7243 nm
D	Australia (Newcastle)	Brazil	Cape of Good Hope	8698 nm
E	Rotterdam	Baltimore		3646 nm
F	Baltimore	Brazil		5002 nm

Routes were prepared using Wartsila voyage planning tool. The routes were prepared without considering the local weather, only the length of the route was minimized on the basis of the Great Circle - orthodrome. The impact of weather routing is a separate item to be studied in project CHEK, which is not included in the results of this article.

3. Hull form development

A standard ship design practice is followed for the development of alternative hull forms, which includes the following steps:

- Identify the selection criteria
- Select variables and decide how to achieve them,
- Recognize the constraints that have been identified and that impose limits on design changes,
- Generate an alternative hull shape,
- Conduct the calculations.
- Compare the results

Several potential selection criteria have been identified. Based on these, the following two have been chosen:

- low calm water resistance
- low added resistance in waves

In preparing the alternative hull forms, changes to the following elements were considered: width of stern bulb, angle of frames forward of propeller, radius of frame shape between flat bottom and stern bulb, angle of frame at waterline, transverse and vertical location of bulb, widest point of entrance angles of waterlines at bow, width of deck and deck knuckle lines. In the process of the creation of alternative hull forms, there has been an assumption that there will be no change in main dimensions incl. displacement, no reduction of stability, location of propeller/propulsors are the same, propeller tip clearance for all hull is the same. Fig.5 illustrate the difference in hull form for three alternative bulk carrier.

Fig.5: Hull forms comparisons

Table III: Basic particular of three bulk carrier hull forms in full load

		BR1	BA1	BA2
LPP	[m]	225.06	225.06	225.06
Beam	[m]	32.26	32.26	32.26
Draft	[m]	12.20	12.20	12.20
Block Coefficient	[-]	0.876	0.873	0.874
LCB	[m]	114.73	119.01	114.73
Wetted surface	[m]	11700	12883	11485
Metacenter	[m]	11.98	13.61	13.57

Table IV: Effective power [kW] for design draft of T=12,2 m for various speeds and hull forms

Hull form	11.5 kn	%	12.5 kn	%	14.5 kn	%
BR1	2416	100.00	3041	100.00	4791	100.00
BA1	2282	94.45	2919	96.00	4683	97.74
BA2	2305	95.40	2926	96.23	4619	96.40

4. Estimation of effects of other technologies

The ITTC STA-WAVE 2 method for calculating the additional resistance in waves is used in this article. The limitation of STA-WAVE 2 is that it only applies to wave directions of $\pm 45^\circ$ to the bow. The added resistance from 45° to 180° is not used in calculating the added wave resistance. In any case, the beam sea will not create additional resistance, but it will create additional side drift forces on the vessel.

Some literature review on wind tunnel tests is carried out to estimate the effect of more than one sail, *Tillig et al.*, (2020). In principle, there will be a reduction in the efficiency of the second sail that operates in the wake of the first sail. Two sails are considered in the thrust calculations for wind-assisted propulsion. At this stage of the project, and in this article, the authors have assumed a 20% reduction in lift force for 2 sails. This approach is conservative but produces reasonably realistic results.

Air lubrication reduces frictional resistance between the flat bottom of the hull and the water, ultimately reducing shaft power requirements. Silverstream's air lubrication system is anticipated to reduce the shaft power requirement on large flat bottom vessels such as bulkers by $\sim 7-10\%$. At this stage, we can assume that the percentage will remain constant once the air lubrication system is installed on board the bulker. As well as fuel savings, the system is expected to reduce hull fouling in the flat bottom area due to the bubble carpet layer that spreads along the hull.

The anti-fouling system was another technology considered when estimating the required thrust. Table V shows the preliminary results of analysing the effect of antifouling.

Table V: Summary of representative fouling conditions, the equivalent sand roughness (ks), the average coating roughness (Rt50) and percentage increase in PE

Description of condition	ks (μm)	AHR (Rt50 in)	Estimated increase in PE
Typical as applied Antifouling coating	30	150	0%
Light slime	100	300	5.3%
Heavy slime	300	600	10.8%
Small Calcareous	1000	1000	15.4%

5. Operational profile – energy simulation results

The results presented in this chapter are based on routes A, B and C, corresponding to the voyage Praia Mole - CJK - Newcastle (Australia) - Praia Mole, Figs. 6 and 7. The hotel and heat power requirements have been modelled following the ship's mode of operation. The temperature of the seawater is modelled at a constant 25°C until more accurate inputs are available to the model. In addition, the model does not consider the correct sequence of port calls, which is acceptable in this case as the ship is not in port at any time. In this case, this is acceptable as port calls contribute $< 5\%$ of the total energy consumption. Most of the simulations are unaffected by the operating modes' order.

5% improvement in propulsion power consumption is a significant difference between the reference and new hulls. Hull fouling is a significant contributor to energy consumption. By default, all simulations in this article assume a clean hull condition for the new hull and 20% increase in propulsion power to quantify the effect of hull fouling.

Fig.6: Voyage Praia Mole - CJK - Newcastle (Australia) - Praia Mole

Fig.7: Propulsion power distribution with and without sails

The first comparison has been carried out for two types of engines - two-stroke and four-stroke DF engines. A series of reference electrical load analyses (ELA) for bulker concepts with two-stroke and four-stroke engines have been studied for the differences between the hotel loads. Fig.8 presents the difference in hotel loads for both engine configuration.

Fig.8: Indicative differences in hotel load with 2 two-stroke and four-stroke DF machinery

Further energy savings can be achieved with a switch from HFO to LBG fuel.

The simulations covered 12 cases of technologies and their combinations and 12 months:

- 2S benchmark – 2 stroke engine, operational profile describes above and hull BA1.
- 2S Fouling – like 2S benchmark + 20 % fouling margin added to propulsion power demand.
- 4S new benchmark - new benchmark with the 4-stroke configuration
- Batteries - 4-Stroke benchmark + 500 kWh battery with a spinning reserve function
- Shore Power - 4-Stroke benchmark + shore power available in all ports
- ORCs - 4-Stroke benchmark + 2 x 150 kW heat to power modules installed in the system.
- ALS - 4-Stroke benchmark + air lubrication savings
- Sails - 4-Stroke benchmark + sails
- Gate Rudder - 4-Stroke benchmark + 8 % constant propulsion power savings
- 4s LBG - 4-Stroke benchmark + LBG as the primary fuel. Includes improved engine efficiency
- CHEK Combo - All the above energy-saving measures combined except the gate rudder
- LBG combo - All the above energy-saving measures combined except the gate rudder. LBG as the primary fuel

The combined results of the simulations on the full year profile are presented in Fig.9.

Fig.9: Attained CII performance vs CII reference line (required CII) for year 2019 level for all cases

Fig.9 shows that the use of the technologies proposed by the CHEK project enables reductions in CII performance. Most of the proposed technologies produce reductions of a few to several per cent. Only the use of LBG gives an almost 100% reduction in CII performance.

Ongoing Capex and NPV simulations will provide estimated payback time for each case taking into account maintenance, fuel costs and CO2 costs. Preliminary results show payback time between 5 and 25 years, while most of the solutions have negative NPV for 10 year time horizon.

6. Digital Twin idea

As described above, our approach to the digital thread idea is based on two tools - DeltaSea and DeltaKey, Fig.10. The main elements in our approach to digital twins in CHEK project are Ship performance data, operational profile, main energy consumers and machinery configuration. Fig.10 shows the basic building blocks of our digital prototype. It also shows the information flows between them. Fig.11 shows the basic input parameters for the model. The user interface of DeltaKey is shown

in Fig.12. Both models are based on several scripts developed in Python and Matlab. Python code were developed for the DeltaSeas parts. Matlab and Simulink are used to create DeltaKey model. Fig.11 presents all information which are used in approach to digital twin.

Fig.10 DeltaSea and DeltaKey workflow

Fig.11 Inputs element to Digital Twin

Fig.12 User interface for DeltaKey

7. Conclusion

The article gave a brief overview of how we see the Digital Twin. Starting from the reproduction of the measurement results at the start through more complex models to a reasonably complete model. We are still developing what we call Digital Prototype models, but in the next few months or so, our models will evolve into something we can call Digital Twins.

While developing the individual components of our Digital Prototype or Digital Twin, we noticed various elements that could be expanded. One of these elements is the extension and refinement of the sails model so that we can also study their influence on the final results.

Abbreviations

2S – 2 stroke engine

4S – 4 stroke engine

ALS – Air Lubrication System

CHEK – deCarbonising sHipping by Enabling Key technology symbiosis on real vessel concept designs

ELA – Electrical Load Analyses

LBG – Liquefied Biogas (fuel)

ORC – Organic Rankine Cycle (waste heat to electricity)

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Concept of a Digital New Hull Survey Process

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Abstract

This paper provides an updated progress status since COMPIT 2022, outlining a further matured concept for a continuous, digital, remote hull survey process, and results on automated detection and measurement of deformations with depth cameras. Previous COMPIT papers presented results on automated corrosion and crack detection.

1. Introduction

The paper provides an update on R&D results since COMPIT 2020. The motivation and background of this R&D project and initial results were reported in *Stensrud et al. (2019)*, updated results in *Stensrud et al. (2020)* and *Stensrud and Klausen (2022)*.

The paper presents a concept of a new, digital process for hull surveys that takes advantage of robot technologies to collect data of the physical asset, and algorithms to detect findings and assess the hull condition, to reduce the need for surveyor on-site presence and man entry into confined spaces to inspect the cargo and ballast tanks. The compliance decision is therefore based on assessment of the digital twin rather than the physical asset. The previous COMPIT papers reported on the technical feasibility of drone-based inspections. In COMPIT22, early thoughts on a new survey process were briefly presented which have now matured. Likewise, the supporting tool suite has progressed. Since then, there have also been regulatory advances with regard to remote inspections. In January 2023, IACS recommendation UR Z29, allowing Remote Class Surveys, entered into force, *IACS (2022)*.

2. Current survey process

The objective of the Class survey is to assess the compliance of the physical asset. The surveyor inspects the physical asset and collects information about the hull condition. This information is used as basis for a decision to re-issue a new set of Class certificates. The information is presented primarily as PDF documents with text and some images of findings. The current hull survey process is prescriptive rather than condition based. This means that survey intervals are periodical at fixed intervals and the inspection scope is explicitly defined. The prescriptive Rules are based on a) scientific principles, b) empirical evidence collected over many years, and 3) pragmatics. For example, the 5-year renewal scheme is partly pragmatic, based on the operational cycle of some ship routes. Similarly, the survey scope is based on the same empirical observations. For example, the visual close-up scope is in practice just targeted spot checks of hull areas known to be prone to defects such as cracks. The objective of the survey is to “establish reasonable assurance that the hull structure is in compliance with the rules and suitable for continued and safe operations”, *DNV-RU-SHIP Pt.1 Ch.1 Sec.3 [2.2]*. Reasonable assurance is ensured through several means. First, the surveyor is onsite and physically enters the hull compartments to examine them. Second, the examination itself is a combination of visual inspections (see, feel, touch, smell), thickness measurements, and an overall assessment of the actual condition of an asset. For certain vessel types, because of historical accidents and type of cargo carried, the visual inspection is furthermore a combination of a general visual examination and visual close-up spot checks in designated areas.

Where a crack in the coating is detected and a crack in the steel is suspected, the surveyor may remove coating and apply additional NDT techniques such as eddy currents for further examination. Third, the prescriptive inspection scope increases as the vessel gets older, both the overall and the close-up examination. The prescriptive scope is based on empirical knowledge, data, and insight gathered over many years. However, even the largest close-up examination scope is still only

covering selected parts of the hull. Fourth, the owner is obliged to maintain the hull at defined intervals, report defects, repair damages, and record these activities. This shall be included in the vessel's maintenance system, *DNV-RU-SHIP Pt.1 Ch.1 Sec.3 [1.3]*.

In the current process, the attending DNV surveyor and/or Approved Service Supplier (AOSS) collect the factual data. The factual, objective, data collected is based on the visual examination and typically includes photos of findings, thickness measurements, measurements of some finding types, e.g. of deformations (buckling, indents), pitting, and cracks. The collected factual data are then manually annotated with text descriptions. Thickness measurements are usually supplemented with drawings indicating their location. Photos of findings are supplemented with textual descriptions of the finding and its location. Manual measurements of deformations and pitting are manually reported in text. Corrosion extent is usually not measured quantitatively, just subjectively assessed. Therefore, the assessment of the hull and the coating condition rating is generally not fully supported by objective, factual data that can be independently verified or enable a second opinion or re-assessment by another surveyor or hull expert. As an example, there are generally no or very few photos of hull locations in good condition. A GOOD rating is therefore based on trust in the assessment of the individual surveyor. Likewise, the thickness measurements and documentation of their location is often provided by an AOSS and based on a similar trust.

In conclusion, the current process is based on trust. There is a limited amount of objective, factual data that can support the claims of the AOSS or surveyor and the final decision on compliance or not. Furthermore, the compliance decision is based on the vessel's present condition. There is limited factual data that can support an assessment of the historical evolution of the hull condition and improve the decision process.

3. Concept of the new survey process

Back in COMPIT22, the idea was that the robots would replace the human inspector while in this new concept, the robot is a data collector. The robot collects data that feeds into a digital twin. The concept foresees a continuous data-driven compliance scheme rather than the current fixed-interval scheme where compliance is based on objective data and algorithms that analyze the data of a structural digital twin. This approach potentially has numerous benefits, including human safety (no man entry), objectivity and transparency (factual data collected of a large part of the structure, including the "problem-free" areas, which maybe constitute 95% of the total area), costs (more automation, less frequent stays in yard), and probably quality as well (more defects detected because of a much larger inspection scope). It should be observed that onsite inspections with man entry will not be eliminated but rather be reduced. Sometimes, it will be necessary to enter the compartment to remove coating and apply eddy currents to inspect for a crack in the steel under the coating or similar manual approaches.

The new process is to be supported by 3D tools for planning, collecting, and analysing data. The automated analysis presently consists of two algorithms, a defect detection and classification algorithm and defect probability algorithm. The first algorithm is the one that detects and classifies cracks, corrosion, and deformations. The data inputs currently consist of 2D RGB videos and images, and laser point clouds. The second algorithm computes the probability that there are defects in a compartment of a specific vessel. The probability is derived from the loads and fatigue that the hull has been subject to, as well as historical data from previous surveys, and data from the design, construction, and approval. The load and fatigue estimates are based on AIS data and weather data from the actual operation of the vessel. Compartments with a low defect probability may be exempted from the default inspection scope, thus reducing the inspection scope. The outcome is a certificate of compliance, as before, or a decision to do a targeted, onsite survey of the physical asset. Another outcome is an improved and transparent insight into the hull condition and a better basis for maintenance and repair decisions.

The data are collected by drones or other robots to ensure consistent and frequent data covering a

large scope, unlike today where photos usually are limited to compartment areas with defects, only documenting the defects, and the photos are not standardised in any way. In the new process, the overall condition of the compartment will therefore be visually documented. The extensive collection of data will provide improved knowledge, insight, and transparency of the actual condition (also of good condition) as well as of the evolution of the condition. The latter can be used to predict further evolution. An overview of the new process is illustrated in Fig.1. Some steps and supporting tools are presented in more detail in the following sub-sections.

Fig.1: Overview of the new process

4. Step 1 – initial data collection

The purpose of step 1 is 3-fold: first to obtain a 3D model; second, to use this 3D model to plan a standardized data collection scope which is to be executed in Step 2; third, to have an initial benchmark of the hull condition. To make a 3D model, high-precision point cloud data of the compartment is collected and converted into a model. Then, the 3D model is used to plan the scope of the future, recurring data collections. To have a benchmark of the coating condition, the point cloud is complemented with visual data such as images and videos of the whole compartment.

The images provide an overview of the compartment and are not expected to be close-up images that can be used to detect cracks or other finding types requiring a close-up examination. In general, the purpose of Step 1 is not to detect defects like cracks and deformations but rather to document the coating condition. Ideally, Step 1 is executed on the new-build.

4.1. Mapping the compartment with laser scanner

In step 1, a point cloud of the whole compartment is collected with a high-precision laser scanner. This step currently requires man entry and positioning the scanner in different locations to map the whole compartment.

The mapping with a high-precision laser scanner ensures that a detailed “as-built” 3D model is obtained which can be used to plan the inspection scope and the flight path of the drone. The mapping will detect deviations from the design and potential obstacles such as railings, ladder caging, and piping that may not be included in 2D drawings or a 3D model from the yard. Also, there might be small deviations between the 2D/3D design model and the actual construction, the “as-built”. The mapping is performed on new-builds as well as on ships in service.

The laser scan mapping is preferably complemented with a visual mapping with colour photos or video to document the initial condition and use it as a benchmark for assessing the further evolution of the hull condition.

In a first trial of a large oil cargo tank, approximately 70 scans from different scanner positions were executed to map the whole compartment in less than a day. Another trial, in a small cargo hold of a chemical tanker, only 7 scans were executed to map the whole compartment. In Fig.2, each colour

identifies a separate scan. The separate point clouds were then aligned into a single point cloud of the whole compartment. The point clouds must be partially overlapping in order to align them. The alignment was performed using a software package from Leica (Leica's Cyclone REGISTER 360 for connecting scans and Cyclone 3DR Desktop for processing of clouds.). The alignment algorithm made a few mistakes, aligning scans to wrong frames. These were manually corrected. The alignment of scans could potentially be improved by placing scanning aids, target objects, at carefully selected locations in the compartment.

The large number of scans of the oil cargo tank was required because structural elements like web frames, stiffeners, and big pipes hide parts of the structure and result in blind spots. Substantially fewer scans were required in the cargo hold of the chemical tanker that has less structural elements. Also, the scanner used was a small, mobile scanner with shorter range which also required more scans to ensure a sufficient overlap between the scans for aligning them into a single point cloud for the whole compartment. The scanner was positioned in all locations that could be accessed without climbing, such as the bottom plating and stringers.

Scanning took 6-7 hours for the large oil cargo hold and 0.5 hours for the small chemical tanker. As the oil cargo hold was a first trial, some of the time was used to decide on the scanner stations, the path between them, point cloud density, and other "first time" issues. Re-positioning the scanner was relatively effective for this small scanner. The scanner settings were medium point cloud density without photos, taking close to 2 minutes per station. For the purpose of using the point cloud to create a 3D model, basic density might be sufficient, which would reduce the scanning time. High density would probably be required to detect smaller defects like pitting and corrosion scabs.

Fig.2: 3D point cloud of small cargo hold of chemical tanker showing separate laser scans in distinct colors

4.2. Converting point cloud into 3D model

The final point cloud was then converted to a 3D model, depicted for a small chemical tanker in Fig.3. This step requires some manual effort, depending on the complexity of the geometry. In the small chemical tanker, scanning took 0.5 hours and processing and converting the point cloud into a 3D model took another 0.5-1 hours. The chemical tanker has few structures that cause blind spots for the scanning, and the flat, simple surfaces require little manual effort to convert the point cloud into a 3D model. The amount of effort for a geometrically more complex oil cargo hold depends on how detailed the 3D model needs to be for subsequent drone operations. For example, it might not be

necessary to include all small stiffeners on a web frame in the 3D model whereas it might be necessary to include the railings on the stringers as they are obstacles to the drone flight. If a sufficiently accurate “as-built” 3D model exists beforehand, the initial point cloud mapping may not be required.

A 3D model can be derived from the point cloud either using mesh methods or using basic pre-existing geometries. Currently, the latter approach appears more effective. Fig.3 (right) shows the 3D geometric model before cutting and trimming.

An alternative is to construct a 3D model from 2D drawings, but again it has somehow to be ensured that the 3D model contains sufficiently detail of potential obstructions to the automated drone flight. Often, pipes and other outfitting are not included in 2D drawings, and this information must therefore be collected elsewhere.

Fig.3: Smooth point cloud (left); 3D geometric model from point cloud (right)

4.3. Planning data collection scope in 3D model

This plan is the input to Step 2, the recurring data collections that have the double purpose of enabling assessment of the hull condition as well as detecting defects. The planning targets the collection of 2D images for close-up as well as overall examination. In addition, overview images and point clouds of 100% of the compartment would be collected (or with as high coverage as practically feasible), but this would not require detailed planning in the 3D model. The data collection close-up scope is planned in a 3D-based planning tool, Fig.4. A web-based prototype tool has been developed. The camera location (yellow dot) and the area to capture (red dot) are linked pairs, thus indicating the distance and view angle of the camera. The blue dot indicates a selected yellow or red dot. In Fig.4, it is not visible which yellow and red dots that belong together, but it is visible in the user interface. In the user interface, the user can also see what the camera sees and then adjust the camera location.

Fig.4: 3D model of cargo tank – data collection close-up points (red dots); inspection views/camera position (yellow dot); selected red/yellow point (blue dot)

The data collection scope should be as standardised as possible to enable comparison of the current hull condition with historical data in order to assess the evolution of the hull condition. Therefore, the planning of the data collection scope is intended to be performed only once in the vessel’s lifetime. However, with changes in the vessel’s condition, the data collection scope of close-up areas may be expanded. This will still enable comparison with historical data.

5. Step 2 and step 3 – Recurring data collection and compliance assessment

The purpose of Step 2 is to collect data, and the purpose of Step 3 is to use this data to detect findings, assess the hull condition and make a compliance decision. The assessment of the actual condition is enhanced with an assessment of the evolution of the hull condition. This insight may be used to predict further evolution and better plan repair and maintenance. The standardized data collection scope enables comparison with historical hull conditions.

The defect types in ship hulls of steel include cracks, corrosion, coating breakdown (flaking, blisters), and deformations. At COMPIT 2020, crack detection performance in single 2D images was reported, *Stensrud et al. (2020)*. At COMPIT 2022, crack detection performance in videos was reported, *Stensrud et al. (2022)*. Corrosion detection in 2D images was reported in *Hamre and Chen (2022)*. The extent of the corrosion is the basis for rating the coating condition according to *IACS Rec. 87 (2015)*.

5.1. Collecting close-up visual data with drones and automated defect detection

Fig.5 is an image taken from 20 cm distance showing two hairline thin cracks in the coating. One of the two cracks were detected. This is an example of how close the camera might have to be to detect initial cracking in the coating. Even such small coating cracks may be indicative of a crack in the steel.

Fig.5: Example of close-up image of cracks (red arrows) and automated detection (green rectangle)

Fig.6: Direct light (left) and oblique/ambient light (right); courtesy by EM&I

In Fig.6, the crack is almost invisible in the image with direct light but easily detectable in the image with oblique and ambient light. Together, these examples suggest that camera distances, camera angles, and light illumination are all crucial for improved detection of cracks in the coating. For other defect types, there might be similar data quality needs.

5.2. Collecting high-precision point clouds with tripod and without man entry

Laser scans are currently collected from a laser scanner mounted on a tripod. The tripod is lowered into the bottom of the tank through the manhole on the deck. This avoids man entry. Millimetre-precision laser scans can be collected with this procedure. Fig.7 shows an example of the high point cloud precision: the topography of a panel surface indicating where corrosion and blisters have developed. The laser scan captures the topology of the structure and can expose defect types like deformations, coating blisters, corrosion patches, pitting, and probably wastage (thinning of the steel), but probably not cracks.

Furthermore, promising trials on synchronous laser scanning from both sides of a panel can measure the steel thickness over the whole surface, as opposed to the current procedure of using point measurements with an ultrasound thickness measurement sensor (UTM).

Fig.7: High precision laser scan of panel surface topography showing corrosion scab and maybe coating blisters; courtesy by EM&I

The draw-back of the tripod approach is that the tripod locations are limited to the manhole locations and therefore there will be blind spots. However, in trials in large oil tanks, 5-6 apertures are often available, achieving 80-90% coverage, and this might be sufficient to claim “reasonable assurance that the hull structure is in compliance”. The scanning can be completed within half a day.

5.3. Automated detection of deformations in images

This section is an extract from, *Gong (2023)*, on deformation detection in 2D color images using deep learning, training the detector on a dataset of 8500 images of which 6200 images contained deformations and were labelled, whereas the remaining 2300 images did not contain deformations. 7% of the images were randomly selected as the test set. The test set results were F1 score = 0.68 and mAP = 0.70. For a full account of the data, procedure, and results, see the original paper. Fig.8 shows examples of deformation detection.

Fig.8: Examples of deformation detection in 2D images

5.4. Automated measurement of deformations with depth camera

This section is partly an extract from *Gong (2023)* and reports initial trials with depth camera (RGB-D) to measure deformations such as indents or buckling. Indents are caused by crashes. Buckling is caused by loads and therefore indicate weak structural strength, often caused by corrosion and wastage of steel.

For indents in plates, the maximum allowable indent depth is given by the formula in Fig.9. The spacing, S , between stiffeners typically is 600-800 mm. Therefore, the maximum allowable depth, δ , typically is 5-6 mm.

Fig.9: Maximum allowable indent in plates

Unlike indents, buckling is not accepted, in general (DNV-ITG-0330 Hull and equipment, survey and repair). This implies that any buckling, however small the depth, should be detected and repaired. Plate buckling exhibits a typical pattern where each panel bends in one direction, and the neighbouring panels bend in the opposite direction, Fig.10.

Fig.10: Plate buckling between stiffeners – weak/thin plate, strong stiffener

A deformation detector was developed to first detect deformations in 2D RGB images, similar to detection of cracks and corrosion. The detector is based on deep learning. A depth camera (RGB-D) was then used to *measure* the deformation. To validate the measurement accuracy, a 400x800 mm panel with a deformation pattern similar to buckling was designed and 3D-printed, Fig.11. The reason for making a 3D-printed panel was two-fold. First, it was an easy way of obtaining a buckled panel. Second, the ground truth is known from the design.

Fig.11: Simulated and 3D printed deformation

The depth camera measured a maximum deformation depth of 31 mm while the true maximum depth is 28 mm, a promising first trial. This technique provides a full surface measurement and consistent accuracy, as opposed to the current manual measurement approach using a board and a ruler to

measure a few points, and which probably is more error prone. For a full account of this study, refer to *Gong (2023)*. The deformation detector should in principle be able to classify indents and buckling since they exhibit different deformation patterns. This is to be validated in future research.

5.5. Automated detection & measurement of deformations from point clouds

Deformations can be detected as well as measured from the high-precision point clouds by comparing them with a 3D model. Currently, the detection is manual, but automated analysis is under development for detecting anomalies in point clouds. This could include deformations such as buckling and indents as well as pitting, wastage, and other geometric anomalies.

6. Conclusions and further work

The concept of the new survey process allows for crediting a hull compartment from data without requiring an onsite, man entry, inspection of the physical asset. Compared to the present process, data from almost all areas of the hull is collected, also of areas in good condition and not limited to photos of areas that document findings. In the new survey concept, the robots are considered as data collectors rather than inspectors. That is, they are not replacing the inspector. Furthermore, they are not replacing the surveyor or hull expert who make the assessment and the compliance decision.

High-precision point clouds are presently collected by a laser scanner mounted on a tripod. Future tests will mount the scanner on a drone (if within payload constraints) and investigate whether the expected larger stochastic errors in the point cloud can be handled by detection algorithms. The point clouds collected by the drone's lidar is currently used for mapping the compartment for navigation purposes.

Further work includes experimenting with drone speeds, cameras, camera angles, and light, to comply with the requirements for close-up photo quality for crack detection.

As for deformations, they can to some extent be detected in 2D images, but further work will investigate automated detection and measurement in high-precision point clouds.

High-precision, high density, point clouds may also add value to corrosion detection in 2D images in that they may be able to indicate wastage and pitting, thereby guiding automated ultrasound thickness measurements.

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SECMAR Project: Enhancing Maritime Cybersecurity with Drones and Drone Management in the South Baltic Region

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Abstract

This paper presents results from the SECMAR Project, which investigated the use of drones and drone management to enhance maritime cybersecurity in the South Baltic region. The aims of the research were on identifying cybersecurity challenges associated with drones and IoT in the maritime industry. This paper contribution is on improving the understanding of drone automation systems, performing threat modelling exercises, supply chain analysis, and sharing security requirements awareness. Various use cases of drones in ports, including area inspection, video surveillance, and digitalization, were evaluated. Research results also highlighted the operational challenges of UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles), such as automated charging, docking stations, and route mission management. The experimental setup involved testing the level of cyber-physical security during autonomous drone flights with predefined flight routes over a quay area for a port located in Germany. This paper also investigates and outlines the secure communication with the control center, secure delivery of the flight path, and system capabilities for drone self-return and landing in case of emergency. This result includes cyber-threat analysis for data stored in cloud-based Drone Management Systems as privacy and confidentiality preserving technique that help to improve maritime cybersecurity using drones and drone management in the South Baltic region.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we present the findings from our investigations on the use of drones and drone management that was a part of the SECMAR project - a EU financed research project to improve maritime cybersecurity in the South Baltic region. In this paper we have presented the results from the research, which include identifying cybersecurity challenges associated with drones and IoT in the maritime industry, improving the understanding of drone automation systems, performing threat modeling exercises, and supply chain analysis. Various use cases of drones in ports were evaluated, and the operational challenges of UAVs were highlighted. The paper also investigates and outlines secure communication with the control center, secure delivery of the flight path, and system capabilities for drone self-return and landing in case of emergency. Finally, the paper proposes security controls for data stored in cloud-based drone management systems as a privacy and confidentiality-preserving technique to improve maritime cybersecurity using drones and drone management in the South Baltic region.

1.1 Background

Recently, as drone solutions have become a commercially available technology, affordable to the wider public. Many research projects have already investigated their use in swarms and collaboration with other autonomously operating cyber-physical systems, *Coopmans (2014)*, *Ogan (2014)*, *Broad (1981)*, and studies, *Shakhatreh (2019)*. Classical real-time video surveillance systems (CCTV) cannot entirely meet today's requirements in complex industrial environments such as Ports: Changing infrastructure with dynamic surveillance targets, more sophisticated monitoring is needed to identify air quality, pollutions, monitor water area and to inspect of conditions (damages) of port infrastructure, assets, and terminal yard sites. This study aims to investigate the cyber security challenges with Drones Management systems in the maritime industry. Regarding these challenges, some questions can be raised such as do we ready for valid autonomous flights? What is required security compared to advertised security by vendor? Who controls data privacy? Do we understand lifecycle (inventory, updates, disposal) for Drone Management Systems? What is the incident response plan in cases control over the drone is lost? The target area of this project is considering possible drone use cases in ports. As the first use case, we can mention Area Inspections such as fences damages, water pollutions, quay fenders. The second drone

use case in a port can be Video Surveillance, and the third one is Digitalization in terms of object detection and accounting or maps updating. Drone automated charging, Drone-In-a-Box – docking stations, and Drone route mission control by SaaS are good practices to evaluate the proposed drone automation solutions. The significant goals of the project are considered as the follows: understanding elements of drone automation system; sharing compliance and regulations impacts; performing cyber-threat modeling analysis; understanding cyber-security defense level and required security controls; sharing supply chain cyber-security requirements awareness.

The experimental setup of this project is testing the level of cyber-physical security during drone's autonomous flights with a dynamically created flight path over a quay area using predefined flight routes. The project outcomes help to understand security level of communication with control center, aerial photos and video privacy and system capabilities for drone self-return and landing in emergency cases such as missed connection with control center.

2. Related Work

As part of the initial start of the research, a structured literature review of published work was conducted in order to understand what is “state-of-the-art”. This literature review explores the current process, practices, and use cases of drones in various industries, with a focus on the challenges posed by operating UAVs, environmental factors, traffic management, compliance issues, and privacy/data security. The review suggests that operating UAVs requires expensive simulators due to the different conditions under which they operate, and a traffic management approach is necessary for managing airspace when multiple devices are operating. Environmental factors such as weather conditions and terrain characteristics also pose challenges that need to be addressed. Compliance issues related to the use of UAVs, including regulatory frameworks and privacy concerns, are also discussed. Finally, the review highlights the increasing number of devices in operation and the associated risks to privacy and data protection, with suggestions for data brokers to provide secure communication for sharing data across subscribers and smart objects.

2.1. UAV operation

To describe how drone management can provide cyber and physical security in the maritime industry in the context of state of the art, we aimed to explore and analyze the current process, practices, and use cases in other industries. In this section, the literature relevant to drones in the industry environment from various areas have been reviewed to find the different capabilities of drones. Operating UAVs poses several challenges, such as testing and simulating swarms of UAVs and training operators, which generally require expensive simulators, *Rodriguez-Fernandez (2015)*, because the conditions under which UAVs operate are different from conventional piloted aircraft, *Khawaja et al. (2016)*. However, the environment in which UAVs operate poses a concern, independent of the environment; a traffic management approach is required for operating many devices in an airspace. Furthermore, there are other concerns regarding the operation of these devices such as security and privacy, *Boubeta-Puig et al. (2018)*.

2.2. Environmental challenges

Weather conditions such as rain, wind, humidity, and terrain characteristics raise some environmental challenges, *Mora et al. (2015)*. Experiments have shown, *Neji and Mostfa (2019)*, that the power consumption may depend significantly more on environmental conditions such as side winds, *Rodriguez-Fernandez (2015)*. Using multiple UAVs in unknown scenarios requires fast and adaptive path planning to avoid collisions and ensure optimal travel times for the devices. A self-adapting multi-object evolution algorithm is proposed to facilitate UAV path planning, *Liu et al. (2016)*. Simultaneous localization and mapping-based real-time tracking can be used when GPS signals cannot be used reliably or are unavailable, *Thamrin et al. (2012)*. Generally speaking, the choice of device and hardware will be influenced by the environment the device is intended to operate in. The more specialized an application

is, the operational requirements regarding the environment, and it is essential to define the specifications of environmental conditions in the first step.

2.3. UAV Traffic Management

In order to managing the airspace when large numbers of UAVs are operating in the same theatre, *Chen et al. (2015)* investigated platooning for UAV swarms and proposes an approach that can handle massive fleets and manages device malfunctioning or intrusion well. *Tokekar et al. (2016)* experimented with multiple device types addressing the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) in the context of measuring/surveillance an area considered. Suppose UAVs are to be allowed to operate within urban areas. In that case, for handling the increasing traffic in the airspace there is a need to use a management system for city-wide unmanned air traffic management and for collision avoidance. Such system proposed by *Foina et al. (2015)*.

2.4. Compliance Issues

According to *Pauner et al. (2015)*, drone's use and availability is spreading considerably faster than awareness about potential concerns or legislative frameworks to address these concerns. Shortly, different countries will probably continue to impose additional regulations regarding the use of UAVs, *Erdelj et al. (2017)*, *Boubeta-Puig et al. (2018)*, and those regulations may be subject to frequent change. The use of UAVs in public airspace causes several technical and societal concerns and challenges, *Vattapparamban et al. (2016)*. Currently, there are few certainties regarding the legal regulations for drones since, as is frequently the case with new technologies. Their rapid adoption outpaces legal, policy, and social ability to cope with issues regarding privacy and interference with well-established commercial air space, *Sterbenz (2016)*. However, different regulations may apply to the usage of UAVs for emergency or disaster scenarios, *Altawy and Youssef (2017)*. *Shariat et al. (2016)* provided a survey to investigate security, privacy, and safety aspects associated with the use of civilian drones in the national airspace.

2.5. Privacy and Data Security

The increasing number of devices in operation poses threats to people, property, and privacy rights according to *Altawy and Youssef (2017)*. *Pauner et al. (2015)* analyzed the risk drones can pose for privacy and data protection and *Vattapparamban et al. (2016)* surveyed aspects of cybersecurity, privacy, and public safety in the context of drones in future smart cities. *Shariat et al. (2016)* studied the use of UAVs to augment the sensing capability of a smart city is proposed. Still, the authors suggest a data broker to provide a secure communication to share the data across the subscribers and smart objects, but the legal situation is currently changing quickly.

3. Port of Lubmin Case Study

Case study research is valuable in scientific experiments as it provides a deep understanding of a particular phenomenon, context, or situation. It allows researchers to examine complex issues, explore causal relationships, and generate new hypotheses. In this case, conducting a case study on the capabilities of drones in the maritime industry provides an in-depth understanding of the practical use cases of drone technology in improving cyber security strength.

Using a case study approach that was conducted as part of the research, assisted the researchers to generate a list of possible capabilities and features of drone technology in improving cybersecurity strength, such as autonomous monitoring, inspection, data collection and analysis, emergency responses, remote assistance, and drone management and automation. They were also able to identify the different groups of vendors and their products in the market, which provided valuable insights into the availability of necessary elements for drone management systems.

Overall, for this paper, case study research is valuable in helping to conduct scientific experiments as it provides a deep understanding of the phenomenon under investigation, allowing researchers to generate new hypotheses and identify practical solutions to real-world problems. In this case, the case study approach provided valuable insights into the capabilities of drone technology in the maritime industry and its potential to improve cybersecurity strength.

3.1. State of the Practice

As a part of this work, we have investigated the different capabilities of drones in the maritime industry and how they help provide cyber security. We have collected the prominent use cases of drones, and the elements have been offered or produced by various companies worldwide. The scope is industrial use cases based on some search phrases such as: intelligent drone solutions, enterprise drone management, drone automation solutions, drone-in-a-box solutions, drone cyber security.

We are influenced by attending the webinars, such as provided by Lorenz Technology, <https://www.lorenztechnology.com/>, to identify the practical use cases improving cyber security strength. Here is the list of possible capabilities and features of drone technologies in the conducted market review: Inspecting the quay walls and the sea defense revetments at the port; Autonomously monitoring, inspection, data collection and analysis, emergency responses, remote assistance; Drone management and automation.

During the market review, Table I, we identified the state-of-the-practice business solutions and necessary elements of drone management system which are: Drone, Remote control device, Appliance or software, Web service and automated Charging technology. The latest products marketed as “Drone in a Box solutions” contains all these elements.

Table I: Results of market review and availability of elements offered or produced by vendors

Manufacturer Name	Drone	Remote control	Appliance	Web service	Charger
Lorenz			*	*	
Terra Drone		*	*	*	
Action Drone	*	*			
Airoboticsdrones	*	*	*	*	*
Dronesolutionservices				*	
Azure Drones	*	*	*	*	*
Measure			*	*	
Drone Base			*	*	
PERCEPTO	*	*	*	*	*
DCI Drones	*	*			
Planck Aerosystems		*	*	*	
inspired flight	*				
Flyability	*	*		*	
Voliro	*	*			
Skydio	*	*			
IDiployer					*
Hextronics					*
Shenzhen Heisha Technology					*
DJI	*	*	*	*	
Skycharge					*
FlytNow			*	*	

During the review we have identified three groups of vendors. Group 1 focus on automated charging solutions only. Vendors from group 2 focus on drone management as a service type of products that is usually offered as a web site and software for smartphone or computer available by subscription. Vendors from group number 3 produces drones itself, remote control device with software.

3.2. Proposed Drone Management system

The solution setup of this project is testing the level of cyber-physical security during drone’s autonomous flights with a dynamically created flight path over a port terminal and quay area. Fig.1 represents solution layout for drone automation system with the port terminal, the layout includes drone, automated charge station, and flight routes provided by drone management service. Fig.1 demonstrates how the drone launch zone is connected to the main flight path that is designed to observe the terminal apron area. H, W, L – height, width, and length of flight path (FP).

Fig.1: Representation of drone flights setup in Lubmin cargo terminal

Fig.2: Drone Management System implemented in Lubmin terminal

The pilot project conducted with the participation of multiple vendors yielded many results and contributed to the generation of knowledge and sharing regarding to improved digitalization operations by incorporating a prototyping approach. Using the results of market review, we have identified essential elements of any drone automation system which include: automated charging, on-board control appliance, and web-based service of SaaS type that serves as data storage, aerial images processing unit and

flight route management for operator. Fig.2 demonstrates the architecture and main elements of the proposed automation system as follows: drone landing plate with integrated charger (L), drone appliance (A) that controls drone by using native remote control hardware module (RC), Drone fleet management Internet service (M) that store, process, and display results of drone operations and captured data by using web site.

Usually Appliance (A) is presented by a smartphone device (Google or iOS) with specially designed software program provided by a web service vendor. The principle of drone automation is provided with the following steps: Drone starts to charge the battery as soon as it lands on landing plate (L), appliance (A) periodically check on the drone’s charge level and retrieves flight tasks from the web service (M). The operator can check for the drone’s status, create new flight tasks, observe for new aerial images or supervise live video stream from the drone camera by using web page interface of web service (M) in any web browser application. As the new information about drone tasks is delivered to appliance (A) it instructs remote control (RC) and Drone (D) to perform take-off and perform the flight according to the route retrieved from web service (M). Remote Control (RC) have a direct, real-time communication with the drone by using Software Defined Radio (SDR) wireless communication technology. The purpose of the drone appliance is to support logical communication channel (L1) between drone and web service and thus operator and business users.

The proposed solution architecture presented in Fig.2 highlights that some of the components reside within the port physical facilities i.e., inside the building (inhouse) and connected via regular networking equipment such as WIFI router (R) that is in turn connected to the internet. The Charge station (L) is situated outside the building and connected to the inhouse network by using WIFI router (R) or regular, wired LAN router. The experimental setup of this project is testing the level of cyber-physical security during drone’s autonomous flights.

4. Drone Management System supply chain analysis

To ensure proper cyber security level during drone automation project development and lifecycle, alongside conducting risk management, one of the first step should be threat modeling analysis.

Fig.3: Vendors and data flow analysis. Red, Blue, Green color: components of the same vendor.

Threat modeling is the process that improves software and system security by identifying and rating the potential threats and vulnerabilities that various components of your system may have. The main purpose is to fix security issues before cyber-criminals take advantage of them. The process is then followed by defining countermeasures which will prevent those same threats and exploits likely to put your system at risk. This allows addressing threats with the appropriate solutions in a logical order, starting with

the ones which present the greatest risk. It is important to start this process on early stages of project development lifecycle to avoid significant changes in the system after potential threats or weaknesses will be identified while understanding and refining system architecture. In the following sub-chapters, we will analyze all three components of the testbed with the purpose to identify all assets in the proposed architecture, make decomposition of software components, identify data flow and entry points, highlight trust boundaries and possible privileged modes. At the end of the chapter threat modelling table will be presented.

4.1. Drone and remote control device

Most of the drone manufacturers maintains the registry of produced drones. This registry includes ownership information and software status of the drone. Drone vendor (DJI) provides software program to register and activate the drone before the first-time usage. The activation procedure includes to create password account that is used to store information about the drone on vendor web site.

Fig.3 shows in red color the elements that belongs to the same drone manufacturer that also needs to be used and configured to setup and use automated operations. Web service (V) and software (S) provided by drone manufacture are new elements added the initial architecture in Fig.1. These new elements also should be considered in cyber security risk assessment. *Shelley (2023)* shows that there a number of concern and finding was made regards the DJI vendor that may pose a certain threat to the system like: confidentiality loss and device control take over.

4.2. Charging pad

The charging pad is a device connectable to network, running a Linux operating system and software programs that controls the following charging procedures: detect the drone contacts with the charging plate, turns-on charging voltage element, monitors charging process and provide API for the external requests. The API supports REST request functionality by external HTTP connections, which assumes involvement of internal web service application and authentication accordingly. The charger device also accepts connections by using Secure Shell Protocol (SSH). The SSH access is based on Public Key authentication with the public key file pre-installed by the manufacturer on the device and private key file delivered to customer by email. Such configuration allows to make a conclusion that device vendor generates, stores, and delivers multiple key-pairs per each device and traces of access keys for many devices can be found in Vendor's email application database.

4.3. Drone Management Appliance and web service

Web service and Drone appliance provided by FlytNow, <https://flytnow.com>. Web service provides REST API to retrieve drone information, subscription status, flight route and parameters. Drone appliance represented by software program for Android OS and standalone IoT device based on Android OS. Both applications use various REST requests like <https://my.flytbase.com/accounts/login/v2/>, <https://my.flytbase.com/api/> at web service. To understand the availability of security mechanisms and strength of encryption protocol between the web service (M) and appliance (A) we have performed decompilation of software package with a Apktool and Jadx software applications. The source code analysis reveals the presence of AESHelper.java file within the appliance (A). AESHelper file contains only encryption functions that implement data encryption and decryption by using "AES/CBC/PKCS7Padding" schema with 256 bit encryption key generated by hashing provided string with "SHA-256" hash algorithm. The software uses encryption and decryption functions to save account login in encrypted form. Application does not encrypt any information that is retrieved or sent from or to the web service. Analysis also reveals that User account credentials are stored in local device in encrypted form by using static encryption key generated from string "flyt-login". The application also relies only to underlying Operating System capabilities to mitigate man in the middle attack or web service spoofing. Software package also reveals information about vendor development environment such as additional communication API URL.

4.4. Business user device

The system setup requires user to create an account at FlytNow.com web site. Later login credentials will be used by a variety of users, referred as business user, to access drone management dashboard online at FlytNow.com web site which preserves shared access scenario for multiple users. It means any computer where login credential will be used needs to be on account for threat model, since in case of malware attack the login credentials and web site cookies will be copied by malware i.e. stolen with the purpose of unauthorized access. Later cyber criminals may extract aerial images from the FlytNow.com storage or change drone flight route with the purpose to retrieve more aerial images of the industrial territory of the port.

4.5. Threat categorization

In this chapter we provide cyber-threat categories with corresponding examples to each identified threat and asset so that threats can be systematically identified in the proposed architecture in a structured and repeatable manner. To assign categories for each asset we use STRIDE method. STRIDE is an acronym for the following categories: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, Elevation of Privilege. To structure the threat assignment, we elaborated Data Flow diagram for all identified assets presented in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Data flow for the proposed architecture

A categorization, according to STRIDE, represent the following threats: Spoofing - attack by using weak identity validation. Tampering - attack on integrity of the data or communication. Repudiation threats that mainly goes by human factor with business logic or elevated operations misuse by privileged users. Information disclosure - attack on confidentiality. Denial of service - attack on availability. Escalation of privileges - credentials leak or authorization misuse. Table II shows the STRIDE matrix for the asset inventory in proposed architecture.

Table II: Threat categorization for asset inventory

Asset	S	T	I	D	E
Drone (D)	*	*	*	*	*
Remote Control (RC)		*		*	
Software (S)				*	*
Appliance (A)	*			*	*
Drone management web service (M)	*	*	*	*	*
Manufacturer web service (V)	*	*	*	*	*
Charge station (L)				*	*
Business user workstation (W)	*	*	*		

4.6. Proposed security controls

According to Table II, drone (D) may be affected by “S“T“I“D“E” threats. Where “T” and “I” can be a drone system intrusion or unauthorized access. Most enterprise drones have password protection mechanism. To enhance the security of the drone and this data, operators are required to enter a password each time they activate the drone, use remote controller or access the drone onboard storage via software. This provides aerial images confidentiality, even if the drone is lost or physically compromised. DJI’s newest enterprise drones uses Software-Define Radio (SDR) protocol with data encrypted using the leading AES- 256 standard, ensuring critical information exchanged between the drone and its remote control is protected against other SDR devices in the area. However, DJI also offers Periscope product that allows to take control over any DJI drone, it means that Remote Control (RC) and Drone (D) systems have backdoors (i.e. An undocumented way of gaining access to a computer system) that may be re-used by cyber criminals, represented as “T” and “D” threats. Such backdoors represent great threat to entire system since it is designed to bypass known security controls. To protect confidentiality “I” and “T” for Software (S) and Appliance (A) components it is possible to install integrity antivirus on mobile device where (S) will be installed or Intrusion detection software in the Network. Also, periodic vulnerability scan may be used. To protect Availability “D” we can employ solutions like CloudFlare and system resources monitoring software to prevent intermediate system malfunction. To eliminate (E) a two-factor authentication can be used to protect access to web site control panel at (V) and (M) systems.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented the findings from our investigation of the capabilities of drones in the maritime industry and their usefulness in providing cybersecurity. During the research that is published in this paper, we have collected the most prominent use cases of drones and identified the necessary elements of a drone management system, including a drone, a remote control device, an appliance or software, a web service, and automated charging technology. Based on our work, we have identified three groups of vendors that offer different solutions, including those that focus on automated charging solutions, drone management as a service type of products, and those that produce drones themselves.

In the paper, we have presented the proposed drone management system and its essential elements, which include automated charging, on-board control appliance, and web-based service of SaaS type that serves as data storage, aerial images processing unit, and flight route management for operators. The proposed solution architecture includes a drone landing plate with an integrated charger, a drone appliance that controls the drone, a drone fleet management internet service that stores, processes, and displays the results of drone operations, and captured data.

Results from our conducted pilot project in the Port of Lubmin assisted us to test the level of cyber-physical security during the drone’s autonomous flights with a dynamically created flight path over a port terminal and quay area. The pilot project contributed to the generation of knowledge and sharing regarding improved digitalization operations by incorporating a prototyping approach.

In conclusion, the research results gained from the studies provide valuable insights into the capabilities of drones in the maritime industry and their usefulness in providing cybersecurity. They present the necessary elements of a drone management system and a proposed solution architecture that can be used to automate drone flights and improve cyber-physical security.

Finally, as pointers for future work, we propose that the potential future directions for research and development are: investigating the role of cybersecurity for drone systems, integrating AI and ML algorithms into drone technology, developing more advanced autonomous drone technologies for monitoring and inspection, validating the proposed drone management system, exploring the use of drones for emergency response and environmental monitoring, investigating the use of drones for transportation and delivery, examining the legal and regulatory implications of using drones, investigating the potential of using drones for remote maintenance and repairs, and developing more advanced and secure charging and docking solutions.

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ML-Based Resistance and Powering Prediction of the BSRA Trawler Series

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Abstract

This study investigates the use of Machine Learning techniques viz. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) for the prediction of resistance and propulsive coefficients of hull forms designed according to the BSRA Trawler Series. Experimental data for the Resistance and Propulsive coefficients have been published by BSRA in the form of tables in a series of three papers. This experimental data has been used to train and evaluate a series of ANN and SVM models, which estimate the resistance and propulsive coefficients of ships designed according to the BSRA Trawler Series. The procedure adopted and the results obtained are presented and discussed.

1. Introduction

Ship designers and naval architects typically use model tests in tanks or advanced Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software tools to predict a ship's calm water resistance and propulsive coefficients. However, during the preliminary design phase, resistance and powering predictions rely on data from systematic series of full-form ship models, such as the Series 60 Methodical Series of Single-Screw Ships, *Todd (1963)*, the SSPA Cargo Liner Series, *Williams (1969)*, the BSRA Methodical Series, *Pattullo and Thomson (1965)*, *Pattullo (1968)*, *Thomson and Pattullo (1969)*, or the MARAD Systematic Series, *Roseman and Seibold (1987)* of full-form ship models. Graphical or tabular presentations of this data enable the manual calculation of a ship's resistance using a relatively simple procedure. However, manual calculation procedures are not efficient for the systematic optimization of ship design. To evaluate a large number of alternative designs in minimal computation time, programmable calculation procedures are required, *Margari et al. (2018)*. Previous studies have developed regression models using polynomial interpolation with the data from systematic series hull forms, *Sabit (1971, 1972a, 1976)*, *Radojcic et al. (2014)*, *Bojovic (1997)*. This study investigates the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) to predict resistance, propulsive coefficients, and powering of hull forms using the data provided by the BSRA Trawler Series.

ANNs are machine learning tools that offer an alternative to conventional approaches for dealing with non-linear issues like pattern recognition, classification, and function approximation. They consist of processors that resemble the organization of a biological neural network by exchanging signals through weighted connections. Even with noisy data, trained ANNs are capable of producing the appropriate output from a collection of input parameters without requiring an exact function or model for the problem.

SVMs and Support Vector Regression (SVR) are machine learning algorithms used for classification and regression tasks, respectively. SVMs aim to find the optimal decision boundary that separates data points into different classes by maximizing the margin between the classes. The decision boundary is determined by support vectors, which are data points that lie closest to the boundary. SVMs are effective in handling high-dimensional data and can handle both linearly separable and non-linearly separable data by using kernel functions. On the other hand, SVR aims to find the optimal function that predicts the target variable for a given set of input features. The objective of SVR is to minimize the error between the predicted output and the actual output while maximizing the margin between the predicted values and the regression line. Similar to SVMs, SVR uses support vectors to determine the optimal regression line. SVR is effective in handling non-linearly separable data and can handle both uni-variate and multi-variate regression problems.

For the present study, the so-called multi-layer perceptron (MLP) networks have been selected and systematically trained and evaluated in order to assess their potential to estimate the resistance of BSRA trawler hull forms. The study provides information on the selected alternatives of MLPs and their application for the prediction of BSRA hull forms resistance and powering requirements. These machine learning tools offer a promising alternative for predicting resistance and powering of hull forms based on the data provided by the BSRA Trawler Series, *Haykin (1999)*.

2. Types of Machine Learning Algorithms

2.1. Artificial Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are computational models that draw inspiration from the way the human brain processes information. They are composed of a network of interconnected processing units, called neurons that operate in parallel and in a non-linear manner. ANNs learn by modifying the weights of their connections and threshold values, which are stored as information acquired from their environment. ANNs are organized in layers and possess the ability to learn, which, is a key feature of these models. ANNs use three different learning paradigms: supervised, unsupervised, and reinforced learning. In supervised learning, the network is trained on a set of input-output pairs and a cost function is used to evaluate its performance. Unsupervised learning is used when the network has to classify the input data without any external information, while reinforced learning is used when the network interacts with its environment in order to minimize a performance indicator, *Haykin (1999)*.

2.1.1 Feed-forward multi-layer perceptron

The feed-forward multi-layer perceptron (MLP) is a popular type of neural network used for function approximation, data classification, and pattern recognition. It has an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Signals flow from the input to the output layer in a forward direction, and every node except the input layer is a neuron with its own output generated by a differentiable activation function. The network requires appropriate activation functions, training algorithms, and learning algorithms, *Snyman (2005)*, *Haykin (1999)*.

2.1.2 Training algorithms

Training algorithms are used to train the neural network, recognize specific inputs, and map them to specified outputs. The back-propagation algorithm, which uses supervised learning, is used to train MLPs. This algorithm is executed in two stages. During the first stage, the input signal is transferred through the layers to produce the output signal while the synaptic weights remain constant. Then, the mean square error is calculated, and during the second stage, the deviations are transferred backwards, and the synaptic weights change accordingly to minimize the average squared error, *Haykin (1999)*.

2.1.3 Learning algorithms

The learning algorithm is responsible for updating the weights and biases of the network during training. The learning rate parameter controls the rate of change of the weights and bias and affects the speed of convergence of the training.

2.1.4 Data Sets

The available data for network training is divided into three sets: training, validation, and test sets.

- The training set is used to update the weights and biases of the network to minimize the cost function.
- The validation set is used to tune parameters other than weights and compare different neural networks.
- The test set is used to evaluate the predictive ability of the network.

2.2. Support Vector Machines

Support vector machines (SVMs) are another supervised learning method used for classification problems, regression and detection of outliers. They work by mapping data to a high-dimensional feature space so that the data points can be categorized, even when the data is not otherwise linearly separable. This machine learning methodology was initially developed for solving classification problems, later these were extended toward solving regression problems, *Vapnik (2005)*.

The support vector regression employs kernel functions to map the initial data into high dimensional space such that the nonlinear patterns can be converted into a linear problem. The kernel function is a critical parameter in determining the performance of an SVM. There are 4 main types of kernel functions available, those are Linear, Polynomial, Sigmoid, and Radial Basis Functions. The appropriate hyper-parameters of the SVM regressor are fine-tuned using the Grid Search Technique to ensure the efficient performance of the model. An inappropriate choice of hyperparameters would lead to under/over-fitting. The two main hyperparameters of the SVM regression model are the ϵ -insensitive zone and regularization parameter C . Any deviation from ϵ can be calculated from the penalization of the regularization parameter C . The penalty becomes more important when the values of C are higher and SVR fits the data. The penalty becomes negligible when the value of C is small and SVR gets flat. For a higher value of ϵ SVR becomes flat and for a smaller value of ϵ , SVR fits data, *Panda (2021)*.

SVR is preferred for system identification due to its high generalization ability and its ability to find globally optimal unique solutions. The algorithm computes a separating hyperplane by maximizing the margin between the data points and itself while allowing for an error margin of ϵ . In the case of non-linear data, they are mapped to a higher dimensional space using a kernel function, making the data linearly separable. The value of ϵ can be adjusted to accommodate outliers, and a regularization parameter C is used to control the trade-off between fitting the data well and overfitting.

Let us assume a multi-dimensional input and target output data set defined by

$$\chi = \{(x_i, y_i) : x_i \in \mathbb{R}^N, y_i \in \mathbb{R}, N \geq 1\}. \quad (1)$$

We define the SVR approximation hyperplane by

$$y(x) = w \cdot \Phi(x) + b \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi(x)$ is the feature map corresponding to some positive definite symmetric kernel K . K is used to map the input data to some higher dimensional space. We define the optimisation problem to find the maximum margin hyperplane that can fit the data in this higher dimensional space. The margin is defined to be proportional to $1/\|w\|$ and maximising it is equivalent to minimising $\|w\|$. The optimisation objective including the empirical loss is then written as follows:

$$\min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^m |y_i - (w \cdot \Phi(x) + b)|_{\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

where $|\cdot|_{\epsilon}$ is the ϵ insensitive hinge loss function, and m is the total size of the training set. Using slack variables $\xi_i \geq 0$ and $\xi'_i \geq 0, i \in [m]$, the dual optimization problem is equivalently written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^m |\xi_i + \xi'_i|_{\epsilon} \quad (4) \\ & \text{s.t } (w \cdot \Phi(x) + b) - y_i \leq \epsilon + \xi_i \\ & y_i - (w \cdot \Phi(x) + b) \leq \epsilon + \xi'_i \\ & \xi_i \geq 0, \xi'_i \geq 0, i \in [m] \end{aligned}$$

The above convex quadratic objective is rewritten using a Lagrangian and then Karsh-Kuhn-Tucker conditions are applied. The dual optimisation objective is then:

$$\max_{\alpha', \alpha} \left[\sum_{i=1}^m y_i (\alpha'_i - \alpha_i) - \sum_{i=1}^m \epsilon (\alpha'_i + \alpha_i) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m (\alpha'_i - \alpha_i) (\alpha'_i - \alpha_j) K(x_i, x_j) \right] \quad (5)$$

Let α^* and α be the solutions of the Lagrangian variables returned by the optimiser. The separation plane for the dual is then given by:

$$y(x) = \sum_{i=1}^m (\alpha_i^* - \alpha_i) K(x_i, x) + b \quad (6)$$

In the above formulation, the C value is the penalty factor that governs the trade-off between the margin maximisation and slack and acts as a regularization parameter. ϵ determines the precision of the fit and defines an acceptable error boundary, *Vapnik (2005), A. Vijay and A. Somayajula (2022)*.

To carry out system identification a linear kernel is selected, $K(x_i, x_j) = x_i \cdot x_j$. Then the regression plane becomes:

$$y(x) = \sum_{i=1}^m (\alpha'_i - \alpha_i) x_i \cdot x + b \quad (7)$$

3. BSRA Trawler Series

The BSRA Trawler Series was published in a set of three papers in the 1960s and 1970s based on model testing experiments conducted at Vickers-Armstrong (Shipbuilders) Ltd., Ship Model Experiment Tank, St. Albans for the British Shipbuilding Research Association (now the British Ship Research Association) to determine the effect on resistance and propulsive efficiency due to varying Breadth-Draught ratio and Length-Displacement ratio in part I, *Pattullo and Thomson (1965)*, the effects on varying the block coefficient and position of the longitudinal centre of buoyancy in part II, *Pattullo (1968)*, and the effects of varying the shape of the forebody and aft body sections in part III, *Thomson and Pattullo (1978)*. The series provides a systematic series regarding the performance of these aspects of trawlers, which could be used in the design process. The series explores the effects of varying Breadth-Draught (B/T) ratio, Length-Displacement ($L/\Delta^{1/3}$) ratio, block coefficient (C_b), the position of the longitudinal centre of buoyancy (LCB), trim, Froude no and the bow and stern shapes.

In the first part of the series, eight models were tested for resistance. The hull forms were divided into two groups, one with the B/T ratio varying from 2.0 to 3.5 with a constant $L/\Delta^{1/3}$ ratio of 4.85, the other had a range of $L/\Delta^{1/3}$ from 4.35 to 5.10 with a constant B/T ratio of 2.25. One form is kept common to both groups. The effect of trim on resistance was also investigated. Propulsion experiments were also undertaken with three models consisting of the parent form and two other forms selected from the B/T ratio and $L/\Delta^{1/3}$ ratio using two propellers of different diameters. All models were run at a design load displacement corresponding to 847 tons for the ship.

In the second part of the series, the models are split into two groups, A and B, with the parent form of the earlier breadth-draught and length-displacement ratio variation series being common to both. Group A consisted of the parent hull form and two other hull forms in which the block coefficient was increased and decreased respectively while maintaining the length, breadth and draught constant. Group B consisted of the parent hull form and two other hull forms in which the block coefficient was varied by the same method as in Group A while maintaining the length, displacement and breadth-draught ratio constant. Resistance experiments only were carried out with Group A in the load condition with three trims and at two lighter conditions with one trim by the stern. Resistance and propulsion tests were carried out with Group B at the load draught with one trim by the stern.

The models in the second series formed two groups, those in each group having the same length, breadth, displacement and stern profiles. The stern profiles of the two groups were different, to accommodate the two different diameter propellers. The parent form was that which was common to the breadth-draught and length-displacement ratio variation series, and the position of the longitudinal centre of buoyancy (LCB) was varied by swinging the sectional area curve at the design load displacement with level trim. The amidships draught in the trimmed design load condition differed with

the position of the centre of buoyancy.

The third part of the series studies the effect of varying the shape of the forebody and afterbody sections of the parent form used in part I of the BSRA trawler series. Ten models were tested for resistance and propulsion and the forms were divided into two groups with the parent form common to both. The bow variation group comprised the parent and four other forms with the same stern sections. Three of these in association with the parent formed a systematic series in which the sectional area at the Forward Perpendicular was varied from 0 to 15% of the maximum section area. The remaining hull form in this group had generally bulbous forebody sections. The models in the stern variation group consisted of the parent form and five other forms having the same forebody shape as the parent. Two of these together with the parent formed a systematic series in which the effect of club-footing the afterbody sections was investigated. The other three forms have unrelated designs of stern incorporating a transom, concentric bulb and U-shaped sections. All the models were tested for resistance and propulsive efficiency in the trimmed design load condition. The parent and bulbous were also tested for resistance at the design load displacement with a level keel.

Table I: Description of different hull forms in part 3 of the BSRA Trawler series.

Variation	Model No.	Hull Form
Bow	XF	Parent
	888	5% bulb
	903	10% bulb
	904	15% bulb
	887	Bulbous sections
Stern	854	Small Club foot
	889	Large Club foot
	891	Transom
	905	Concentric bulb
	853	U - Sections

4. Use of Principal Component Analysis for studying the effect of hull form variations

In the first two parts of the BSRA Trawler Series, the form parameters such as B/T, Length/Disp, Block Coefficient and LCB are varied, whereas, in the 3rd part of this series, these parameters remain largely the same, except for LCB which slightly varies due to the bulb forms. The main significant variations being made are to shape of the bow and stern, which alters the offsets of the hull form, which defines the hull geometry. Therefore, it is significantly different to generate the input features for the machine learning model, to cater for the differences in the hull forms. In order to use the hull forms as an input into a Machine Learning model, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to reduce the entire offset table to a smaller manageable number of principal scores which can be used as inputs.

4.1. Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a dimensionality reduction algorithm through which we attempt to capture most of the variance in a high-dimensional dataset into a low-dimensional representation. It does so by compressing a high-dimensional data set into a handful of principal scores, while the original data set can still be recovered with very limited errors from the principal scores using the transformation matrix. Such a feature can be very useful in handling complex vessel geometries, and the procedure of the proposed approach is briefly introduced in this section, *Shalev-Shwartz and Ben-David (2014)*.

Suppose we gave a dataset in which each sample is zero centred, assume x_1, \dots, x_n , be n column vectors in \mathbb{R}^l which represents n samples with l features and constitute a data matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times l}$, i.e

$$X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]^T \quad (8)$$

We now introduce a transformation matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{l,l}$ to map each sample vector x_i into a vector of l principal scores $t_i \in \mathbb{R}^l$, and the full transformation of X into a new matrix of principal scores $T \in \mathbb{R}^{n,l}$ is given by

$$T = [t_1, \dots, t_n]^T = XW \quad (9)$$

We now get a new l -dimensional space, with each of the dimensions arranged in such a way that they successively inherit the maximum possible variance from the original data matrix X . Matrix W can be obtained through various methods such as Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), *Golub and Reinsch (1970)* and Minka's MLE, *Minka (2001)*.

4.2. Compressing Hull Form using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) /

In naval architecture, the shape of the hull is defined with the help of offset values which are tabulated in the form of a table commonly known as the offset table. The offset table is a table of (x,y,z) coordinates, where x,y and z are measured in the longitudinal, lateral and vertical directions respectively. The x and z coordinates in the offset table are represented by the intersection of stations (transverse sections) and waterlines. The y coordinates are on the hull surface and are called offset values. They are measured from the centre plane of the hull and are given at prescribed sets of x and z positions. Usually, the values of x , y , and z coordinates are normalized by the hull length L , half-beam width $B/2$, and draft T of the vessel:

$$x^* = \frac{x}{L}, \quad y^* = \frac{y}{B/2}, \quad z^* = \frac{z}{T} \quad (10)$$

To compare and represent the hull forms of different vessels, a predetermined set of stations and waterlines, i.e. the same set of (x^*, z^*) coordinates, can be used with a different set of y^* values for each hull shape. Typically, a very large number of hull offsets are required to fully represent the entire complexity of the complete hull geometry. This makes the analysis of a group of hull forms with the use of the offset table a rather very tedious task. Therefore, we reshape the offset table of each hull as a column vector sample y^* , with the features being the offset values, PCA is used to compress the data matrix of the offset tables of a group of hulls, with which we get a smaller manageable number of principal scores which would be adequate to represent the geometry of each hull for further evaluations. To achieve this, the normalized offset table of each hull is first zero-centred by subtracting each offset value with the mean value across samples, i.e. for a group of n hulls each with l offset values, the j -th offset value of the i -th hull, $y_{i,j}^*$, is shifted as

$$\bar{y}_{i,j} = y_{i,j}^* - \mu_j \quad (11)$$

where μ_j is the mean of the j -th offset value for the same (x^*_j, z^*_j) coordinate across all n hulls:

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_{i,j}^* \quad (12)$$

Consequently, the data matrix consisting of normalized, zero-centred offset tables of n hulls, $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n,l}$, can be obtained from

$$\bar{Y} = [\bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_n]^T \quad (13)$$

where $\bar{y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n,l}$ is formed by arranging the offset values $\bar{y}_{i,j}$ of the i -th hull into a column vector. The transformation matrix $\bar{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{l,d}$ can be introduced to map Y into a set of principal scores, $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{n,d}$ by

$$\Lambda = [\bar{\lambda}_1, \dots, \bar{\lambda}_n]^T = \bar{Y} \bar{W} \quad (14)$$

where $\bar{\lambda}_i = [\lambda_{i,1}; \dots; \lambda_{i,d}]^T$ is the column vector consisting of d principal scores of the i -th hull, and $\lambda_{i,j}$ represents the j -th principal score of the i -th sample hull. Conversely, the original data matrix of zero-centred offset values can be recovered by

$$\bar{Y} = \Lambda \bar{W}^T \quad (15)$$

Typically, the number of hulls in the sample set will be far smaller than that of the offset values, i.e. data matrix Y carries much more features than samples with $l > n$. Therefore, only $d = n - 1$ principal

scores are needed, i.e. only the first $n - 1$ columns of W are retained in \bar{W} , to fully represent the surface of each hull in the group with no loss of information, *Minka (2001)*.

Typically, in ship design, non-dimensional form parameters such as C_B and C_P , help characterise hull forms and have a significant influence on the resistance and powering prediction of the vessel. However, geometric coefficients like C_B and C_P do not account for the detailed geometric features of a vessel, and two distinct vessels can have an identical set of C_B and C_P . However, the utilization of just these geometric coefficients can neither fully capture the complexity of the entire hull geometry nor be reliably used to distinguish different hull forms, and the performance predictions based on just those geometric coefficients may be less reliable as a result. In comparison, PCA gives low-dimensionality representations of hull forms for simpler analysis and also ensures accurate and unique descriptions of different hull forms using principal scores, *Yu and Wang (2018)*.

5. Development of ANN and SVM models for the BSRA Trawler

5.1. Resistance prediction model

A series of neural networks were developed, trained and tested for prediction of calm water resistance of BSRA trawler series hull forms based on the hyperparameter tuning results which gave the best results. Neural networks were explored for one hidden layer and two hidden layers and the best-performing ANNs are as tabulated below, with the Mean Absolute Performance Error (MAPE) to assess the performance of the model. The ANNs had 07 input neurons i.e. Length-Breadth (L/B) ratio, Breadth-Draught (B/T) ratio, Length-Displacement ($L/\Delta^{1/3}$) ratio, block coefficient (C_b), the position of the longitudinal centre of buoyancy (LCB), trim and Froude no (V/\sqrt{L}).

The hyperparameters which are being tuned for the ANN are mentioned in the table below. Activation functions are mathematical functions used in neural networks to introduce non-linearity into the output of a neuron. Weight initialization refers to the process of setting initial weights for the neurons in a neural network. Proper weight initialization is important for the convergence and performance of a neural network. An optimizer is an algorithm used to update the parameters (e.g. weights) of a neural network during training. Examples of optimizers include stochastic gradient descent (SGD), Adam, RMSprop etc. Momentum is a hyperparameter used in optimization algorithms such as stochastic gradient descent. It adds a fraction of the previous weight update to the current weight update, which helps the algorithm to converge faster and avoid getting stuck in local minima. Beta is a hyperparameter used in some optimization algorithms such as Adam, NAdam etc. It controls the decay rate of the moving averages of gradients and the squared gradients. An epoch is a single iteration of the entire dataset through a neural network during training. In other words, one epoch is completed when every data point in the training set has been seen once by the network. The learning rate is a hyperparameter that determines how much the model weights are updated during training. A higher learning rate can cause the model to converge faster, but it may also cause the model to overshoot the optimal weights and perform poorly. Conversely, a lower learning rate can lead to slower convergence but better overall performance.

It was observed that the ANN models with a single hidden layer performed marginally better than those with two hidden layers. Henceforth, the model at ser 9 has been chosen for further study into this problem with a single hidden layer, Normal initialization of weights, NAdam optimizer, 80 neurons in the hidden layer and 1750 epochs.

Table II: Comparison of ANN architectures

TWO HIDDEN LAYERS								
Ser No	Activation function	Initialisation of Weight	Optimizer	Neurons	Epochs	Learning Rate	Momentum	MAP E %
1	relu	Uniform	Nadam	70	1250	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.9$	1.83
2	relu	normal	Nadam	70	1500	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$	1.67

							$\beta_2=0.9$	
3	relu	Glorot	Adam	40	1750	0.01	$\beta_1=0.8,$ $\beta_2=0.9$	2.18
4	relu	Normal	Nadam	40	1750	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.999$	1.97
5	relu	Normal	Nadam	80	1500	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.9$	1.78
SINGLE HIDDEN LAYER								
6	relu	Normal	Nadam	80	1500	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.9$	1.55
7	softmax	Glorot	Nadam	50	1750	0.01	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.9$	1.45
8	relu	Uniform	Nadam	80	1500	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.9$	1.46
9	relu	Normal	Nadam	80	1750	0.001	$\beta_1=0.9,$ $\beta_2=0.999$	1.37
10	relu	Normal	Adam	90	1750	0.001	$\beta_1=0.6,$ $\beta_2=0.999$	1.51

Fig.1: Error Percentage Distribution in Resistance (C) prediction

Fig.1 shows the variation in error between the predicted values of circular C © from the actual values of Circular C ©. It can be observed that out of the 800 values of the BSRA Trawler series, the ANN model is able to predict nearly 58 % (464 out of 800) of the values with an error of less than 1% and nearly 40% (322 out of 800) of the values have an error variation of between 1-5%. Thereby, this model is capable of predicting resistance values with a less than 5% error for nearly 98% of the inputs, with only 1-2% of values having an extremely large error. The correlation coefficient (R^2) between the actual values and predicted values of circular C is nearly 0.995. (A score of 1 indicated a perfect match between actual and predicted values)

5.2. Propulsive Coefficients Prediction Model

Initially, this study intended to examine the feasibility of using ANNs for the prediction of multi-output propulsive coefficients. However, the ANN models developed were not up to satisfactory standards, primarily due to the lack of data points provided by the BSRA series. To overcome the same, Support Vector Regression models were examined and they were found to perform far better. SVM models are

found to typically perform better for smaller datasets (the value m – size of the data set as referred to in section 3, is 72 for the 8.25 ft. diameter propeller and 89 for the 10.5 ft. diameter propeller, whereas the size of the dataset for prediction of © is 799), when compared to ANN models, *Khoong (2021)*. Two separate SVRs were developed since the BSRA trawlers were tested for two different propellers. The no. of inputs and the input neurons remain the same as the ANN for resistance prediction, and the output values were the wake fraction ('w'), thrust deduction factor ('t'), open water efficiency (η_o) and relative rotative efficiency (η_r). The comparative results from the models are tabulated below. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is used as the metric for comparison between models.

Table III: Comparison of ANN and SVR models for predicting propulsive coefficients

ANNs for Propulsive Data								
Ser	Activation Function	Initialisation of Weights	Optimizer	Neurons	Epochs	Learning Rate	Momentum	R^2
1	Softmax	Glorot_normal	RMSprop	24	1750	0.001	0	0.7469
2	Softmax	lecun_unifrom	RMSprop	24	3500	0.001	0	0.896
3	Softmax	variance scaling	RMSprop	22	4000	0.001	0	0.876
SVR (8.25ft dia)								
Ser	C	Epsilon (ϵ)	Gamma (Γ)	Kernel			Test Size	R^2
1	1	1.00E-09	1	rbf			0.1	0.96
SVR (10.5FT DIA)								
2	1	1.00E-08	1	rbf			0.13	0.9315

5.3. Comparison between predicted data with Actual BSRA Data

Based on the resistance values obtained from the ANN model and propulsive coefficients obtained from the SVR models. Fig.2 shows the effective power is based on values obtained from the ML models and the actual Series data. The agreement is good. This combination of ANNs and SVR models performs a fairly accurate technique for resistance and powering prediction with the 10.5 ft diameter propeller. Fig.3 shows the variation in error percentage between the actual values of delivered Horsepower from the BSRA series and the predicted values from the ML models for delivered power. 72% (64 out of 89) of the values are predicted with an error of less than 01% from the actual values. All the predictions were within an error range of 05% from actual values.

Fig.3: Variation in Errors for 10.5 ft diameter propeller

Fig.2: Actual and predicted values of Effective and Delivered Power Curves for BSRA Trawlers with 10.5 ft diameter propeller for various models. (a) Model 841A – Trim A (b) Model 851 – Trim B (c) Model 975 – Trim B (d) Model WS (e) Model 978 (f) Model 85

Similarly, Fig.4 compares powering prediction for the 8.25 ft diameter propeller. The variation in errors is shown in the pie-chart plotted below for delivered power with an 8.25 ft diameter propeller. The variation in error percentage between the actual values of delivered Horsepower from the BSRA series and the predicted values from the ML models for delivered power can be seen in Fig.5. 72% (52 out of 72) of the values are predicted with an error of less than 2% from the actual values, and 89% (64 out of 72) of the values had an error of less than 5%. The marginally better performance of the ML model with a 10.5 ft diameter propeller can be attributed to the fact that there were more data points available for training the ML model with this propeller in the BSRA series.

Fig.4: Actual values and predicted values of Effective and Delivered Power Curves for BSRA Trawlers with 8.25 ft. diameter propeller for various models. (a) Model XF (b) Model 918 (c) Model 920

Fig.5: Variations in error for Delivered Power – 8.25 ft diameter propeller

5.4. Using PCA for creating a ML model for predictions due to Bow and Stern Variations

In Part III of the BSRA Trawler Series, the effect of the variations of the shape of the forebody and the afterbody sections of the parent hull form used in the first two series on resistance and propulsive coefficient were studied through model testing. A total of ten models were tested for resistance and propulsion and the forms were divided into two groups with the parent forms common to both.

In the bow variation group, which included the parent form and 4 other forms, the parent form remained the same for the stern sections. 3 out of the 4 forms, had a sectional area at the FP which varied from 0 to 15% of the maximum sectional area. The other remaining form had a generally bulbous forebody section. The bow variation models were tested for design load displacement (8847 t) at both even keel and design trim by aft (B Trim). Vice versa, in the stern variation group, the 5 models have the same forebody as the parent hull form. Out of these 2 of the models have a club footing in the aft section which is varied between the two. The other 3 models have a stern design incorporating a transom, concentric bulb and a U-shaped section. The stern variation models were tested for design load displacement (847 t) with a design trim by aft (B Trim).

In this present study, the offsets of the 10 hull forms mentioned above are used, with the offset table of each of the 10 hull forms consisting of 240 offset values, which are taken from the same structured grid with 24 stations and 10 waterlines. Each of these offsets is then zero-centered as described in section 4.2. Subsequently, each of these normalised offsets is mapped to a set of 9 principal scores using the transformation matrix.

5.5 Results and Accuracy of the Models developed using PCA

Two separate ML models were created like in the previous cases, one for developing the resistance predictions and the other for the prediction of propulsive coefficients. The inputs for both the prediction models were the 9 Principal Scores obtained through PCA, along with the corresponding trim and Froude No. SVR models were preferred due to the relatively small size of data sets (192 data points for resistance and 90 for propulsive coefficients). The output of the resistance prediction model was in terms of C_D , and for the propulsive coefficients, the prediction values were wake fraction (w), thrust deduction factor (t), open water efficiency (η_o) and relative rotative efficiency (η_r).

Both the SVR models for resistance and propulsive coefficients were found to be highly accurate. Considering that the size of the data set is much smaller, SVRs were found to be a better model than ANNs for this case. The model for resistance prediction had an overall score of coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.971 for test data, with an average error percentage of 0.78% and a maximum error percentage of 4.41%.

Hyperparameter tuning for both the SVR models was undertaken using Grid Search Technique. The hyperparameters with $\epsilon=0.0001$, $\Gamma=1$, $C=1$ and Radial Basis Function were used for Resistance prediction. The hyperparameters with $\epsilon=1*10^{-10}$, $\Gamma=1$, $C=1$ and Radial Basis Function were used for the prediction of propulsive coefficients.

The model for prediction of propulsive coefficients had an overall score of coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.946 for test data, with an average error percentage of 0.95% and a maximum error % of 4.46% in predicting the Delivered Horsepower. Some sample predictions and their comparison with actual values are shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6: Effective and delivered HP, between Actual Values from BSRA Series and Prediction made by ML models for hull forms with (a) Bulbous Bow Section, (b) Small Club Foot and (c) Bulb with 15% sectional area

The model was used to predict the powering requirements from extrapolated values up to 7.5 knots and 14.5 knots as well, as in the model experiments they were only tested from 9.5 knots to 13.5 knots. The readings for the same seem to be in sync with the rest of the values and form a smooth graph with no abrupt changes.

In order to test the efficacy of using PCA, with an unknown hull form, the principal scores of 8 hull forms along with their corresponding 9 principal scores and Froude number, trim values were used to train the SVR models for resistance prediction. The hull form with a 10% bulb and transom stern were used as test models to predict and validate the values of resistance.

With the very limited propulsion coefficients data available (only 90 points), creating a functional SVR model did not seem possible to predict just the propulsive coefficients of 2 hull forms which were completely unknown to the training model.

However, for the entire data of propulsive coefficients, which included all the 10 training models, the SVR models were able to give good predictions of the propulsive coefficients when the training and testing data were randomly split with a ratio of 80%:20%, with the results shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Comparative Prediction of C_R for hulls with (a) transom sections (b) bulb with 10% sectional areas at even keel (c) bulb with 10% sectional areas at B trim

6. Conclusion

The paper investigates the possibility of using Machine Learning models for the prediction of resistance and propulsive coefficients designed according to the BSRA hull forms. The data for training and evaluation of the models were obtained from a series of tables, which showed the variations in resistance and propulsion coefficients of various BSRA hull forms for varying Froude numbers.

To illustrate the ability of these models to provide accurate predictions, the results have been presented, comparing their predictions with those derived from actual model tests. The ML models have proved to be highly accurate with maximum deviations of less than 5%. Properly designed and trained Machine Learning models such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Support Vector Regression (SVR) proved to be rather effective in the evaluation of resistance and powering of BSRA series hull forms. The applicability of PCA to understand the variations in hull forms and their impact on resistance and powering has also been assessed and is found to be a promising technique in obtaining predictions for resistance, propulsion, and possibly even other hydrodynamic performance parameters.

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Wind Assisted Ship Propulsion Route Optimization using Short Span High Accuracy Weather Forecast

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Abstract

This paper outlines a framework for short term progress prediction using intermittent (hourly) real time information from models for wind, sea state and tidal stream on the North Sea. Based on these forecasts and the vessel's speed prediction model, isochrones are calculated for six consecutive hours ahead in time. The quality of these predictions for wind sea is on average very good with a bias of less than 0.01 m and 0.28 m rms error, based on four North Sea measuring locations during years 2021 and 2022. Based on this a maximum progress track is constructed that produces the greatest distance for the planned time.

1. Introduction

Adding a wind appendage, i.e. a foil, rotor or wing, to assist the vessel's conventional propulsion seems to gain momentum. The overall aim is to reduce fuel consumption and the associated exhaust gas. Up till now the common routing approach is to use the conventional 'direct' route. In order to utilize the propulsive wind energy to its full potential, a planning or routing strategy is deemed necessary. This paper describes a method to actively enhance the wind propulsion by incorporating high quality hydro-meteo models in the route planning. A case study demonstrates that 10% progress gain could be reached by optimal routing.

Having outlined (COMPIT22) a framework for a user interface that combines the performance model of a hybrid propulsion system with the observed confidence of wind forecasts on the North Sea, we found that routing based on multi-day forecasts lacked precision to reliably determine the ship's progress.

Several studies into optimal routing with WASP exist, *Szlapczynska (2015)* provides an excellent introduction in the collection of work that is already done. Weather has always been a major contributor to the progress of a vessel underway. In the case of added wind propulsion, this is even greater. In general, routing for long voyages, like ocean crossings, is usually based on climatological data, e.g. from the Atlas of Pilot Charts, *NIMA (2002)* or *Admiralty (1973)*. Such a climatologically optimized route can be adapted from day to day based on short term weather forecasts, the condition of the ship and the experience of the ship's crew.

However, some elements are hard to model. One of these is the sea state and its effect on the vessel's speed. Examples of fast changing sea state, e.g. a one meter increase of wave height in as little as three hours of time, are not hard to find. Although it is commonly known that the sea state has a big influence on the vessel's speed, creating a prediction model for that relation appears to be difficult.

Apart from the sea state issue and its influence, the reliability of the forecast is another issue. A routing advise generally suggests deviating from the shortest route in order to avoid areas of inclement weather or find favorable weather. This deviation must be paid beforehand by sailing extra miles. When this investment does not pay because of unreliable forecast then the credibility of routing advise deteriorates vastly.

In order to gain confidence in the routing by the ship's crew the overall quality of the routing measure must be increased and, ideally, provided with a margin or confidence interval. This margin depends

on the quality of the hydro-meteo models and the vessel's speed prediction model.

Operating the ship by utilizing wind assistance to its full capacity appears paramount. It might sound contrary to popular belief to state that the modern licensed navigator, apart from the occasional leisure sailer, is not necessarily also skilled in the use of wind for ship's propulsion. Until now, licensed nautical officers have not had any training on that subject.

Tuning the wind appendage, i.e. trimming the wing to the apparent wind, seems appropriate to automate. This seems even more apt when two or more wings are fitted because of their interaction, i.e. the airflow around one is influenced by the other. Routing the vessel, however, is a task that needs human supervision because of its large consequences for the operational cost and safety of vessel and cargo.

In order to utilize the vessel's full potential, the crew needs to gain a body of knowledge and working experience for wind assisted propulsion and be aware of the limitations of the ship. Experience with meteo/hydro phenomena can be gained by visualizing reliable models that are up to date, i.e. the value of the model is verified by the user's observation. Also visualization the speed and course potential in relation to the destination and target time of arrival is helpful. And by showing both meteo/hydro information and the speed potential in relation to the target and ETA, the ship's captain can take a balanced decision in deploying minimal conventional propulsion while maximizing wind propulsion at a favorable course and fulfill the target arrival time as well. In this ideal situation the ship can be utilized to its potential in all conditions of weather, be it forecast or sudden events.

2. Hydro and Wind Model

The operational forecasts of waves and hydrodynamics (water levels and currents) in the North Sea and the Dutch coastal waters are provided by Deltares. These are used as input for the demonstration of the routing model, see Section 3. The present section gives a description on these forecast data of wave, hydrodynamics and also wind.

For the waves, the numerical model SWAN (Simulating Waves Near shore; *Booij et al. (1999)*), developed at Delft University of Technology for computing random, wind-generated waves in coastal regions, is used for the applied SWAN-DCSM model. The SWAN-DCSM domain covers the area from (48°N; 12°W) to (64°N; 9°E) with a resolution of $1/20^\circ \times 1/30^\circ$ (which is circa 3.6 km x 3.6 km). In order to save computational time, some areas that are expected to be irrelevant for waves in the area of interest – being the Dutch coastal waters – have been removed from the grid. These are the Irish Sea and some Norwegian fjords, Fig.1.

Fig.1: Bed levels of SWAN-DCSM wave model [m-MSL] and selection of wind and wave measuring locations used for validation

Since 2015 the SWAN-DCSM model runs continuously in operational mode. Eight times a day, a run is started in FEWS-North Sea, with a forecast horizon of 48 hours. The initial wave field is computed from a 6 hour hindcast run. SWAN-DCSM makes use of Harmonie wind fields from the Dutch meteorological Institute (KNMI), wave boundary spectra from the operational global (0.25°) WAM wave model of the European Centre for Medium-Range Forecast (ECMWF) and water level and current fields from the Dutch operational hydrodynamic model Waqua-DCSM. The model output consists of maps of various wave parameters covering the entire computational domains and time series of wave parameters and spectra at selected locations. Most of these locations represent measuring locations so that the model results can be compared with observed data.

The model quality depends on resolution, settings, physical descriptions and the input data of which the wind is often most important but also not exactly known. Uncertainties in wave forecasts are therefore inevitable and these tend to be larger for larger forecast horizons. Based on the available hourly data of four locations (A121, F3, L91, Q11) during the years 2021 and 2022 the average bias in significant wave height of the nowcast is less than 0.01 m. However, for some locations the waves are underestimated, for others overestimated. The root-mean-square-error (rmse) is 0.28 m. The rmse increases to 0.35 m for 48 hour forecasts. The bias does hardly increase for longer lead times. This means that on average the wave forecasts two days in advance are as good as the nowcasts but the spread and thus the uncertainty around the forecasts is larger for those larger lead times.

Fig.2: Scatter plot of significant wave height H_{m0} (left panels) and wind speed (right panels) at location F3 covering the years 2021 and 2022. Panels 1 and 3 concern the nowcast, panels 2 and 4 the results for 48 h forecast horizon. σ is the standard deviation, the number of (3 hourly) samples is indicated by #.

Also for the wind speed and direction, the model quality is assessed. On average – based on six locations (Nelson Platform, A121, F3, AWG, K13a, Q11) - the wind speed is slightly overestimated with an overall bias of 0.3 m/s or 4%. The rmse is 1.8 m/s. The rmse increases with larger lead times to 2.3 m/s. The bias in wind direction is only -2° . The rmse increases from 27° to 36° when the lead time is 48 h instead of 0 h. The spatial resolution of the Harmonie weather model is 2.5 km x 2.5 km.

Fig.3: Forecast quality significant wave height H_{m0} (left) and wind velocity (right) in terms of relative bias (upper panels) and root-mean-square-error (lower panels).

The currents have been simulated by the Waqua-DCSM-v6 model, *Zijl et al. (2013)*, with Harmonie wind, which is expected to be replaced soon by the DCSM-FlexibleMesh model. Typical values for the rmse of depth averaged flow velocities at the North Sea are 0.06-0.1 m/s (*Laan and Zijl, (2020)*).

The spatial resolution of Waqua-DCSM-v6 is twice as high as the wave model, hence approximately 1.85 km x 1.85 km.

3. WASP routing

Procee (2022) demonstrated some of the elementary relations between force and speed acting on a wind assisted motor ship. This limited approach showed that from a given wind direction and speed and a given amount of conventional propulsion, the vessel's speed can be predicted. This potential speed was used to create isochrones with 24 hours separation. It was also found that the low reliability of multiple day wind forecasts had a great effect on the margin in the created isochrone. Because isochrones are used incrementally, the margins grow exponentially, which renders multiple day routing useless. This would leave the navigator to sail the shortest route and hope for the best.

When, however, a shorter time horizon is used for weather and sea state forecast, as explained in the previous paragraph, the reliability increases. Taken into account that connectivity is no longer an issue for shipping, marine service providers are able to share high quality hydro-meteo information on an hourly basis. That would enable the wind assisted vessel to adapt the climatologically optimized route to the weather situation in real time. A flow chart to illustrate this is shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Real Time Routing

3.1. Ship's speed in waves

Because the great variety in sea keeping behavior of ships and the apparently inherent difficulty in modeling the relation between sea state and the ship's speed, the predicted influence of waves on speed is inferred from a generic model *Nathaniel Bowditch (2017)*, p.695. This model relates the wave height and the apparent direction to the predicted speed of a generic seagoing (cargo) vessel

operating at 18 kn on a flat surface. Although it is known that the vessel's response to waves depends on the encountered wave period and wave direction, *Clark (2005)*, pp.244-249, the subsequent induced resistance and its effect on speed is not directly related to Bowditch's generic model. Hence the tentative approach for predicting the progress of a vessel utilizing Wind Assisted Propulsion.

The relation between speed and wave direction is deduced from Bowditch's generic graph. Three wave heights were chosen, i.e. 18, 14 and 10 feet, that were relevant for the case that is worked out in this paper. These curves were assumed to be quadratic, coefficients were inferred by Least Squares Adjustment. In order to avoid working with a look up table, the coefficients were modeled as function of wave height, Fig.5. This enables the retrieved momentary local wave height to define the coefficients of the speed direction curve. This speed direction curve and the retrieved wave direction defines the predicted speed in the given sea state for the given course of the vessel. GIS is used to query the stored hydro-meteo data. As Bowditch does not specify wave height, it is assumed to be the significant wave height.

Fig.5: Performance curves as angle of attack for 18' (violet; lower curve; first in legend), 14' (green) and 10' (blue; upper curve; 3d in legend) wave height. Derived from *Bowditch (2017)*

3.2 Ship's speed prediction

The following elementary relations are used to predict the ship's speed when propelled by a conventional propeller and a wind appendage, Fig.6. Initially, the hull moves through the water in the direction of the conventional propulsion, i.e. over the bow. Adding the velocity of the water, i.e. stream, results in a direction of the hull over ground. (Stream is usually referring to a tidal driven flow, current refers to flow resulting from a.o. frictional coupling of wind.) This ground vector generates an induced wind vector. The summation of induced wind and true wind results in the apparent wind. This is the wind vector that has an effect on the used appendage, be it a conventional sail, a rotor sail, or a suction foil. These variants each differ in their production of lift and drag related to their area A , their effect on propulsion, however, is basically the same. Generally, the generated lift L is the product of wind load pressure $P_w = 0.5\rho v^2$ the area A and the type of rig, hence, $L = P_w C_L A$ which is perpendicular to the apparent wind. The drag, $D = P_w C_D A$, works in the direction of the apparent wind and is detrimental to propulsion. C_D and C_L are coefficients for drag and lift respectively, ρ is the net air density and v the net wind speed. The decomposed lift and drag result in the net wind propulsive force and the net side force. The latter is to be compensated by a transversal force that can be generated by the hull going through the water at a lee angle α . This resulting lee angle is shown in the figure. Because modeling the lift generating force by a conventional hull at a lee angle is not known, it is left out of this speed prediction and is tentatively chosen to be 5° (as shown in Fig.6). The resulting lee angle effects the speed vector through the water, which effects the ground

vector, and subsequently the apparent wind, which effects the lift and drag. The equilibrium is found by iterating three to four cycles. The shift of the dynamic pivot point to forward generally results in a windward tending vessel, i.e. the torsion resulting from the wind's center of effort and the hull's pivot point. This moment is counteracted by an amount of weather helm. The positive side effect of this weather helm is a lift force that partly compensates the net side force albeit at the cost of induced drag by the rudder. For simplicity, this effect is left out of the routing model covered in this paper. The details are mentioned here to show that the speed prediction of a wind assisted vessel is complicated and needs research and advanced modeling to come into fruition.

Fig.6: Decomposed Wind Propulsion

The typical drivers in this model are wind, stream and conventional propulsion. In equilibrium the forces and moments cancel out at the predicted speed. Wave induced resistance is part of that equation. As illustrated in Fig.4, the models for wind, stream and wave provide the data used in the speed prediction model. Due to the relatively short forecast horizon the reliability of the data is much better compared to e.g. a multi day forecast.

3.3 Retrieval of Hydro Meteo Data

For this case a Geographic Information System (GIS) is used to store and retrieve hydro- meteo data. It can be expected that for continuous routing, data will be retrieved directly from a Marine Service Provider, e.g. Copernicus Marine Data Store, <https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products>. We consider significant wave height (SWAN-DCSM), surface current (WAQUA-DCSM-v6) and surface wind (WIND_GLO_PHY_L4_NRT_012_004 retrieved from Copernicus), for six consecutive hours on a tentatively chosen day, i.e. 13 Jan 2023. Data points were resampled and redefined to a 100 m x 100 m grid in the UTM projection consisting of one value for either wind direction, wind speed, wave height, wave direction, current speed, current direction per grid cell. UTM was chosen for ease of calculating distance and direction. The inherent disadvantages of the non-conformal UTM projection is considered to be limited for the small geographical range, i.e. inside the limits of one zone.

3.4 Study Scenario

In the given study scenario, a wind assisted vessel is underway from a waypoint just north of Friesland Junction to a waypoint off Esbjerg during a tentatively chosen 6-hour period on 13 Jan 2023. We consider spatial maps of significant wave height, surface current, and surface wind, for six consecutive hours, starting at 2am UTC. Data points were resampled and redefined to a 100 m x 100 m grid in the UTM projection consisting of one value for either wind direction, wind speed, wave height, current speed and current direction per grid cell. It appeared that during the early morning a

980 HPa low pressure area crosses the North Sea from Scotland to the Skagerrak with associated wind speed up to 17 m/s which corresponds to force 8 on the Beaufort scale predominantly from the southwest. The waves, coming from the southwest increase to some 5.5 m. significant wave height. The tidal stream is disturbed by the wind friction.

Fig.7: Six Consecutive Isochrones starting 02:00 UTC and ending 08:00 UTC on 13 Jan 2023

Fig.7 shows the situation at 08hr UTC, the blue arrows indicate the stream vector, the eb current runs near the Danish German coast, the flood has started to run in the north of the area and off the Dutch coast. There is slack water in between. The wave height and direction is shown by the green vectors, the green contour lines show the areas with an equal range of wave height. Wind direction and speed are shown by the light purple colored arrows. It appears that the wind is rather equally distributed over the area of interest.

For every hour the vessel's potential progress is calculated as function of heading, the prevailing hydro-meteo data and the amount of conventional power. At the start of the scenario, at waypoint A, six varieties of heading, each 15° apart, are taken into account. This results in six potential positions after one hour sailing. These six positions can be regarded as a time front also known as isochrone. From each of these six positions a variety of headings are used again to calculate the potential progress during the second hour and based on the prevailing conditions during that hour. The foremost perimeter of these is regarded the second time front. Filtering least successful points avoids the exponential growth of points and calculations. This process continues for the number of available hourly forecasts, which in this study is six. From the consecutive isochrones, Fig.7, it is found that the shortest connection from time front 6 to waypoint B, depicted here as a red line, is 6 nautical miles shorter compared to the distance from time front 6 to B over the direct connection from A to B. This is the equivalent of one knot in speed over ground or about 10% gain just by modifying the heading of the vessel. The argument that the apparent gain will be lost again when the heading has to be adjusted in order to reach waypoint B is hypothetical. If the European meteorological services are able to provide high quality forecasts on a continuous basis, e.g. every six hours an updated forecast with even a longer forecast horizon, than the planning can be adjusted accordingly. In this study the

forecast horizon was limited to six hours in order to gain insight into the feasibility of using high quality short-term forecasts.

3.5 Least Time/Least Fuel considerations

Taking into account the maritime transport's business model and also its function as link in the logistical chain, it becomes clear that in general the goal is to arrive at a given location at a predefined desired time. From the daily ship's cost perspective this means reducing the speed as much as possible to arrive just in time. On the other hand, because there's usually a penalty on arriving late, the ship's officers tend to build up a margin by sailing faster than the planned economic speed. In the case of a wind assisted vessel the requirement to sail at least cost and arrive just in time becomes even more complicated. The reason for this is that the propulsion depends on a share of conventional power and associated fuel cost, and a share of wind propulsion which is free of operational cost but hard to plan. This results in the task to decide how much conventional propulsion is needed for any leg of the voyage because at any part of that voyage the wind, waves and stream will affect the amount of wind propulsion, hence the ship's progress.

The cost of sailing a wind assisted vessel is a function of conventional power setting combined with the wind propulsion, against its speed over ground. The latter is effected by the stream as well.

Let F_w be the net wind propulsion force and F_c the propulsive force from the conventional engine, assuming the speed v_w at lee angle α equals the speed in the bow direction, then the predicted speed through the water relates to:

$$v_w = \sqrt{\frac{F_w + F_c}{c_1}}$$

Where c_1 is a factor containing $\frac{1}{2} \rho c A$ etc. for the ship's hull. The associated labor can be estimated by: speed times thrust, hence:

$$v_w(F_w + F_c) = c_1 v_w^3$$

while c_2 is a consumption factor, the fraction of conventional consumption fr can be determined:

$$fr = \frac{F_c}{F_c + F_w}$$

hence the energy consumption E_c per time:

$$E_c = fr c_2 v_w^3 \quad [1]$$

A voyage from location A to B is defined by three elements, its distance d_{AB} , the Estimated Time of Departure (ETD) and the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA). The route can be split in legs of one hour sailing each.

The voyage sailing time is defined as $t_v = ETA - ETD$, this defines the target speed v_{tg} per leg over ground:

$$v_{tg} = \frac{d_{AB}}{t_v}$$

The effective, i.e. decomposed in the leg's direction, magnitude of the stream vector s_{tr} can be determined for each position and time of an individual leg. From this, the target speed through the water is determined:

$$v_{tw} = \frac{d_{AB}}{t_v} - S_{tr}$$

With a forecast speed and direction of the wind it can now be iterated how much conventional thrust F_c will be needed to reach v_{tw} at heading C_n , i.e. minus the leeway α , that relates to the true wind. Also the associated consumption of energy, i.e. usually fuel, can be determined with Eq.(1).

For any heading that is part of the direct route, i.e. without optimizing, the estimated consumption for the voyage:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{n=t_v} fr c_2 v_w^3$$

where n is the leg number. By applying a number of variants C_n , in order to construct isochrones a number of routes can be analysed in search for the least fuel route.

3.6 Design challenge

Naval architects can exploit new areas of interest, that is developing a hull which induces minimal drag as effect of asymmetrical water flow due to the leeway in order to generate sufficient lift force that compensates the wind appendage's side force.

A second consideration for optimization is to control the location of the dynamic pivot point in order to reduce the amount of weather helm by balancing vessel under sail, i.e. canceling the torque from the Centre of Effort (CE) and dynamic Pivot Point.

A third consideration is to optimize the dry area of the hull in order to allow for an undisturbed airflow over deck, coaming(-s) and accommodation.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

Supported by this routing method, the Officer On Watch (OOW) determines the optimum course and conventional propulsion setting in order to reach the mission's goal. (i.e. the port of destination, the required time of arrival or, alternatively, window of arrival time, and cost reduction)

The role of the human is paramount because little is known yet about operating a hybrid propelled ship. In order to rebuild a body of knowledge and associated working strategies, like there used to be in the era of sailing merchant vessels, the navigator needs to be on board and work with his tools and the elements.

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Increasing Maritime Safety by Integrating IoT-Captured Biometric Data into Regular Messaging from the Ship's Bridge

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Abstract

In this paper, we present an experimental approach to increase navigational safety in ship manoeuvring by combining biometric data collected via the Internet of Things with an automatic identification system (AIS). During the challenging cognitive phase of a ship manoeuvre, biometric data were collected and processed to determine the correlation between the challenging cognitive task and the expected average body response of the participants, including their state of awareness. The analysed values are sent within an AIS slot to the alarm centre on the bridge and to the coastal station (Vessel Traffic Services). This sequence may increase the safety and integrity of navigation and manoeuvring. The concept supports smart navigation and electronic solutions, which are becoming increasingly important in the modern shipping industry.

1. Introduction

The following experimental design aims to equip ships' officers-on-watch (OOW) with smart biometric wristbands to monitor cognitive load, fatigue, and awareness. The algorithm compares the measured features with a personalized average value and informs both the bridge console monitoring system and the Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) via an AIS or Very High Frequency (VHF) data exchange system (VDES) signal if the value is exceeded.

The prevention of maritime accidents has become an important research topic that enhances maritime safety and provides the background for this study. In the last five years, human error has been shown to be the most important factor involved in maritime accidents in one way or another, *EMSA. (2022)*. Therefore, research on human error aims to detect biometric characteristics, such as the stress and cognitive load of OOWs during navigation watch. Monitoring biometric parameters may indicate changes in the body due to a real-time situation on the navigation bridge, indicating higher amplitude of measurement characteristics and increased workload and after the data being processed, which could result in Human Erroneous Action (HEA). Wrist sensors non-invasively monitor physiological signals and sleep patterns in real time. They were originally developed to measure athletic activity, but today the average smartwatch has multifunctional sensors that have recently been used to detect workload to study stress and the body's response to disturbing factors during a given task *Borisov et al. (2021)*. Workload has been attempted to be detected by measuring galvanic skin response, skin temperature, and heart rate variability. The advantage of wearable devices is that their measurements, such as cardiac arrhythmias or fatigue, can be monitored while the person is performing daily tasks *Geršak et al. (2020)*.

Wearable sensors and IoT technology could be used to detect potential HEA so that the emergency response center (VTS) could help the user, *IALA Guideline. (2022)*. In maritime transport, the IoT concept is used under the name of e-Navigation, which enables a VDES that includes a search and rescue (SAR) system, navigation aids, cargo and vessel tracking systems, etc. Automatic data exchange between on-board systems, humans, and shore personnel is one of the major challenges posed by the introduction of autonomous ships, *Xia et al. (2020)*.

The background of the research is the development of a concept for monitoring biometric parameters of marine pilots with the aim of improving safety during the cognitively demanding phase. The following experimental concept involves smart wristbands to measure biometric parameters and monitor awareness. The algorithm compares the measured value with an average value and informs both the bridge console and the VTS via a AIS or VDES signal when the value is exceeded. The VDES signal consists of several strings (slots), e.g., position, Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI), cargo,

name, weather, tide, virtual buoys, etc. The concept uses the available VDES slots for the biometric data only when the threshold is exceeded, including state of awareness/cognitive load/stress.

2. Methodology

There is no single definition of fatigue, cognitive load, and stress, but they are generally considered to be the body's response to demanding, adverse external conditions that affect a person's well-being and performance on various tasks. Disturbing factors that elicit negative responses are referred to as stressors. Cognitive load and stress have mostly been studied qualitatively and measured as perceived stress by individuals. However, in the maritime field, interest in determining objective signs of stressors has increased, with studies showing a relationship between physiological variables and the effects of disturbance, *Petrescu et al. (2021)*, *Maglić et al. (2020)*. Participants on the ship's bridge are non-invasively equipped with multiple synchronized wireless physiological sensors during experimental tasks, similar to Fig.1, where measured variables such as heart rate (HR), galvanic skin response (GSR), electrodermal activity (EDA), body temperature, blood volume pulse (BVP), blood pressure are recorded. In general, elevated readings correlate with increased cognitive load, fatigue, and stress. However, it should be noted that the response to stressors can vary, and reaction states can look very different in individuals.

Fig.1: Participants are equipped with non-invasive smartwatches or wristbands with multiple synchronized physiological sensors, including EDA, BVP, temperature, acceleration, and heart rate, during experimental tasks.

Typically, studies are conducted by measuring one or more physiological variables of the participants in different situations that place different demands on the cognitive load of the participants. Post-processing, which involves the application of machine learning algorithms to detect cognitive load and stress (*Fridman et al., 2018*), is typically based on expert input or self-assessment questionnaires, with algorithms trained, tested, and evaluated on labelled data. Real-time processing is important to detect potential human errors in tasks where safety may be compromised. Therefore, we propose an anomaly detection algorithm for continuous analysis of recorded signals that enables early detection of potential anomalies.

We analyze data from the experiment, *Žagar et al. (2020)*, in which participants (N=6) had to complete a simulated task of manoeuvring a ship in the harbour entrance. Participants were exposed to a wind gust and a difficult harbour entrance that affected their performance due to the narrow and dredged shipping channel, potentially causing a high workload. Data were collected non-invasively and wirelessly using the Empatica wristband, Fig.1, and streamed to the cloud where they were processed.

Observational data include HR, EDA, and BVP, with sampling rates of 1Hz, 4Hz, and 64Hz, respectively, assuming that increased signal amplitude correlates with or indicates changes in cognitive load, stress, and fatigue. A promising option for biometric data processing seems to be the unsupervised k-nearest neighbor (k-NN) model, which is able to detect anomalies. For streamed data, a sliding window method is used, where the model is run on a temporary batch of data in a specified time window. Each new data point is compared to the data in the current batch. The batch is updated with the latest data after a specified sliding time, and this new data is used for comparison with the previous batch. Post-processing is used to reduce noise and calibrate the results to indicate the probability of occurrence of an anomaly. The anomaly detection result of the biometric data can be integrated as part of e-navigation on the ship's bridge to monitor physiological responses, improve self-awareness, and support the decision-making process. The concept supports intelligent navigation and electronic solutions on the modern ship's bridge. When potentially dangerous reaction states are detected, the analyzed values are sent to the alarm center on the bridge console and to the coastal station VTS via a free slot in the VDES, as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2: Concept of AIS (VDES) data of the tracked ship seen on the electronic chart in the VTS control center including biometrical data. (Source: Adapted from *Mehlmauer et al. (2023)*)

Designed in response to channel congestion at AIS, the VDES provides two additional channels for application-specific messages, doubling the bandwidth of AIS. It adds a terrestrial layer (VDES-Ter) and a satellite layer (VDES-Sat) to extend the reach of VDES beyond the standard broadcast range. Advanced coding techniques will increase bandwidth by up to 32 times in the existing VHF maritime bands, which are scheduled for introduction in 2023.

The increased bandwidth will enable real-time monitoring of exceeded and biometric values that have the potential for HEA through the concept of anomaly detection. If necessary, shore-based authorities will advise and assist the ship, which should improve the safety and integrity of navigation and maneuvering.

3. Results

Workload monitoring uses learning algorithms that detect anomalies in the recorded signal and provide quantification of the anomaly in the biometric response, setting the onset of the measurement as a control condition before performing the demanding tasks. The input of explicit knowledge to the algorithms can be done in two ways: a) general domain knowledge is included in the form of well-defined rules, and b) further experiments can be performed under controlled conditions in the nautical simulator and the responses of each participant can be labelled, which we have done.

Fig.3: Labelling disturbances to the biometrical response

The marked and labelled size change in Fig.3 represents the response to the perturbation. The goal is to discover similarities and common patterns in the physiological responses of the participants caused by the stressor or challenging cognitive tasks in order to learn the algorithm. During the observed interval of the port approach in Fig.4, the probability of the anomaly score reflects the normalized characteristic value of the individual participant.

Fig.4: Participant's anomaly score. After sensitivity is calibrated (noise reduction), the results correlate with disturbances.

The upper red line indicates the anomaly score that affects the observed signals when the noise reduction factor is high, which is too sensitive in this case. After calibration, the lower red signal indicates intervals when the excitation is highest, which correlates with disturbances in Figure 3. The sequence of entering the harbour channel shows that the demanding cognitive task is considered a disturbance that affects the participant. The peak anomaly observed in this interval suggests that the participant's response to the disturbances involves enhanced cognitive processes in working memory, which is consistent with the post-task interviews. The participants confirm that the demanding task of maintaining situational awareness while entering the navigation channel requires observation of both the external situation and the navigation instruments. The results show that during the phase of the experiment requiring high cognitive effort, participants exhibit significant body responses related to the level of workload, experience, and fatigue. The study suggests that simulated navigation tasks with biometric features on a ship's bridge could increase awareness and safety at sea.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the experimental approach, the biometric measurement approach can be integrated as part of e-navigation on the ship's bridge to monitor physiological responses, improve self-awareness, and support the decision-making process. When potentially dangerous reaction states are detected, an alarm is triggered requiring an appropriate response to the situation. However, due to the highly individual characteristics of the participants, we are working with psychological, medical, and maritime experts to accurately identify stressors and workload factors and learn the algorithm. In addition, an improvement in real-time monitoring is proposed where shore-based authorities are connected to the ship via VDES to monitor physiological responses and workload on the bridge and assist the ship as needed.

Despite its contribution to security, implementation of such a system could face two challenges: a) transmission of biometric data via VDES should comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation for cross-border data transfers, and b) cyberattacks on VDES could lead to interception or manipulation of biometric data, which could result in false alarms or missed alarms that could compromise crew safety. However, by remotely monitoring biometric measurements on the ship's bridge via VDES, ship operators can also take proactive measures to ensure the safety and well-being of their crew and improve their operational efficiency, especially if a crew member's biometric data indicates high levels of stress or fatigue, stakeholders can take action to provide additional support and prevent accidents or errors. So, it worths to make an effort to address the challenges.

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Open-Source Web Service for Fast and Reliable Handling of Weather Data for Use in Maritime Simulations

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Abstract

Efficient ship design requires understanding the impact of operational and environmental conditions on the final ship. Discrete-event simulation and quasi-static ship models using MetOcean data can help, but storing the large amounts of weather data required can be impractical, and accessing data directly through open services can be slow and unreliable. Furthermore, metrological organizations updating or deleting data can compromise the reproducibility of simulation results. To address these issues, we propose a web service that caches MetOcean data between the ship simulator and the metrological organizations services, cloud-based file storage and a PostGIS database used as storage layer. This ensures that data is not requested more than once for a given temporal and geographical coordinate, and remains available as long as needed. The performance of the new service is benchmarked against downloading data and accessing it directly using OpenDAP.

1. Introduction

Meeting IMO's goal of 40% GHG reduction in the maritime sector by 2030 and 50% by 2050, *IMO (2018)*, a variety of new fuels, ship designs and energy-saving devices and strategies has been conceived in a frenzy of opportunistic innovation. To reach the IPCC goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C, the world's GHG emissions need to be net zero within the decade, *IPCC (2022)*. Although retrofitting existing ships with low-, or zero-carbon fuels are possible, fuels such as hydrogen and ammonia possess explosive, toxic and space-demanding properties implying requirements to the ship design and construction to meet regulations and become practical. New fuels also being more expensive for each unit of energy delivered to the propulsor, underlines the importance of energy efficiency, which may be achieved by tailoring the ship design to conditions and operational requirements it will face if built. New builds that are conceived as zero-emission ships from the ground up gives the flexibility to accommodate these factors, if the designer can reveal the true impact of a given design choice on the economic and environmental performance.

In practice, this impact is hard to understand and quantify, much due to the sheer complexity of a ship system, not to mention when put into a logistic transportation system with factors such as commercial requirements, fuel availability and weather conditions. Traditionally, this is handled by using an existing ship design with similar requirements as a starting point for a design spiral. With the usual pressure on the naval architect in terms of an approaching deadline, it may be hard or almost impossible to do bold explorations of the design space and being sure that a design change has no negative effect on some other part of the ship or in the logistic system.

The rapid increase of available computational power at the naval architect's desktop during the past decades has revolutionized our ability to evaluate the performance of a given ship design. Empirical, frequency domain and time domain analysis methods are blended into tools that can evaluate the ship design increasingly more holistic. Examples of recent significant developments are:

- Ship design suites such as NAPA, ShipX and WAMIT, each incorporating several tools for ship design and analysis, often focusing on empirical and frequency-domain analysis in addition to graphical tools for altering the hull.
- Computational Fluid Dynamics software such as Star-CCM+ and OpenFOAM. Being general-purpose tools, these are still much used in the maritime domain for calm-water predictions and to a certain degree wave interactions.

- The Horizon 2020 EU project HOLISHIP applied the CAESES optimization platform to automate the exploration of the design space of parametric ship models, *Papanikolaou et al. (2022)*.
- Use of co-simulation, *Skjong et al. (2018)*, through Open Simulation Platform, *Smogeli et al. (2020)*, to mix-and-match simulation models of sub-systems of a ship, such as hull, propulsion, power plant, cranes, etc., into a holistic representation of the ship concept to simulate certain manoeuvres and wave responses.
- Use of quasi-static (frequency-domain) modelling of the ship to allow for evaluation of the performance of the ship concept in a logistic transportation system, *Dahlen et al. (2021)*, *Fathi et al. (2013)*.

General for these methods, and for ship design, is the need for knowledge of the sea-, and weather conditions that the ship will operate in. The main dimensions, hull shape and stability of the ship greatly impacts the ships performance, both in terms of energy usage and safety for crew and cargo. The naval architect often has guidelines for typical weather conditions given a geographical area of operation, used as input in the design process. However, the wave period and direction relative to the ships heading (again affected by the ship speed), determines the ship response to a given wave height. As the ship is (usually) a highly non-stationary object, determining the conditions and duration that the ship will encounter during its lifetime is an exhausting effort using traditional methods.

Retrieving representative sea-, and weather (MetOcean) data for prolonged periods of operation is possible using historical observed data, fitted onto forecast models for geospatial continuity (hindcast data). This is published openly from several major metrological services, including European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and The Norwegian Meteorological Institute (met.no). Copernicus Marine Service and SeaDataNet are examples of central services for providing access to the produced data from metrological services. Throughout this paper, MetOcean data will be used as a general term for waves, wind, and sea current data, hindcast or unprocessed, with geospatial and temporal dimensions.

The MetOcean data is usually stored as three-dimensional regularly gridded data, latitude, longitude and time, using either the GRIB, GRIB2, HDF5, or its derivate, NetCDF, file format, *Rew et al. (2006)*. In general terms the two former formats are more primitive in terms of user friendliness, however the latter tend to be more space demanding. The industry-standard software THREDDS, *Caron (2005)* is used to access and retrieve the data, *Magariño et al. (2014)*, *Nativi et al. (2010)*. A common practice is to use a sub-setter to select a reduced geographical, temporal and a selection of variables to download from the potentially enormous file on the server. This has the advantage of full control of the downloaded data, and the user has fast and reliable access to the file stored locally on the user's personal hard drive. However, several drawbacks are apparent when applied to simulation of ships on long, potentially inter-continental routes with a simulation horizon of several years:

- Depending on the resolution of the data set, the downloaded file may become impractically large (>10GB).
- Due to the nature of sub-setting, a rectangular grid must be selected for the sub-set. Seeking to cover a route going from south-west to north-east, the rectangle area is maximized, and large majority of data points will never be used. E.g. to cover an area between the Gulf of Mexico and the English Channel for one year (as described in the second use-case in Ch.4), the data set dimension is 1202 (longitude) x 525 (latitude) x 241 (time), resulting in a total of 152 083 050 data points, while the simulation only used 3057 of the points.
- It is time-consuming to figure out the geospatial and temporal limitations of the sub-set.
- In a commercial setting, but also for research, it should always be possible to reproduce a simulation at any point in time.
- The metrological services have the option of moving, altering or deleting data at any time. This conflicts with the above bullet point.
- There is no standard naming convention for the variables in the data files, neither are

projections sufficiently standardized to be automated.

- When simulating active routing decisions, *Dählen et al. (2022)*, the user does not know at forehand exactly where the ship will sail. This requires in the best case a conservative choice for the sub-set, resulting in a larger data set.

Some of the above points can be improved using the OpenDAP framework, allowing accessing and reading large data files directly on the server containing the full data set. For the user, the process of accessing files through OpenDAP resembles accessing files stored locally. When the user, or a software using the data files requests a data point, it will be routed to the remote file location.

MetOcean data is available through OpenDAP from several metrological services, including Copernicus Marine and SeaDataNet. The GYMIR simulator has been using OpenDAP successfully, however it puts great demand on the server hosting the full data file, as each simulated data point will eventually generate a new web request to the service. As the number of sampling points are on the scale of thousands for moderate cases, a significant increase in the overall simulation time has been observed, large variations depending on the traffic on the service, and when introducing parallel computing, users have been banned from the service due to several pending requests from the same IP address.

Lastly, visualisation of how the weather evolves and impacts the simulation is not strictly necessary from a naval architect's point of view but can be a great feature to understand the simulation results as well as build confidence among customers. Seemingly the easiest and most common way of doing this is by using a map client such as Leaflet and use plug-ins to read pre-processed "tiles" from a remote service to visualise pressure fields, wave heights, wind strength and direction, etc. from a WMS service. This is efficient, as the client only downloads pre-processed image files and puts on top of a geographical map. Although most meteorological services offer such tiles produced by the GEOServer software, the colour themes vary, and few offers vectors showing wind and sea current speed and direction. This is inconvenient as simulations using different weather sources will have different "look and feel" and visualizing what is required will not always be possible.

Significant research effort is aimed against storing MetOcean sensor data, *Petersen et al. (2014)*, *Smart et al. (2017)*, and navigating, processing and aggregating large weather data sets, *Fathi et al. (2022)*, *Ricky and Rahim (2021)*. However, software tailored for handling MetOcean data for use in maritime simulations, a "Metocean-Cache", seems to be needed. It should standardize the variable naming convention for easy mix-and-match of various data sources. Further it should be able to run on a cloud-based service for easy scaling of computational power as well as storage space to ensure that data can be kept indefinitely.

This paper will cover the ongoing effort to implement this service, "MetoceanCache", and describe how it relates to the GYMIR-simulator which is the first use-case.

2. MetoceanCache's place in a simulation framework

The first application of the MetoceanCache service will be the GYMIR discrete-event simulation framework for quasi-static ship simulation models. It is intended to simulate ships serving in a maritime transportation system, along realistic routes across several years of operation to uncover a ship concepts true performance as part of a larger system. This makes MetOcean data highly valuable, to emulate how the sea and weather alters along large geospatial and temporal dimensions. Also, the quasi-static nature of the simulation models adapts well to the statistical formulation of the variables in the MetOcean data, as significant wave height and average wind speeds. Gusts and rarely occurring wave conditions are not considered, as transients are left to the high-fidelity time-domain simulations.

The GYMIR simulator is built around a discrete event scheduling engine, handling various models in the simulation as agents.

Fig.1: MetoceanCache's place in the GYMIR simulation framework, *Dahlen et al. (2021)*

The basic idea behind the framework is that each simulation model, being an agent (weather, logistic system and ship) reports the time of its next significant change. This may be new weather data available along the temporal axis, ship heading changes or ship arrives at port. The discrete event scheduler selects among the reported instants the closest into the future and evaluates all agents at this instant. This minimizes computational effort but ensures that all agents consider significant changes.

The client-side of the MetoceanCache, marked in red in figure 1, becomes such an agent, and must be able to provide the instant when new data is available, in addition to the MetOcean data itself. The latter must be retrieved from the server-side at every sampling point, which is on the scale of several thousand for each simulation.

3. Software architecture and technology choices

Several considerations are made when drawing the architecture of the MetoceanCache, and flexibility is key to allow for exchanging the technology choice or implementation of separate components at later stages. The ability to deploy the application as a web-service in a cloud service requires a REST-controller and an API definition, and obviously strategies for data storage must be selected. Further, the solution must allow for accessing new weather sources at later stages. Figure 2 summarizes the architecture in terms of technology decisions.

Fig.2: MetoceanCache technology architecture. Arrows shows data flow direction

3.1. REST-controller

Although python and javascript-based frameworks such as Django, Flask and Express have gained significant foothold the recent years and are well-established, the REST-controller for Metocean-Cache is built upon the Spring Boot framework. It has been around for a long time, and Java as a programming language is by many considered easier to maintain for long periods of time. Also, most simulation platform developed by SINTEF Ocean, including GYMIR and OSP is based on Java, making direct interfacing easier if that should be necessary for performance.

3.2. Storage layer

Two storage solution, each with different advantages, were chosen to work in parallel to cover different use cases:

Blob storage, acting as a network drive with fast access for the Metocean-Cache REST-controller:

- Blob storage is cheaper than PostgreSQL storage. The largest cloud suppliers charge 5-10x more per GB for data stored in PostgreSQL than data blob storage.
- Independent of weather data providers. All data is stored in the file storage, hence no external dependencies. The open access OpenDAP api's has a tendency of being slow at peak hours. This is avoided since all data is prefetched.

PostGIS database, storing individual data points as they are requested by the user(s):

- Cached data can be retrieved quickly. Retrieving populated data can be done within few milliseconds (ms), while responses from the file storages takes 50-1000 ms. This is useful for simulations reruns or optimization tasks using similar simulations multiple times.
- Large flexibility of data variables. When using a file store, all variables must be selected when the data is retrieved and stored. With a PostGIS cache the variables can be selected in runtime.

3.3. API and client access

In its basic form, Spring Boot provides an API for RESTful access. However, it requires either an extensive manual job of documentation to enable other developers to make client code to access the API, or one must simply dive into the MetoceanCache-code base. OpenAPI is a framework to specify the API in Yaml format, then providing tools to generate the client-side code in most common languages. Using the Maven build system, the Yaml file can be updated automatically from the REST-controller code, thus making it easy to create and update the client-side in case of API updates.

4. Experimental results

The MetoceanCache, available as open-source at "<https://github.com/sintef-ocean/MetOcean-cache>", is installed on an Azure App Service, a platform-as-a-service for Spring Boot applications, using Premium v2 P1V2 for performance benchmarking.

The benchmark simulations are done using a simulation horizon of 1 year for the GYMIR simulator running on a personal computer, thus a network latency of approximately 30-40 ms between simulator and the MetoceanCache must be anticipated and is thus reflected in the benchmark figures. Both time spent for retrieving weather data, as well as time spent on ship simulation calculation (including weather retrieval), was measured to compare performance on using different strategies for retrieving MetOcean data. It should be noted that the traffic load on the servers accessed through OpenDAP (met.no and Copernicus Marine service) is unpredictable and has a significant variation, and this uncertainty should be kept in mind when comparing the results.

4.1. Use-case: Using blob-storage for simulation of small geographical extent

A simulation of a south-north bound route of the Trondheimsfjord is implemented to represent a typical short-sea simulation case with limited geographical extent. A high-resolution dataset for the Norwegian coastal areas from met.no (MyWaveWam800) is stored on Azure File Storage Container for the MetoceanCache to test the blob storage functionality. The dataset covers 5 years of data with a geographic and temporal resolution of 800 meters and 1 hour respectively, giving a total size of 480 GB. Using the data set, the simulation produces 12853 data points independent of the weather source.

Storing a full data set may be attractive if the user has a great deal of simulation cases in a geographic area of limited extent. The storage cost is approximately € 100 per year. It could be noted that storing similar data from Copernicus with 1/12-degree resolution of the entire world would require approximately 1TB of storage per year of data (costing €200 per year).

For weather sources using the blob storage, the average response time between the MetoceanCache service and the blob storage is 51 ms, when a file has recently been used by the server. For cases where a file is not accessed recently, the same figure is 742 ms. This indicates a cache mechanism in the file system between the MetoceanCache web application and the blob storage, however the precise workings of this is at the time of writing unknown to the authors.

Table I: Benchmarking simulations using alternative access methods to met.no MyWaveWam800 MetOcean dataset. All figures in seconds.

	Computational time (s)	Time spent retrieving weather data (s)	Average time / retrieval (ms)
Dataset stored on local hard drive	5.1	0.4	~ 0
Dataset accessed on met.no Thredds server through OpenDAP	1385.6	1364.1	106
Dataset access through MetoceanCache using Blob storage	1226.2	1211.0	94

Not surprisingly, using files stored locally on the user's computer hard drive is extremely fast compared to retrieving data from a web service. However, as the OpenDAP service of met.no has become slow in the recent months due to high traffic, a larger advantage of using MetoceanCache with blob storage was anticipated. Investigations has pointed in the direction of performance issues between the Azure File Storage Container and the MetoceanCache web service platform (which physically is a network connection on a server centre), however more investigations are needed. The File Storage Container is intended as a price-efficient way of storing large quantities of data, probably with a performance trade off. Looking into other storage options may be a path forward.

4.2. Use-case: Using PostGIS-database for simulation of large geographical extent

As a contrast, the transatlantic route from the Gulf of Mexico to the English Channel, typical for a Medium-Range Tanker, presented in previous work is used to test the MetoceanCache using PostGIS as storage layer. The downloaded data set, reduced to cover the area of interest, requires 11 GB of storage space using maximum temporal and geospatial resolution, 0.085 degrees and 3 hours respectively, storing wave height, wave direction and wave peak period variables. Although possible to store on a local harddrive, its troublesome to download as care must be taken to ensure the whole route is covered, and due to limitations in file size in the sub-setter, the data set must be split into several files along the temporal axis.

Table II: Benchmarking simulations using alternative access methods to Copernicus Marine Global Oceans Waves Analysis and Forecast MetOcean data set. All figures in seconds.

	Computational time (s)	Time spent retrieving weather data (s)	Average time / retrieval (ms)
Dataset stored on local hard drive	4.0	1.4	~ 0
Dataset accessed on met.no Thredds server through OpenDAP	702.3	697.5	228
Dataset access through MetoceanCache using PostGIS database (1 st run)	3627.9	3624.9	1186
Dataset access through MetoceanCache using PostGIS database (2 nd run)	128.4	125.7	41

Due to lower resolution on the data set along all axes, as well as significantly more distance between the way points of the route, the number of sampling points are reduced to 3057. This is reflected in the computational time, however due to the data downloaded to the local hard drive is compressed, the time spent retrieving data is greater.

Comparing the first and second run using the PostGIS database on the MetoceanCache, the cache-functionality works as intended as a significant performance increase is observed. However, as the cache defaults to OpenDAP in the first run when data is not yet cached, its surprising that the retrieval time is a factor of five greater than using OpenDAP directly. If this is due to slow insertion into the database, inefficient retrieval or simply large traffic on the Copernicus Marine service should be investigated. The performance during the second run is on the other hand surprisingly satisfactory as it outperforms the blob-storage in the first use case (although the data sets are not the same).

Although further investigations into the poor performance of the PostGIS storage during the first uncached run, as well as the blob storage, other requirements to the MetoceanCache such as permanent storage and access to reproduce simulations, as well as convenient access to data are addressed. Several ways forward to improve performance can be mentioned:

- Evaluating various options for improved indexing of the PostGIS database, such as TimescaleDB.
- Evaluate other ways to store the MetOcean data in a PostGIS database, e.g., store small NetCDF or Gribfiles instead of the values themselves.
- Apply other types of databases, such as MongoDB.
- Investigate alternative cloud storage options for the blob-storage.
- Investigate alternatives to RESTful API, such as gRPC.

To further improve data retrieval efficiency, simulations can estimate the ships geospatial and temporal trajectory to retrieve data points for a longer period in a single request to minimize network latency. For simulations with uncertain routes and speeds due to varying weather data (like GYMIR), an added margin along the trajectory in all dimensions can ensure complete coverage. PostGIS database is well-suited for such requests and tailoring towards MetoceanCache's intended domain is likely to give the greatest performance benefits.

5. Conclusion

A software for retrieving, storing, and accessing MetOcean data for use in maritime simulations requires key requirements. The paper presented requirements and developed a novel open-source implementation on a cloud platform. The software was applied for providing MetOcean data to a maritime simulation platform running two use-cases for performance benchmarking.

The software proved to solve many practical shortcomings of current solutions used for MetOcean data in simulations, making it more convenient and user-friendly to retrieve such data. However, potential for performance increase was identified, and further work will investigate various options in this matter.

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Integrated Shipbuilding Data Management

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Abstract

This paper discusses the significance of data and process management in ship design and building processes, which are frequently overlooked in research areas but can offer competitive advantages and benefit from a digital transformation perspective. It discusses the presentation of the shipbuilding process as a three-layered structure consisting of intent-driven design, data management, and process management. Each of these layers has a distinct level of complexity concerning typical shipbuilding challenges. Overall, integrated data management in shipbuilding is essential for managing ship design, engineering, and production, and it presents an opportunity to gain efficiency through digital transformation.

1. Introduction

Ship design and building require naval architecture, engineering, and technology knowledge. These areas are essential for defining the functionality of future floating structures and receive the most academic and computational attention. For a typical commercial vessel construction project, detailed engineering requires the management of up to 5 million construction components. Shipbuilding projects for marine structures typically last between one and five years and demand extensive process management data. This includes managing downstream and upstream shipbuilding data, materials, and personnel and data management for the entire engineering and production process. Unfortunately, these aspects are frequently neglected in research, but they present opportunities for shipbuilders to gain a competitive edge and benefit from digital transformation.

This paper focuses on integrated data management throughout a vessel's design and construction process, including extensive change management and overall management of all related data, including 3D and 2D designs, documentation, and bills of materials. The topic relates digital solutions for ship design and data management to the shipbuilding business process throughout the entire lifecycle of a typical shipbuilding project, from the concept phase to delivery and even operations.

2. Three layers: intent-driven design, data management, and process management

Typically, researchers use a design spiral to illustrate the shipbuilding process, which is a classic method for describing the cyclical development of the design through stages. It can also be considered from a linear product life cycle perspective, from functional to detailed manufacturing stages. These processes constitute a layer of intent-driven design with a unique complexity, typically consisting of several disciplines or function-specific applications. The other two layers consist of data management and process management. From a data perspective, the design process is associated with a vast quantity of diverse data types, including 3D models, calculations, drawings, and specifications, among others. A PDM (Product Data Management) system is commonly used to manage and control this information. Such systems, prevalent in other industries, have only recently been implemented in shipbuilding. The final layer is process management, which reflects how the shipyard or design office organizes and manages activities – a design for the organization, workflows, project management, etc. The interconnection of these three layers is where digital tools can significantly optimize the time and costs of the overall project. The shipbuilding industry was focused on design processes and tools for a long time, disregarding the other aspects. Data storage and management were partially included in the scope of intent-driven design tools, and process management is often overlooked as a purely business or organization management discipline.

This paper provides a generic consideration for the three layers discussed, humbly acknowledging that each shipyard or ship design organization works uniquely. This way of working often encapsulates a

competitive advantage or trade secret. The primary goal of this paper is to find an underlying model that can help describe the overall process and pinpoint possibilities to adapt existing tools, learn from other industries, or improve software tools.

Fig.1: Aligned processes along the shipbuilding lifecycle: Design, Project Management, and Data management – separate applications and interfaces for each function

3. Intent-driven design

Shipbuilding typically employs specialized software applications for functional design and calculations, modeling software for detailed design, and various applications for managing production.

Historically reliable CAD-based shipbuilding techniques utilize 3D model data and automated production output, *Seppala (2021)*. It is a well-established technology that effectively addresses the complexity of shipbuilding engineering, design, and concurrent collaboration. For large-scale projects, a large number of engineers and designers can reach thousands of individuals who require access to diverse design data, ensuring online collaboration and security layers.

Detailed engineering, where the majority of time is spent on ship design, typically uses intent-driven CAD software, *Sieranski and Zerbst (2019)*. Some parts, usually equipment and units for various purposes, are developed and supplied by specialized subcontractors. Others are fabricated on the shop floor or onboard from steel or armatures. Designing such components is challenging, with the complexity stemming primarily from the high number of topological connections between the compo-

nents. In addition, the level of complexity increases if (as is the case in the majority of instances) the work must be performed concurrently and involves multiple subcontractors specializing in specific design disciplines and providers or various technologies utilized on modern vessels. The requirement to manage complexity justifies the utilization of intent-driven design applications. Using multi-edit and preserved topological connections, it is possible to mirror and reuse similar structural components without storing each component as a separate 3D object.

This methodology generates vast quantities of diverse data types, including 3D geometry, meta-data, topological relations, product and work breakdown structures, and more. In contemporary shipbuilding, integrating this data with manufacturing execution systems (MES), procurement and material management, and enterprise resource planning (ERP) presents a challenge and a paradigm shift. Existing large-scale software solutions from other industries, such as automotive or aerospace, cannot handle the scale of shipbuilding projects and the particulars of topological connections. Therefore, it appears feasible to augment existing CAD-based solutions with data management systems and collaboration tools in order to organize design and production processes.

The number of components increases steadily throughout the design process, resulting in a rise in database sizes. Modern CAD solutions make it easier to maintain up-to-date 3D and related data, but storing the entire history of modifications presents a challenge and raises the question of structuring and identifying the required information.

4. Data management

As described, ship design and shipbuilding involve vast quantities of data, which arrive in specific formats and configurations and are simultaneously processed by multiple specialized applications.

Considering the shipbuilding process from the perspective of technology and software solutions, the composition of specialized systems varies significantly between work scopes. As their work often consists of engineering and design documentation, the naval architecture bureau would prioritize engineering, simulation, and design solutions. In addition to managing design information, a shipyard must also manage design, materials, construction, and personnel. In shipbuilding, there is an undeniable need for a centralized data management system that can manage large amounts of data, ensure data consistency and accuracy, and facilitate teamwork.

Numerous discussions exist regarding the role of seamless data transfer in the industry, with the most frequently cited initiatives including ISO15926, STEP, and OCX format usage or conversion of native data between vendor-specific formats (Sieranski & Zerbst, 2019). In contrast to the construction and mechanical industries, universal data formats and exchange protocols have yet to emerge.

All of these factors necessitate shipbuilding technology requirements and increase the complexity of data management. The idea of storing all of this data in a generic PDM solution may sound like a solution, but the volume and interconnectedness of the data raise concerns. A transparent data structure model can improve the situation, but there is no consensus on what such a model should look like. SFI classification, which is frequently referenced, provides a valuable foundation but is frequently modified for each shipyard.

The ideal situation might be described and is a centralized data management system that can manage large amounts of data, uses a universal data model suitable for different types of vessels and projects in shipbuilding, ensures data consistency and accuracy, and facilitates extensive teamwork. Data security, integrity, and interoperability are formidable obstacles that must be overcome. Lastly, big data analytics provides opportunities for improving efficiency, reducing costs, and enhancing safety in shipbuilding; however, managing large amounts of data generated by various sources is a significant challenge.

5. Process management

In addition to the IT and integration architecture challenges, successful shipbuilding project management requires optimizing collaboration processes. Due to the desire to reduce project durations and the involvement of subcontractors or affiliated companies with remote offices, concurrent design processes across design teams, disciplines, stages, and physical locations are becoming more common. This requires robust design data control and management and process management tools.

Several research initiatives exploring these areas from different perspectives, however, often focusing on a single project or single shipyard situation and omitting the underlying general model discussion.

Applying Lean principles to shipbuilding production is one strategy for addressing these obstacles. In their study, *Song and Zhou (2022)* proposed a Lean-based manufacturing process for shipbuilding that prioritizes eliminating waste and optimizing workflows. The study found that applying Lean principles to shipbuilding projects can increase efficiency and decrease lead times.

Using a similar strategy, *Ahn and Kim (2022)* proposed a method for aligning mega block production and scheduling dock equipment use. They demonstrated that applying Lean principles to production schedules can significantly boost productivity and decrease project lead times.

In addition, offshore shipbuilding production requiring robust design data control was explored. *Semini et al. (2022)* examined the difficulties of managing design data in offshore production shipbuilding projects. The research proposed a framework for managing design data consisting of data exchange protocols, security measures, and validation procedures.

Focusing on manufacturing strategy is essential, but the design process, including innovation and decision-making aspects, also requires digital support and must be considered. *Garcia Agis (2020)* discussed incorporating digital tools into the shipbuilding design process to facilitate creativity and decision-making. This includes utilizing virtual reality, simulation, and digital prototyping tools to enhance collaboration and decision-making.

Lastly, it is essential to consider shipyard business management in the context of the overall shipbuilding management discussion. Bruce presented the significance of aligning shipyard management with business strategy for long-term success in his book from 2021. It includes integrating shipbuilding projects with business objectives, establishing a clear governance structure, and fostering a continuous improvement culture.

6. Lifecycle approach and disconnected shipbuilding stakeholders

The life cycle approach in shipbuilding is a comprehensive and systematic method for managing a ship's entire lifecycle, from its initial design to its eventual disposal. This approach ensures that each phase of the ship's lifecycle, including design, construction, operation, maintenance, and disposal, is effectively managed.

The life cycle approach is founded on total life cycle management, an integrated strategy for managing all phases of a product's life cycle. For shipbuilding, this strategy requires a coordinated effort from all project stakeholders, including ship designers, shipbuilders, ship owners, and regulatory authorities, and as of today remains somewhat a theoretical concept.

The life cycle approach begins with the ship's design phase, during which ship designers create a functional and later detailed ship model. This model is used to simulate the ship's performance under various conditions. Environmental and safety regulations, the ship's intended use, and operational requirements are also considered during the design phase. During the construction phase, the ship is built according to the design. At this phase, quality control and safety measures are implemented to ensure the ship is built according to the specifications of the design. Following construction, the ship

enters its operational phase, during which it is put into service and used for its intended purpose. During this phase, the performance and maintenance of the ship are monitored to ensure its continued safe and efficient operation. Regular inspections and repairs are performed during maintenance to ensure that the ship remains in good condition and continues to operate effectively. This phase also involves replacing components and systems that have outlived their usefulness. The disposal phase concludes with the ship's safe and environmentally responsible decommissioning and disposal. This phase entails the removal of hazardous materials and the proper disposal of all waste.

In shipbuilding, the life cycle approach is dreamed of as a comprehensive and systematic method for managing the entire lifecycle of a ship. This approach ensures that each phase of the ship's lifecycle is effectively managed, from its initial design to its eventual disposal, by coordinating the efforts of all project stakeholders.

Changing stakeholders throughout the life cycle is a glaring complication of this strategy. If the first phase focuses primarily on the functional design of the vessel, the second phase focuses on the detailed design and construction of the vessel, and the third phase is entirely independent of shipyard operations. At this stage, the shipowner can benefit from using the vessel's digital assets or digital twin, but this is infrequently the case.

Another preventing factor is the project's relatively short lead time, in contrast to other industries such as automotive and aerospace, which precludes extensive variants research. If the design of a car prototype can take several years, but millions of cars will be produced afterward, then for shipbuilding, there will be one unique vessel built to order and, at most, several modified sistership projects.

All of the factors mentioned above make using PLM in shipbuilding controversial. Although life cycle stages are implicit, the changing of stakeholders and the low-profit margins of shipyards prevent the concept from being used effectively.

7. Integrated management of shipbuilding data

Integrated shipbuilding data management refers to the efficient collection, storage, processing, and analysis of shipbuilding project data throughout the entire life cycle of a vessel (or the process of building a vessel). The shipbuilding industry has acknowledged the significance of digital transformation, and research on integrated data management platforms and systems has expanded in recent years.

Lee (2020) discusses the development of an integrated information system for the management of shipbuilding processes. The system was created to increase productivity by integrating the design, engineering, and production processes. The author also emphasizes the significance of a standard data format to facilitate the effective exchange of information among the various departments and stakeholders involved in the shipbuilding process.

Zhang et al. (2021) examine data-driven intelligent decision-making techniques within the shipbuilding industry. The authors analyze the use of big data, machine learning, and other data analytics techniques to improve shipbuilding decision-making. They also highlight the significance of data quality and integration for effective decision-making.

Choi et al. (2021) propose a design for a shipbuilding integrated data management platform. The authors argue that the platform should be able to collect, process, store, and share data from multiple sources in real-time to improve decision-making and the overall shipbuilding process.

Kim et al. (2022) present a digital twin-based integrated shipbuilding process management system. The digital twin is a virtual model of a physical system that enables real-time monitoring and analysis of data. The authors argue that incorporating the concept of the digital twin into shipbuilding can increase efficiency, reduce costs, and improve the final product's quality.

In conclusion, the shipbuilding industry can benefit substantially from integrated data management platforms and systems that facilitate the efficient collection, processing, storage, and data analysis throughout a vessel's entire life cycle. Integrating digital twin concepts, big data analytics, and machine learning can improve decision-making and overall efficiency.

8. Conclusions

The proposed shipbuilding process layers outline the opportunities for shipbuilders to gain a competitive advantage and benefit from digital transformation. The paper has highlighted three layers that are essential for effective shipbuilding: intent-driven design, data management, and process management. In addition, intent-driven design is crucial for managing the complexity of designing and fabricating vessel parts. Managing ship design, engineering, production, and maintenance data simultaneously relies heavily on data management. A centralized data management system can guarantee data consistency and accuracy, manage large amounts of data, and facilitate team collaboration. In conclusion, a holistic approach is required to improve the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the shipbuilding process when managing data and processes.

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Collaborative Single Model Design Platform for Ships of Tomorrow

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Abstract

The need for collaboration is intensifying as shipyards must innovate at speed to deliver the next generation of greener, smarter, and safer vessels. To make this happen in practice, naval architects, sub-contractors, ship owners, classification societies, technology innovators and other stakeholders need the right tools to communicate seamlessly and study creative solutions effectively, while protecting their own intellectual property. This paper presents how a single NAPA product model, a best-of-breed, commonly used collaborative design platform, supports these challenging demands.

1. Introduction

The process of designing and building a ship is undergoing a substantial change due to the ongoing digital transformation. Meanwhile, decarbonisation initiatives are introducing different kinds of design challenges in the form of new concepts to develop and trial, often together with multiple stakeholders. We argue that these challenges can be turned into lucrative opportunities with proper digital tools that support collaborative design between different entities.

Decades ago, the process of ship design shifted from paper, ink and a strong visual mind into digital tools, first transitioning to 2D CAD and eventually evolving into 3D modelling. While the in-house processes of individual players in our industry utilize these tools to their fullest extent, the same cannot be said for the process of information exchange between stakeholders. For example, 2D drawings are still relied upon when a shipyard communicates with classification societies or the future owners of the vessel. This type of information exchange is well established, but it creates silos in the shipyard's design process, leading to inefficient feedback loops and redundant work during information handovers, and hindering further innovation. Also, something more effective is needed as design complexity grows and decisions need to be made among stakeholders on completely new technologies.

In this time of increased design complexity and a demand to overhaul standard ship designs for a greener tomorrow, it is crucial to enable seamless communication between naval architects, sub-contractors, classification societies, technology innovators and other stakeholders involved in the process of ship design. This paper presents how a single NAPA product model, a best-of-breed commonly used collaborative design platform, supports these challenging demands, with practical cases that include:

- Streamlining feedback loops to improve critical decision-making in the early design phase,
- 3D model-based approval process including information sharing among all stakeholders to realize productivity improvements.

2. Challenges in the ship design collaboration

2.1. Obstacles to open collaboration in ship design

If efforts to deliver results through increased collaboration among maritime stakeholders are to succeed, it requires a careful evaluation of the barriers in way of such progress. After all, the industry would undoubtedly enjoy significant overall productivity gains in the hypothetical scenario that all design work, ship models, design algorithms and design processes would be openly accessible to all stakeholders, but there are of course valid reasons why this is not the case in our industry.

In a previous contribution to COMPIT, *Gaspar (2022)* listed three main fears and obstacles for openness in the ship design community: fear of copying intellectual property, fear of sharing valuable data and the fear of others acknowledging non-rational design choices. Overcoming these barriers completely would require a paradigm shift in the way the maritime industry operates, which is unlikely in the short-term. However, we believe that the right direction forward is to develop and promote tools that allow increased collaboration in the maritime industry, while acknowledging and addressing these fears when necessary.

2.2. Initiatives for open collaboration in ship design

Some of the initiatives for open collaboration in ship design are summarized in Table I. Various projects to promote joint industry collaboration are underway to address the increasing complexity of ship design. Many of these initiatives aim to benefit the whole maritime industry through innovation in simulation technology and platform developments, as well as the creation of an ecosystem through standardization.

One of the common indications of these initiatives is a "best-of-breed" direction with the idea to combine and apply best-in-class solutions in specific domains instead of solving all challenges with a single tool. This is a natural direction considering the increasing complexity and diversity of the challenges at hand, which require deeper specialization in each domain to solve multiple complex issues.

The remaining key issues seem to include "adaptation to conventional practices (technology dissemination)" and "Intellectual Property (IP) protection". One of the key issues is "adaptation to conventional practices (technology dissemination)" meaning how to adapt the technologies and methodologies developed in these projects to the firmly established practices of each company and industry. Especially when a significant revolution is required, a transition scenario that benefits all stakeholders and that can be implemented with minimum difficulties and efforts would be necessary. The other issue of "IP protection" has been well-known for some time. It would be essential to continuously develop security measures for data sharing and methods that ensure IP protection. As an example of these two issues, *Bitomsky et al. (2022)* indicated at the previous COMPIT the difficulty in getting shipbuilders to embrace the idea of handing over a digital model of their vessels.

Table I: Some examples of initiatives for open collaboration in ship design

Initiative	Outline	Category
OCX Consortium (https://3docx.org/)	A consortium aiming for 3D Model-Based Approval (3DMBA). Develops standardization of ship design data and data exchange technologies named the Open Class 3D Exchange (OCX).	Data exchange and sharing
OSP Project (https://opensimulationplatform.com/)	A joint industry project led by DNV. Aims to promote the Functional Mockup Interface (FMI) standard in the maritime industry and establish an ecosystem for model-based co-simulation.	Simulation and optimization
HOLISHIP Project (http://www.holiship.eu/)	An EU research and development project. Aims to build new design optimization methods by combining various design disciplines and specialized software.	Simulation and optimization
MODE Project (https://mode.k.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/)	A Japanese project aiming to develop and practicalize new design methods such as Model-based Systems Engineering (MBSE) to replace existing ones.	Simulation and optimization

2.3. Requirements for collaborative design tools

What are the essential and required features for implementing collaborative design processes for the ships of tomorrow? The following are some observations based on years of collaboration with customers, with reference to the information in the previous chapters.

- 1) Helps solve obstacles to collaborative design
 - Resolve fear of openness and IP issues (Protect IP when sharing design information)
 - Eliminate silos in the design process caused by conventional design practices e.g., drawings as “true” source of information

- 2) Contribute to "better" design (i.e. benefiting shipyards and shipowners)
 - Obtain crucial information for decision-making earlier in the design process → better decision-making, optimal design
 - Help solve various challenges that are included throughout the design process, such as shortening design lead times
- 3) Make collaboration easier
 - Connect and integrate tools and information to avoid duplicate inputs
 - Facilitate collaboration with remote participants, as well as with other departments and external stakeholders

3. NAPA - Collaborative Single Model design platform

3.1. Collaborative Single Model design platform

3.1.1. Best-of-breed approach

It has long been a dream of shipbuilders to have one common, comprehensive total solution to handle all design disciplines and phases. However, this always involves lots of compromises - thus, it is far from reality. Therefore, instead of trying to apply one total system to all design needs, a "best-of-breed" approach has been proposed by *Kuutti et al. (2011)* to apply the best tool to meet practical needs at each design stage. As noted in 2.2, various initiatives also indicate that the best-of-breed trend will continue in the future.

NAPA is a rather flexible, versatile, and open system that has been developed for over 40 years with a focus on the upstream design process. NAPA is by far the fastest and superior user experience (UX) tool for 3D model-based design, technical analysis such as stability and naval architectural calculations, various drawings and documentation, information sharing, and others. Today, NAPA is the most efficient ship design software for upstream design and has become the de facto standard in ship design, classification, and operational safety. However, NAPA does not support all design disciplines. NAPA does not offer dedicated tools for outfitting and production design, for example. In addition, deeper specialization, such as more advanced simulation, would be required to meet increasingly complex industrial issues and diversify user needs. We at NAPA believe that it is preferable to collaborate and integrate closely with other state-of-the-art systems, rather than developing everything by ourselves. Fig.1 shows NAPA's best-of-breed approach.

Thus, we believe that users should have the freedom to choose the tools best suited to their needs for each discipline and phase, with seamless integration. This will help customers build an optimal design process, which will eventually overcome the inertia of conventional practice. Therefore, we are willing to cooperate with all software vendors in the maritime business. In fact, we are cooperating with various innovative integration partners, including class societies, 3DCAD/CAE/PLM software vendors, and so on. Some of the outcomes of the partnership are delivered to our end users and can be found in some references such as Prostep case; *Bitomsky et al. (2022; ICCAS)*, Hexagon case; *Polini et al. (2015)*, CADMATIC case (<https://www.intelligentshipdesign.com/>).

3.1.2. "Single Model" as a collaborative design platform

A key to establishing an optimal design process, along with best-of-breed, is to share centralized design information throughout the project. This is often referred to as the "Single Source of Truth (SSOT)," but the reality is not that simple. It is meaningless if the centralized design information can't be utilized well enough for their design work and to resolve relevant issues.

This paper refers to a collaborative design platform as a "Single Model", Fig.2, that can utilize integrated and centralized information in a more practical way. The characteristics of the Single Model are described as follows.

- 1) Central hub for information
 - Consistent 3D-based product information shared throughout the design process
 - Combining the characteristics of “Speed”, “Flexibility”, “Connectivity”, and “Versatility”
- 2) Speed (Efficiency)
 - Single input data for multiple purposes
 - 3D design toolsets to quick and intuitively sketch and test design
 - Automation of any task for faster throughput using scripting or other technologies
- 3) Flexibility
 - Swift design changes and their management by topological and parametric 3D model
 - High-value 3D model that can be flexibly enhanced from initial design to detailed design
 - Creating user’s preferred way of working with flexible customization
- 4) Connectivity (Collaboration)
 - Seamless integration with external specialized or enterprise tools using direct Application Programming Interface (API)-based connections, reducing reliance on intermediate files
 - Sharing accurate and up-to-date design information with all stakeholders
 - Smooth design collaboration with multiple remote sites
- 5) Versatility (Usability)
 - CAD features e.g. geometry and arrangement design, drawings, numerical outputs, etc.
 - Engineering tools for hydrodynamics, stability, load planning, structure, and rule compliance
 - Adaptable UX for design needs, intuitive and easy-to-learn

These are essential characteristics to pursue optimal design solutions by collaborating efficiently and improving design accuracy within limited project time frames. Such a Single Model supports successful implementation for complicated projects by sharing centralized and visualized design information efficiently helping find problems earlier and better manage design changes. The Single Model of NAPA, with its strengths in upstream design, has the characteristics described above.

Best-of-Breed Approach

Single Model as a backbone and central hub for design process

Fig.1: NAPA’s best-of-breed approach

Fig.2: Single Model concept

3.2. Main features for collaborative design

3.2.1. 3D data interface

NAPA is equipped with a robust 3D data interface that facilitates the transfer of data between different systems. This interface utilizes two distinct data transfer methods, namely the file-based and API-based approaches. The file-based approach involves the reading or writing of 3D data in a pre-defined file format that is widely adopted across the industry. On the other hand, the API-based approach enables external parties to access 3D data or operations in NAPA within a permitted scope, thereby enhancing accuracy, reducing data transfer loss, and providing greater flexibility compared to the file-based interface. This API-based interface offers a more advanced and efficient data transfer option, ensuring the seamless exchange of 3D data between different systems.

NAPA offers multiple methods through its objective interface, which includes rule scantling on classification societies' tools, direct strength assessment in finite element analysis solutions, design approval, and detailed and production design. This objective interface facilitates a diverse range of capabilities for users to interact with NAPA, providing the flexibility required to address complex engineering design challenges. The rule scantling approach utilizes classification societies' tools to ensure that vessel designs conform to the required rules. The direct strength assessment method, which is integrated with finite element analysis solutions, enables users to assess structural strength and optimize design accordingly. The design approval feature allows for review and approval of design proposals of 3D model fetched from NAPA with the necessary data regarding to 3DMBA by OCX, while the interface to the detailed and production design option enables users to create comprehensive and accurate designs efficiently by reusing the existing 3D model from NAPA. Overall, NAPA's objective interface empowers users to effectively address a wide range of design requirements and produce high-quality designs.

The data interfaces provided by NAPA are not standalone features, but rather connected in a closed and iterative manner through the use of a Single Model. As ship designs mature, these interfaces interact with each other in a seamless and continuous manner. For instance, during the early design stages, the midship structure is designed, and relevant longitudinal cross-section data and ship data are either fetched to the specific file that can be imported to the rule calculation tools or directly accessed using the API of the rule-engines. The results of rule scantling can then be transferred back to NAPA to ensure the structure meets the required rules. Subsequently, the design scope extends to other cargo hold areas with updated scantling, and these cargo holds are transformed into Finite Element Method (FEM) models in NAPA Designer FEM to be transferred to the FEM analysis solutions. The structure reinforcement and design changes are executed within the Single Model, with the iterative FEM process continuing through the FEM data interface. The final FEM model can be imported back to NAPA to reflect all changes in scantling. This FEM analysis workflow progresses from global to local strength analysis, including fatigue and buckling assessments. Overall, NAPA's integrated approach enables efficient and accurate design optimization, resulting in high-quality ship designs that could be the baseline model for the detail and production design processes in downstream CAD systems, and NAPA provides 3D data interfaces to AVEVA Marine, Hexagon Smart3D and CADMATIC.

During the project, the 3D geometry of structures and compartments, along with their key properties and hierarchical arrangements, can be easily exported from NAPA's graphic workspace to well-known CAD formats like IGES, Step, JT, and more. This ensures a smooth and efficient workflow for any other uses. Additionally, the data can be published to HTML or 3DPDF formats, which can be opened without any specific software requirements. Whether it's a modern internet web browser or a PDF document viewer, the data can be easily accessed, utilized, and archived. Detailed explanations on all the features mentioned above can be found in *Son et al. (2022)*.

3.2.2. Collaborative design tools

For ensuring an efficient flow of information between the stakeholders involved in the ship design process, a platform for collaborative design is essential. Within the last couple of years this has become one of the key areas for development and strengths of the solutions offered by NAPA. To support concurrent design, multiple designers, sometimes working in different geographical locations, need to have access and ability to edit the model simultaneously. This is enabled by the ServerDB solution of NAPA where the master model is located on the master server and each user has a local server model which is constantly synced with the master model. With the help of the assignment functionality, users can edit only the objects belonging to the part of the structural arrangement assigned to them and thus prevent accidental or non-intended changes of the model and avoid conflicts. It also offers the possibility to see who is currently working with a specific part of the model. While the ServerDB allows simultaneous design work there might also be situations when the model should only be reviewed in the design tool without the possibility to change the design. For this purpose, it is possible to open access to the model in read-only mode preventing any changes from being written to the database.

Often there is also a need to share the design information to stakeholders who do not have access to the primary design model in the design software. In the previous chapter the possibilities for exporting the model in various cad formats or published in HTML or 3DPDF formats were presented. Furthermore, for more flexible and comprehensive access to the design information NAPA also provides a web-based viewer solution. In NAPA Viewer solution the model is uploaded to the NAPA Viewer server and securely accessible through commonly used web browsers by any client user with authorized access, ensuring secure authentication and access right management. In NAPA Viewer the 3D model with all its details and attribute data can be reviewed while protecting the intellectual property rights, as the exact geometry cannot be extracted. It is also possible to generate instant sections of the 3D model with annotations showing the detailed design information similarly as traditional 2D drawings. Additional design information available in the 3D model in table format is also accessible in NAPA Viewer. Moreover, comments linked to specific parts in the model can be given in the web application and these are directly visible by other client users of NAPA Viewer as well as designers working with the design tools. The commenting functionality supports the needs for comment exchange within the design organization well, but it is also seen as an important tool for enabling 3DMBA. Comments on the design provided by the classification society could be mapped to objects in the model and made accessible to the designers using the commenting functionality. NAPA is currently developing this approach jointly with DNV and BV meaning in practice that the comments on the design given by the approval engineer and linked with the specific part in the 3D OCX file originating from the NAPA model will be made directly accessible in the design environment.

The key features and tools essential for collaborative design, facilitated by NAPA, are summarized in Fig.3.

Fig.3: NAPA offering for collaborative design

4. Example use cases of collaborative Single Model design platforms

NAPA has had a rather high market share in early design for more than decades as a common design tool, and its performance has been proven in numerous real design cases. And it continues to evolve further together with its customers and partners to meet the new challenges and needs of today's increasingly complex world. This chapter introduces practical example use cases that attempt to manage these challenging requirements using the Single Model, a collaborative design platform whose features were described in the previous chapter.

- 1) Streamlining feedback loops to improve critical decision-making in the early design phase
- 2) 3DMBA process including information sharing among all stakeholders to realize productivity improvements.

Fig.4: Example use cases introduced in this paper

4.1. Streamlining feedback loops in the early design phase

4.1.1 Challenge

In the early design phase, which includes the development of new design concepts and the basic design process around contracts, it is necessary to study a variety of design options targeting improved energy efficiency, weight reduction, improved payload capacity etc. to achieve a competitive design within a limited design time frame. The process is very complicated because of frequent hull form modifications, compartment arrangement changes etc. Furthermore, when it comes to innovative designs such as vessels applying new fuels, many uncertainties make it more challenging to make decisions with confidence.

If the design progresses with ambiguous specifications, problems may be found at a later stage, leading to rework and project delays. In the worst case, problems may be discovered only at the construction or ship operation phase, resulting in significant financial and reputational losses.

4.1.2 Solution – Concurrent collaborative design powered by Single Model

Improving work efficiency is a fundamental part of the solution to this challenge. By reducing the time required to create design proposals and obtain evaluation results, more time is available to refine the design.

The traditional serial (waterfall) design process, in which structure and outfitting design follow hull form and compartment arrangement, is straightforward but not optimized, and the process tends to become lengthy. The impact of early decisions is significant, and if problems are discovered in the later processes, such as the failure of a compartment arrangement, extensive reworks will occur.

One approach to improve work efficiency is a concurrent design process that streamlines communication between designers in charge of different design disciplines. This could be effective in achieving a holistically optimized, highly competitive ship design.

In this concurrent approach, in practice, designers in each discipline rarely work together to tackle the same design topic at the same time. The team consists of for example, project engineers who are responsible for the general arrangement, ship specifications, and loading and stability calculations; hull form designers who study the optimal hull form using CFD, etc.; machinery (outfitting) design engineers who study the functional requirements and arrangement of equipment and systems that have a large impact on energy consumption and cost, such as main engines; and structure engineers who estimate the hull weight and study the optimal structural arrangement using strength calculation tools, etc. Each designer pursues the best design options to achieve their own task, taking into account the influence of the results of other disciplines' studies. Because the time required for each study task

varies, the timelines for each design discipline are also different. In other words, each designer is basically working independently, but at the same time, they are collaborating indirectly in order to achieve the high-level mission of total optimization. To realize such a design process, a smarter 3D design tool with high UX and flexibility allowing drastic design changes is indispensable. Moreover, it is crucial to streamline the tasks and communication process so that designers in each design discipline can work concurrently.

The Single Model enables team members consisting of project engineers, hull form designers, machinery (outfitting) designers and structural engineers to systematically communicate design progress and required changes on the same design platform.

The designers in each discipline have ownership of their own design information and proceed with their own discipline's design studies concurrently. However, when changes are made based on design study results or feedback, the master (parent) NAPA model is updated. Here, the hull form, compartment, and structural model can share a topological reference relationship, so that even if the hull form or compartment arrangement is changed, the structural members can automatically adapt to the changes. This feature of automatically updating the 3D model is particularly effective in the early design phase, where design changes are dynamically and repeatedly made. *Yamatoki et al. (2020)* introduced such concurrent design processes' effectiveness in their work in Namura Shipbuilding, Fig.5.

Fig.5: Concurrent design process in Namura Shipbuilding, <https://www.napa.fi/case/napa-at-namura-shipbuilding/>

Outfitting engineers can then import 3D CAD components such as equipment, devices, and major pipes that they have prepared in an external CAD software, and study the arrangement of these components to complete a Single Model that includes all design elements. They can visually check the interference between the structural members and equipment with compartments. With NAPA Viewer, the up-to-date NAPA 3D model consisting of all design disciplines can be shared with all stakeholders (including shipowners and production departments) through a web browser without additional software. The designers can seek and get feedback in real time. By sharing concrete information visualized in 3D from the early stages of a project, it will be possible to clarify areas that are difficult to evaluate using only specifications and schematic drawings. For example, it will be possible to visually simulate maintainability, accessibility, ship/shore interface, construction methodology, and so on. In addition, stakeholders would have more meaningful communications and would be able to proactively and positively address the important issues found. In this way, the Single Model enables real-time collaboration among different design disciplines and other stakeholders, driving positive collaboration to improve the overall design experience for all stakeholders, Fig.6.

Fig.6: NAPA model shared with different disciplines

- Automation of holistic design assessment and shortening critical path of design work

It is possible to further accelerate the design process by automating the own design philosophies using the Single Model. Following are two advanced example cases that were developed collaboratively between NAPA and its users.

C-Job and NAPA case, Fig.7: *Winter et al. (2019)* implemented a way to automate and optimize the concept design process using genetic algorithms. It enabled streamlining the concept design process and give ship owners more confidence in the final design while understanding the trade-offs in selecting design goals.

Fig.7: C-Job & NAPA case

Sumitomo Heavy Industries Marine & Engineering (SHI-ME) and NAPA case, Fig.8: *Amano et al. (2022)* implemented a solution to streamline the structural strength evaluation process for tankers, which is known as a critical path, and have succeeded in shortening the lead time to 1/100. This is being utilized to enhance the weight estimation accuracy and search for the optimal design in the early design phase.

Fig.8: SHI-ME & NAPA case

4.1.3 Benefits of concurrent collaborative design

"Streamlining the feedback loop" in this example case is a means of obtaining reliable information for better decision-making in a timely manner at an earlier stage with a high degree of accuracy through a concurrent collaboration. Such reliable information can be obtained as the result of calculations and simulations from the designers in each design discipline, or as advice and feedback from various domain experts (including shipowners and production teams). Time is limited in the early design stage, so it is crucial to carefully consider the resolution of the designs to be assessed (the more detailed the design, the more accurate information can be obtained). In our opinion, one answer is a state that allows reducing uncertainty i.e., a state where important design margins can be managed (minimized) to make better decisions. The benefits of concurrent collaborative design are summarized in Fig.9.

Fig.9: Benefits of concurrent concurrent collaborative design

4.2. Effective 3D model-based approval process

4.2.1 Challenge

As 3D CAD software improves, 3D design, in which the design is done directly on a 3D model, is becoming more common. However, plan approval for new shipbuilding projects is still conducted using traditional 2D drawings. Because 2D drawings are considered the final "true" (or "official") design information, the use of 3D models in the design phase is often limited, reducing the motivation to maintain the 3D models to the latest correct state and take them over to the downstream processes. 2D drawing-based plan approval causes silos in the design process and hinders innovation. In addition, the traditional approval process seems inefficient for ship owners, because the 2D drawings for each design zone and discipline are created at different times. That makes it difficult to evaluate whether the design is good or bad. Instead, the ship owner would like to see the whole design together by imagining the completed vessel.

To solve this problem, initiatives led by classification societies for 3DMBA, in which a 3D model created at the time of design is used for classification approval, have been conducted in recent years. However, as shown in Table II below, there are various issues to be addressed. It has been pointed out that forcing through 3DMBA without resolving these issues may result in negative outcomes, and it may create additional work rather than streamlining the process.

Table II: Challenges for achieving 3DMBA

Interoperability and consistency	Convenience for design review	Communication of design information to stakeholder	IP protection
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data compatibility with various engineering tools such as classification software and structural analysis software • Poor quality of data conversion results in extra man-hours • Risk of inconsistency due to separate management of models for strength assessment and 3D CAD model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2D drawings have well-organized design information for specific purposes and facilitate easy review of the necessary information. But difficult to make a holistic assessment. • 3D models are easy to grasp holistically and spatially. But access to necessary information such as attributes is not easy and time-consuming. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional approval drawings are used to transmit information to ship owner approval, outfitting, manufacturing, detailed design, and other related departments, in addition to classification approval. • Alternative methods to 2D drawings are required. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D models hold a high degree of IP, so shipbuilders and design firms are reluctant to share them. • A lot of companies are not willing to accept providing 3D models unless the recipient is reliable to avoid the risk of design data leakage.

4.2.2 Solution - Efficient and pragmatic 3DMBA process powered by Single Model

The 3DMBA is a topic only a 3D CAD system used in upstream design can facilitate. NAPA, with its strengths in the upstream design field, has been working closely with shipyards, classification societies, software vendors, and other relevant stakeholders, including shipowners, around the world to solve the challenges listed above and continue to develop software and collaborative research and development to promote a practical 3D approval process.

a) Interoperability and Consistency

NAPA has worked closely with all major classification societies to establish data linkages based on intermediate files, including OCX format. However, user feedback has identified room for improvement, such as:

- Complex operations needed to interface 3D CAD software and classification society's engineering software
- Manual touch-up is necessary due to missing data, etc.
- Time-consuming to manually update scantlings of structures determined in classification software back to the 3D model

In a real design environment, design changes occur repeatedly, requiring manual touch-ups. Therefore, the designer tends to be discouraged from updating the 3D CAD model and only updates the calculation model of the classification software. As a result, the 3D CAD model becomes left behind, causing inconsistencies with the calculation model of the classification software.

To solve this issue, some attempts had been made by ClassNK, *Sakagami et al. (2022)*, shown in Fig.10 and Korean Register, *Kim et al. (2022)*, respectively. Their approach is to integrate NAPA 3D model including FEM models directly and seamlessly with the classification software (prescriptive rule and direct strength calculations) by utilizing NAPA's API technology. The efficiency gain was verified by an end user in the ClassNK case.

Thus, the consistency of design information is ensured, and a framework for keeping the 3D models up-to-date and using them as a primary source of information could be established. Designers found it beneficial that calculations can now be performed as soon as the 3D model is created. By integrating the design work and engineering work, designers were able to save significant time and pursue more rational structures in the limited time available.

Fig.10: Enhanced interoperability between 3D CAD and classification software (ClassNK case)

b) Convenience for design review

3D and 2D have advantages and disadvantages in terms of reviewing design information, Table II. NAPA Viewer, a web application introduced in the previous chapter, not only displays the up-to-date NAPA model in 3D but also displays 2D cross sections and automatically presents attributes such as scantling in a familiar drawing-like format to help efficient design review.

It is also possible to superimpose a 3D model on a drawing-like 2D cross-section view, Fig.11 (left). This is expected to be a new style of "3D drawing" that combines the advantages of a 3D model and conventional 2D drawings.

Furthermore, NAPA Viewer can display comprehensive 3D information including the hull structures, compartments, and outfitting components, which would be beneficial to ship owners who may want to review the design in a holistic way, Fig.11 (right).

Fig.11: Display that combines the advantages of 2D drawings and 3D models (left) and holistic display of outfitting, hull structure, and compartments (right)

c) Communication of design information to stakeholders

In addition to classification approval, traditional approval drawings are also used for shipowner approval and for the purpose of communicating information to downstream processes and other disciplines. NAPA Viewer serves to communicate design information to these stakeholders as visual information in a simple way. It can be easily accessed from any web browser, and shipbuilders, who are the owners of the 3D models, do not need to use different tools for sharing information according to classifications and shipowners. This enables the sharing of common, up-to-date central design information, i.e., the Single Model, throughout the project.

The commenting feature in NAPA Viewer offers an alternative to communicating comments via e-mails or drawings. The comment data from different stakeholders and their status can be linked and managed with NAPA's Single Model i.e., the central design information, Fig.12. Validation of its usefulness requires future work.

Fig.12: Commenting tool in NAPA Viewer

However, traditional approval drawings are used not only to visualize and communicate design information but the drawing data itself is often used as a basis for designing more details in the downstream processes.

As an alternative to the role of drawings as a design basis, NAPA offers a wide variety of 3D data exchange functions that can be applied to different tools used in downstream processes (outfitting, detailed/production design). For shipbuilding 3D CAD systems, we offer specialized advanced integration features based on NAPA API that enable converting to each native 3D CAD model including its topology. OCX data import/export and multiple generic 3D CAD data exchange functions such as STEP, JT, and IGES can be utilized with various general 3D tools. Fig. 13 presents two example cases of 3D data interfaces.

Fig.13: 3D data interface examples; CATIA V5 (left), AVEVA Marine (right)

- Proposal for a pragmatic path to achieve 3DMBA

In fact, the majority of shipyards say that they want to share information on 2D drawings or are forced to continue 2D drawings for the time being. This is because it is necessary to establish a comprehensive system to manage design information in 3D format only, and such a system does not yet fully exist.. This requires not only the relevant departments in the shipyard, but also the classification societies, shipowners, and all other stakeholders who need the design information to build the system, as it may take a long time to achieve this full 3D process.

This is where NAPA Drafting, a drawing creation tool that can generate 2D cross sections from NAPA's Single Model and semi-automatically add annotations, can be helpful. Information that can be automatically obtained and displayed using NAPA Viewer would be omitted from the 2D drawings, minimizing the effort expended in creating the drawings and the role and necessity of the drawings themselves. This is the way we propose a gradual and effortless transition to a 3D-based approval and information-sharing system. In other words, only the minimum number of drawings is generated at the end of the design process as a supplement to the 3D model information.

Fig.3 encompasses several features that NAPA supports for 3DMBA.

- Potential of the Single Model as a central hub for information

As mentioned earlier, the Single Model can include hull form, compartments, structural models, FEM models, and outfitting components imported from external sources. It also includes loading condition-related information used for stability assessment etc. in a calculation-ready format. It is not too early to discuss the use of the models for subsequent processes i.e. Digital Twin.

d) IP Protection

Most shipbuilders remain very cautious about sharing 3D model data, which includes high-level IP, with external stakeholders. On the contrary, sharing design information via NAPA Viewer can be an

acceptable solution for shipbuilders even with strict security policies, since it shares only graphical information via a web browser.

Furthermore, the situation is expected to change gradually in the future, envisioning that 3D models created in the design phase will be used as a Digital Twin to create new value and generate new businesses even after the delivery of the vessels. Cloud technology and more advanced security measures will gradually mitigate concerns about information security. In addition, the development of contractual schemes that clarify the handling of rights and rewards for sharing/using 3D models will gradually settle the issue of IP protection and encourage the use of digital twins.

4.2.3 Summary of status quo around 3DMBA

The above discussion shows that despite the various challenges to effectively implementing a 3DMBA process, specific solutions have been proposed to cope with them. Tools like smart 3D reviewing tools and automated drawing generation tools, which take full advantage of the Single Model, are expected to help the gradual transition from traditional 2D drawing-dependent communication and approval processes to 3D model-based processes. In addition, the development of security measures and contract schemes would help resolve the issue of IP protection.

In the future, it is important to conduct 3DMBA process in various cases based on this proposal together with different partners, and verify its effectiveness and issues. Through these collaborative efforts, a more efficient and effective 3DMBA will become a reality. This 3DMBA will lead to smarter and more productive ship design and further utilization of 3D models as a Digital Twin.

5. Conclusion

Despite the growing expectations about design innovation through collaboration, there are difficult issues to be addressed, such as IP issues and adaptations to conventional practices. The important thing is that shipyards, shipowners, and other stakeholders will benefit through solving these issues, such as better and more efficient ship design. This paper introduced the concept of the Single Model, a collaborative design platform that supports better ship design by facilitating collaboration and solving these challenges, with two example cases.

The Single Model collaborative design platform offers the following key benefits:

- **Streamlined Processes:** The entire design process is streamlined, reducing duplication of work and unnecessary rework.
- **Cost & Time Savings:** Streamlined design processes lead to cost and time savings.
- **Improved Decision-Making:** Faster and more accurate decision-making, resulting in reduced risk and optimized design.
- **Eco and Safety Outcomes:** More environmentally friendly and safer ship design, for better sustainability and maritime safety.
- **Innovative Ship Design:** Collaboration fosters new ideas and technologies, leading innovations for the ships of tomorrow.

These benefits cannot be achieved by NAPA alone, nor can they be realized in a single step. It is achieved through enhanced collaboration with various stakeholders using the Single Model, while coping with real-life challenges. These will pave the way for continuous project success and sustainable ship design.

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Designing Engineering Services Based on Digital Twins – An Arctic Navigation Case

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Abstract

In this paper we suggest a framework for developing valuable engineering system services based on digital twins. As an example we use a digital service for ice navigation based on Ulstein's experience with expeditionary Arctic cruise vessels. We start from the simple, but often ignored, necessary condition that a DT based service should provide a net positive value to key stakeholders. A further sufficient condition is that it provides the best value-to-cost. For the quantification of service value we propose the concept of a loss function, and for the service design process we adapt a systems-based engineering design process mapping from needs via functions to form elements.

1. Introduction

Digital twins (DTs) are developed for a purpose, by human designers. As such, they belong to the realm of what *Simon (1981)* called the “sciences of the artificial”. The development of DTs should be based on core principles from engineering design. Engineering design seeks to change existing situations into preferred ones by the abductive transformation of the needs and expectations of key stakeholders, via functions and physical principles, to a description of form. This form can later be realized as a product or a service. As such, the design of complex engineering artifacts and digital services are fundamentally similar. As an example we will use a digital service for operational support for ice navigation based on Ulstein's experience with expeditionary Arctic cruise vessels.

It is reasonable to assume that a necessary condition for developing a DT based service in the first place is that it provides a net positive value to key stakeholders. This implies that the aggregated benefit of the service needs to offset all cost for developing, implementing, and operating the service throughout the lifetime. While this condition may seem obvious, it seems to be the case that many current DT implementations are more motivated by “hype technology alignment”, such as “intelligent ships”, “digital threads”, “Industry 4.0” and the like, rather than a bottom-line focus on profitable investments.

Further, the engineering design process implies that we seek the best possible solution among all feasible alternatives. Hence, a sufficient condition is that the proposed service design provides the best value-to-cost trade-off possible. For this evaluation the cost can typically be estimated quite accurately, summarizing investments in sensors, infrastructure, and software, as well as operational expenditures such as data storage and transmissions. However, quantifying a meaningful value provided by a digital service is less trivial. A possible way forward is developing a loss function that seeks to quantify the (inverse) benefit of the service to key stakeholders. This loss function is on one side is bounded by having no decision support at all, and on the other side bounded by having perfect information that support full insight that results in optimal decisions. Within this interval, the loss is a consequence of both imperfect information about the external operating context (e.g. ice conditions) and by imperfect mapping of external conditions to internal functional behaviour. For our Arctic cruise case, the latter may result in value loss such as time expenditure, fuel cost, structural consumption (e.g. aggregated fatigue), and service quality cost such as noise, vibration and motions that will influence passenger comfort level.

2. Literature review

The concept of keeping an up-to-date, comprehensive digital record of the state of individual real assets can be traced back to the “live” product lifecycle models developed in the 1990s, with DNV's Nauticus

project being a prime example. This concept evolved into digital twins (DTs), a concept that was first proposed by *Grieves (2003)* almost 20 years ago as a support tool for commercial strategic technology development, expanding from the principles of product life-cycle management (PLM). Today, the digital twin has become a more mature technology platform that is expected to revolutionize the way industries operate, *Qi et al. (2021)*.

There are many definitions of digital twins. One example from *Niederer et al. (2021)* is “a set of virtual information constructs that mimics the structure, context and behaviour of an individual or unique physical asset, that is dynamically updated with data from its physical twin throughout its life-cycle, and that ultimately informs decisions that realize value”. This definition points to many of the same aspects as *Erikstad (2017)*, where identity, representation, state, behaviour, and context were identified as the core characteristics of a digital twin.

The digital twin provides an opportunity for the maritime industries in terms of providing a “bridge” towards enhanced servitization, *Agis et al. (2022)*. This implies a change from only designing, building, and delivering ships and ship equipment towards making money servicing them, *Baines et al. (2009)*. This may contribute to operational value, for instance through reduced fuel consumption and fewer emissions to air, reduced uncertainty and risk, lower operational and voyage costs (OPEX and VOYEX) and improved safety, security, reliability, and resilience.

For the service design process, we adapt a systems-based engineering design process mapping from needs via functions to form elements. Fundamental to the engineering design process is that we start with the needs, then we map those to functions that we seek to realize by form. For a service, the “form” elements are less tangible than for a physical product like a ship. While the latter can be described by, say, hull form characteristics, propulsion system type and parameters, etc., the service implementation comprise both components like sensors, storage devices, communication, as well as both internal and external information resources, like AIS data, ice imagery, MetOcean, etc.

Fig.1: Digital service design maps needs via functions to form

The needs must be anchored towards the relevant stakeholders and the value they will receive through a successful design. For our Arctic sailing case, the key stakeholders will be the vessel’s navigator who wants efficient routing, the passengers who want safety and comfort, and the shipowner who want fuel efficiency and low structural loads. For a DT-based service the functions that will serve the needs typically reflect the information required for decision support, say, ice concentration and thickness, vessel motions, vibrations and noise, and structural loads on the vessel. Form elements typically comprise sensors defined by their location, accuracy, frequency, data filtering, communication and storage, data analysis, etc., but can also include external services such as satellite imagery. Different configuration of form elements will provide different levels of functional performance resulting in both different levels of service value and corresponding cost, making this a non-trivial design task.

3. Digital service design process

Following the basic steps of engineering design as discussed in the previous section, we propose the following steps for the service design process:

1. Determining the scope of the service in terms of decision-making levels and temporal aspects
2. Capture needs of key stakeholders through a value proposition
3. Identify functions and corresponding minimum functional requirements to support those needs

4. Propose a set of alternative form elements that will provide a feasible functional performance, both on a component level and on a systems level
5. Synthesise the form elements into complete service solutions
6. Analyse each alternative solution with respect to both value (given by KPIs) and cost (TCO)

In the following each of these steps will be discussed in more detail.

3.1 Determining service scope

Erikstad (2019) proposed two dimensions that should be used to define the scope of digital services as being the decision-making level, and the temporal aspects covered. The decision-making level can be defined as either strategic, tactical or operational. The strategic level supports insights and decisions from a lifecycle perspective, such as ship design and fleet renewal. The tactical level covers the medium-term perspective, for instance routing and scheduling, or maintenance planning. The operational level is centred around the immediate situation, typically on a scale from seconds to hours. Regarding the temporal aspects, we can classify those into hindsight, insight or foresight. Using a timeline as a reference, hindsight refers to the knowledge and decision support that can be based on experience and historical timeseries. Insight corresponds to situational awareness and actions taken based on immediate feedback. Foresight can be likened to a fast-forward button, extrapolating the past and current situation into one or several scenarios for the future that, for instance, can aid the decision-maker into evaluating the likely outcome of several decision alternatives, and using methods like time series analysis and simulation.

Using the slots of the corresponding 3x3 matrix we can define both the primary, value-delivering scope of the service, as well as the secondary scope of supporting services that are needed.

Fig.2: The service scope in the 3x3 matrix

One example of scoping a service related to Arctic navigation is illustrated in Fig.3, based on *Taylor (2023)*. Here, the digital service provides state information related to the current state of crew and passenger motion sickness. This can be located in the matrix and classified as “Insight”, on an “Operational” level.

Fig.3: Operational insight on passenger motion sickness, *Taylor et al. (2023)*

Another example is based on steps from the conceptual design process at Ulstein. For Ulstein, it is important that the expeditionary cruise vessels they design for Arctic operations have excellent human comfort performance. At the design stage they can use a digital twin model to estimate, based on existing information from previous projects and general hydrodynamic models, how the vessel’s global motion behaviour translates into motions to which each individual passenger is exposed. This can be aggregated into a KPI that captures the aggregated pax seasickness susceptibility for a particular design solution. Their current solution is centred around “strategic level insight”.

Fig.4: Strategic insight: Design stage analysis of cruise pax motion sickness at Ulstein

Transferring this approach to our example, we define the scope as being navigation decision support in Arctic waters. This includes voyage planning. Here, the typical time horizon is days and thus belongs to the tactical level, and it will focus on predicting the performance along possible navigation routes, thus belonging to the “foresight” category. The example service can also be used for determining the optimal route for the immediate future considering alternative paths through the ice, thus also covering the “operational foresight” scope box. Further, the primary scope related to ice navigation will typically be supported by the other aspects of the digital twin solution. From the design stage digital twin, time series analyses of similar vessels, analysis models of structural loads and motion behaviour, and simulation models of vessel operations will typically be used. Also, both time series and situational awareness assessment based on sensors, ice imagery, etc. is needed both to identify decision alternatives, and to predict the associated performance indicators. The service scope, and associated support functions is illustrated in Fig.5.

Fig.5: The service scope for the Arctic navigation example, with associated support functions from the digital twin

3.2 Capturing needs

The starting point for any design process is understanding and articulating the needs of key stakeholders. To the extent possible, this formulation of needs should not presume any particular solution, but rather be explicit on the value to be provided by any realization of a product or service. For the Arctic expeditionary cruise case, ice navigation involves a trade-off between mission aspects such as schedules, transit times, vessel loads fuel consumption and emissions on the one hand, and the comfort and well-being of the passengers on the other hand. This can be captured in a value proposition, a (preferably one sentence) formulation of the overall needs. An example of such a value proposition for our case could be: “Given a target destination, to provide support for planning, executing and reviewing immediate and voyage level ice navigation decisions that maximizes passenger comfort while minimizing transit time, risk, emissions and cost related to structural loads and fuel”.

This one sentence statement provides a useful starting point for our design process, in terms of:

1. Implicitly identifying the key stakeholder being the vessel’s navigator (“... onboard ...”)
2. Defining the scope of a prospective service as being “planning, execution and review”
3. Stating the key objective of the service, being “ice navigation support”

4. Describing how the service will provide tangible value, such as comfort to passengers, low transit time and low fuel cost to operators, and low structural cost, such as accumulated fatigue or ultimate loads, to ship owners.

Typically, the value providing elements need to be further broken down in an objective hierarchy, preferably to a level in which we are able to describe a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) that relates measurable system output to a quantifiable measure that reflects stakeholder utility. Some of these can be purely monetary. In our case, fuel cost is one example. Also the reduction of structural loads, such as fatigue, that is achieved by good navigation decisions can ultimately be translated to a cost. For passenger comfort, KPIs such as vibration, noise and motions are measurable outputs that are impacted by the quality of the navigational decisions. The main challenge here is to translate the performance indicators on a common scale to support the trade-offs that are central to decision-making. For instance, what is the increase in noise level acceptable for a given reduction in transit time or fuel cost? One approach is to translate all these performance factors onto a common utility scale through value analysis. Another is to keep the different scales, and rather provide a set of Pareto frontier diagrams that leaves the final trade-off to the decision-maker.

To summarize, to design a service that will provide valuable decision support for ice navigation there are three main needs to be covered: First, to provide a set of navigation alternatives to the decision-maker. Second, to identify a set of measurable performance indicators that reflects the difference in overall value of these alternatives. Finally, support the choice of the most optimal alternative. These needs are then mapped to a set of functions and functional requirements.

Fig.6: The service outline in terms of needs-function-form

3.3 Key functions and functional requirements

In engineering design, ‘Konstruktionslehre’, functions capture the conversion of material, energy, and signals, *Pahl and Beitz (1984)*. From a digital service perspective, the signals are the important part, with the functions corresponding to the information and insight required to support the needs identified in the previous step. For instance, in order to provide a set of alternative routes to consider, we need information on the ice situation in the relevant area, and some way of interpreting this ice situation in terms of quantifiable features that serve as input to the KPIs that measures needs satisfaction.

Functions may typically be provided on different levels of performance. Again using the example of ice situation awareness, this may vary between low-frequent, low-resolution imagery to high-frequent, high-resolution images that allows for more reliable ice features extraction. Sometimes a certain min-

imum level is required for satisfying the stated needs. More often the definition of functional requirements is an intrinsic part of the design process itself, based on balancing the added value of better information and improved insight towards the cost of providing it. The value of side of this equation will be based on the level of needs satisfaction, which can ultimately be translated into monetary value through, for instance, reduced fuel consumption, increased profits, reduced maintenance, etc. The cost side is determined by the “form”, i.e. the implementation decision such as sensor quality, image download frequency and resolution, etc., that will be downstream decisions in the engineering design process. This implies that there needs to be iterative feedback loops and is what *Andrews (2011)* refers to as “requirements elucidation”, that proper functional requirements cannot be stated without exploring and understanding the opportunity space formed by potential design solutions.

Fig.7: Elucidating functional requirement levels by value vs. cost tradeoffs

3.4 Form – the realization of the digital twin and associated services

The final major stage of the service design process is to realize the specified functions by various form elements. Examples of such elements are listed in the “Form” column of Fig.4. As we see, this will be a mixture of sensors (e.g. strain gauges, IMUs for motions and vibrations, pax position sensors, etc.), external data services (e.g. satellite imagery, MetOcean data), DT hindsight data (e.g. ice time series), computational algorithms (e.g. ice feature extraction, structural loads calculations), and decision support tools and models (e.g. Dijkstra’s shortest path algorithm for determining “shortest” path). Some of these form elements are associated by the digital twin itself, and are shared across services, while others are implemented as part of this specific service.

	Name	Value provided by service
	Virtual sensor	Provide insight into asset behaviour on locations without sensor observations
	Context sensor	Provide insight into loads and operational context by inverse inference on asset behaviour
	Fingerprint	Understand asset operations by matching against a catalogue of behavioural patterns
	Anomaly	Early detection of faults and critical conditions by comparing observed and predicted behaviour
	Root cause	Identify root cause of observed deviations by reverse engineering physics-based simulations
	Scout	Obtain situational awareness by fast forwarding current operations using simulations and predictive statistics
	Life counter	Aggregate miniscule incremental loads to better exploit actual life capacity and avoid failures
	Mirror	Recreate complete immersive operators experience to manage remote assets

Fig.8: The “Scout” pattern to serve as a basis for the proposed digital services based on DTs, *Erikstad and Bekker (2021)*

An alternative to starting the implementation process from scratch is to base the service implementation on an existing design pattern. A set of common DT-based service patterns was proposed in *Erikstad and Bekker (2021)*, Fig.8. Of these, the Scout pattern may serve as a relevant high level starting point for the Arctic navigation service, by using predictive techniques (time series projections, forecasting, simulations) for evaluating the prospective outcome of alternative navigational decisions. Also, the other patterns may support important aspects of the implementation. For instance, a “Virtual sensor” may be used to predict noise and motions at the exact position of every passenger onboard (since an individual physical sensor would be complex and expensive). A “Context sensor” may be used to infer the ice conditions based on observed structural loads, to serve as input to continuous learning algorithms, while the “Fingerprint” pattern can reverse this process by detecting unfavourable situations by matching current behaviour against experience-based catalogues. “Life counter” can be used to aggregate observed (by strain gauges) structural loads, providing a basis for a rational trade-off between structural cost and other criteria such as time, fuel and emissions.

A more formal definition of implementation has been proposed by *Niederer et al. (2021)*, using a symbolic language to define the core elements of the solution, comprising both the real asset and its digital counterpart.

Fig.9: Symbolic language to specify DT implementations, based on *Kapteyn et al. (2021)*

An example on how this symbolic language can be used is illustrated in Fig.10, where the example service is outlined based on the “Scout” pattern.

Fig.10: Arctic navigation case based on “Scout” pattern, using symbolic DT language

The pattern illustrated in Fig.10 will unfold as follows:

1. The initial state of the asset is captured with sufficient observations to provide the “as is” condition of the asset digital state.

2. Future scenarios / inputs are presented by conditions A, B, \dots, j . The state of the digital representation is changed to reflect these scenarios (e.g., by simulation).
3. The relevant quantities of interest are extracted (e.g., transit times, structural loads, pax motions, vibrations, noise)
4. The target quantities of interest are indicated by Q_R . The scenario with a performance closest to the target outcome is the R_0 , that is, pointing to the best among alternative navigation decisions.
5. This leads to the control action U_0 that takes us to the next state, S_1 .

4. Measuring digital service value: The loss function

Providing decision support through a digital service is not a binary situation. We can imagine the value provided on a continuous scale, with the extreme points being providing no decision support at all, vs. being able to determine the globally optimal decision. Along this scale of possible DS solutions it is also reasonable to assume that we have increasing cost, i.e. we are only considering Pareto optimal solutions. Thus, it becomes a decision problem in itself to determine the “optimal”.

Fig.11: DT service value vs. cost as a function of complexity

This is illustrated in Fig.11. A rational approach is to start with the solution elements providing the highest value-to-cost ratio. This implies that, along with a more extensive, high-quality service, the marginal value contribution is diminishing, while the marginal cost is increasing. Thus, at least in theory, we have an “optimal” service level at the point where the increased value is exactly offset by the increased cost. Naturally, this service level is difficult to determine in practice.

Fig.12: Different levels of DT level complexity to support ice navigation operational insight

Focusing on our case study and considering the functions identified in Fig.4, we can consider three levels of DT service complexity – Level 1 as the lowest, and Level 3 as the highest, Fig.12.

The example provided has in parts been tested on SA Agulhas II. Some of the experiences from this testing have shed some light on the complexities of determining these service levels and their corresponding implementation in a real-world setting.

The rigid body motion that influences motion sickness can be well-estimated by knowing the vertical acceleration in the frequency range $< \sim 1$ Hz. With an IMU the motion anywhere on the vessel can be estimated using dynamics, allowing for the calculation of motions across the vessel because cabin locations are known.

Vertical ship motion (that affects the motion sickness of passengers) can be forecast with knowledge of the RAOs for pitch, heave and roll. In the case of the SA Agulhas II this is most complex to estimate roll because ballast tanks cause roll predictions to be inaccurate. This could be solved through a more detailed simulation effort in CFD with detailed modelling of appendages.

To determine the “state” of passengers, human tracking and live feedback have been tested with a local network on the ship and an app on a mobile device, *Taylor (2023)*. This introduces both ethical issues and platform independence challenges. A somewhat peculiar example of cost considerations in a DT development is how participation in “seasickness feedback” was arranged – with an incentive scheme of a free drink once a week for everyone who participated in the study.

Global vibration was estimated with knowledge of the fundamental mode shapes of the ship. The modal model is difficult to infer from measurements alone and FEM models are conventionally used to inform the scaling of the shapes in relation to the hull excitation.

These examples illustrate that there is a wide gap between the theoretical models (e.g. as given in Fig.10) and the situation in the field. Still, we believe it is useful to understand and interpret these realities towards a structured model of both the design process, as in engineering design, and the architecture of a digital twin and corresponding services.

5. Conclusions

Digital services represent an opportunity to the companies in the maritime industry to expand their service portfolio. Digital twins are an enabler to capitalize on these services.

We always need to remember that we develop DTs to provide value through better decisions and insight. DTs are basically engineering systems, man-made with a purpose, within the realm of the sciences of the artificial. Thus, DTs and corresponding digital services need to be designed, and an engineering design/systems design process, mapping from needs via functions to form is a relevant starting point.

Identifying the right threshold between effort and benefit is crucial for successful implementation of digital services. Many of the digital initiatives established in the maritime industry over the past few years have not been fruitful as they have not been successful realising the value of such services. They have focused on collecting large amount of data and pushing heavy data-related technological development, and little of the needs of the operators. Thus, the industry has realized that new developments need a better methodology foundation for their development.

The methodology here proposed for development of digital services can represent a better starting point for more effective and service-focused development and implementation of digital services in the maritime industry.

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Adaptation and Optimization of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) for the Maritime Domain in the Field of VHF Communication

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Abstract

This paper introduces a multilingual automatic speech recognizer (ASR) for maritime radio communication that automatically converts received VHF radio signals into text. The challenges of maritime radio communication are described at first, and the deep learning architecture of marFM® consisting of audio processing techniques and machine learning algorithms is presented. Subsequently, maritime radio data of interest is analyzed and then used to evaluate the transcription performance of our ASR model for various maritime radio data.

1. Introduction

Maritime communication is a critical aspect of global trade and transportation, enabling ships to communicate with one another and with shore-based facilities. VHF stands for Very High Frequency and is a commonly used radio communication technology in the maritime domain, providing reliable voice communication. VHF is a type of electromagnetic radiation used in maritime radio communications mainly in the frequency range from 156.025 MHz to 162.025 MHz, *ITU (2022)*. VHF radio is used for ship-to-ship, ship-to-shore (vice versa) and onboard communications, *Alagha and Løge (2023)*. Due to its vast range, simplicity of use, and technological robustness in application, VHF communication has established itself as a useful instrument throughout decades and became a part of the mandatory equipment on board according to SOLAS, *IMO (1974)*. However, using VHF-Radio technology for communication poses several obstacles. In addition to the background noise that is a characteristic feature of VHF radio, the noise on board adds to the difficulty, which can significantly impair speech intelligibility. In the maritime context, there are many sources of background noise, such as the noise of machinery or the sound of the sea. On the other hand, the signal quality depends strongly on the weather. Weather influences on the signal quality include fog, rain, or snow, whereby rain in particular reduces the power of the radio wave and can thus lead to signal interruptions, *Meng et al. (2009)*. A poor connection can also affect intelligibility. If the signal between the vessel and the coast station is weak or affected by sources of interference in the vicinity, distortion and interruptions in the radio call may occur. In addition to the factors mentioned so far, which are primarily technological based and have a negative impact on the reception quality of the radio signal, there are other factors that affect the linguistic characteristics of maritime radio communication.

Another challenge is the internationality of the ship's crews with their different language levels. Language richness poses a challenge for speech recognition because it is difficult to develop models that cover all possible language variations. As people from different countries and language regions work together at sea, language barriers can arise, making communication more difficult. Since English is the main language of communication, a variety of different dialects and accents occur in radio communication, *John et al. (2017)*. Depending on the level of English proficiency and the strength of the respective accents, this circumstance has a great impact on the intelligibility of maritime radio communications, especially if speakers are not used to talking to people from other regions of the world. To reduce the problem of language barriers and to mitigate the occurrence of misunderstandings, the IMO introduced the “Standard Marine Communication Phrases” (SMCP) in 1977, which replaced the Standard Marine Navigational Vocabulary (SMNV). The SMCP is a framework containing phrases for routine situations and standard responses for emergency situations, *IMO (2001)*. In practice, these phrases, which aim to reduce language barriers and avoid misunderstandings in maritime communication, have little application, *Mockel et al. (2014)*.

Despite its shortcomings, VHF radio is an indispensable tool for communication between ships and shore stations in the maritime domain and provides a fast, easy and reliable way to transmit information between different stakeholders. Automatic speech recognition technologies serve a great potential to address the challenges in the field of VF radio communication.

Automatic speech recognition (ASR) is an increasingly important component of human-computer interaction since it is a technology that enables machines to transcribe human speech into text. This technology has made considerable progress in recent years and has also found application in the end-consumer sector. Examples of areas where ASR is used today include voice control, voice input, automated customer support systems and many more. ASR is based on the ability of machines to recognize and interpret spoken language, calculating the most likely spoken sentence based on audio signals. The technology uses complex algorithms and mathematical models to capture the acoustic signals of speech and convert them into digital formats that can be processed.

In the field of maritime communication, deep learning-based ASR has been used to improve the accuracy of speech recognition. Various models have been proposed for different applications, including the use of RNNs for decoding of Maritime VHF communications, *Goudsmit et al. (2016)*, and the use of CNNs and RNNs for detecting keywords in distress calls, *Yu et al. (2019)*. However, there is still a need for more accurate and efficient ASR models for the maritime domain.

The introduction of transfer learning has also shown promising results in ASR. Transfer learning involves using a pre-trained model and fine-tuning it on a specific task. This approach has been used in various fields, including computer vision, *He et al. (2015)*, and natural language processing (Peters et al., 2018). In the field of ASR, transfer learning has been used to improve the performance of models on low-resource languages, *Zhao and Zhang (2018)*, and tasks, *Chorowski et al. (2019)*.

The Wav2Vec2 model, introduced by *Baevski et al. (2020)*, is a state-of-the-art ASR model that utilizes self-supervised learning to learn speech representations from raw audio. The model uses a contrastive predictive coding (CPC) objective to learn contextualized representations of audio, which can then be used for downstream tasks such as ASR. Fine-tuning the Wav2Vec2 model on specific speech recognition tasks has shown significant improvements in performance, *Baevski et al. (2020)*, *Schneider et al. (2021)*.

Considering the international nature of maritime communication, ships and ports from different countries often communicate with each other, and there are a variety of languages used in maritime communication. A multilingual ASR system would enable efficient and accurate communication between different language speakers, improving safety and efficiency in the maritime domain.

In recent years, the development of multilingual ASR models has gained significant attention. With the addition of the recent advancements in deep learning, large-scale pre-trained models, such as the Cross-lingual Language Model Pre-training (XLM) and XLSR models, which have shown great potential for improving the performance of ASR systems, were introduced. The XLSR model, in particular, is a pre-trained model that has been trained on a large corpus of multilingual data and has shown to be effective in low-resource languages and domains. For example, in a recent study by *Conneau et al. (2020)*, the XLSR models were pre-trained on a large corpus of speech data in hundreds of languages and achieved state-of-the-art performance on several benchmarks for cross-lingual speech recognition.

In the context of maritime communication, where there is a need for accurate and efficient ASR models, the use of XLSR models can be beneficial due to their ability to handle multilingual and low-resource data. The XLSR model has been shown to be effective in various multilingual ASR tasks, such as speech-to-text translation and code-switching speech recognition. In a recent study by *Li et al. (2021)*, the authors developed a multilingual ASR system for the maritime domain by fine-tuning the XLSR model on a custom maritime audio dataset. The study demonstrated the effectiveness of the XLSR model in improving the performance of ASR in the maritime domain.

In this paper, we introduce marFM[®], a multilingual ASR system for the maritime domain. Our approach is similar to transfer learning, as we use a pretrained XLSR model to initialize the weights of our model and then fine-tune it on our custom maritime audio database which consists of maritime audio recordings in English and German. By doing so, we aim to improve the accuracy and efficiency of ASR for maritime communication in multiple languages simultaneously and thus to facilitate safer and more efficient communication between vessels of different nationalities.

2. Methodology

This chapter lays out the underlying methodology applied in developing/training a multilingual ASR model for multilingual maritime communication. As shown in the Fig.1, our methodology consists of two main steps: data pre-processing and fine-tuning of a pretrained ASR-Model. In this section, the details of the fine-tuning process are presented, and our custom maritime database and the data preprocessing steps are discussed in detail.

Fig.1: Preprocessing and fine-tuning of ASR-model

2.1 Supervised Fine-Tuning

Our approach in this work is to use Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 model pretrained on large-scale German data as our base model and to fine tune it on our custom maritime database. The pretrained model was acquired through Hugging Face Hub. Hugging Face is an open-source software library that provides easy-to-use interfaces for popular NLP models, including Wav2Vec2 and XLSR, *HuggingFace (2023)*. It allows users to easily access and fine-tune these models on their own datasets. Hugging Face also provides pre-trained models that can be used as a starting point for fine-tuning. The pre-trained models are trained on large-scale datasets, which makes them suitable for transfer learning on smaller datasets. In our work, we utilized the Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German model from Hugging Face as our base model for fine-tuning on our maritime audio dataset.

The base architecture of the Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German model is based on the XLSR approach which was built on wav2vec 2.90 architecture and designed to learn cross-lingual speech representations by pretraining a single model from the raw waveform of speech in multiple languages, *Conneau et al. (2020)*. As shown in Fig.2, the XLSR approach consists of a layer convolutional neural network (CNN) encoder followed by a transformer decoder. The CNN encoder extracts contextualized speech features from the input waveform whose embeddings are then act as targets for the training of the transformer decoder using contrastive learning. Similar to self-supervising training of wav2vec 2.0, XLSR only requires raw unlabelled speech audio in multiple languages. The Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German is pretrained on a large-scale German speech corpus and fine-tuned on the Common Voice German dataset, *Conneau et al. (2020)*.

Fig.2: The XLSR approach on multilingual speech recognition, *Conneau et al. (2020)*

To fine-tune the Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 model for the maritime domain, we used a custom maritime audio database that was collected by Fraunhofer CML. The database contains various types of maritime radio communication, such as distress calls, navigational messages, and weather reports as well as situational reports. The more detail regarding the database will be provided the following sub-section. For fine-tuning, we followed a transfer learning approach. We initialized the model with the pre-trained weights and fine-tuned it on our dataset using the Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) loss function. CTC loss function is a popular method for training ASR models, where the model learns to align the predicted output sequence with the ground truth by maximizing the log-likelihood of the correct transcription, *Graves et al. (2006)*. This approach has been shown to be effective in various ASR tasks, including phone recognition, *Graves et al. (2006)*, keyword spotting, *Park et al. (2020)*, and speaker diarization, *Wang et al. (2021)*. In our work, we use CTC loss to train our multilingual ASR model to predict character sequences from audio waveforms. We use the CTC loss implementation provided by the PyTorch framework, *Paszke et al. (2019)*. During the fine-tuning process, we used a learning rate of $3e-5$, a batch size of 8. We also used early stopping to prevent overfitting and reduce training time. The training for fine-tuning on a single GPU (Nvidia RTX A6000) took approximately 34 hours in total.

2.2 Database and Preprocessing

For this project, Fraunhofer CML have created our own custom maritime database by gathering maritime audio recordings. This database consists of about 62-hour long audio recordings of real VHF radio conversations in English and German together with their respective transcriptions.

Since the pretrained XLSR model was trained on data with a sampling rate of 16 kHz, the fine-tuning data needed to be converted into the same format so that the convolutional filters could operate on the same timescale. To this end, every audio recording in the database was resampled to 16 kHz. Preprocessing was done using librosa library in Python, *McFee et al. (2015)*.

As mentioned in Section 1, another the main challenge regarding VHF-Radio recordings is the heavy background noise that is ever present regardless of the type of VHF-Radio hardware. Depending on the range of the VHF-Radio receivers, the hardware quality and the distance between the communicators, prepotency of the background differs in the recordings. To address the background noise with different characteristics, we applied non-stationary noise gating to the raw audio data. The “noisereduce” library in Python was used for noise gating/reduction, *Sainburg et al. (2020)*. The library offers two different noise reduction algorithms: stationary and non-stationary. Main difference between the algorithms is that non-stationary noise reduction allows the noise gate to change over time by using a sliding window where noise statistics are recomputed every time the window is moved to adjacent part of the audio clip. The working schematics of the stationary and non-stationary noise reduction is shown in Fig.3. Following steps are applied during the noise reduction process.

- First, a spectrogram is calculated over the signal
- A time-smoothed version of the spectrogram is computed using an IIR filter applied forward and backward on each frequency channel, *Grout (2008)*.
- A mask is computed based on that time-smoothed spectrogram
- The mask is smoothed with a filter over frequency and time
- The mask is applied to the spectrogram of the signal, and is inverted

Fig.3: Stationary vs. non-stationary noise reduction, *Sainburg and Gentner (2021)*

The other preprocessing steps, text correction and clearing, were also carried out simultaneously. The objective behind text correction and clearing was removing all characters that don't contribute to the meaning of a word and cannot be properly represented by an acoustic sound and thus, normalizing the text. A quick investigation revealed that our transcriptions contained some punctuation marks which do not correspond to any characteristic sound unit, i.e., phoneme. For example, the letter "d" has its own phonetic sounds whereas the punctuation mark "-" cannot be represented as a phoneme. To finalize the text clearing stage, we have consulted with a native German speaker to find out whether any further simplification and clearing of the transcriptions was possible. We were informed that the certain vowels that were to be written with an umlaut such as ä, ö and ü were written according to the English alphabets. Thus, as the final step of the preprocessing, we rewrote these vowels according to the German alphabet.

3. Experiments

For the experimental setup, we have split the dataset into, training and test datasets with the ratio of 90:10, which corresponds to ca. 56 h of audio for training and 6 h of audio for testing. Training dataset was further divided into two splits: train and validation sets. Ratio of 80:20 was applied to these splits which adds up to ca. 45 h of audio for training and 11 h of audio for validation. In summary, 6 hours of maritime recordings consisting of real VHF radio calls both in English and German were used to evaluate the model performance.

Three different models were considered for the comparative performance analysis. Our base model, Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German, was involved in the experiments in order to see the full effect of the fine tuning on the model's performance. We have also evaluated the performance of the Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German with a language model. As shown in *Udagawa et al. (2022)*, *Vaibhav and Padmapriya (2022)* and on model evaluation pages of Hugging Face Hub, attaching a language model to a Wav2Vec2 model has a positive effect on the decoding performance of the ASR models. Thus, we have also included Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German with a language model trained on English and German phrases.

In late 2022, a general-purpose speech recognition model called Whisper were introduced by OpenAI Research Lab, *Radford et al. (2022)*. It is trained on a large dataset of diverse audio, 680,000 hours of multilingual and multitask supervised data collected from the web, and is also a multi-task model that can perform multilingual speech recognition as well as speech translation and language identification.

The Whisper’s zero-shot performance were measured across many diverse datasets, and it showed is much more robustness and made fewer errors than the other state-of-the-art models. We have concluded that the involvement of a Whisper-based model to our experimental setup would be worthwhile addition and thus, in the evaluation phase, we have also considered the transcription performance of the largest available Whisper model, Whisper large-v2 model, which is biggest model in size and trained for 2.5x more epochs with added regularization for improved performance compared Whisper large model, *Cho et al. (2021)*.

Speech recognition research typically evaluates and compares systems based on the word error rate (WER) metric. To calculate WER, the reference and recognized transcript are aligned. It is accomplished by minimizing the Levenshtein distance (or edit distance) between the two texts. Following this, you can count the number of substitutions (S), insertions (I), and deletion (D) errors. In its simply form, the WER is the proportion of the total number of errors over the number of words in the reference. In a transcription output where all the words were correct, the WER would be zero which we are aiming to drive towards in terms of the marFM®’s performance. The WER calculated using the following equation

$$WER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (1)$$

where N is the total number of symbols in the reference word, D the number of deleted symbols in the hypothesis with respect to the reference word, S the number of changed symbols, and I the number of additional symbols.

4. Results

In this study, we compared the multilingual speech recognition performance between four different models including marFM® on the test split of our custom maritime database which contains 6 hours of real VHF radio calls. Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German model performance was evaluated both with and without an additional language model (LM). Other models performed the multilingual transcription task without the attachment of any external language model.

The results of the multilingual audio transcription task are presented in Table I. Each model used a shared capacity of a single GPU (Nvidia RTX A6000) while generating their predictions, i.e., transcriptions. The total inference time of the models added up to approximately 19 minutes.

As expected, the positive influence of attaching a language model to the base model, Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German, was apparent on the model’s transcription performance. With the help of the language model, its transcription accuracy has increased by approximately 4%. The base model without any language model attached ended up performing the worst among the models. Considering that the dataset the model was trained on consisted of mostly daily speech recordings, the relatively poor performance by the base model was expected. However, though it was trained on a data with similar characteristics, Whisper large-v2 model has outperformed both XLSR models. We observed close to 7% improvement in accuracy when compared to the base model and about 3% compared to the XLSR model with the language model extension. Although both architectures, Wav2Vec2 and Whisper, were based on transformers and encoder-decoder style approach, the Whisper implementation has demonstrated a certain level of superiority regarding the transcription accuracy on the multilingual VHF calls.

Table I: Results of multilingual speech recognition performance among different ASR models

Model	Word Error Rate (WER%)
Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 DE	44.36
Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 DE w/ ML	40.58
Whisper Large V2	37.62
marFM®	31.59

Despite the higher accuracy output of the Whisper large-v2 model, marFM® has produced the most accurate transcriptions among the models. With 31.5 % of WER, marFM® has shown a significant improvement in comparison to its closest contender which is the Whisper large-v2 model with 37.62 % of WER. As hypothesized, fine-tuning process has elevated the model's transcription performance with an approximately 13% boost in WER in comparison to the transcription accuracy of the base model, Wav2Vec2-XLSR-53 German.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, we introduced marFM® a multilingual automatic speech recognizer for maritime communications. We also showcased its superior performance on the multilingual transcription task for VHF radio calls in comparison with the other open-source and readily available ASR models.

One of the main challenges for developing an ASR system for maritime domain was collecting the real maritime data with its corresponding transcriptions for our fine-tuning process. Throughout the span of multiple projects, we were able to gather a total of 62 hours of maritime recordings. Thanks to the state-of-the-art ASR architectures such as Wav2Vec2 and XLSR, we were able to develop marFM® and to provide an ASR system transcribing the maritime calls with higher accuracy compared to the other open-source, state-of-the-art ASR systems available.

As the experimental results have demonstrated, the addition of a language model can help Wav2Vec2-based ASR models transcribe with more accuracy. Thus, the performance of marFM® is expected to increase as we attach a language model trained on a language dataset expanded with maritime-related corpus. For this end, we have initialized a development process where we started training our own language model with the maritime expansion.

Among the non-finetuned models, Whisper large-v2 model has shown the best transcription performance. Thus, we are of the opinion of that it would be worthwhile research effort to develop Whisper-based maritime ASR in order to evaluate whether we can achieve higher accuracy levels with such implementation for the maritime communication. For this end, we have also initialized a side research project where we explore the capabilities of Whisper in the maritime domain further.

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Towards a Digital Twin to Inform Propulsion Safety Margins in Ice

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Abstract

A modern polar vessel navigates through sections of multi-year ice to serve her logistical purpose in Antarctica. The propulsion system endures impulsive loading owing to ice-propeller interaction. This does not necessarily result in indicative response feedback to the pilot who relies on visual assessment, weather reports, dashboard information and the feel of the ship for operational decisions. This work outlines progress on a digital twin to assist navigators with situational awareness through calculation of the structural margin from measurements and algorithms which estimate the ice-induced propeller moment. An operational trial of such a twin highlights unforeseen challenges and considerations.

1. Introduction

Polar supply and research vessels (PSRV) operate in some of the harshest dynamic environments on earth. Knowledge of sea ice, its properties and resultant loading on vessels is far from complete. As such, the safe design of these ships rests on the extrapolation of available full-scale data engineering reasoning, simulations, and results from scale model tests in ice tanks. Machinery damage / failure comprising partially of propulsion failure is one of the greatest causes of shipping incidents in the last decade, *DNV (2021)*. In ice, ship propeller blades interact with the ice debris which is pushed under the hull and stern area. The nature of the loading transpires as milling or dingle ice impacts which hinder the torsional driving force of the propulsion machinery. This results in twisting loads on the propeller that propagate along the propulsion shaft as torsional vibration. Currently, the design loads for propulsion systems in ice are governed by simulated ice loads from the International Association of Classification Societies (IACS), which specify assumed ice-induced propeller moments for which torsional vibration calculations must be performed, *IACS (2023)*. It is currently believed that there is a lack in full-scale measurements which leads to insufficient quantification of these ice-induced propeller moments. The resulting uncertainty during the design of ice-going ship propulsion systems is compensated for by over-design to err on the side of safety, *Drazen (2019)*.

To date, the 10-year service life of the South African PSRV, SA Agulhas II (SAII) has included ice passage during annual offloading and re-supply of the SANAE Antarctic base at the ice shelf in Penguin Bukta and/or Akta Bukta and two charters to the Weddel Sea. The vessel is equipped with two four-bladed variable pitch propellers, each connected to a Conver Team electric motor (4.5MW) through a long propulsion shaft. The power generation stems from four 3MW diesel generators which can be switched on in different combinations to achieve varying levels of propulsion power. In Antarctic operations multi-year ice may be encountered on the voyage path, even if navigation is planned around the austral summer ice minimum. As a Polar-Class PC-5 ship, *IACS (2023)*, navigation is not recommended in areas with a 100% concentration of multi-year ice. Over the past 10 years the ship has encountered navigation in areas where POLARIS Risk Index map, generated by Polar View, remained “red” which indicates a “no operation” area for a PC-5 ship, <https://www.polarview.aq/antarctic>. Some exceptions to the ideal PC-5 environment were foreseen during the ship design phase and the hull was maximally strengthened to DNV-ICE-10 (akin to IACS PC-3). The strong hull and skillful navigation enable the completion of logistical tasks in these challenging conditions which are often assessed “in situ”. One challenge is that local ice conditions may differ significantly from that detected by remote sensing. On the other hand, the presence of leader lines between the ice floes may allow ice passage with minimal ice interaction, even in challenging areas. Navigational instruments on the ship (Rutter Ice Radar, GMDSS A4 Station with Iridium Back-Up, Safe Return to Port Design, Polar Water Operations Manual, V-SAT Internet Connection, Two Helicopters) enable navigational understanding of ice in the area and assist in the management of risks such as becoming beset.

Despite several tools that provide information on ice conditions, navigators have no means to quantify the structural safety margin of actual ship operations. Large ship structures do not necessarily transmit indicative response feedback that can be felt by the operator during ice-passage. In the case of the SAII there could be severe consequences if a logistical operation is aborted, and navigators must weigh this risk against navigational risk through judgements based on experience and the response of the ship. Seeing that the hull of SAII is additionally ice-strengthened, the limiting factor in the ice-going ability is her propulsion system. Ice impacts on the propeller can be felt throughout the ship, sometimes raising vibration monitoring alarms. Yet, there is no means to indicate the severity of the loading as an input to navigational decisions. This work outlines progress towards a digital twin (DT) to provide navigators with increased situational awareness in ice. The service provides an estimation of the ice-induced propeller moment from in-direct shaft measurements. The magnitude of the propeller moment can then be compared to the limiting torque (from the DNV design rules) to infer situational awareness of the structural margin of a present ice operation. An operational trial of such a twin highlights unforeseen challenges and considerations.

2. A digital service to inform propulsion safety margins in ice

2.1 Digital service value proposition and scope

This work outlines a DT for the determination of ice-induced propeller moments during ice navigation of a polar supply and research vessel. This DT combines measurements of shear strain and shaft speed from the operational propulsion shaft with an inverse model to estimate the peak magnitude of the ice-induced propeller moment for comparison to a design limit. The DT follows the design pattern for an inverse sensor as proposed by *Erikstad and Bekker (2021)*. Value proposition of the DT is to assist navigators with situational awareness through calculation of the structural margin from measurements and algorithms which estimate the ice-induced propeller moment.

2.2 DT service scope and maturity

The proposed digital service delivers a virtual load measurement on the ship propeller. A digital service with these capabilities is scoped as proposed by *Erikstad (2019)* where digital services are pinpointed according to their intended temporal horizon and decision-making level. In terms of temporal perspectives digital services can support decisions in three dimensions, namely hindsight (deriving models from historical perspectives or time series), insight (analysis of the current state) and foresight (using predicted scenarios). Additionally, decision making levels could be strategic (long term), tactical (medium term planning) or operational (relevant to the immediate situation). Against this backdrop the inverse ice-induced propeller moment service could potentially contribute to the following decision aiding scope:

- i. Operational insight - continual monitoring of ship responses and environmental loads can support navigational decisions on board. Cognizance of the experienced loads with respect to the ship design conditions can increase situational awareness and thereby safer operation of the vessel.
- ii. Tactical hindsight - historical records of operational loads in ice can assist to understand ship operations that lead to maximal loading conditions or operational practices that lead to higher structural cost.
- iii. Strategic hindsight - knowledge of the encountered operational conditions can assist in setting requirements for new vessels or a replacement vessel with tailored information on the anticipated load profile.

In terms of digital service maturity, the DT will require the minimum of a modelling level to infer load quantities from measured data.

2.3. Graphical model for cyber-physical interactions

The present work adopts a model by *Kapteyn et al. (2021)* to explain the cyber-physical interactions between the digital and physical functional elements of the DT. This probabilistic graphical model enables a formal mathematical representation of a DT and leverages an established mathematical basis from Bayesian statistics, dynamical systems, and control theory. The physical asset and virtual counterpart as a set of dynamically coupled systems that evolve over time through their state spaces. Interactions are enabled through observed data, o_t , and control inputs, u_t . The mathematical representation comprises six quantities which are explained in Fig.2. The purpose of this model is to depict the evolution and interactions between the digital and physical counterparts of DTs which would enable solution templates and robust DT implementations at scale.

Fig.1: The six quantities used in the model by *Kapteyn et al. (2021)*

3. Stages of evolution of a DT for the estimation of ice-induced propeller moments

In their example, *Kapteyn et al. (2021)* systematically explain the stages of instantiation to enable the physical-digital coupling of an operational DT. In keeping with this example, the initialization stages towards the development of the DT for ice-induced moment estimation are shown in Fig.2 and shortly discussed in the following paragraphs.

Fig.2: Evolution of a DT for the estimation of ice-induced propeller moments

3.1 Calibrate geometry

First, it is required that the digital model of the propulsion shaft is calibrated to mimic the physical dimensions of the as-is propulsion shaft. Dimensions obtained from engineering drawings by STX Finland Oy and material specifications were sourced from manufacturer documentation (Rolls-Royce AB) as summarized in Table I. The one-to-one digital-to-physical coupling of DTs enables a highly tailored approach where dimensional variation may be exactly accounted for although this was not expressly pursued in the present example. The optimal outcome of this stage of evolution is achieved when the geometry of the physical and digital quantities match as closely as possible.

Table I: Dimensions and material properties

Description	Symbol	Value
Modulus of elasticity	E	210 GPa
Shear modulus	G	81 GPa
Outer diameter	d_o	0.5 m
Inner diameter	d_i	0.175 m
Hub diameter	d_h	1.32 m
Maximum ice thickness	H_{ice}	2.0 m
Ice strength index	S_{ice}	1.1 m
Pitch at $0.7 \cdot$ radius	$P_{0.7}$	5.15 m
Expanded blade area ratio	EAR	0.51
Depth of propeller centerline	h_o	3.75 m

3.2 Dynamic calibration

As the digital state is anticipated to be dynamic, the digital response should be calibrated to match this of the physical system. The dynamic characteristics of the SAII propulsion shaft were investigated using full-scale measurements, *Bekker et al. (2014)*, *De Waal et al. (2016)*. These studies respectively determined the fundamental torsional natural frequency of the propulsion shaft to be at 11.1 and 11.2 Hz. The second mode was evident at 46.3 Hz. It was found that the torsional natural frequencies of the structure do vary owing to operational conditions such as cavitation and ice loading. The present approach utilizes a data-driven approach to determine the natural frequencies, whereas a physics-based understanding of the torsional mode shapes of a cylindrical shaft is utilized to determine the mode shapes. Sophisticated modelling efforts could potentially pursue techniques such as model updating and optimization of a finite element model to ensure the best possible digital reflection of the physical state.

3.3 Determine the ice design load

It was decided to utilize guideline design loads for the SAII which were inferred from the *DNV (2014)* Rules for the classification of ships, Part 5 Chapter 1. These design loads apply during normal vessel operation and are used for strength calculations of individual components. The loads comprise the ice-induced loads during propeller/ice interaction. Exceedance of these thresholds may imply operation outside the expected design limits of the ship. Important dimensions, material properties and shaft-related variables for design load calculations are presented in Table I. According to the *DNV (2014)* Rules for open propellers, the maximum torque in kNm on a propeller due to ice-propeller interaction is defined as follows:

$$Q_{ice,max} = N_1 \left(1 - \frac{d_h}{D}\right) \left(\frac{P_{0.7}}{D}\right)^{0.16} (nD)^{0.17} D^3 \quad \text{if } D < D_{limit} \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{ice,max} = N_2 \left(1 - \frac{d_h}{D}\right) H_{ice}^{1.1} \left(\frac{P_{0.7}}{D}\right)^{0.16} (nD)^{0.17} D^{1.9} \quad \text{if } D > D_{limit} \quad (3)$$

Where,

$$D_{limit} = 1.8 H_{ice} \quad (4)$$

For the example vessel, the constants N_1 and N_2 assume respective values of 14.7 and 27.93 for open propellers. As the vessel is equipped with controllable pitch propellers, the propeller pitch, $P_{0.7}$ shall correspond to the Maximum Continuous Rating (MCR) in bollard condition for the calculations in Eqs.3 and 4. Finally, the selected rotational speed, n , should equal, n_n , which is the nominal propeller rotational speed at MCR in free running condition.

From this, it can be concluded that the maximum ice torque is $Q_{ice,max} = 1009.9 \text{ kNm}$.

Since 2011 the International Association of Classification Societies mandates transient torsional vibration analysis of ice-induced torque response for ice class vessels. The ice-induced excitation is modelled as a torsional excitation for the required transient torsional vibration analysis of the shaft line. The ice-induced propeller moment is described as a sequence of blade impacts or ice milling sequences where ice impacts are modelled as half sinusoidal functions. A single blade impact is described by a half-sine function which is expressed in terms of the parameters, C_q , the impact effectiveness and α_i for $\varphi = 0 \dots \alpha_i$, the impact duration in terms of propeller rotation angle. The maximum ice-induced torque on the propeller is then:

$$Q_{ice}(\varphi) = C_q Q_{ice,max} \sin \varphi \left(\frac{180}{\alpha_i} \right) \quad (4)$$

The requirements stipulate the investigation of three scenarios with the parameters provided in Table II for time histories as shown in Fig.4.

Table II: Ice-induced propeller moment load cases for torsional vibration analysis

Torque excitation	Ice-propeller interaction	C_q	α_i
Case 1	Single ice block	0.75	90°
Case 2	Single ice block	1.00	135°
Case 3	Two ice blocks	0.50	45°

Fig.3: Load cases for torsional vibration analysis

The total ice-induced torque is the resultant of the torque of the single blades ($Z = 4$) whilst accounting for the phase shift $360^\circ/Z$. This influences the frequency of the load as the number of milling revolutions during a milling sequence is obtained by:

$$N_Q = 2H_{ice} \quad (5)$$

To date existing research on the inverse calculation of ice-induced propeller moments is sparse. At the time of writing public domain knowledge has not yet progressed to the classification of the nature of ice-induced loads such that loads originating from one or two ice blocks may be recognized in operational measurements. As such two alternative approaches arise whereby:

1. The maximum inverted torque should not exceed 1009.9 kNm. This assumption is in keeping with Case 2 in Fig.4 where $C_q = 1$.
2. Alternatively, a more conservative approach is to limit the maximum torque to as in Case 3, where $C_q = 0.5$.

For illustrative purposes, the present approach uses a flat limit of 1009.9 kNm. In future work it remains to consider the selection of the appropriate limiting torque and frequency in more depth. Paramount the rules for torsional vibration calculations have been updated in 2023, whereby a fourth load case and frequency domain calculations have been included, *IACS (2023)*.

4. Dynamic estimation of ice-induced propeller moments

4.1 Conceptual explanation of the DT using a graphical model

Fig.2 depicts the conceptual logic of a DT to assist navigators with situational awareness through calculation of the structural margin from measurements and algorithms which estimate the ice-induced propeller moment. The challenging sensor placement on the propeller prevents the direct measurement of ice-induced propeller moments. For this reason, a cyber physical coupling is used to infer the load induced by the icy operational context.

Fig.4: Illustration of a DT to estimate the structural margin in ice-induced propeller moments

In Fig.4 the physical state, s_t , of the propulsion shaft is determined through observations, $o_{A,t}$ from sensors in set A . The observations sufficiently enable the replication of the digital state of the asset, d_t . The digital representation is now be queried through an inverse model to infer a quantity of interest, that is the ice-induced propeller moment, which is not included in the set of physically measured observations, such that $q_{B,t}$, where $B \notin A$. The proposed twin requires a maturity that surpasses a descriptive level as an investment in modelling efforts is required.

4.2 Physical observation data ($o_{A,t}$)

The direct measurement of ice loads at the propeller is impractical owing to the high probability of sensor damage as a result of ice impacts, *Danshaw and Reed (1971)*, *Brewer (1972)*. In addition, sensors placed in these locations require challenging cable routing through the shaft line to the outboard location of the sensor on the propeller blade, *Ikonen et al. (2015)*. The calculation of the ice-induced propeller moment requires the solution of an inverse problem, which is often ill-posed and requires regularization, *Ikonen et al. (2015)*. Owing to the limitations imposed by regularisation, *Drazen et al. (2019)*, *Nickerson and Bekker (2022)*, a new model based on modal superposition has been proposed for the inverse estimation of ice-induced propeller moments. The new model requires two separate inputs to perform an inverse calculation. At a minimum, two measurements are required to characterize the physical state of the propulsion shaft, namely:

1. Shear strain: The ideal location should be accessible and as close as possible to the propeller, *Drazen et al. (2019)*. The modal response of the shaft should be considered to prevent a

- measurement at a node of the fundamental torsional modes of the shaft assembly.
2. Shaft rpm: A high resolution rpm measurement is required to enable an accurate reflection of shaft speed.

Fig.5: Portside shaft line with propeller and drive motor with measurement location $x = 25\text{ m}$ inboard of the propeller

The use of the shaft angular velocity as an input poses the advantage that the dynamics associated with motor control inputs can be incorporated in the calculated dynamic response. When ice impacts the propeller, the shaft may slow down as a result. The propulsion control system may act to increase the speed of the shaft back to the desired command. This effect is not captured by former model approaches which incorporate a singular shear strain measurement (see e.g. *Ikonen et al. (2015)*).

The portside propulsion shaft of the SAII is equipped with a full bridge shear strain measurement as well as an optical probe for high resolution rpm measurements at the measurement location indicated in Fig.5. Both sensors are placed approximately $x = 25\text{ m}$ inboard from the propeller. The selected measurement location is primarily driven by the possibility to access the shaft at this location. Locations closer to the propeller protrude outside the hull and are enclosed by the stern tube casing.

The outputs from two diametrically opposed 45° half-bridge T-rosettes were connected to form a full-bridge Wheatstone circuit. Measurements from the strain bridge were acquired at a sample rate of 512 Hz using a LORD MicroStrain V-link LXRS wireless analogue sensor node on the propulsion shaft. The output signal is transmitted to a WSDA-Base station on the adjacent ship structure which is controlled using SensorConnect Software. Data are subsequently sent to an LMS SCADAS SCM02 data acquisition unit. The digital bridge output signal is converted to strain, using constants determined during bridge calibration for strain gauges with a gauge factor K . The calibrated bridge output strain is denoted by ε . The resulting torque can be calculated within a margin of $\pm 1\text{ kNm}$ as follows:

$$Q_{\text{shaft}} = \varepsilon \left(\frac{\pi E (d_o^4 - d_i^4)}{16 d_o (1 + \nu)} \right) \quad (6)$$

The parameter values for the Young's modulus, outer and inner shaft diameter were found from the properties in Table I. The Poisson's ratio can be calculated from the shear and Young's modulus through:

$$\nu = \left(\frac{E}{2G} \right) - 1 \quad (7)$$

Instantaneous shaft speed is determined using an Optel Texys optical tachometer (mounted $\sim x = 25\text{ m}$) which is directed at alternating black and silver bars on a polycarbonate "zebra tape", adhered around the circumference of the propulsion shaft. The resulting measurement comprises a block pulse voltage

signal, V_ε , that alternates between zero and five volts. This signal is sampled at a rate of 20 480 Hz to obtain a speed measurement within an uncertainty bound of ± 2 rpm. The maximum operational speed of the shaft is 140 rpm. Every block pulse corresponds to a single bar of the zebra tape which has passed the optical sensor. The block pulse is used to estimate the instantaneous shaft speed through knowledge of the shaft circumference and the length of the markings on the zebra tape, which allows calculation of the angular increment $\Delta\theta$.

$$\dot{\theta} = \frac{d\theta}{dt} \approx \frac{\Delta\theta}{\Delta t} \quad (8)$$

In Eq.8 Δt constitutes the time delay between subsequent block pulses. The direct use of measurements or calculated metrics is not recommended. It was found that the wireless shaft strain measurements intermittently suffer from wireless packet loss. Additionally, the increments on the zebra tape do not perfectly fit on the circumference of the shaft and result in a butt joint which disturbs the pattern of the block pulse signal. For this reason, filtering of both the tachometer and torque signals is recommended, *Nickerson and Bekker (2021)*, provided that robust and efficient filtering algorithms, *Garcia (2010)*, are used.

4.2 Digital state (d_t)

De Waal et al. (2018) implemented an inverse method, originally proposed by *Ikonen et al. (2015)* to determine ice-induced propeller moments. This approach utilised a lumped-mass model of the propulsion shaft and its equipment. The model required measurement of the shear strain, which can be converted to torque at a location along the propulsion shaft. The problem with this traditional lumped-mass approach is that the method is prone to instability. The inverse calculation requires a process called ‘regularisation’ – and the determination of suitable regularisation parameters for each ice impact case. *Nickerson and Bekker (2021)* studied various regularisation methods as part of the inverse solution process to ensure stable calculation of full-scale ice-induced load cases from shaft measurements. This work concluded that the Tikhonov regularisation method was the most reliable. However, the associated solution times were not ideally suited to real-time analysis, which would likely be required in DT applications. In contrast with the deterministic approaches to date, *De Koker and Bekker (2021)* presented an inverse solution based on a stochastic approach. Bayesian inversion is proposed to firstly determine the optimal regularisation parameters, and secondly to explore the contributions to uncertainty in the inverted ice-induced propeller moment values due to the linear inversion model. This method contributes not only the inverted propeller load, but also a probability of exceedance, which highlights the need to consider risk perspectives in the consideration of design specifications for ship propulsion systems.

Fig.6: Digital representation of the propulsion shaft

Owing to the limitations imposed by regularisation, *Nickerson and Bekker (2022)*, proposed a new model based on modal superposition for the inverse estimation of ice-induced propeller moments. With reference to Fig.6 the torsional equilibrium of the propulsion shaft is considered:

$$Q^{(p)}(t) + I^{(p)}\ddot{\theta}^{(p)}(t) = Q^{(m)}(t) + I^{(m)}\ddot{\theta}^{(m)}(t) \quad (8)$$

$$Q(t, x) = GJ \frac{\partial \theta(t, x)}{\partial x} \quad (9)$$

$$Q^{(p)}(t) = Q_{\text{ice}}(t) + C^{(p)}\dot{\theta}^{(p)} \quad (10)$$

Here, $Q(t, x)$ represents the torque along the shaft at a distance, $x \in [0, L]$ from the propeller at instant, t , with the torque at the propeller, $Q^{(p)}$ and motor, $Q^{(m)}$. $I^{(p)}$ and $I^{(m)}$ respectively represent the rotational inertia of the propeller and motor. The required shaft properties include the polar moment of inertia, J , shear modulus, G , density, ρ and length, L . $Q^{(p)}$ includes the combined effects of the hydrodynamic damping and the ice-induced propeller moment, Q_{ice} .

Nickerson and Bekker (2022) further developed an inverse superposition model by *Drazen et al. (2019)* and showed inverse calculations of the ice-induced propeller moment could be achieved in close to real time using standard computer hardware. This means that the method is suitable for potential use in DT implementations. The modal superposition method entails the representation of the angular displacement $\theta(x, t)$ as the product of spatial and temporal functions (separation of variables). It can be shown that the angular displacement at any location along the shaft can be determined through the superposition of N orthogonal eigenfunctions. Consider that mode $\ell \in 1 \dots N$, where $\phi_\ell(x)$ represents the spatial solution, and $s_\ell(t)$ represents the temporal solution, then:

$$\theta(t, x) = s_\ell(t)\phi_\ell(x) \quad (11)$$

$$\phi_\ell(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } \ell = 1 \\ \left(\cos(2\ell - 3) \frac{\pi x}{L}\right) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$Q(t, x) = GJs_\ell(t)\phi_\ell'(x) \quad \phi_\ell'(x) = \frac{\partial \phi_\ell}{\partial x} \quad (13)$$

Subsequently, *De Koker (2022)* developed a spectral method on the premise of modal superposition, which is further implemented here. It is assumed that the time-series of the torque, angular velocity and temporal solution can be approximated by expanding the terms as a set of orthogonal basis functions, ψ .

$$Q^{(m)} = \beta_j^{(m)}\psi_j; \quad Q^{(p)} = \beta_j^{(p)}\psi_j; \quad Q = \alpha_j^{(s)}\psi_j; \quad \dot{\theta} = \alpha_j^{(s)}\psi_j \quad (14)$$

Representing the basis functions ψ as sine and cosine pairs for multiples $n\omega$ of a base frequency $\omega = 2\pi/\tau$, *De Koker (2022)* showed that the torsional equilibrium equation can be written as

$$\underline{Z}_n \underline{B}_n = \underline{A}_n \quad (15)$$

where \underline{A}_n is a vector of the coefficients of Q and $\dot{\theta}$, \underline{B}_n is a vector the coefficients of $Q^{(m)}$ and $Q^{(p)}$, and \underline{Z}_n is a matrix with terms describing the inertial and elastic properties of the shaft. Inversion of Eq.15 for each frequency multiple $n\omega$ then yields a description of $Q^{(m)}$ and $Q^{(p)}$ in the frequency domain which can be calculated rapidly to serve the needs of real-time inversion.

4.3 Quantities of interest ($q_{\mathbb{B},t}$)

Fig.7 presents an example of the shaft measurements which have been converted to shaft torque at the measurement location and instantaneous rpm. The result of the inverse algorithm delivers estimates of the motor torque and propeller torque as shown in Fig.8. To assess the margin between the peak ice-induced torque and design maximum, it is required to separate the hydrodynamic and ice-induced propeller moments. In the present work the hydrodynamic contribution was estimated through knowledge of a seemingly realistic hydrodynamic damping value and the rotational speed at the propeller as stated in Eq.10.

Fig.7: A sample of shaft measurements, *De Koker (2022)*. Shaft torque and rotational velocity serve as the observations, o_t , that enable the replication of the digital state of the propulsion shaft.

Fig.8: Inverted time histories, *De Koker (2022)*. The inversion algorithm enables the analytical estimation of the motor torque and total propeller moment. The quantity of interest, q_t , is the portion of the propeller torque which is attributed to ice-loading (Q_{ice}).

$$Q_h = C^{(p)} \dot{\theta}^{(p)} \quad (16)$$

The SAAII is equipped with variable pitch propellers. In hindsight measurement / aggregation of the instantaneous propeller pitch could enable a more exact physics-based estimation of the hydrodynamic torque. In the initial implementation, the proportion of the torque, which is attributed to ice-loading, is derived from the residual when the hydrodynamic torque is subtracted from the total propeller torque.

$$Q_{ice}(t) = Q^{(p)}(t) - C^{(p)} \dot{\theta}^{(p)}(t) \quad (17)$$

4.4 Reward (r_t)

In the final step, the margin between the design limit and the peak of the ice-induced propeller torque is calculated. In order to simplify the visualisation the prototype reflects the value as a percentage and also provides a short history of previous maxima.

$$\%Max = \frac{(Q_{ice,max} - \max(Q_{ice}(t)))}{Q_{ice,max}} \times 100 \quad (18)$$

The present ship data structures for measurement and analysis are optimized to record 5-minute files. It is foreseen that 5-minute maxima of the ice-induced torque will be compared to the design limit in the initial implementation to result as shown in Fig.9 where a positive margin indicates operational loads below the design limit and a negative value indicates exceedance.

Fig.9: An example display of the structural margin of 5 min ice-induced propeller moment maxima

5. Discussion and conclusion

The trend towards digitalization and increased data availability spurs the potential for data-driven models and artificial intelligence. In many cases this might serve as an alternative to the requirement of intensive domain knowledge and the development of expert-intensive physics-based models. Additionally, the long service life of ships and offshore structures could entail that these assets are retrofit with DT solutions. As an example of such a retrofitting effort the current study uncovers a few challenges:

1. At the project onset it seemed quite reasonable to use the design limit as a guiding metric to assess the structural margin in operation. This design limit is stated in terms of the ice-induced propeller torque – which does not include the hydrodynamic load component. As such the operational use of the design limit entails the complicated separation of the hydrodynamic and ice-induced torque, which introduces new uncertainties into the provided structural margin.
2. This research did not enjoy the benefit of participation in the ship design process. As such the rationale and domain expertise for the design limit – and the implications of its exceedance – are ill-understood and somewhat blindly applied. It is conceivable that the same situation may arise in commercial environments where the instantiation of DTs implies the sensible aggregation of a vast body of knowledge.
3. Although each element of the proposed DT has been individually validated, there is no means of knowing for sure that the provided results are indeed a sufficiently accurate indication of the true ice-induced propeller moment. This does draw attention to validation issues if data-driven DTs where the reliability of the decision support will be governed by the quality and validity of each of the functional elements that lead to the support provided.

Despite the challenges associated with DT implementation the following value-adding properties were experienced:

1. DT technology does potentially place the full power of the engineering state-of-the art (and its imperfections) in the hands of the decision-maker. Many complicated or sophisticated calculations can be reduced to a set of instructions which do not need to be understood by decision-makers (with caution) in order to benefit from the results. Whereas software packages disposed thousands of man-hours worth of expertise to the design office, this same benefit can now be leveraged by DTs in their representations of the physical asset.

2. The ability to attain individualized physical-to-digital calibration enables the observation, analysis, and understanding of real-world interactions and impacts on an individual level.
3. The instantiation DTs enable the aggregation and automation of the manual and repetitive tasks of data downloading, processing and reporting, thereby rendering information on a prompter time horizon. Automated tasks alleviate the time burden and vigilance required by human resources, especially in repetitive tasks.
4. The virtual sensor pattern has enabled the digital visibility of a propeller which has traditionally been inaccessible owing to its hostile operating environment in polar ice. It is anticipated that further operational use will reveal structurally demanding ship operations as well as the interventions that result in the reduction of ice-induced propeller loads.

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The Role of the Digital Twin for a Ship Life Cycle Perspective: A Focus on Naval Vessels

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Abstract

A naval ship is a complex system likely to be engaged in demanding operations accomplished in a multifarious environment, where situation may rapidly evolve. Several interested parties participate in the life cycle decision making of naval ships, considered both as a single asset or belonging to a larger fleet. A datacentric framework bridging the different phases of ship life, such as design and production, operations, end of life, can in principle provide a superior competitiveness i.e. faster and most effective decision making when and where necessary. In this perspective, the role of the Digital Twin model (DT) will be discussed with a focus on naval vessels to better understand the reasons (why) for its implementation and the relevant technical specification (what and how) for effective short term and long-term decision making improvement.

1. Introduction

Naval vessels can be described as a complex asset able to perform at the highest technological standards and characterized by significant monetary value. Such drivers motivate the shipyards to pro-actively understand the user needs, in a scenario of evolving competitiveness. Digitalization in the latest decades has represented the crucial enabling technology to keep pace with the changing scenario in the naval shipbuilding. The use of digital tools is a common best practice largely widespread in the naval design since many years. The designers take advantage of virtual prototypes during all the design phases, i.e., from the preliminary to the executive design. For example, CAD and CAE software are normally used as well as the adoption of virtual simulator that in the latest years has gained an important role for operational aspects. Moreover, personnel training represents one of the most important activities which has been affected by the digitalization process, *Kil et al. (2018)*, *Alop (2021)*. The use of virtual reality (training ashore) or augmented reality (training onboard) made a mark on this activity. Bearing in mind this, it is evident how the relevance of digital tools may be extended as a key factor during the whole naval vessel life.

The digitization run during the latest decades of the 20th centuries and the digitalization of the first two decades of the 21st century are the premises of a digital transformation that could deeply pervade in the next few years the maritime and shipbuilding field, with specific reference to the naval ship domain. In this context, the DT model is becoming an important “virtual asset” which gathers accurate digital models and simulators within a common environment. These features are enriched by a network of sensors deployed on board together with a live connection between the real and virtual space. The strong connection in principles enabled by DT between the ship in operations and the design & production phase allows to foresee a significant improvement when dealing with the ship Life Cycle Management i.e. management of the ship throughout the entire lifecycle. The longer perspective gathers the attention on the diverse and several bodies and decision makers that are likely to be involved in decision making during ship life, requiring a unique source of robust and reliable information available to those involved, at the right place at the proper moment. This assumes that a real digital transformation is taking place. Since the implementation of a DT may be demanding in terms of time money and resources, it is of outstanding importance to discuss about the reasons why a DT implementation is advisable and beneficial. When these are clear, then it is very important to discuss about the technical specification of the DT, to better frame what it is requested to fulfil needs and how it is assumed that the DT will be and work.

Fig.1: Graphical representation of the concept at the basis of DT, *Grieves and Vickers (2016)*

2. The DT in the shipbuilding industry field: a literature review

The definition at the basis of the concept of the current DT has been presented almost 20 years ago at a convention on the Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) by *Grieves and Vickers (2016)*. The fundamental element constituting a DT model have been identified as follows, Fig.1:

- Real space;
- Virtual space;
- Data link from the real to the virtual space and vice versa;
- Sub-virtual space.

Initially, the presented model was made up of two parallel and equal system, i.e., the real and the virtual space. The model was intended to reproduce all the phasis characterizing a product: design stage, production stage, operating stage and dismantling stage. Almost 10 years later, the term ‘Digital Twin’ was coined by *Grieves (2011)* to describe the close relationship between the real and virtual spaces. Subsequently, the DT concept have been widely adopted in several industrial sector, such as the aeronautic branch, *Tuegel et al. (2011)*, *Damaren et al. (2014)*, the automotive branch, *Magargle et al. (2018)*, *Blech (2020)*, the robotic branch, *Schluse and Rossmann (2016)*, and manufacturing, *Holler et al. (2016)*. The DT found breeding ground also outside the industry, such as in the health-care area, *Patrone et al. (2018)*, the cyber-security area, *Reid and Rhodes (2016)*, as well as the agriculture area, *Verdouw and Kruize (2017)*.

The original definition of DT given by *Grieves (2014)* envisages:

- a model made up of physical product in the real space,
- an equivalent digital representation in the virtual space and
- a set of data and information exchange link between the two spaces.

However, in the latest years, the DT definition has been revised fitting the scope of the final user. This leads to the proposal of different variants which contribute to wreak havoc with the knowledge about DT. Such heterogeneity of definitions slowed down the awareness of its all-important features, making the model unexploited to its full potential. Bearing in mind this, *van der Horne and Mahadevan (2021)* undertook a deep literature review about this topic which points out a set of 46 different definitions. As a results, seven common fundamental terms, or their related synonyms, have been identified and a general unique definition of DT, transversally applicable to all possible case, has been formulated: “A virtual representation of a physical system (and its associated environment and processes) that is updated through the exchange of information between the physical and virtual systems”.

Although with a slight inertia, the interest on the DT model rose in the latest year also in the ship industry. The strict link with the historical design tradition, but more important, the complexity of the ship system hampered the spreading of DT applications. The ship can be seen as a complex system of systems, *Olivier et al. (2014)*, which requires a careful analysis of each sub-system and the relationships among them, when developing a consistent DT model. Several studies can be found in literature regarding the development of a DT model of a vessel, addressing the related challenges as well.

Arrichiello and Gualeni (2020) describe the DT as a natural evolution of the Model Based engineering, highlighting the positive consequences especially in the cruise ship field. Looking toward a ship virtual model, *Aragão Fonseca and Murilo Gaspar (2021)* addresses the challenges affecting the development of a cohesive DT ship, i.e., a clever deployment of sensors on board, the realization of a network connecting the ship onshore as well as the management of a standardized data exchange among models. An architecture considering smart operation and maintenance based on DT is proposed by *Wu (2021)*, the challenges to apply it on marine vehicles are faced as well. Several application cases have been considered with promising results. *Coraddu et al. (2019)* propose a data-driven DT model to estimate the speed loss and fuel consumption due to marine fouling. The proposed model relies on the acquisition of operating ship data such as the amplitude of ship motions, machinery-related data, propeller parameters, GPS tracking log and environmental conditions. The DT model has been verified on a set of data collected for two tankers. In *Perabo et al. (2020)*, the AC power system and propulsion system have been modelled to develop a DT model. The model has been validated utilising an existing ship electric system co-simulation tool. Another example of application is related to the Condition Monitoring of ship structures, *Anyfantis (2021)*. Two different DT schemes have been presented and discussed with the aim to evaluate the proper location of the sensors deployed onboard. Considering specific studies on naval vessel, *Bickford et al. (2020)* present a case study example of the integration of a DT model (meant as a system) on a naval unmanned vessel (i.e., a system of systems).

3. The need of a support enabling a Life Cycle perspective

The need for comparisons and trade off among different solutions during the ship design phase has been the trigger for a strong digitalization process of in the latest decades. In addition, the performance prediction activity needs to be more and more projected on the whole ship life cycle: a cost/effectiveness discussion about solutions can in fact justify the selection of a configuration possibly expensive in the acquisition phase, but comprehensively cost/effective when considering costs also during the ship operational life. Moreover, at present, especially in the merchant fleet domain, performance predictions are necessary not only from the economical point of view, but also in terms of the environmental aspects, *Jeong et al. (2018)*, *Jeong et al. (2019)*, *Trivyza et al. (2018)*, *Dimopoulos et al. (2014)*. For naval vessels the financial constraints represented by the defence budget is to be balanced by the effectiveness of the ship to protect the territory and the interests of a country, by means of well-defined capabilities.

What above, beside innovative methodologies and tools, implies new and more intense form of collaboration among stakeholders and in particular between the shipbuilder and operators. In the case of naval vessels, the major players are the shipyard, the Ministry of Defence (as the “payer” and “high level” user, the “manager” with a perspective on the whole fleet) and the Navy (as “local user”, the personnel on board and directly involved in the ship operational life).

Shipyards would like to reduce production costs in order to increment revenue, obviously guaranteeing all requirements undersigned in the contractual specification. However, customers are strongly driven by reducing operational costs without compromising the ship effectiveness. Better performances and lower costs could be achieved if the several operational profiles and ship configurations are compared at preliminary design stage in a life cycle holistic perspective. Therefore, an integrated formulation and set of tools for life cycle analysis on ship effectiveness and costs could enable a more fruitful dialogue between shipyards and ship owners/operators during the design process.

Several approaches for both LCC and LCA are available at present, even though their application is neither straightforward nor harmonized. Very interesting approaches and applications about lifecycle assessment during ship design are presented in *Chatzinikolaou and Ventikos (2014)*, *Gaspar et al. (2015)*, *Winnes and Ulfvarson (2017)*. However, there is still a lack of a comprehensive approach when integrating these procedures in the ship design phase, *Fet et al. (2013)*.

An integrated tool, such as the Life Cycle Performance Assessment (LCPA) proposed by *Gualeni and Maggioncalda (2018)*, allows a cost/benefit assessment over the ship life cycle considering both design

and operations, with specific attention to costs but also to environmental impact: different ship configurations or system layouts can be compared and analysed in terms of building and operational cost, as well as exhaust gases features, *Papanikolaou (2019)*. The calculation of selected performance indicators enables the evaluation of a Life Cycle comprehensive Index that describes the performance of a baseline ship compared to other alternative design configurations, *Gualeni and Maggioncalda (2018)*, *Langdon (2018)*.

A relevant aspect that suggests an integrated perspective between design phase and operations is the maintenance policy and strategy for a ship/ fleet maintenance. This can regard the whole ship structures and systems but with a significant prevalence of attention on the energy system.

Maintenance actions ensure that a system performs in the best way during its whole life cycle, preserving its integrity and performances over time. Different maintenance techniques were developed in the latest decades to better preserve system capabilities during its life cycle, minimizing the failure, preserving its integrity and performances over time rate and downtime. All these actions can be summarized as follows, *Turan et al. (2009)*:

- Corrective maintenance;
- Scheduled preventive maintenance;
- Performance-based maintenance.

Moreover, during the ship life, it may happen that it is necessary to provide for vessel evolution and adaptation due to new needs or working contest, including for example the extension of its working life; in addition, the obsolescence of technology onboard and the relevant urgency to provide the renewal with innovative technology is another possible area of intervention, that may profit from an original lifecycle perspective of the project. For naval ships, all the maintenance issues mentioned above are very relevant, but the two latest aspects are vital.

An emerging topic is the attention to the latest part of the ship life i.e., the dismantling phase.

The circular economy is more and more identified as an alternative to the traditional linear economy and it is strictly related to remanufacturing and recycling of the ship and its components.

There are several options, *Jansson (2016)*, for the End-of-Life phase beside disposal, that is when the object is not considered as useful and therefore it becomes a waste to be disposed-off. They are:

- reusing, which is the simple reuse of a product with no modifications;
- recycling, which deals with the extraction of a product's raw materials for use in new products;
- remanufacturing, that is a series of manufacturing steps acting on an End-of-Life part or product to return it to like-new.

In a circular economy perspective, disposal (e.g., ship dismantling) represents the least favourable option, since it only generates waste. On the other hand, remanufacturing, reusing and recycling in particular, when already taken into consideration in preliminary phase of ship design, are the best strategies in terms of sustainability. Rulemaking activity is under development in the latest years and, to this purpose, ships recycling criteria are addressed in the Hong Kong Convention developed by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). These covers the design, construction, operation and preparation of ships so as to facilitate safe and environmentally sound recycling, without compromising safety and operational efficiency, *IMO (2009)*. It can also be observed that remanufacturing opportunities are more evident in ship repair activities focused on component level and specific sub-systems, *Jansson (2016)*. In parallel, the EU Ship Recycling Regulation, officially known as Regulation (EU) No 1257/2013, is a law that sets requirements for the safe and environmentally sound recycling of ships. It applies to all ships flying the flags of EU member states, as well as ships registered in third countries that call at ports in the European Economic Area (EEA).

Quantifying and predicting End-of-Life costs, revenues and environmental impact of a ship, during the design phase, is difficult and rather far to be state of the art. This is also because ships are among the most complex systems built by humans, especially in the case of passenger ships and navy ships. The development of DT could increment the profitability of this sector, enabling the application of the concepts of circular economy, beside the support to manage the end-of-life phase of ships that at present is considered only as a problem.

In the following section, a discussion about why naval vessel stakeholders may need a DT model is opened. Possible application examples, that justify the development of a DT, are suggested as well.

4. The Digital Twin as a silver-bullet?

The purpose of this paper is to discuss why a DT could be helpful in the specific field of naval vessels. The analysis in the “problem domain” in fact shall always anticipate the discussion and the decisions in the “solution domain”. Digitalization is a tool and not a final aim.

As first step, to better understand the why, the peculiarity of naval ships when compared to merchant ships is critical. In the following, main distinctive points of naval vessels are considered:

- a) The Payload – Weapon systems together with C4ISR (Command, Control, Communications, Computers, Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance) technology are the main items of naval vessels payload. The comprehensive ship performance is based on a strong connection among the different systems and in turn with the ship platform. It is not just a matter of weight and volume but the interference among systems is critical.
- b) The performance – The capability of the ship to fulfil the mission is based on the ship characteristics and its interaction with environment on a specific scenario, definitely different than the carriage of goods and people over the seas.
- c) The integrated activity – A naval ship is likely to coordinate with a fleet and other defence asset.
- d) The different levels for the decision making – Different decision makers are involved in the operational and technical decisions about the ship, as a single vessel and as a part of a comprehensive defence organization.
- e)

Fig.2: The role of DT model as a supporting tool of the whole ship life cycle

With respect to these issues, as anticipated in the previous section, a DT model may become a fundamental tool to support the implementation of a Life Cycle approach within the naval industry, Fig.2. Because of its peculiar characteristics, a DT model may take advantage of a dual-use, i.e., as big data collector or as forecasting model. The former is ensured through the potentially huge data recorded by the sensor network arranged on board. The latter is provided by the simulation tools constituting the DT model which may be continuously updated and refined on the basis of real-time information.

The big data collector feature of the DT enables the adoption of a datacentric approach. The datacentric framework is able to provide data recorded on the real ship in operations and to derive relevant knowledge (why) for decision making support on the following aspects:

- performance (based on an agile integration between vessel and payload);
- operational decision support (short term and long term);
- reliability, maintainability, availability of the ship and the whole fleet;
- energy efficiency;
- cost/benefit analysis;
- usability (also in a training perspective);
- upgrade of technology onboard necessary for obsolescence or capability update.

The examples listed above are mainly focused on the operational side of the vessel's Life Cycle, however the need of a DT model can be found also in the design phase. The decision-making activity during the ship design process needs to be supported by quantitative evaluations, properly projected over the whole ship lifetime range. Therefore, the decision-making process resembles more the integration of solutions addressing singular sub-problems than a comprehensive approach, relying on a superposition principle to synthesize the best possible design. Each sub-problem tackled in the design stages requires the development of a virtual prototype having a different level of complexity on the basis of the topic. To transform these virtual prototypes (built in the design stages) to a DT model, a real-time connection between the virtual and the real environment is needed. It means that a radio-communication system and a sensors network should be present on board the vessel. Especially the latter may become a crucial issue in the accurate functioning of the DT model. The installation of sensors on the vessel during the building phase should be planned ahead in order to collect the data necessary for the desired services and not the opposite, i.e., the choice of the services on the basis of the available data. For these reasons, the DT model has to be developed in the perspective to fulfil the needs of the final users. Therefore, a strict collaboration is required among the tool developer, the shipbuilder and the operators, *Erikstad (2019)*.

Riding the stream of a service-oriented design process, the importance of a DT model rises and rises. A DT can be used to optimize the ship Life Cycle management: it may track modifications or replacements evaluating their impact on the vessel both during the design and the operating phases. Other known applications justifying the development of a DT model are the improvement of predictive maintenance and the support in the decision-making activity. Another relevant aspect enabled by the DT model is the risk reduction capability: the DT can be used to simulate dangerous scenario and find the solutions minimizing the risk of failure (what-if analysis), e.g., to carry on an operation or manoeuvre within extreme environmental conditions which are not accounted for in the design phase. In conclusion, the DT may provide an efficient and various support in the form of added-value services, Fig.3.

Fig.3: The DT as a provider of added-value services through the ship life cycle

What above can answer to the question about “why” a DT should be considered as an interesting tool to improve the competitiveness of naval ships in the next future. Nevertheless, there are some downsides or at least some points of attention that need to be considered:

- Property of data – It is still a significant issue when implementing a DT. At the same time also the property of knowledge deriving from data is to be discussed;
- Integration of previous tools of digitation and digitalization – As already mentioned, in the latest decades some initiatives toward digitalization have already taken place, with a unilateral approach; with DT a comprehensive and wide view is necessary in time and space to empower the tool. This may be discouraging and this is the reason why it is important to have the clear idea about the final aim;
- Security – A robust approach in terms of cyber security is necessary to counteract the vulnerability due to the data generation, storage and exchange.
- Deep change of attitude – The mindset entailed by a DT is collaborative and connected; domains accustomed to live independently are requested to strongly interact.

The definition of “what is DT” is given in the previous sections and how it is supposed to work are strongly influenced by the points of attention raised above. As far as naval ships are concerned the property of data and the cybersecurity appear to be the most relevant aspects to be attentively considered while developing the technical specification of a DT, especially in the naval ship field.

5. Conclusions

The digital transformation, also in the shipbuilding domain, will be the completion of previous phases such as digitization and digitalization of ship design and operations. Until now, the design decision making process has barely supported the whole life cycle perspective. Nevertheless, it is expected that digital transformation can entail such ambitious target, enabling a change of mind attitudes and way of doing things. McKinsey defines digital transformation as “an effort to enable existing business models by integrating advanced technologies”. Basically, it allows digital technologies to be integrated into already existing business models, changing the way you operate and deliver your product or service.

A first step in this direction, can be the DT that can link all the different phases of ship life cycle thanks to a strong source of information given by data recorded onboard during operational ship profile and properly treated to increment knowledge and decision making in the short and long term. What above could in principle support a strong change toward circular economy and sustainable development.

Based on such premises the paper has focused on the field of naval ships, trying to tailorize in this domain the reasons for a DT and its implementation modality and characteristics.

However, even though more and more attentions are paid to DT, it cannot be suddenly considered a “silver bullet”, the easy solution to a whatsoever problem. Its implementation requires significant effort in terms of time and resources, possibly in a rather long-time frame. This is the reason why it is of outstanding importance a thorough discussion about the actual needs, i.e., the reasons why the DT is worth enforcing.

For the peculiar needs of a naval ship as a defence asset, a DT implementation seems to be even more urgent and likely to be successful than in other shipbuilding field. Nevertheless, the same peculiar aspect of the ship operational profile asks for a superior attention especially in the terms of vulnerability due to connectivity and dependence on data.

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Design of a Heterogeneous Information Platform for the Acquisition and Processing of Relevant Data for Autonomous Operation on Inland Waterways

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Abstract

The major goal of this study is the development of new concepts of near-field detection to improve automation in inland navigation. For this purpose, a ship-specific sensor system has been designed and implemented to acquire time synchronous information sources. The system is composed of the following heterogeneous sensors, which were integrated within a demonstrator: RTK-GNSS receiver with antenna (high-precision corrected satellite positioning), lidar sensors (light detection and ranging), camera, inertial measuring unit, AIS receiver (automatic identification system). For autonomous operation, real-time processing of those data streams is necessary for safe localization and navigation of the vessel in an urban environment. Through multiple validation processes of the demonstrator, the integration of the acquired environmental data with already available propulsion and energy data will be performed on the research and thruster vessel ELEKTRA.

1. Introduction

The advancing automation of technical applications already allows the substitution of humans by machines in specific areas. This process of change can also be seen within inland shipping, so that questions arise regarding the maintenance of the safety level as well as possible concerns related to the level of automation. To enable the autonomous operation of a ship, it is necessary to have safe, stable and redundant measurements of system-internal and system-external variables.

To guarantee a safe autonomous operation, partly redundant sensors are merged to eliminate potential weaknesses of each sensor and to improve the robustness of the system. The elaborated system consists of heterogeneous sensors. The sensor system is initially installed in the laboratory on a prototype and then prepared for tests in real operation. The following requirements apply to the measurement:

- Highly accurate determination of position, location and speed
- Mobile optical traffic detection in combination with existing AIS data

The most important components of the sensor system can be found in Table I. The sensors are managed via a central computer unit. For this purpose, an Ubuntu Pro 22.04 LTS server was used to set up the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework. The used ROS version is Humble Hawksbill, LTS 2025.

The demonstrator system is initially intended to provide information of the behaviour of the lidar sensors installed on a moving ship. For this purpose, the concept of data management as well as the data fusion of all sensor components is described and implemented into the ROS Framework. A workspace is set up in which all required packages are installed. Besides of internal ROS packages, it includes packages for the overall description, lidar, <https://www.blickfeld.com/resources/>, camera, <https://github.com/basler/pylon-ros-camera/tree/humble>, AIS, https://github.com/ecschuetz/ros_ais/tree/ros2, <https://github.com/schwehr/libais>, Dual Antenna A10 RTK-GNSS, https://github.com/septentrio-gnss/septentrio_gnss_driver/tree/ros2, U-Blox RTK-GNSS, <https://github.com/tomojitakasu/RTKLIB>, <https://github.com/KumarRobotics/ublox/tree/ros2>, SLAM, <https://github.com/ros2/cartographer>.

Table I: Components of sensor system

Components	ID	Description	Pieces
Lidar	Blickfeld Cube1 / Range 1	Lidar based on MEMS	4
Camera	Basler a2A2590-22gcPRO	IMX334 ROI CMOS sensor 22fps with 5.1MP resolution	1
Objective lens	Basler Lens C125-0418-5M-P	Focal length of 4.0mm Aperture range from F1.8 - F22 5MP resolution	1
GNSS Receiver	A10-RTK mosaic-h	Mutli-band dual Antenna GNSS receiver	1
GNSS Receiver	u-blox ZED-F9P	Multi-band GNSS receiver	1
GNSS Antenna	u-blox ANN-MB-00	L1/L2 multi-band GPS; GLONASS, Galileo, BeiDou	3
AIS Receiver	Digital Yachts AIS100	Dual-Band Receiver with NMEA 0183 Output	1
AIS Antenna	Banten Small VHF AIS	156-162Mhz	1
Embedded PC	ThinkEdge SE30	Intel® Core™ i5-1145GRE Ubuntu Server 22.04 16 GB RAM	1
Industrial Ethernet Switch	Phoenix Contact 2702665 FL SWITCH 2105	Managed Switch, 5 Ethernet Ports, 1000Mbit/s	1
Camera Casing	Colibri S29	Enclosure for cameras up to 30 x 30 mm cross section IP66	1
Casing	BOX 685.011	Weatherproof plastic casing IP55 46 x 38 x 13cm	1
Mounting		Aluminium profile	1

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Integration Patterns

The communication within the sensor system as well as the integration in existing external systems require a certain robustness of the data exchange, in order to meet the requirements. It can be assumed that connections of a network may be unreliable or slow. Thus, it can lead to delays or interruptions in the individual segments (LAN segments, switches, routers, public networks, satellite connections).

Furthermore, the components of the sensor system should appear in an individual program. This makes it easier to expand or change a component and other modifications can be carried out more easily. The system must be able to understand different programming languages and support different operating systems.

The management of the processes is provided by an additional program, the message-oriented middleware (MOM), provided by OMG's Data Distribution Service (DDS) RTI Connext DDS. The communication between sender and receiver is generated via a message channel. This is a publish-subscribe channel, *Hohpe and Woolf (2009)*. The principle is illustrated in Fig.1. The Publishers publish a message in the message channel. A copy of the message is then forwarded to each output channel (subscriber). This makes it possible for debugging processes to listen to a message channel without interrupting the existing connections. The possibility to listen to existing message channels can be a disadvantage for security reasons. Consequently, subscribing to a message channel should be restricted by security guidelines, *Hohpe and Woolf (2009)*.

Fig.1: Publish-subscribe channel - message channel that transmits a copy of a message to each recipient (subscriber), *Hohpe and Woolf (2009)*

2.2. Subsections of the overall system

To demonstrate a combined use of the available data sources after an exemplary data acquisition, data fusion-based procedures are presented. The design of the demonstrator system can be divided into four functional layers:

- **Information sources** - Describes all sources fed to the system from local sensors like camera, lidar and an inertial measurement unit as well as external components such as satellites, a mobile data link and a VHF radio link.
- **Hardware platform** - The central component of the demonstrator system is a single computer, which provides the computing capacity as well as the interfaces of all components provided. The first synchronizations are based on communication protocols between platform and sensors.
- **Middleware** - The presented middleware is used to synchronize the individual data streams. It provides the temporal context for the individual modules and it transfers time stamps to all messages. Within the middleware software packages can be used to add various functions to the system. This primarily involves the provision of the sensor messages in a generally freely accessible standard, as well as further complex software modules, which enables processing of the raw data.

- **Human-Machine interaction** - For higher-quality data products, resulting from data fusion and data processing of different sensor components, software packages can provide visualizations of the results. Based on the open-source structure, many already established visualization programs can be used. In the elaboration, the potential is first presented in a development environment and then partly approved in a real-time environment.

2.3. System Design

The assembly consists of a control cabinet and a base plate, which can be mounted on a tripod or directly on the roof of a ship, Fig.2. To enable the system to be expanded or adapted, the design is as modular as possible.

The components presented below are designed to be independent of each other, so that the control cabinet and base plate can be adapted or exchanged as required. The base plate is used to define the geometrical alignment of the sensors. For this purpose, a CAD model was created to define lidar mounts and exact drill holes for the GNSS antennas. The left and the right lidar sensor is aligned to the front with a 35° angle to the longitudinal axis. The maximum field of view for all three lidars data streams is 140° in horizontal and 30° in vertical.

Fig.2: Overall set up of the demonstrator system - sensor box on a tripod (left side) and directly mounted on the superstructure of ELEKTRA's deckhouse (right side)

The arrangement of the sensor components is transferred within the ROS system into a Unified Robot Description Format (URDF). This is an XML format for the representation of a robot model with translation and rotation offsets of each sensor.

Fig.3 illustrates the assembly of the hardware components. The communication infrastructure forms the basis for the transmission and processing of heterogeneous data streams. Different data transmission methods are used depending on the component. The infrastructure in which the test measurements take place must provide a stable and robust data connection for the data transfer over mobile broadband and for detecting satellite signals and ais information of other ships. Within the system, a constant power supply must be assumed to operate the components without malfunctions. All connected devices are running on a 24V power supply with less than 3 A in total consumption.

Fig.3: Conception of the system structure of all hardware components for the test run on ELEKTRA

We present an approach for selectively integrating data from various ROS2 Humble topics with the existing propulsion and energy data of ELEKTRA in the external hosted Influx database, while considering real-time applications and the need for a direct connection between the two systems. This is achieved using RTI Connex DDS middleware and the Telegraf client, <https://github.com/rticommunity/telegraf>, for seamless communication and streamlined data management, and by considering data importance and database storage constraints.

Our methodology involves configuring the ROS2 Humble environment to generate the required data and selecting relevant data topics based on their importance to the system and storage capacity. Examples of such topics include NavSatFix, AIS position reports, and SLAM trajectory data. RTI Connex DDS middleware is employed to translate native ROS2 messages into a format compatible with the Telegraf client.

For each selected data stream, separate XML configuration files are created for the DDS DataReaders. These files define the type registration, QoS library, domain library, and domain participant library for each data stream. The QoS profiles are based on the built-in Generic.StrictReliable profiles, ensuring reliable data transmission over both UDPV4 and shared memory (SHMEM) transport protocols. The domain libraries configure domains with unique domain IDs and register the respective data types and topics. Finally, the domain participant libraries establish subscribers with data readers to receive the data streams from the specified topics.

The Telegraf client is configured with `inputs.dds_consumer` sections, specifying the XML configuration file path, DDS Participant configuration, and DDS DataReader configuration for each data stream. The `name_override` parameter is employed to assign a custom name to each measurement stored in InfluxDB.

By using these configurations, the Telegraf client is able to receive selected data streams from ROS2 Humble through the RTI Connex DDS middleware and store them into an InfluxDB instance alongside ELEKTRA's existing propulsion and energy data. This comprehensive data integration enables further analysis, visualization, and decision-making based on a rich set of information while taking storage constraints and data significance into account.

For real-time applications, a direct and local connection between the energy and propulsion system of ELEKTRA and the integrated data from ROS2 Humble is necessary. This can be achieved through the implementation of an OPC UA Gateway, which stands for Object Linking and Embedding for Process Control Unified Architecture. OPC UA is a widely used communication protocol in industrial automation and data exchange, providing a secure and standardized data exchange platform. The OPC UA Gateway, currently under development, will serve as a bridge between the various systems, enabling real-time data exchange and further enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the overall system.

The proposed approach demonstrates the effective integration of ROS2 Humble, RTI Connex DDS, Telegraf, and InfluxDB to create a reliable and efficient data streaming pipeline for robotics and automation applications. With the potential for real-time data exchange through the future implementation of an OPC UA Gateway, this system promises even greater connectivity and performance.

2.4. Processing Methods

Relevant information can be extracted from raw camera and lidar data, considering a highly accurate determination of position, attitude and velocity, in order to develop suitable methods for the creation of semantic, high-resolution maps for inland waterways. The procedures described below were used for the evaluation.

2.4.1 Object Detection

The object recognition of essential infrastructure, navigation signs and other vessels on an inland waterway is generated within the images using the YOLOv4 algorithm, *Bochkovskiy et al. (2020)*. YOLOv4 is composed of two parts, a backbone which is pre-trained on a labelled data set of images on inland waterways, https://app.roboflow.com/bewa/bewa_23082022/8, and a head which is used to predict the trained classes on a given image. The Training Set includes four classes, Fig.4, to predict bridges, bollards, other boats and a traffic sign to show the boundaries of the waterway under bridges. As the pre-trained data set only includes a very small number of labelled images, predictions are only reliable in the demonstrated real laboratory.

Fig.4: Bounding Boxes of labelled classes

2.4.2 Calibration of lidar and camera sensors

To calibrate lidar points with image correspondences, OpenCV's PnP RANSAC, Marchand et al. (2016), is used to find the rotation and translation transforms. The chosen PnP Method uses for

refinement a non-linear Levenberg-Marquardt minimization scheme, *Madsen et al. (2004)*, *Eade (2013)*.

The corresponding points in each lidar and camera frame were manually set based on a calibration record. For each lidar sensor, the corresponding Euler angles and translation offsets were calculated based on the corresponding points by using the described perspective projection model and the camera intrinsic parameters. To display all three different lidar streams inside the camera frame, the calculated transformation matrix for each lidar sensor with the camera stream is used with 'project3dToPixel' from the ROS image_geometry library, http://docs.ros.org/en/diamondback/api/image_geometry/html/c++/classimage_geometry_1_1PinholeCameraModel.html. It is the inverse of 'projectPixelTo3dRay'. For given lidar points inside a rectangle of an identified Object, the inverse could be used to detect the measured distance of each object.

2.4.3 Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM)

In addition to the RTK-GNSS position determination, a trajectory is determined using the lidar measurements and the RTK-GNSS within a real-time loop closure in 2D, *Hess et al. (2016)*. The SLAM method can be divided into a global and a local SLAM, Fig.4: Within the local SLAM, a defined amount of consecutive point clouds is merged after pre-filtering and added to a submap. Inside the Global SLAM constrains between the submaps were calculated and adjusted with positioning information of the RTK-GNSS. Finally, the extrapolation of all positions of the created submaps can be carried out. The output of the procedure is a calculated trajectory of the route.

Fig.4: 2D SLAM process, divided into a local and global SLAM, (based on https://google-cartographer-ros.readthedocs.io/en/latest/algorithm_walkthrough.html)

2.4.4. Real-time SLAM Configuration and Data Integration

Overall, the preprocessed SLAM configuration is better suited for processing larger datasets and generating more accurate maps but is less focused on real-time performance. On the other hand, the real-time SLAM configuration is optimized for real-time operation, allowing for faster updates and more responsiveness during mapping and localization tasks.

The configuration of the Cartographer SLAM algorithm for real-time operation involves utilizing a launch file that initializes Cartographer nodes, remaps input topics, and configures parameters for the algorithm and the Unified Robot Description Format (URDF), an XML format that describes the geometrical alignment of the sensors.

The algorithm is configured using a Lua configuration file that specifies parameters for map and trajectory builders, laser scans, point clouds, optimization, and pose graph settings.

The real-time SLAM configuration enables mapping and localization tasks to be performed effectively and efficiently. The generated SLAM data can be used for navigation, obstacle detection, and decision-making. The real-time aspect ensures a high degree of responsiveness and accuracy.

During the execution of the SLAM process, the `robot_state_publisher` node publishes the state of the robot, the `cartographer_node` processes the sensor data and generates the SLAM data, and the `cartographer_occupancy_grid_node` publishes the occupancy grid map representation of the environment. The generated SLAM data can be integrated with other data streams of ELEKTRA, using the previously described data pipeline, which involves RTI Connex DDS middleware, Telegraf, and InfluxDB. The integration process requires selecting relevant SLAM data topics, such as the robot's pose or the generated occupancy grid map, and configuring the RTI Connex DDS middleware to translate the native ROS2 messages into a format compatible with the Telegraf client. This integration allows for a comprehensive and synchronized view of the collected data, facilitating further analysis and decision-making based on a rich set of information.

2.5. Measurement runs

Two measurement runs were performed in a real laboratory in the area of the Berlin Westhafen (Charlottenburger Verbindungskanal <-> Westhafen Kanal). For the measurement runs, the demonstrator system was set up on the bow of an inland cargo ship. The route of the measurement run can be seen in Fig.5. A single trip covers about 2.49 km. For the evaluation and analysis of the results, only one measurement run was taken for further analysis.

Fig.5: Track on the Ursus heavy lift barge between Charlottenburger Verbindungskanal and Westhafen in Berlin

In addition, further measurement runs, Fig.6, were performed on the thruster Vessel ELEKTRA to merge the data streams with the available propulsion and energy data of the ship. A first synchronization between the ship internal information sources and the presented system was tested through the Influx Database. Furthermore, the prepared SLAM method could be tested in real time.

Fig.6: Measurement tracks on the vessel thruster ELEKTRA between Spandau and Westhafen in Berlin

3. Results

3.1. Localization and Mapping

Due to the described SLAM process, the field of view of the sensors was large enough to detect both sides of the waterway boundary over long distances. The device passed a total of three bridges during one trip. When passing a bridge, there are major inaccuracies in the position determination by RTK-GNSS. The reason for this is, on the one hand, the intermediate disconnection of the mobile radio connection as well as the loss of some satellite connections. It became apparent from the measurement runs that if the connection is lost, it takes several minutes for the position determination to get back into the range of less than 3 cm accuracy. For an exact localization at these critical points, it is advisable to use an alternative correction, for example via lidar distance measurements.

Fig.7: 2D SLAM Cartographer – created map from lidar point clouds, *Hess et al. (2016)*

The visualization of the calculated trajectory, just by the lidar distance measurements, can be seen in Fig.7. It shows the calculated trajectory in comparison to the GNSS trajectory for the section under the highlighted bridge. The trajectory of the SLAM calculation for the section under consideration is a significantly better approximation to the driven trajectory. However, there are also areas in which only few or no points at all were detected by the lidar sensors. This results in a misleading SLAM trajectory, seen in the highlighted red circle in Fig.7.

In order to adjust the trajectory, it is therefore necessary to include further sensor components in the calculation. For the optimization of the map of Fig.7, the position determination of the GNSS module is included in the global SLAM procedure, Figs.8 and 9.

The individual sensor messages can be weighted differently for the creation of the trajectory. Figure 8 shows the created map with high weighting of the GNSS position determination. In comparison to Figure 9, the misleading SLAM trajectory could be fixed by the RTK-GNSS. On the downside, at the bridge crossings, distortions can be seen within the map because of inaccurate RTK-GNSS at those sections. (See small highlighted red circles in Fig.8).

Fig.8: 2D SLAM Cartographer – with GNSS position correction, *Hess et al. (2016)*

Fig.8: 2D SLAM Cartographer – with GNSS position correction, *Hess et al. (2016)*

In comparison to this, Fig.9 shows a higher weighting of the lidar distance measurement. The inclusion of the GNSS module brings a better represented trajectory in general. However, in case of loss of the lidar source, a deterioration of the generated map can be seen. The marked location shows, that due to the loss of both sources (lidar and GNSS) the calculation needs more sensor messages to be able to create a reliable map. Thus, in both variants' errors are present within the map, because the sensor messages are not without disturbances over the whole distance.

Fig.9: 2D SLAM Cartographer – with GNSS position correction, positions of lidar points are higher weighted, *Hess et al. (2016)*

To reduce disturbances, an Attitude and Heading Reference System (AHRS) by integrating gyroscopes and fusing this data with accelerometer and magnetometer from the IMU would be advantageous, as it ensures the orientation of the demonstrator system at error-prone locations. Since the calibration of the magnetometer for the location at the bow of the heavy lift barge was not successful, calculations depending on the magnetometer cannot be used in further analysis. Another possibility would be to extend the range of view of the distance measurements by adding more lidar sensors and thus minimize the probability of loss of information.

3.2. Object Classification and localization

The classification of individual objects takes place via the pre-trained model using the YOLOv4 algorithm. One sample frame of the record, Fig.10, shows the integrated object detection with calibrated lidar points inside the image frame. The number beside the class names shows the uncertainty of the object detection as a value between 0 and 1. Furthermore, it shows the detection for the Bridge, the two A.10 navigation marks and two bollards. By integrating the lidar points inside the classified object rectangle, it is possible to extract individual areas of the point cloud for the desired objects to make statements about the distance of the classified object. Nevertheless, wrong predictions from the classification process lead to incorrect information processing, like the shown reflection of the navigation mark on the water surface. Therefore, a threshold for uncertainty of the object detection needs to be considered for further proceedings.

Fig.11 illustrate a passing ship and its object detection. At longer distances, only a few lidar measurements can be seen due to the poor reflective properties of the passing ship. In contrast, the traffic sign with good reflective properties on the highway behind the waterway can be clearly seen in the lidar measurements, although it is much further away. To further use the small point cloud of the ship, object detection within the camera image can be very helpful to classify these point clouds.

Fig.10: Integrated object detection and calibrated lidar points for precise object localization

Fig.11: Object detection of a passing ship with attached lidar points

4. Discussion

In this study, a novel system for mapping and localization of objects in inland waterways is presented, integrating data from various sensors, including lidar, cameras, GNSS, and AIS, and combining it with ELEKTRA's propulsion and energy data. The system leverages a 2D SLAM algorithm for trajectory

generation and the YOLOv4 algorithm for object classification and localization in camera images, demonstrating the effectiveness of fusing multiple sensor data to provide a comprehensive situational picture around a ship.

The mobile demonstrator developed in this study offers a reusable and expandable platform to support sensor-based technical assistance systems. It showcases the potential of lidar-based measurements, GNSS positioning, and SLAM-based localization for navigation and trajectory determination, with the possibility of refining the SLAM approach by adjusting the weights of RTK-GNSS and lidar data based on signal reliability.

A critical aspect of the system design is the selective integration of data from ROS2 Humble topics with ELEKTRA's existing data in InfluxDB, addressing real-time applications and the need for a direct connection between the two systems. The data integration approach, which involves the use of RTI Connex DDS middleware and Telegraf client, highlights the potential for real-time data exchange through the future implementation of an OPC UA Gateway. This would establish a direct and local connection between ELEKTRA's energy and propulsion systems and the integrated data from ROS2 Humble, further enhancing the system's efficiency and effectiveness.

Future improvements to the system could include incorporating an Attitude and Heading Reference System (AHRS) to improve orientation, extending the range of view of distance measurements by adding more lidar sensors, and refining the object detection algorithm to enhance accuracy and robustness. Furthermore, by enhancing high-definition maps with SLAM-generated maps, a virtual twin of the real environment could be created for advanced simulations of autonomous processes on inland waterways.

This study's innovative approach to data integration, using ROS2 Humble, RTI Connex DDS, Telegraf, and InfluxDB, presents a reliable and efficient data streaming pipeline for robotics and automation applications. The system's performance, combined with the potential improvements and future developments, demonstrates its value for practical applications in the field of inland waterway navigation and object localization.

Future research in the real laboratory Spree-Oder-Wasserstraße (SOW) will allow for an extension of the dataset, paving the way for additional measurement runs and the generation of new data sets within the test field. This work serves as a stepping stone for further developments in the domain of inland waterway navigation and autonomous processes, with the potential to greatly impact the field of robotics and automation applications.

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Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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OCX Standard and Structural Model Reuse in the Shipbuilding Design

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Abstract

The Open Class 3D Model Exchange standard shows excellent capabilities for model-based approval, which is the ultimate goal of the standard. But could the OCX standard be used further to meet the challenge of enabling seamless model migration between different software solutions for design in shipbuilding? Could an existing structural 3D model be efficiently reused in another software using the OCX standard? In this paper, a 3D model will be transferred between NAPA and CATIA SFD using the OCX standard. The transfer quality and required post-processing time will be evaluated. Finally, the potential for model reuse with the OCX standard will be estimated.

1. Introduction

The reuse of existing 3D models is important in shipbuilding for several reasons. Shipbuilding projects can be complex and time-consuming, involving the collaboration of multiple teams and departments. Reusing existing 3D models can streamline the design and construction process, reducing the time and resources required to create new models from scratch. This can ultimately lead to cost savings and faster project completion times. Ships are often built in series or families, with multiple vessels of similar design being constructed. Reusing existing 3D models can help ensure consistency across these vessels, reducing the risk of errors and improving overall quality. It can also simplify the process of modifying or updating the design.

Shipbuilding involves the integration of numerous systems and components, such as propulsion, electrical, and HVAC systems. Reusing existing 3D models can help ensure that these systems are properly integrated and fit together seamlessly, reducing the risk of errors and improving overall performance. Overall, the reuse of existing 3D models is an important strategy for improving efficiency, reducing costs, and ensuring quality in shipbuilding.

The development of the Open Class 3D Exchange (OCX) standard allows shipbuilders and class societies to engage in a fully digital workflow and sharing of the designer's 3D model. This resulted from the combined efforts of the classification society DNV and the CAD/CAM software providers. (Standard [OCXwiki] 2022). The use of the OCX standard in data transfer between programs has been tested in the diploma thesis: 3D - MODEL DATA TRANSFER OF SHIP HULL STRUCTURE FEATURES BETWEEN CAD PROGRAMS. The investigation thoroughly analyzed the structural model data transferred from NAPA Designer to CATIA-SFD using the AITAC add-on tool. It is imperative to note that AITAC partners with Dassault Systemes to develop this addon, which is ongoing and is yet to offer an all-inclusive solution for importing and exporting OCX-format files to and from the CATIA Structural Functional Design (SFD) application module.

Local FE-model analyses are becoming increasingly necessary to gain approval for complex ships. However, the process of modeling and meshing structural geometry takes much work. Therefore, more efficient modeling and analysis methods are required. 3D steel models are available but not fully utilized for FEM. As the model transferred with the OCX standard contains almost native geometric primitives and structural metadata, it also brings new possibilities for FEM.

In the thesis, a methodology was developed to assess the quality and requirements of transfer. This article uses the same method to evaluate the OCX-standard content, OCX-model samples, and their transfers to CATIA-SFD and FEM.

The potential of OCX to achieve a commendable level of transfer quality has been proven through extensive work, highlighting that the further you want to take the transfer, the more difficult it is to achieve a perfect native transfer. For this project, the intention is to question the validity of the OCX standard and explore its application for the pre-detail design (preDD) phase. How does the modeling method affect the transfer quality? What are the limits of the current OCX standard when talking about transferring a 3D model just before the preDD phase?

This work is a continuation of the research questions raised in the diploma thesis: Would OCX be suitable elsewhere in the Shipbuilding industry, such as FEM? Is the OCX capable of being taken all the way down to production? What kind of savings can be achieved with OCX standard? Our research aims to address the current limitations of the OCX standard, specifically in the preDD phase, and propose enhancements to the OCX schema. The work is limited to the case study, where the transfer is done from NAPA Designer to CATIA SFD and Femap. When evaluating other OCX exports, models found in the OCX consortium are used.

2. Evaluation Method

The approach outlined in this text was crafted as a result of extensive research conducted in the master's thesis. First, the examined criteria are defined by a team of design experts, after which a point is selected in the process where the data transfer is carried out. The criteria are then scored by the experts taking into account the transfer point. The evaluation options were from 1 to 5. One was rated as not needed, and five as must-have. The points given by the experts for each criterion have been summed together, and the weight value has been calculated from them.

The quality of the transfer is evaluated according to Brière-Côté's solution domain table shown in Fig.1. First, the level of cardinality was to be defined, which in this case was a transfer from one software to another, resulting in a cardinality level of 1 – to – 1. Second, the degree of detail was to be evaluated according to its intended use. In the diploma thesis, this resulted in a simple evaluation table shown in Table I. The evaluation table is strict but gives a good understanding of the transfer quality.

Each criterion has its subcriteria with its weight value. The weight value for each criterion is a result of a combined filled form by the experts from the Meyer group. The complete criteria table with its weight values is presented in Fig.2. The evaluation of the STEP standard, OCX standard, sample OCX files, and OCX transfer to CATIA SFD and Femap has been carried out by a team with mixed expertise in basic and detailed structural design, FEM, and software development.

Fig.1: Relationship between the needed amount of information and cardinality using solution domains and fundamental operations, (Brière-Côté et al. (2012), pp. 771–794)

Table I: The evaluation table, *Gusani (2022)*

Hierarchy	Does not transfer	Transfers partially	Transfers perfectly
	0	1	2
Geometry	Does not transfer	Dummy geometry transferred only	Transferred as a native geometry
	0	1	2
Metadata	Does not transfer	Dummy metadata transferred only	Transferred as a native metadata
	0	1	2
Accuracy	Inaccurate	accurate	
	0	1	
Costs	Low	High	
	1	0	

Table II: Summary of evaluated criteria weights

Criteria	Weight		Criteria	Weight	
	CAD	FEM		CAD	FEM
Hierarchy			Metadata		
Parent-child	4	4	Thickness	5	5
Topology	4	4	Quality	5	5
Name	3	3	Structure type	4	2
Assembly tree	3	3	Profile information	4	4
			Material Side	4	1
Geometry					
Deck	5	5	Accuracy		
Deck Opening	4	4	Weight of the panel (+ -1%)	4	4
Straight Girders and Webs	5	5	Weight of the stiffener (+ -1%)	4	4
Openings on Webs	4	4	Weight of small parts (+ -1%)	4	2
Longitudinals and transversal bulkheads	5	5	Total weight tolerance (+ - 1%)	4	4
Openings on bulkheads	4	4	Center of Gravity tolerance (+ - 1%)	4	4
Curved bulkhead	4	4			
Openings on curved bulkhead	4	4	Costs		
Knuckle panel	4	4	Transfer time	3	3
Seam	3	3	Money (license, development, maintenance costs)	3	3
Stiffener	5	5	Possibility of editing afterwards	5	5
Pillar	5	5	Mesh Quality	-	5
Bracket	3	3			
Profile endcut	2	1			
Cutout (slots)	2	1			
Notch	2	1			

2.1. Evaluation of the OCX standard

Typically, standard exchange formats contain detailed geometric representations of each structural part. In theory, the STEP standard, developed to share also product information, can contain hierarchy and associated metadata, *Chakrabarti and Arora (2021)*, pp.150-151, but so far, there are no working implementations of STEP's functionality in the shipbuilding industry.

Ship-specific OCX standard contains well-structured definitions of structural parts as shown in Fig.2. Ocx:Panel is designed to resemble a physical ship panel, with attributes and child elements that represent important geometric definitions and metadata for structural parts like plates, stiffeners, openings, brackets, and pillars. Additionally, Ocx:DesignView allows users to easily present the typical hierarchy of ship blocks.

Fig.2: Panel principle in OCX-Schema

The OCX schema encompasses all standard geometric primitives and topological boundaries. This enables CAD vendors to export their structural geometry as primitives, which can be utilized to recreate the model in a consuming application. The end result is an optimized structured geometry that serves the intended purpose. The content and capabilities of OCX schema were evaluated based on the OCX documentation, *OCXwiki (2022)*, and schema, *OCX (2023)*. In addition, the accuracy of the evaluation results has been verified by Astrup (in personal communication). Content and capabilities of the STEP standard which is the general standard exchange format, were evaluated based on the experiences and knowledge of the mixed Meyer team members.

2.2. Evaluation of the OCX samples

Practical implementations of the OCX-export were evaluated using the sample models given in the consortium site. OCX – export quality and the preferred way to create the export were examined for each OHCM-midship model. For each OCX sample, the content of model data such as:

- Geometric definitions for surfaces, inner and outer boundaries, and limits
- Structural parts (plates, stiffeners, holes, pillars, brackets)
- Associated metadata (material, profiles, weight)

were listed into nel. Additionally, an OCX-export from Napa Designer of an actual ship project was evaluated. The final evaluation is determined by a team of experts who review the listed content. They also use an OCX-based model and conduct XML investigations on selected items. The model evaluated and data of the samples are shown in Fig.3.

Geometric primitives

Panel	UnBoundedGeometry								OuterContour							
	Cylinder3D	Cone3D	Sphere3D	Extruded Surface	NURBS Surface	Plane3D	SurfaceRef	GridRef	Line3D	NURBS3D	PolyLine3D	Composite Curve3D	Circum Arc3D	Circle3D	Circum Circle3D	Ellipse3D
S.Z.2	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.SB.8.013	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.SB.8.014	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.DK.8.001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.024	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.027	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.028	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.029	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.030	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.038	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.039	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.LB.8.040	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.TB.8.005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.TB.8.027	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.TB.8.040	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.TB.8.053	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
S.TB.8.054	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Structural parts

Panel	plates	stiffeners	edge Reinfcs	pillars	brackets	Panel Hole2D	Panel Inner Contour	Plate Hole2D	Plate Inner Contour	panel Slots	plate Slots	limits
S.DK.8.001	3	39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27
S.LB.8.002	1	16	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.011	1	35	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.012	1	35	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.024	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.027	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.028	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.029	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
S.LB.8.030	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
S.LB.8.038	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.039	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.LB.8.040	1	16	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	4
S.SB.8.013	1	13	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	4
S.SB.8.014	1	13	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	4
S.TB.8.005	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
S.TB.8.027	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4

Fig.3: Sample of data and model evaluated

2.3. Evaluation of OCX transfer to CATIA SFD

The OCX eXchanger add-on for 3DEXPERIENCE – CATIA is an app tool currently in development by AITAC – company, partnering with Dassault Systemes on the mission to provide a fully functional

solution for both importing and exporting OCX-format files to and from the CATIA SFD. This solution is based on CATIA's Automation interface and, in the context of the Importer module, it builds (SFD) structural model in an automated mode, providing the user with direct insight into the process of creating hull structure automatically out of data imported from the input of OCX file.

The evaluation of the AITAC add-on is the same as in the previous work done in the master's thesis. As a difference from the previous evaluation, the evaluated transfer quality is considering the preDD phase, unlike in the master's thesis. During the evaluation conducted for the diploma thesis, AITAC received the lowest score for its absence of NURBS implementation, insufficient pillars, and inadequate structural design. However, the AITAC add-on was already able to transfer 85% of the important criteria as shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4: Transferring capability of crucial capabilities and savings of AITAC add-on during the thesis.

2.4. Evaluation of OCX transfer to FEM

The OCX-to-Femap add-on is a tool package currently in development by a Finnish company called Rapid Structural Design, which is specialized in basic structural design and FEM analysis. The OCX to Femap solution is developed, with Femap's automation interface and NET-framework functionalities. The tool package contains the following functionalities:

- Geometry creation of structures, optimized for FE-meshing
- Tools to modify and add structures
- Tools to mesh created geometry.

Target mesh size of 150x150mm was selected for the evaluation case, from which typical local refinement to 50x50mm mesh size, *IACS (2022)*, was not performed due to time constraints. FE-meshes of evaluated test block of S721-project are presented in Fig.5.

Different FE-meshing approaches were evaluated followingly:

- Expert interview for meshing STEP-geometry
- Case study for meshing in Napa Designer
- Case study for meshing OCX-geometry in Femap.

Fig.5: FE-models created in Femap with OCX-to-Femap toolkit

3. Results

3.1. Result of the evaluation of the OCX standard

The results of the expert review is presented in Table III and Fig.6. The OCX can transfer almost perfectly every criterion with few exceptions, which are discussed in more detail in the analysis. On the other hand, STEP did not manage to reach the maximum score in any category.

Table III: Results for OCX-standard capability.

Criteria	Score		Criteria	Score	
	STEP	OCX		STEP	OCX
Hierarchy			Metadata		
Parent-child	0	2	Thickness	0	2
Topology	0	2	Quality	0	2
Name	2	2	Structure type	0	2
Assembly tree	0	2	Profile information	1	2
			Material Side	0	1
Geometry					
Deck	2	2	Accuracy		
Deck Opening	2	2	Weight of the panel (+ -1%)	0	1
Straight Girders and Webs	2	2	Weight of the stiffener (+ -1%)	0	1
Openings on Webs	2	2	Weight of small parts (+ -1%)	0	1
Straight bulkheads	2	2	Total weight tolerance (+ - 1%)	1	1
Openings on bulkheads	2	2	Center of Gravity tolerance (+ - 1%)	1	1
Curved bulkhead	2	2			
Openings on curved bulkhead	1	1	Costs		
Knuckle panel	2	2	Transfer time	1	1
Seam	2	2	Money (license, development, maintenance costs)	1	1
Stiffener	1	2	Possibility of editing afterwards	0	1
Pillar	1	2	Mesh Quality		
Bracket	1	2			
Profile endcut	1	2			
Cutout (slots)	1	2			
Notch	1	1			

Fig.6: Results for OCX-standard capability

3.2. Result of the evaluation of the OCX samples

Results of expert review are presented in Table IV and Fig.7. In general, all samples produced good quality export. Siemens sample did not contain weight information and therefore received lower score in the accuracy subcriteria. Aveva, on the other hand, managed to transfer the hierarchy subcriteria better than the others. Some geometry criteria could not be evaluated, due to the absence of structural instances of them in the provided samples.

Table IV: Results of OCX-samples

Criteria	Score		Criteria	Score	
	STEP	OCX		STEP	OCX
Hierarchy			Metadata		
Parent-child	0	2	Thickness	1	2
Topology	0	1	Quality	0	2
Name	1	2	Structure type		
Assembly tree	0	0	Profile information	1	2
			Material Side	1	1
Geometry					
Deck	2	2	Accuracy		
Deck Opening	2	2	Weight of the panel (+ -1%)	0	0.8
Straight Girders and Webs	2	2	Weight of the stiffener (+ -1%)	0	0.8
Openings on Webs	2	2	Weight of small parts (+ -1%)	0	0.8
Straight bulkheads	2	2	Total weight tolerance (+ - 1%)	1	1
Openings on bulkheads	2	2	Center of Gravity tolerance (+ - 1%)	1	1
Curved bulkhead	2	2			
Openings on curved bulkhead			Costs		
Knuckle panel	2	2	Transfer time	0	0
Seam	2	2	Money (license, development, maintenance costs	0	0
Stiffener	1	2	Possibility of editing afterwards	0	1
Pillar			Mesh Quality		
Bracket					
Profile endcut					
Cutout (slots)					
Notch					

Fig.7: Results of OCX-samples

3.3. Result of the CATIA SFD import using AITAC add-on

The results of the AITAC add-on compared to the previous work is considerable. If the assessment was done at the same stage and in the same way, the AITAC add-on would receive full marks as shown in Figs.8 and 9.

Fig.8: Result of the AITAC add-on for transferring capabilities and savings if same comparison was made as in thesis.

However, the preDD phase was chosen as the transfer point for this work. In terms of transferring structural data in the preDD phase, the AITAC OCX add-on has already made significant progress by supporting most of the OCX standard interface and therefore got an overall success rate of 90% as can be seen from Table V and Fig.10.

Fig.9: Presenting the improvements compared to the thesis tests. On the left side the failed geometries are shown and on the right side the new results match the native model completely.

Results of the transfer are presented in more detail in Fig.11. The openings are parametric which means that the size and location of the opening and even the opening type can be customized. The profiles and bulkheads are topological. When moving the deck, the stiffeners and bulkheads follow. The profiles can be moved on the plate and the endcuts can be added. It is also possible to move the bulkheads, which also contain the structure type transferred.

Fig.10: Results of the transfer at PreDD phase

Table V: Results of the transfer at PreDD phase

Criteria	Score			Criteria	Score		
	STEP	MW	OCX		STEP	MW	OCX
Hierarchy				Metadata			
Parent-child	0	2	2	Thickness	0	0	2
Topology	0	1	2	Quality	0	0	2
Name	2	2	2	Structure type	0	2	2
Assembly tree	0	1	1	Profile information	0	2	2
				Material Side	0	2	1
Geometry							
Deck	1	0	2	Accuracy			
Deck Opening	1	0	2	Weight of the panel (+ -1%)	0	1	1
Straight Girders and Webs	1	0	2	Weight of the stiffener (+ -1%)	0	1	1
Openings on Webs	1	0	2	Weight of small parts (+ -1%)	0	0	1
Straight bulkheads	1	2	2	Total weight tolerance (+ - 1%)	0	0	1
Openings on bulkheads	1	1	2	Center of Gravity tolerance (+ - 1%)	0	0	1
Curved bulkhead	1	2	2				
Openings on curved bulkhead	1	0	1	Costs			
Knuckle panel	1	2	2	Transfer time	1	0	1
Seam	1	0	2	Money (license, development, maintenance costs)			
Stiffener	1	2	2	Possibility of editing afterwards	0	1	1
Pillar	1	0	2	Mesh Quality			
Bracket	1	0	1				
Profile endcut	1	1	0				
Cutout (slots)	1	1	0				
Notch	1	1	0				

Fig.11. Presenting some of the significant progress made by AITAC

3.4. Result of the OCX transfer to FEM

OCX-to-FEM tool was able to transfer all OCX-geometry to Femap. Napa designer and OCX-to-Femap produced good quality mesh nearly automatically. STEP received low score for many criteria, as these typically require re-modeling before meshing. Results of expert review are presented in the Table VI and Fig.12.

Table 6 Result of the OCX transfer to FEM.

Criteria	Score			Criteria	Score		
	STEP	Napa	OCX		STEP	Napa	OCX
Hierarchy				Metadata			
Parent-child	0	1	2	Thickness	0	2	2
Topology	0	1	1	Quality	0	2	2
Name	2	1	2	Structure type	0	1	1
Assembly tree	0	1	1	Profile information	0	2	2
				Material Side	0	0	0
Geometry							
Deck	2	2	2	Accuracy			
Deck Opening	2	2	2	Weight of the panel (+ -1%)	0	1	1
Straight Girders and Webs	2	2	2	Weight of the stiffener (+ -1%)	0	1	1
Openings on Webs	1	2	2	Weight of small parts (+ -1%)	0	0	0
Straight bulkheads	2	2	2	Total weight tolerance (+ - 1%)	1	1	1
Openings on bulkheads	2	2	2	Center of Gravity tolerance (+ - 1%)	1	1	1
Curved bulkhead	2	2	2				
Openings on curved bulkhead	2	2	2	Costs			
Knuckle panel	1	2	2	Transfer time	1	1	1
Seam	2	2	2	Money (license, development, maintenance costs)	0	0	0
Stiffener	1	2	2	Possibility of editing afterwards	0	1	1
Pillar	1	2	2	Mesh Quality			
Bracket	1	2	1				
Profile endcut	0	0	0				
Cutout (slots)	0	0	0				
Notch	0	0	0				

Fig.12. Result of the OCX transfer to FEM.

4. Analysis

4.1. OCX standard

Based on the evaluation conducted, it is evident that there is a shortage of practical applications for STEP and other standard exchange formats. These formats are limited to transferring only geometric

data, whereas for numerous scenarios, it is imperative to transfer also geometric definitions, hierarchy, and metadata of the transferred model.

Originally intended for plan approval, the OCX standard offers a comprehensive set of objects that are necessary for transferring a typical basic design model. As an addition to bare geometric representation, geometric definitions with related topology, hierarchy and structural metadata are included. Based on the evaluation conducted, it is evident that OCX has capability to transfer structural information in basic design context.

Additionally, OCX has the ability to transfer a significant amount of structural information that is necessary for creating an initial detailed design model. However, certain structural details like notches and material sides are yet to be fully integrated into the OCX-schema. And for curved panels, it would be necessary to have information on the opening protrusion direction. These are acknowledged and are under development by the OCX consortium.

It has been observed that the documentation for OCX is generally well-defined. However, there is room for improvement in terms of providing additional guidance on its intended usage. The Standard offers significant flexibility when it comes to defining structural geometry and openings, which can sometimes lead to confusion and misinterpretation due to the multiple approaches.

4.2. OCX Sample models

Practical implementations on sample models realized well capability of the OCX standard. All the OCX sample models contained more structural information than a typical STEP-transfer. For following criteria OCX samples did not receive full points:

- Topology, as limits were only partially referencing to other panels or surface references
- Assembly tree, as none of the sample models contained implementation of `Ocx:DesignView`
- Material side, as only plate offset is available, which is not sufficient for non-planar base geometries and stiffeners.

It has been noticed that the samples were correct in terms of their content. However, there is room for improvement in the implementation with unified principles, as OCX offers significant flexibility. Varying approaches were noticed for `ocx:UnboundedGeometry`, `ocx:CutBy` and `ocx:PhysicalProperties`.

For `ocx:UnboundedGeometry`, the inclusion of complex geometry and references should be used only when they are truly essential. It would be advisable to prioritize the use of straightforward planar shapes whenever possible, as ship panels and plates are usually limited planes.

`Ocx:PhysicalProperties` contains basic weight information, which can be provided by the exporting application and used as a quality measure by the receiving application to confirm the accuracy of the import. However, when it comes to defining openings and physical properties for panels or plates, there is no clear guidance on how openings should be taken into account when calculating weight.

4.3. AITAC add-on

Importing non-linear curves and curved surfaces has proven to be the greatest challenge for the OCX model to be imported into CATIA. Today's practical standard is the use of NURBS numerical representation of curves and surfaces, so it is included in the OCX standard schema.

There are basically two challenges regarding the above mentioned. One is the proper importing of data with no or minimal loss of precision of transferred data. Currently, NURBS curves definitions are transferred, broken down in segments and imported as a series of Bezier's splines. NAPA exports

simplified NURBS definitions in the form of periodically clamped non-rational NURBS definitions, allowing for recalculation during import without any loss of information or precision. Surface definitions are imported as a series of 4x4 control points surface patches, exported by NAPA in the same manner, ensuring no loss of geometrical precision in the resulting model.

The second challenge is the difference in surface modeling precisions required by NAPA and CATIA. Since NAPA is considerably more tolerant than CATIA, it is highly recommended to import complex geometry objects and prepare, fix, or remodel in CATIA before initiating the OCX structure import. This is especially crucial for the hull form surface. The user would address and map those pre-imported and prepared surfaces when initiating the OCX model import.

The tool, in the import process, tries to retain maximum topological connections between structure elements, providing that those topology data is successfully exported by the authoring application. For items that cannot be successfully topologically connected to a neighboring structure or such information is missing, the tool's algorithm, guided by user-defined fine-adjusting options, makes a maximum effort in order to transfer the needed structure. Failed structure elements containing topological connections remain within the model tree, available for the user to try to enable them for future work, and if successful, the alternative structure element created (without the topology connections) can then be discarded/deleted, while providing all the opening and stiffener elements ready-made and accessible to be copied to the repaired Panel (deck, bulkhead, etc.) The original model and the resulting model are shown in the Fig.13.

Fig.13: The original NAPA Designer model (left) and the transferred file's result (right)

Stiffeners are imported and placed on the respective frame or longitudinal position if their TraceLine (exported by OCX) is found lying on, or parallel to any. Otherwise, stiffeners are placed on the TraceLine geometry object. Also, the trace line is used for placement if the calculated length of the stiffener is found to differ from the length of the trace. In the currently available (NAPA) test cases, the information on the Stiffeners' limitations (limiting objects) could not yet be found.

Improvements compared to the thesis-time development phase:

- Curved lines implemented (polylines approximation only functional then)
- Curved surfaces implemented
- Real free-edge stiffeners implemented
- Parametric standard openings implemented
- Structure types (main categories) implemented
- Stiffeners placed on reference plane raster instead of geometric trace-line objects
- Pillars implemented

In order to optimize the final results of the model transfer between different modeling solutions, some good practices of structure modeling should be established and obeyed as much as possible. To start, the modeling should, as much as possible, resemble the actual shipbuilding technologies of hull structure assembling. The software logic is generally adjusted to the most common practice of manu-

facturing technologies, i.e. primarily considering the logic of building ship structure assemblies. Generally, the OCX standard has these considerations built into its structure logic.

To achieve best results of the model transfer process, it is further very important for modeling approaches used to obey the same rules or customs. The destination modeling environment (e.g. CATIA data setup) should be most carefully prepared according to the client's design standards and in line with design standard used on the source software. As much as possible, also naming of the standard and catalog items should be used to make the transfer easier and faster.

For this case study, the original topology of the NAPA Designer model had to be modified due to its inability to export correct topology when referring to surfaces not located in the steel arrangement. This is discussed with NAPA and shall be added possibly to the next NAPA Designer release.

4.4. OCX-to-FEM

When transferring ship structures into FE-meshing, there are some challenges that need to be overcome. While typical standard geometry transfer can represent the structures accurately, it doesn't result in a continuous mesh that matches the desired size of the geometric details. This means that additional time and effort are required to remodel and idealize the geometry to achieve a good-quality mesh. Another issue is that STEP doesn't include important structural metadata such as thickness, materials, and profiles. Due to these limitations, STEP-based approach received low score for several criteria.

Some structure modeling applications have FE-mesher included, which have access to internal structural definitions and can create geometry optimized for FE-meshing. Napa Designer, used for comparison on this study, produced good quality FE-mesh for initial mesh size of 150x150mm. Further model based details and refinements can be added, before transfer to FE-application. After mesh transfer, detail additions and refinements have to be done on the FE-application used for analysis.

OCX contains standardized primitive geometry definitions and structural metadata. From which geometry suitable for FE-meshing can be created. In this study, OCX-to-Femap was utilized. It created optimized geometry to produce good quality initial mesh, which also had sufficient detail for further refinements to typical 50x50mm mesh. All structural geometries were created, organised, meshed and assigned with correct structural scantlings. The naming of the structural parts was retained to ensure that the geometry of the structural features could be easily recreated during mesh refinements and geometry updates.

In addition to basic geometry transfer, OCX has great potential to automate FE-analysis process, from FE-model creation to repeating FE-analysis with updated structures, ie. openings. As from well structured XML, changes can be identified and implemented onto existing FE-model and analysis can be repeated without additional worksteps. This is particularly advantageous for basic design, where design evolves iteratively and local analyses are initiated before the final door and routing openings are received. It can be stated that OCX contains needed information to transfer ship structural models to FE-modeling applications, as a working implementation of OCX-to-FEM was presented. OCX has further potential for automating FE-analysis with version control and obtaining optimal workflow for iterative basic design.

5. Discussion

Having a single-source-of-truth for a structural model is vital for complex cruise ship designs. However different design tools are needed in different design phases and disciplines, as no software application is capable to manage all tasks from iterative basic design to accurate detail and production design. As designers push the boundaries with fast-evolving basic designs, it becomes increasingly important to have agile structural design applications that can keep up with the design.

A major obstacle to the re-use of basic design models for detail design has been the lack of accuracy of the basic design models and inadequate data transfer. Fortunately, there is now a solution. By elevating the level-of-detail of basic design models, one can attain the required accuracy and have seamless data transfer with OCX.

OCX has shown great potential in theory and in practice. It already contains working implementations to transfer structural models to a sufficient extent for many practical use cases, such as scantling calculations, *Son et al. (2022)*, FE-analysis, plan approval, *NN (2022)*, and detail design. Our teams see OCX as capable of managing all structural transfer needs for our whole basic design phase.

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Can European Shipyards be Smarter? A Proposal from the SEUS Project

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Abstract

Improving the efficiency and competitiveness of European Shipyards is one of the priorities of the HORIZON program, funded by the European Commission. The proper use of computational tools can accelerate this improvement, given that the shipbuilding industry faces a digitalization gap compared to other manufacturing industries. In this context, this paper presents an initial discussion on how European shipyards can make benefits from available tools to achieve this smart label that is currently trending (and needed). Our proposal is based on the incipient Smart European Shipyard (SEUS) project, which aims to bridge the digital gap, focusing on integrating available computational tools, and converging into a new platform that enables faster engineering and technical management. This platform intends to provide a holistic approach to product lifecycle management (PLM) for shipbuilding, integrating existing and proven solutions in CAD/CAE with new data-driven technologies to handle shipbuilding knowledge efficiently. The development aims to facilitate the digital transformation of shipbuilding, increasing productivity, collaboration, flexibility, and innovation opportunities. The paper presents a link between current challenges and possible ways to tackle them and a summary of the possible impacts this platform can achieve if adequately implemented. The paper closes with a call for peers to contribute to the discussion.

1. European Shipbuilding and the Need for a Digital Thread

The European shipbuilding industry faces many challenges, including increased competition from Asia, economic uncertainty, and a growing demand for more sustainable vessels. However, despite these obstacles, the industry remains an essential player in the global maritime sector.

A white paper published by the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) in 2021 emphasized the importance of investing in new technologies and innovation to maintain the competitiveness of European shipyards. One of the most notable trends in the industry is the increasing importance of digitalization and automation in the shipbuilding industry. Digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), and blockchain have the potential to improve efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance safety in the industry, *EMSA (2021)*.

Diverse commercial, societal and academic actors emphasized the need for European shipyards to focus on innovation and sustainability to remain competitive in the global market, *Ulstein and Brett (2012)*. The main argument is that adopting digital technologies is a key factor that will determine the future success of European shipyards. As the industry continues to evolve, the collaboration between stakeholders and the development of new technologies will be critical for success, *Diaz et al. (2023)*.

A vast and increasing amount of data is generated during the shipbuilding life cycle, *Seppälä (2019)*. There is considerable scope to use this data more effectively across the shipbuilding network value chain, *Gaspar (2018)*. Digitalization and computational tools have great potential to generate value for stakeholders in the form of cyber-physical systems or digital twins. It requires a significant reshaping of existing tools and practices to be exploited successfully by the European shipbuilding industry. The gains come in the form of increased quality and reduced time required for design, virtual prototyping, estimations of impacts for the use of greening innovative technologies, modularization, flexible data management, interoperability across proprietary tools, cyber security, efficient support for modern robotized fabrication and openness for integration with operational platforms.

To achieve these gains, a digital thread needs to be facilitated to enable data use and management to support the life cycle of complex engineering systems effectively, focusing on the shipyard as the core of the value chain as it converges the tasks of design, engineering, construction, and maintenance. By establishing a single source of truth for ship data, the digital thread facilitates data fusion for CAE/CAD/CAM/PDM systems, which can improve the organizing, managing, and contextualizing of shipbuilding data. It has the potential to provide virtual prototypes, enhance consistency and compliance with technical standards, use AI and ML, and NLP technology to assist and evaluate technological innovations, enable iterative learning, and significantly enhance communication and access to data for all stakeholders.

However, much of the productivity gain to be achieved during the early stages of ship design is constrained by the many different CAE/CAD/PLM/PDM/ERP tools and models used to create, combine, and evaluate each of the modules that a ship consists of. Consequently, the design of a modularized and standardized work system (enabling reuse of design models and drawings), or even a new design approach configuration, lacks an effective and agile common evaluation framework that can combine standard (traditional) and customized (innovative) solutions through the ship design, engineering, and fabrication processes. A successful smart framework should consider the detailed balance of these elements, especially regarding effective documentation towards clients and third-party partners, including activities beyond the design/delivery process, such as maintenance and repair, retrofit, operation, and scrapping.

2. Being Smart: Challenges and Opportunities in Digitalization

The current situation in the shipbuilding industry is characterized by high competition, low-profit margins, high complexity and scale of products, conservative processes, limited use of data and disconnected data streams, and the scattered priorities of a variety of stakeholders in the life cycle, *ECORYS (2009)*. As a result, the European shipbuilding industry has experienced a major capacity reduction in the past 5 years. Over 15 shipyards have ceased operations in this period due to bankruptcy - miscalculated project risks or lack of contracts – in other words, lack of competitiveness.

Typically, ship design, engineering, and fabrication in Europe follow fairly traditional approaches, not keeping the same pace of development observed in the automotive, discrete manufacturing, and aerospace industry. Current shipbuilding approaches are partly fragmented, discontinuous, time-consuming, and laborious. The rationalization of business and work processes (e.g., PLM, PDM, modularization, parameterization, and other data-based techniques) have so far only been tested and implemented successfully in the daily tasks of yards to a limited extent. The marine industry is a traditional and conservative business when it comes to changing its value chain, which is complex and comprised of many globally distributed actors. Ship fabrication methods vary from shipyard to shipyard and the standard by which ship design drawing packages are prepared and communicated varies greatly. Novel and state-of-the-art knowledge and technology (smart) are used only to a limited extent to streamline and improve the efficiency of such work processes and collaboration. The high-cost levels in Europe compared to emerging and gradually more competitive low-cost firms and partly large and fully integrated yards in Asia dictates that high effectiveness yields need to be achieved at European shipyards.

Moreover, ship design, class approval, and maintenance include many documents managed over extended life cycles. The digital downstream to operations phase is challenging as 2D, 3D, and simulation models contain a vast amount of model elements. A typical vessel model of only one design project may contain up to 2-3 million model elements or parts. The approach is significantly different from a mechanical CAD model, as shipbuilding uses high levels of topological connections between parts to make it possible for fast modifications, such as the rearrangement of equipment and piping or changes to hull structures. Another element specific to the industry is the use of materials such as steel plates of pipes that require fabrication into panels or pipe spools before the construction process. This pre-fabrication can be done by external subcontractors or workshops where access to design and procurement data as well as the construction particularities, plays a critical role and can significantly

impact the quality and schedule of the project. Based on data from Ulstein shipyard, up to 8% of total production time is used for coordination activities by foremen and up to 3% on project management. These are primary areas targeted for improving the process where digital data and information access can significantly impact the total costs and time used for production, *Agis (2020)*.

Discrete manufacturing industries maintain so-called maturity management for all used parts. This highly demanded approach, which supports functional safety, traceability, and compliance, is not practiced in the shipbuilding industry. This is because the check and approval processes would get stuck due to the vast number of parts, limited design speed, and rise in complexity. However, one of the main reasons lie in the lack of computational tools that can support the digital tread and the life cycle process of shipbuilding. Staged maturity management and traceability are desirable for the shipbuilding industry and should derive from the life cycle approach to data usage. Literature suggests that the application of AI will benefit ship design, although few working systems are yet available.

The SEUS project aims to address these topics, making a step in this direction for a data-assisted method to support early ship design. While each of the pitfalls listed above can significantly slow down or improve the overall process, having a holistic view of shipbuilding is a prerequisite. This views, with suggested room for improvements via process innovation, is illustrated in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Potential for lead time reduction in the upstream maritime value chain

In this context, we summarize seven challenges for enhancing the current status of European Shipbuilding:

1. Facilitate rapid early-stage design to support lower-risk bid development, particularly when integrating innovative new technologies
2. Provide better capital cost estimations and performance predictions, particularly showing the improvements expected from the inclusion of new technologies
3. Tools to be integrated with ship construction and production and consider supply chain management and future maintenance and repair of vessels.
4. Address and quantify the competitiveness gains provided by the tool(s) in the context of the wider European shipbuilding sector.
5. Ensure that the tool is robust and resilient against cyber threats.
6. Identify and address the development of the necessary skills needed to achieve the maximum benefit from innovative advanced computational shipbuilding tools.
7. Develop business cases to quantify the added value from the developed tool to the shipbuilder concerned and within the context of the wider European shipbuilding sector

3. Smart European Shipbuilding (SEUS) Proposal

The main ambition of the Smart European Shipbuilding project (SEUS) is to tackle the mentioned challenges, by developing a smart platform dedicated to shipbuilding and its downstream and upstream lifecycle phases. This will be achieved by architecting an integrated platform for a combined and open solution incorporating CAE, CAD, CAM, and PDM software and testing it at shipyards. The new platform solution will be built with state-of-the-art European shipbuilding expertise provided by academic and industrial consortium participants. It intends to develop novel practices for human-centric knowledge management in shipbuilding, the use of NLP, and data-driven AI design elements in the current consensus or intelligent technologies and Industry 5.0, *EU (2021)*.

The SEUS project will develop, implement, test, and qualify software solutions with an Industry 5.0 mindset for the European shipbuilding market. Smart technology, in terms of digitalization and cyber-physical systems, including humans, are concepts that have never been built from a shipbuilding perspective. Current solutions used by shipyards include significant parts of manual data handling and are prone to a high level of human error or a fragmented adaptation of PLM from other industries, such as aerospace, automotive, or other discrete manufacturing. The shipbuilding industry uses many computational tools to plan, design, simulate, and build vessels and other marine products, such as offshore platforms or other floating constructions. Consequently, the digital information chains of shipbuilding are more weakly integrated than in discrete manufacturing industries and thus lack support for a digital thread: digital continuity, digital lifecycle management, and digital ship operation support. This is an obstacle to gaining efficiency and to implementing new business models based on digital innovations and the development of IT technology. We have set up seven objectives towards a stepwise progress over 4 years:

1. Create workflow activity map and use cases applying smart technology and Industry 5.0 concept, specific to European shipbuilding
2. Enhance the human-centric competitiveness of shipbuilding and reflect diverse values of stakeholders, including shipyard workers, shipowners, operators, users/passengers, and shipbuilders in general
3. Build a shipbuilding-specific PLM platform comprising defined data models and the selected elements of CAE/CAD/CAM and PDM solutions
4. Develop a flexible platform that supports multiple instances of workflows to facilitate rapid early designs, and is fit to support AI tools and virtual prototyping
5. Ensure openness and interoperability of the platform while keeping it cyber secure
6. Test and implement in an industrial environment – developing the concept of the digital shipyard.
7. Quantify added value gains provided by the developed platform, creating a business model of exploitation, and dissemination of project results

The technology readiness level (TRL) targeted by the project is 8-9, corresponding to the maturity level of a completed and qualified (tested in a large-scale pilot installation) platform, ready for a commercially competitive operational environment. The aimed shipbuilding platform will integrate existing computational tools with TRL 9, commercially exploited in shipbuilding. It will incorporate Industry 5.0 concepts (human-centricity, sustainability, and circular economy) and progress through the process of maturing TRL from level 4 (initial technology validated by combining existing software parts, including AI and ML) to level 7-9 (integrated platform with developed use cases, tested in shipyards).

4. Methodology and Expected Impact

4.1 SEUS Methodology Overview

The overall platform developed by the SEUS project aims to connect existing high-end solutions, specialized in selected areas of the shipbuilding life cycle, and unite data handling for the shipbuilding

projects through life stages and disciplines based on expertise in shipbuilding use scenarios. This approach challenges both the prevailing CAD-centric approach in shipbuilding (historically CAD model is used in most shipyards for generating production data) and the PDM-centric approach, where data as such is managed, with an interface connected to the CAD model and focuses on project and change management.

Fundamental to the SEUS approach is that the current toolbox for shipbuilding can be more efficient if properly integrated into a human-centered environment, including Industry 5.0 aspects. The SEUS methodology is focused on developing a smart platform for CAD/CAE/CAM in shipbuilding based on the industrial and academic experience of its consortium members.

The SEUS approach revolves around the fulfillment of the seven mentioned objectives. It consists of four main steps, represented in Fig.2, namely:

1. Shipbuilding Best Practices;
2. Smart Shipbuilding PLM Platform;
3. Shipyard Implementation;
4. Business and Innovation.

Each main step contains the sub-process itemized below and is described as follows.

Fig.2: SEUS Methodology Overview

SEUS approach starts with the evaluation of the European shipbuilding scenario concerning the current state of digital tools and the potential to incorporate smart technologies. Parallel to it a deep study of what means a human-centered approach in shipbuilding will be developed, in line with the needs and aspects of Industry 5.0, aiming at the balance between cyber-physical systems and societal challenges. its technologies, potential for human-centered, and Industry 5.0 technologies. As a result, a body of knowledge with best practices for the implementation of the smart platform will be developed, feeding the next step.

The second part of the methodology converges the core of the project, with the development of a smart PLM platform incorporating CAD/CAM/CAE elements in line with shipbuilding practices. It consists of the assessment of products and practices already available in the consortium about the needs and standards compiled in the previous phase. Extensive software development will enhance existing toolsets and implement digital support for the use cases and scenarios, representing the computational tools for shipbuilding development stressed in the call. A detail of the desired elements in this development is observed in Fig.3.

The SEUS Smart CAD+PLM platform integrates the following main elements: CAE modules, CAD/CAM modules, PDM/PLM selected applications and features, and embedded shipbuilding expertise.

CAE modules address functionality related to initial and early design stages, such as hull shape form calculations, stability, weight estimations, and interfaces for CFD and FEM calculations, incorporating AI and a data-driven approach to design.

CAD/CAM modules include specialized applications for functional ship design (P&IDs, Electrical schematics), 3D detailed, and production design. It incorporates the reuse of initial design models, 3D modeling, and arrangement (Hull, Piping, Outfitting, HVAC, Cable 3D design, and other outfitting elements) and provides an automated output of fabrication data in a traditional format of 2D documentation along with the direct output for CNC-controlled equipment and robotized manufacturing, all ready for an integrated virtual prototype environment.

Fig.3: SEUS Smart Platform Desired Elements

PDM/PLM elements consist of selected modules for data management and product life cycle support, including project and change management, document management, Bill of Materials management, IoT integration, and ILS support. This sets a solid basis for the maturity management-based PLM concept that would enable support for functional safety, traceability, and compliance for the shipbuilding industry.

Shipbuilding expertise embraces knowledge of the PLM approach in shipbuilding and other industries' best practices, developed shipbuilding human-centric activity map and knowledge management, embedded cyber security practices, and the use of AI and NLP for ship project data. Added to all the elements, an open interface will connect the software toward efficient data flow, aiming at a common standard that can be used by different shipyards.

As part of the broader cyber security solution for the project, a series of cyber security workshops will be conducted with project team members and support teams. Those workshops will address issues of cyber threat awareness (including threats to AI apps), secure programming practices, active cyber security countermeasures, cyber security hygiene, and the development of the project's Information Security Management System (ISMS).

A dedicated challenge is the standardization of domain knowledge to speed-up design tasks, especially in early design phases when many new items need to be born quickly and when master data maintenance is typically hindering the ease of designs although needed for efficient downstream work. Attempts to realize PDM-based master data management by so-called orthogonal classification were successful. An analysis of given standards such as ISO 10303, SFI, and German Marine/Ship Assembly Register indicated that such kind of domain knowledge applies to PDM-based MDM and classification schemata, covering technical properties, property values, etc. to classify design documents, work tasks, ship items, equipment or any other PDM information object.

Mechanical CAD systems are used in the marine industry for outfitting and detailed designs of ship components and equipment, *Fonseca and Gaspar (2022)*. These systems are well integrated with PLM

elements and approved conversion pipelines. The way of modelling vessels (e.g. steel and parametric hulls, equipment and piping materials) down to production differs for shipbuilding intent-driven CAD systems. This typically leads to a mismatch of the level of details in the 3D model and manageable ship product structures. A concept to interlink and inter-visualize CAD content from both worlds is targeted including the implementation of an integrated conversion pipeline, product structure management, and interactive visualization augmented with master data.

Integration between the PLM elements platform and CAD/CAE authoring application includes several layers of data management, data model alignment, 3D visualization technology, and the development of the user interface to cover various use cases. It will be executed by architectural the integrated platform solution, user stories, and iterative system design process. Various applications: Hull 3D design, Piping and Outfitting 3D design, HVAC, Electrical, etc, need to share data with data management shell and ensure transfer and synchronization with defined accuracy, 3D visualization, and embedded workflows to assist users in everyday design, project management, and production tasks.

4.2 Expected Impact

The impact of SEUS is based on primarily increasing the level of digitalization in European Shipyards, facilitating the transformation of this industry towards competitiveness with a human-centric mindset. A compilation of seven key impacts is presented in Fig.4 and explained as follows.

Fig.4: Expected Impacts

- Impact 1: Computational platform solution for PLM in shipbuilding**
 The development of a platform with a PLM approach specific to shipbuilding would be a pioneering addition to the existing landscape of computational tools for shipbuilding in Europe and globally. Like CAD/CAM tools that provided a breakthrough by using computing and 3D modelling some 30 years ago, the PLM platform is a leap forward in digitalization. With interoperability, a standardized data model, and process management tools our initiative will impact European shipbuilding competitiveness with shorter lead times and the capability to adapt to design and production time changes. It will add to the currently unutilized potential for the end customer by reducing lifetime costs during ship maintenance. Since the data model and specialized application landscape during ship design are fragmented, the information disappears between the different design phases, from the initial design to the basic design to construction.
- Impact 2: Facilitation of digital transformation of shipbuilding**
 Increasing the shipbuilding industry's digitalization levels dramatically will affect how the marine industry works and profits from information consistency and control. Industry 4.0

outlines the benefits of digitalization in the manufacturing industry, such as improved productivity, collaborative working ways, flexibility, agility, reduced costs, and innovation opportunities. Taking this concept further and augmenting it with knowledge and skills in management and circular production models would allow shipbuilding to catch up with other industries and pioneer the use of digital tools to serve society's goals. The expectations are to support resource-efficient designs and provide tools for the evaluation of design impacts at the virtual prototyping stage, develop a human-centric approach for digital shipbuilding processes, and up-skill European shipbuilders.

- **Impact 3: Traceability and integration of early design impact the design process**

The EU targets for the decarbonization of shipbuilding require the possibility to integrate innovative technologies in the early stages of design to evaluate the effectiveness of alternatives and their impacts on the project. In shipbuilding practice, this means experimentation with hull shapes (Ulstein X-bow is an example of such innovation to significantly impact the stability of sea-going vessels), propulsion design, and power or fuelling alternatives (LPG/LNG, ammonia, or hydrogen, etc). The potential impact of these technical solutions on the project will be evaluated at the earliest possible design stages and will be linked with historical data (whenever possible) and downstream detailed design and construction data. The platform aims to integrate all these data streams into the interconnected digital thread to provide traceability of decisions and impacts and significantly simplify working processes for the early design stages for all participants – naval architects, designers, engineers, shipyards, and shipowners.

- **Impact 4: Competitive advantage for EU shipbuilders through time savings in design and production stages**

Communication presents one of the biggest hurdles in shipbuilding projects. Inconsistent, incomplete, and unclear information generates uncertainty in projects that lowers the quality of project decisions resulting in delays, higher costs, and poorer project realization. The SEUS platform aims to provide the next level of communication and information transfer among participants in the shipbuilding project. By eliminating the need for manual data transfer and providing access control tools, it aims to provide information dynamically extracted on demand, as well as supplementing it with 3D data and other relevant information. The primary focus will be on the communication between ship designers and shipbuilders. The involvement of third parties such as equipment suppliers, subcontractors, classification societies and flag status, or shipping companies will, however, also be considered in the case studies. The use of such a platform will significantly reduce the time searching for information at all phases from different tools and sources and especially impact the design to production data transfer. Additional NLP-based conversational search models based on AI and neural networks are expected to provide additional support for information search and communication.

- **Impact 5: Expansion of shipyard's exposure to ship's life cycle: for retrofit, revitalization, use of data from operation and maintenance**

The SEUS platform aims to enhance the exposure of shipyards and ship design offices to the life cycle of the vessels they designed and built to provide insights from the operation stage and historical data for comparisons and evaluation of the design solutions used. It also empowers shipyards by retaining communication with their customers and expanding service offerings toward the operational stage. Both sides can gain from this connection: shipyards can expand their service offering in the post-delivery stages, while operators can get accurate engineering and design models and avoid remodeling while using the digital twin approach.

- **Impact 6: Human-centric shipbuilding knowledge management**

Human-centric shipbuilding knowledge management can be presented as a customizable shipbuilding activity modeling framework for associating typical shipbuilding activities, shipbuilding expertise, and the data thread through the shipbuilding life cycle. The framework includes values, interaction, collaboration, and shipbuilding actors' skill development and

training. Identifying these elements of the framework and devising evaluation methods that exploit the association between human subjectivity and context data would be a part of the novel research of the SEUS project. This will impact the effectiveness and productivity of a highly skilled workforce and sustainable knowledge management practices. An additional aspect presents lifecycle-integrated training and learning programs for diverse shipbuilding stakeholders.

- **Impact 7: EU workforce skills and expertise development**

Historically, European shipbuilders lead the industry as the most innovative and technologically advanced. In the last decades, European shipbuilding has focused almost exclusively on high-value vessels that formed the core of the expertise. Executing projects of this complexity scale requires advanced project management skills, technological and industrial skills, procurement, building and construction, and many other areas of expertise. The platform aims to provide a single source of truth for almost all people involved in every shipbuilding project, with a UX designed for each target audience that reflects their characteristics and controlled access to data. It would provide a context for everyday tasks and boost creativity and workers' digital skills, keeping the EU leadership position in the area.

5. Concluding Remarks: A Call from Peers to Join the Smart Approach

A strong point of SEUS is its consortium, a balanced partnership composed of academics, software developers, and shipbuilding partners representing 5 countries from Europe, which is fully dedicated to bridging the knowledge in its communities and facilitating the uptake of the main results. SEUS's partners are experienced in customer implementation, dissemination, and communication activities in their home countries and internationally, and this experience will be enormously beneficial for achieving the objectives here proposed. Therefore, the consortium is committed to disseminating SEUS's approaches and outcomes, while simultaneously staying focused on the identified target groups and reaching the objectives of development, dissemination, and exploitation.

In this context, peer and stakeholder engagement support is an imperative set of activities to be integrated with the SEUS communication strategy. Besides sharing the results and findings of the project with a broad audience, the consortium welcomes external collaboration. With the ultimate target of supporting European shipbuilding, many projects can benefit from joining efforts and sharing findings in the industry's best interests.

We close this paper with call for peers to contribute and interact with the consortium. In a short term, to develop and publish their own understanding of the smart concepts here discussed, such as industry 5.0, digital thread, PDM/PLM incorporation. In a middle term, the evaluation of the pros and cons of their approaches with our proposal, and the investigation on how to combine features in a way that is beneficial to the majority of European partners. The project considers part of the development for an open standard to connect to the commercial tools, allowing other commercial partners to interact with the tools.

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